

The background features a white space with several dashed blue lines representing orbits. There are three blue spheres: one in the upper left, one in the upper right with a ring (resembling Saturn), and one in the lower right. A large central graphic consists of a dark blue circle with a light blue ring around it, containing the text.

Proceedings for the
**6th Shaw-IAU Workshop
on Astronomy for Education**

Special Topics:
Evaluation
JWST: The First Two Years

12 – 15 November, 2024

Compiled & Edited by: Samantha Brown-Sevilla & Asmita Bhandare

Editing supported by: Sophie Bartlett, Eduardo Penteado, Tshiamiso Makwela, Niall Deacon, Gwen Sanderson, Livia Giacomini, Abd Alfady Morcos, Somaya Saad, Ayelet Weizman, Joana Latas, Elisabeta Ana Naghi, Felicia Elena, Breezy Ocaña Flaquer, and Juan Ángel Vaquerizo

The following is a collection of summaries from the 6th Shaw-IAU workshop on Astronomy for Education held 12 - 15 November, 2024 as a virtual event. The workshop was organised by the IAU Office of Astronomy for Education. More details can be found on: <https://astro4edu.org/shaw-iau/6th-shaw-iau-workshop/>.

The IAU Office of Astronomy for Education (OAE) is hosted at Haus der Astronomie (HdA), managed by the Max Planck Institute for Astronomy. The OAE's mission is to support and coordinate astronomy education by astronomy researchers and educators, aimed at primary or secondary schools worldwide. HdA's hosting the OAE was made possible through the support of the German foundations Klaus Tschira Stiftung and Carl-Zeiss-Stiftung. The Shaw-IAU Workshops on Astronomy for Education are funded by the Shaw Prize Foundation.

The OAE is supported by a growing network of OAE Centers and OAE Nodes, collaborating to lead global projects developed within the network. The OAE Centers and Nodes are: the OAE Center China–Nanjing, hosted by the Beijing Planetarium (BJP); the OAE Center Cyprus, hosted by Cyprus Space Exploration Organization (CSEO); the OAE Center Egypt, hosted by the National Research Institute of Astronomy and Geophysics (NRIAG); the OAE Center India, hosted by the Inter-University Centre for Astronomy and Astrophysics (IUCAA); the OAE Center Italy, hosted by the National Institute for Astrophysics (INAF); the OAE Node Republic of Korea, hosted by the Korean Astronomical Society (KAS); OAE Node France at CY Cergy Paris University hosted by CY Cergy Paris University; and the OAE Node Nepal, hosted by the Nepal Astronomical Society (NASO).

THE
SHAW
PRIZE
邵逸夫獎

6th Shaw-IAU Workshop on Astronomy for Education

It is great to see that our online conference format is now settling into a solid organisational routine, while at the same time moving forward with new topics. JWST results are certainly new and exciting both for astronomy itself and for astronomy education. Beyond the beautiful pictures, two key research strands that have profited particularly from JWST observations and measurements are the ones we have explored during the JWST Special Science Topic sessions of this year's workshop: the formation and evolution of galaxies in the early universe, and exoplanets. Both strands also resonate with pupils. The former topic plays a role for how we, as humans, "got here," describing as it does the pre-history of our cosmic environments. The latter, exoplanets, is linked to the question that studies like ROSE have found to be the science question piquing pupils' interest the most: is there other life out there, somewhere?

Our special topic on the educational side was more down to Earth: Evaluation! In both 2023 and 2024, a special partnership with Cardiff University has brought the evaluation specialist and astronomy education researcher Dr. Sophie Bartlett into the OAE team. A number of you will already know Sophie's Evaluation Framework and Toolkit for the OAE (if you don't, check it out!), which is also going to be an important part of the forthcoming OAE Review on Evaluation. The sessions of this special topic are another building block on our way to establishing a culture of evaluation — are our activities and resources working? — within the OAE community.

The main idea of our international online school for astronomy education is and remains that our event is not primarily a scientific conference, where the focus is on opportunities to present one's new results. It's a training event: Each talk should provide participants with knowledge they can put to good use for their own astronomy education activities. Our regular sessions are designed to contribute to that goal: The session on Astronomy Education Research brings you in contact with both the methods and the results of the systematic explorations of what, whether and how students learn about and understand astronomy. The sessions on Astronomy Education for Schools in Practice, held separately for primary and secondary schools, provide real-life examples for teaching and learning about astronomy under a variety of conditions — and hopefully some direct inspiration for your own teaching! The Teaching Methods and Tools sessions take one step back, and consider not the content we teach, but the ways to (effectively) teach it. A tool that is dear to our heart, namely the astroEDU portal, again had its own dedicated session. These proceedings should help you find what in our workshop could be useful to you, both in terms of a written summary and with links to the recordings of the various talks.

Last but not least, our event was about community building. I greatly enjoyed chatting with various participants during our networking sessions, and I am following with interest the increased activity in the sessions held in languages other than English. Save the date for the next Shaw-IAU Workshop, and make sure to be there (virtually) 18 to 21 November, 2025!

Markus Pössel
Director, IAU Office of Astronomy for Education
Heidelberg, December 2024

Contents

Foreword	3
Organising Committees	9
Astronomy Education in Practice	11
Deep Conceptual Understanding through Personalised Learning Paths - The Discovery Space Project	12
Looking for Life in the Universe: Hands-On Activities About Astrobiology	15
AstroJourneys	18
The Role of Natural Effects of the Earth and Man-Made Structures in Learning Astronomy	20
Astronomy and Children’s Literature in the Early Years of Elementary School	22
The Penn State Inservice Workshops in Astronomy (PSIWA)	25
Bridging Scientists and Students with Regional School Partnerships	27
Experiences in Creating and Implementing a Course for Astronomy as its Own Subject in High School	30
Authentic Research Experiences for High School Students in Astronomy	33
Recreating the Early Universe in Classrooms: Leveraging Augmented Reality and ChatGPT in Astrophysics	35
Bringing the Universe into the Classroom: Integrating Astronomy Through Math Problems	35
Poster: STEM+A@Astronomy: Integrating Astronomy into Curriculum by Engineering Design and Science Inquiry	39
Poster: Equipping Educators Through a Train-the-Trainer Mental Health Initiative	41
Poster: Where Did the Stars Go?	43
Poster: Galaxy Formation for School Students	45
Poster: Closer to the Sky: Co-Creating Astronomical Knowledge in the PPG Favela of Rio de Janeiro	47
Poster: Qatar Astronomy Olympiad for Schools 2024	49
Poster: Collaboration Among High Schools, Universities, and High-Tech Enterprises to Jointly Develop Courses	52
Poster: Advancing Astronomical Literacy via Student Writing Contests	54
Poster: Astronomy Education in Tanzanian Secondary Schools	55
Poster: Building a Sky Observation Activity in a School Context	58
Poster: Advancing Astronomy Education in Indonesia Through NASE: Insights from the 2022 and 2024 Courses	60
Poster: Teaching High School Astronomy Through Scientists’ Biographies	62
Poster: Experiential Workshop: Integrating Astronomical Data Sonification with STEAM Education	65
Poster: Astronomy in Amateur Rocket Competition	67

Astronomy Education Research	72
Mixed Methods Designs for Astronomy Education Research	73
Beyond the Stars: Investigating Student Reasoning in Astronomy	75
The Impact of Questions on Students' Estimations of Astronomical Sizes and Distances	78
Framework for the Use of the Celestial Sphere as an Educational Tool	82
Innovation in Astronomy Teaching: A Study of Astronomical Peripateticism and the Flipped Classroom	85
A Study Discussing How to Get the Most out of Collaboration Between Scientists and Teachers	88
Poster: To Make Astronomy Education a Compulsory Subject for All High School Students	91
Poster: Clarifying Uncertainty in the Nature of Science Through Astronomy Examples	92
Poster: Investigating the Efficacy of Experiential Learning Through Observatory In- ternships for Studying Astronomy	95
Poster: Cultural Astronomy: Transformative Potential in Basic Education	97
Poster: Misconceptions on Astronomy Topics in Science Education: A Case Study for Secondary School Students	100
Poster: Continuing Teacher Education: Comets as a Pedagogical Strategy for Teaching Astronomy	102
Poster: Teacher-Centred Approach: Study of Profiles, Needs, and Practices in Astron- omy Education in Primary	105
Poster: Investigating Teachers' Integration of Astronomy and Space in Formal Learning	107
Poster: Use of Astronomy Concepts Within Comics to Motivate Physics Classes	110
 Teaching Methods and Tools	 113
In Praise of Raw Data: Sustainable Printing Techniques to Engage Students with Astronomical Images	114
The Mediterranean Co-Design: The Sabir Project. Towards Co-Designed IBL Activities for High School	117
Engaging Students in Astronomy Through Learner-Driven Questions	121
Engaging PreK - 2nd Grade Students Using Storybook Style Lessons to "See What's Out There!"	122
Tips and Tools for Teaching Astrobiology	122
Astronomy, Language, and Cultural Continuity: Nurturing Connection for Iranian Migrant Youth	126
Opening Windows, Revealing Meanings: Instrumental Reading of Scientific Texts in English	128
Poster: Advancing Astronomy Education Through Dark Sky Initiative on Design Thinking and Social Innovation	130
Poster: Building Visualisations of Objects in Space from Ground Based Observations and Using Technology	132

Poster: Astronomical Peripatetism and Flipped Classroom: The New Horizon in Astronomy Education	132
Poster: Facilitating Celestial Navigation Through Artistic Visualisation of Constellations Using Artsterism	135
Poster: Young Scientific Explainers - A Museum Perspective on Designing an Astronomy Educational Program	137
Poster: From Real-Life Astronomy Research Questions to Olympiad Problems	139
Poster: Engaging the Public with Astronomy Through Interactive Museum Experiences	142
Poster: Sustainable Methods for Teaching Astronomy: Educational Camera Obscura in Non-Formal Spaces	144
Poster: Transforming Science Education in Informal Settings with Astronomy and Meteorology: The Role of Astrometeorology	146
Poster: Enhancing Student Impact Through Innovative Astronomy Teaching Methodologies	148
Poster: We are All Residents of the Milky Way	150
Poster: Satellite Radio Reception Experiment Using SDR as a Teaching Material for High School Physics	151
Poster: Further Adventures with Gee Whizz Astronomy Modelling	153
Poster: Journey Alongside the Centreline	154
Poster: The Knowledge that Emerges from Shadows	160
Poster: Bridging Gaps in Ghana's Astronomy Education for Exceptional Learners Through Innovative TTP	162
Poster: Assessing Student Writing Assignments with Large Language Models	165
Poster: Multisensory Planetarium. The Universe as You Never Sensed It	167
Evaluation	171
Evaluating Without Words	172
The Challenges of Evaluation of Astronomy Activities in the Croatian Educational System	175
Perception Measurement Instrument on the Use of Real Astronomical Data in the School Classroom	177
Enhancing Skill Development in Digitally Instructed Hands-On - Minds-On Astronomy Lessons	180
Embedded Participatory Evaluation to Assess Mission Embedded Education Outcomes	181
Pedagogical Advisor and Couple for the Teaching of Astronomy at Elementary School	184
Mediterranean Co-Design: Evaluating the Project FRESCO (Florence RESidency COdesign)	187
Assessing Learning in Astronomy: Methods and Tools in the Context of Astronomical Peripatetism	191
Hands-On Experiments as Physical Analogies for Exoplanet Weather Phenomena	193
Assessing Teachers' Perspectives to Develop Astronomy Learning Materials with Augmented Reality	195
Engagement: What Is It? How Is It Measured? How to Bring It to the Astronomy Course?	196

JWST – the First Two Years	200
Two Years of Cosmic Exploration with JWST	201
Blowing Bubbles in Galaxies: A Zoo of Bubbles from JWST	204
JWST’s Look into First Galaxies and Black Holes	207
Creating the James Webb Space Telescope First Images	210
Webb: Probing the Material that Builds Planets	210
Tracking Down the Cosmic Origins of Earth’s Water with JWST	213
Exploring Distant Worlds with the James Webb Space Telescope	215
JWST Universe	216
Webb: Bringing the Mission and Its Science to School Students and the General Public	219
The Golden Eye: JWST in Schools	222
Poster: In Praise of Raw Data: Sustainable Printing Techniques to Engage Students with Astronomical Images	223
Poster: James Webb Telescope: Towards an Expanded View of the Universe	225
astroEDU Workshop	230
Arabic-Speaking Community Discussion	231
Hebrew-Speaking Community Discussion	233
Portuguese-Speaking Community Discussion	234
Romanian-Speaking Community Discussion	236
Spanish-Speaking Community Discussion	239

Organising Committees

Local Organising Committee:

Ola Ali, Sophie Bartlett, Samantha Brown-Sevilla, Kshitij Chavan, Niall Deacon, Manisha Dwa, Mariachiara Falco, Carolin Liefke, Tshiamiso Makwela, Eduardo Penteado, Markus Pössel, Gwen Sanderson, Rebecca Sanderson, Sai Shetye.

Scientific Advisory Committee:

Sophie Bartlett, Mike Boylan-Kolchin, Samantha Brown-Sevilla, Silvia Casu, Exodus Chun-Long Sit, Niall Deacon, Federica Duras, Felicia Elena, Beatriz García, Livia Giacomini, Edward Gomez, Joanna Holt, Noorali T. Jiwaji, Joana Latas, Moupiya Maji, Tshiamiso Makwela, Hakim L Malasan, Giulio Mazzolo, Shahrzad Mirsoltani, Abd Alfady Morcos, Elisabeta Ana Naghi, Breezy Ocaña Flaquer, Eduardo Penteado, Julia Plummer, María Claudia Ramírez Tannus, Sarah Roberts, Shylaja B S, Somaya Saad, Saeed Salimpour, Gwen Sanderson, Jungjoo Sohn, Łukasz Tychoniec, Juan Ángel Vaquerizo, Elizabeth Watkins, Ayelet Weizman.

Astronomy Education in Practice

Session organisers: Eduardo Penteadó (OAE Heidelberg), Sophie Bartlett (OAE Heidelberg), Silvia Casu (Istituto Nazionale di Astrofisica), Shahrzad Mirsoltani (Kargahe Setare Project), and Sarah Roberts (Swansea University)

Editing supported by: Eduardo Penteadó

SESSION OVERVIEW

This session focused on practical applications of astronomy education in classrooms, highlighting innovative methods to inspire curiosity and foster scientific literacy. From AI-driven tools and augmented reality to hands-on experiments and storytelling, educators shared how they bring complex concepts like the phases of the Moon, astrobiology, and dark matter to life for students. The talks and posters underscored the potential of astronomy to create engaging, interdisciplinary learning experiences, empowering both teachers and students in the classroom world worldwide.

TALK CONTRIBUTIONS

Deep Conceptual Understanding through Personalised Learning Paths - The Discovery Space Project

Speaker: Maria Luísa Almeida, Núcleo Interativo de Astronomia e Inovação em Educação (NUCLIO), Portugal

Collaborator: Rosa Doran (NUCLIO)

The [Discovery Space project](#) has designed an innovative Exploratory Learning Environment, known as Discovery Space, to enhance students' inquiry and problem-solving skills while interacting with virtual and remote labs. This environment aims to provide personalized support and guidance using AI-driven companions, enabling students to learn at their own pace and rhythm, and assuring true deep learning for all. Pilot scenarios cover topics such as the causes of the seasons, the phases of the moon, and landing on Mars, demonstrating how teachers, with the help of AI, can tailor educational experiences to individual needs.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/jWJL1YEK3PI>

In education, one of the priorities is ensuring that students gain more than just curricular knowledge—they must also develop the ability to think critically, solve problems creatively, and collaborate effectively to navigate the challenges of an increasingly complex world. Deeper Learning helps students not only master core knowledge and skills but also develop essential abilities to apply their learning to real-world challenges and prepare them for a constant evolving global world.

The [Discovery Space](#) is an Erasmus+ project. Based on rooted research in the field and long-lasting experience employing ICT-based innovations in education, it proposes the development of a roadmap for the AI-Enhanced Classroom for Deeper Learning in STEM. This roadmap facilitates the transformation of the traditional classroom to an environment, which promotes the scientific exploration and monitors and supports the development of key skills for all students.

Here, we focus on explaining how the DSPACE approach to the creation of scenarios with the help of AI driven companion can give the opportunity to emphasize the importance of a continuous assessment of problem-solving competence and reasoning skills, which are of fundamental importance for science learning, and thus being able to give support to different levels of students [1].

Figure 1: The workflow of a scenario: at each phase, students will get support to be ready to pass to the next phase.

Figure 2: Adapting learning paths to the needs of the students.

Deeper Learning Overview: A model for progression in learning, describing how students develop their understanding over time, can be categorized in different stages [2]. Surface Learning allows students to acquire foundational knowledge and skills; this stage focuses on initial exposure and understanding. In a next stage, Deep Learning has students making connections and gaining a deeper understanding by engaging with the material critically. And finally, the next stage has students applying knowledge and skills in new and unfamiliar contexts, which is considered the ultimate goal of learning.

William and Flora Hewlett Foundation (2013) [3] define deeper learning as a set of competencies students must master in order to develop a keen understanding of academic content and apply their knowledge to problems in the classroom and on the job. These include: mastery of academic content; critical thinking and complex problem solving; effective communication skills; collaboration skills; an understanding of how to learn; and the growth of academic mindsets. Other deeper learning competencies include: self-regulated learning; creativity and innovation; digital literacy; meta-cognitive Skills; emotional intelligence; global and cultural awareness; ethical and social responsibility.

Pedagogical approaches promoting deeper learning competencies: To foster deeper learning competencies, educators can use diverse instructional methods, which usually have in common promoting active, engaged, and student-centred learning. Examples like Project-Based Learning, Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL), Problem-Based Learning, Challenge-Based Learning (CBL), and Case-Based Teaching (CBT) can be effective approaches to develop deeper learning competencies.

DSPACE scenarios: The project DSPACE has been developing scenarios following an Inquiry-Based Learning approach based on five phases and using online and/or remote laboratories:

- **Engagement:** A phenomenon is presented to the students through an appropriate demonstration, to spark their interest and motivate them to work on its understanding.

- **Hypothesis:** The students are asked to make a hypothesis to explain the phenomenon by identifying the main parameters for its explanation.
- **Experiment:** At this stage the students are performing experimental work, using either a virtual or a remote lab, in order to see the effect that each identified parameter has on the phenomenon under discussion.
- **Data analysis:** The sets of data collected at the previous phase are now analyzed and conclusions are drawn, which either reject or validate the hypothesis made at the second step above.
- **Reflection:** At this stage the students reflect on what they have learned so far, while they are presented with a series of more demanding questions aiming to test how confident they are on their understanding.

These scenarios are implemented within an Exploratory Learning Environment. At each phase, students face challenges designed to assess their problem-solving performance and understanding. Based on these assessments, the platform provides tailored guidance by offering differentiated activities, tasks, or explanations that align with their performance. Students progress through the phases by successfully overcoming challenges, ensuring they master each step before advancing.

The scenarios are collaboratively developed by DSPACE partners and teachers to address specific, commonly encountered misconceptions identified by educators. This collaboration enables the provision of targeted feedback for each student while ensuring individualized support throughout the learning process. The platform also allows real-time monitoring of each student's progress, offering valuable insights on how to actuate.

Although the DSPACE approach is still in the piloting phase, the project is exploring how AI can further enhance the scenarios. AI tools are being used to evaluate student progress, assess the effectiveness of the scenarios in supporting and guiding students, and facilitate the development of their problem-solving and deeper learning skills. Piloting is ongoing, and as the scenarios are implemented at scale, AI will continuously refine the individualized learning paths. This ensures that each student's learning experience is dynamic, personalized, and effectively supports their journey toward deeper learning and enhanced problem-solving capabilities.

Astronomy and interdisciplinary scenarios: The DSPACE project is developing several scenarios centred on Astronomy, such as the phases of the Moon, the seasons, Galileo's moons, and Mars landings. These scenarios will be available on the DSPACE Exploratory Learning Environment (ELE) platform, allowing teachers to use, copy, or adapt them to their specific needs. As these scenarios are implemented and used more widely, the AI models will continuously improve, enabling personalized learning paths that address individual students' needs. This approach ensures that the scenarios are not only engaging and relevant but also tailored to support deeper learning and overcome common misconceptions identified by teachers.

References:

- [1] Koulentianos, D. & Conradty, K. (2023). Discovery Space Project - Deliverable 2.2 Deeper

Learning Competence Framework.

- [2] Frey, N. & Fisher, D. & Hattie, J. (2016). Surface, Deep, and Transfer? Considering the Role of Content Literacy Instructional Strategies. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*.
- [3] William and Flora Hewlett Foundation (2013) Deeper learning defined: <https://hewlett.org/library/deeper-learning-defined/>

Looking for Life in the Universe: Hands-On Activities About Astrobiology

Speaker: Juan Ángel Vaquerizo, Centro de Astrobiología (CAB, CSIC-INTA), Spain

In this talk we will first explain in brief what Astrobiology is: the study of life in the Universe. Afterwards, several simple experiments that are easily reproducible in the classroom will be shown. Thus, through experiments, the scientific activity carried out by astrobiologists is explained.

Talk link: https://youtu.be/Y_aqA7HgYVI

Astrobiology is the study of life in the Universe. The search for life beyond the Earth requires an understanding of life, and the nature of the environments that support it, as well as planetary, planetary system and stellar interactions and processes. To provide this understanding, astrobiology combines the knowledge and techniques from many fields, including biology, chemistry, geology, physics, astrophysics, mathematics, and aerospace engineering. Astrobiologists can work alone on some specific scientific questions, but often astrobiologists from different scientific disciplines work together to examine complex questions that no one field can answer alone. These questions cover topics such as:

- How does life originate?
- How does life evolve?
- What kind of environment is necessary for life to arise and evolve?

- What are the environmental limits or “extremes” under which life can exist?
- What might life look like on another place?
- Is there or has there been life elsewhere in our Solar System?
- How can we detect and identify a habitable environment?
- What is life’s future on Earth?

Astrobiology: An Integrated Science Approach:

Astrobiology has great potential for science education in general and for astronomy education in particular. It has exciting content to engage those who generally do not consider themselves scientifically-oriented or even scientifically-interested. Science school curricula have traditionally been divided into sciences as biology, chemistry, geology, physics, mathematics, or earth science, or an elective such as astronomy or technology. This strategy does not really prepare students for scientific literacy and logical decision-making. In many cases, the current educational system is failing to engage students in science. They see no connection between what is taught in the classroom and what they value in their own lives. Science in the real world is integrated and problem-solving based. It is needed to present to them topics so inherently interesting, and even enigmatic, that students will be pushed to open their minds and to begin the learning process. Astrobiology could be such a subject, a way to understanding broad scientific concepts in a context that is immediately exciting and challenging for students.

The Experiments:

Since astrobiology is not currently part of the school science curriculum, some simple experiments from various scientific disciplines can be used in the classroom to introduce some of the most important questions in astrobiology. We present some of them below.

DNA Extraction: DNA is a biomolecule that constitutes the hereditary material of living beings. DNA contains the instructions that cells must follow to build an organism and keep it alive. All cells that make up an organism contain an identical copy of DNA. Each cell, however, reads a part of these instructions and that is why there are cells with different shapes and functions. The DNA extraction process is the first step of many of the protocols carried out in biotechnology laboratories and is what astrobiologists use to discover organisms adapted to extreme

environments or terrestrial analogues; and try to find out their adaptation mechanisms. Since DNA is found in all cells of living beings, in this experiment we will try to extract DNA from a sample using a simple procedure and using accessible ingredients.

DNA Replication: DNA replication is the biological process of producing two identical replicas of DNA from one original DNA molecule. DNA replication occurs in all living organisms acting as the most essential part of biological inheritance. In this experience, a DNA replication is performed live. In other words, it is done by using people acting as nucleobases and also as the family of enzymes that carry out DNA replication (see image below).

Impact Craters: When we observe through the telescope or look at images of the surface of the Moon, Mars, or Mercury we see that they are riddled with craters. How have they been formed? We know these craters are due to impacts of meteorites, rocky bodies that are part of the Solar System, such as the Sun and the planets and their moons. These impacts occurred millions, and even billions of years ago during the formation process of the Solar System and resulted in the craters seen on most planets and rocky moons in the Solar System. The craters have varied shapes, normally hemispherical, although there are some with an elliptical shape and they also have very different sizes. The largest ones generally have a central beak. In the most recent craters, rays of material can even be distinguished, coming out in all directions, produced by the material expelled from the interior of the crater. In this activity we are going to study how impact craters are produced by carrying out a small-scale simulation that will allow us to establish a simple model to explain their formation. This is the gateway to studying the Earth and other planet's formation and structure as well as exploring geological disturbances such as volcanoes, geological faults and earthquakes. This also serves to interest students in astronomy and planetary geology as they investigate craters on the Moon and other planets and their moons.

Water on Mars: The presence of liquid water on Mars has been investigated for more than a century. Images obtained by spacecraft orbiting the red planet show a geography with features such as canyons and river basins that appear to have been produced by liquid water in times past, when environmental conditions were very different from today. Today there is no liquid

water on the surface of Mars, water vapour represents only 0.01 % of its atmosphere and there are enormous reserves of ice in the subsoil, especially in the two polar caps. Why is there no liquid water? The reason lies in its environmental conditions, which make the water cycle on Mars different from that on Earth, so that it does not go through the liquid state, but rather goes directly from the solid to the gaseous state and vice versa. In this experiment, low-pressure conditions on Mars are simulated with a syringe with a cap to show how water cannot remain in a liquid state.

AstroJourneys

Speaker: Emmanuel Rollinde, LDAR, CY Cergy Paris Université, France

Collaborators: Astrojourneys Consortium

AstroJourneys is an Erasmus project that will run from September 2024 till August 2027. It gathers a consortium of nine partners from five countries and aims at the creation of an AI-assisted learning platform based on “the big ideas in Astronomy” (as defined by the Office of Astronomy for Education of the IAU), curriculum opportunities, and a selection of tools and resources. Resources will be designed in the form of inclusive research experiences based on Inquiry and Project Based Learning. AstroJourneys targets a large community of practice, with about 20 schools, including students, educators, families. Educators will personalise and differentiate the learners’ experiences, supporting their own learning rhythm and directly focusing on their competence profile development needs.

Talk link: https://youtu.be/yHL_x_zCio

AstroJourneys is the name of an Erasmus project that will run from September 2024 till August 2027. It gathers a consortium of nine partners from five countries, including observatories (OLA, FTP, IAC), science associations (NUCLIO, F-HOU) and societies (SPA), science didactics (LDAR-CYU), astrophysics center (MPIA-OAE) and schools (EA). AstroJourneys aims at the creation of an AI-assisted learning platform based on “the big ideas in Astronomy” (as defined by the Office of Astronomy for Education of the IAU). The structure of the platform will follow a 3D matrix correlating big ideas, curriculum opportunities, and a selection of tools and resources. Resources, from the members of the consortium, will be re-designed in the form of inclusive research experiences based on Inquiry and Project Based Learning. AstroJourneys targets a large community of practice, including students, educators, family, and stakeholders. Educators will specifically personalise and differentiate the learners’ experiences, supporting their own learning rhythm and directly focusing on their competence profile development needs.

From resources to journeys: The effort made by the OAE those past years have led to the creation of the “big ideas of astronomy”, the glossary of terms and images. Hence, the complexity of astronomy that may appear too much for many teachers, and specifically primary teachers, begins to be alleviated. Many of the hard questions asked by learners will find their answers there. Besides, a catalogue of activities reviewed by researchers and teachers is under construction through the AstroEdu website. The goal is not to do new activities. There have been numerous amazing activities done by groups of teachers, researchers and mediators all over the world. The focus here is to gather them and to provide a quality assurance to the users. However, getting access to pedagogical activities and answers to hard questions is still not enough to convince teachers to use astronomy in their class. They also need educational sequences. That is where Astrojourneys plays a role.

Building on the expertise of our nine partners, the list of pedagogical activities (including AstroEdu ones) will be even larger. The expertise in science and mathematics education, in inclusive education and in inquiry-based science education will be used to clarify the competencies that are at stake in school curricula, beyond the knowledge in astronomy and to ensure the compliance with UDL and Green competencies (see references below for further details). Then, once all resources are gathered, and once competencies are identified for each single activity, different journeys through those resources will be proposed. Those journeys may specifically be related to one of the big ideas. Hence, the universality of laws may be observed in different activities about movements in the Solar System, detection of exoplanets and measuring the mass of the black hole since all are related to the same laws, that of Kepler and Newton. The richness of the sky may be described by activities about different objects such as the Moon (and its phases), the Sun (and sun spots), the satellites of Jupiter, the detection of asteroids in images and so on. Images from AstroEdu will be very useful to illustrate that richness, while activities on scale models will allow to discuss the different magnitude of sizes and distances in the Universe. Finally, an AI-assisted learning platform associated with an innovative assessment framework will help educators personalise and differentiate the learners’ experiences, supporting their own learning rhythm and directly focusing on their competence profile development needs.

A community of practice: Students (primary to secondary) will, of course, be the immediate beneficiaries of the project. Still, the project will extend to the communities, inviting other members of their families to participate and benefit from the opportunities equally. We expect to engage five pilot schools per pilot country (France, Germany, Portugal and Greece), so 20 schools; three teachers per school from different subject, so 60 teachers; 20 students per school, so 400 students in total. A series of engaging and informative materials will be created to promote the project to the schools and their local communities. All efforts of all participating schools will be highlighted in the project’s social channels, and support will be provided to educators and learners to attract visibility to their work. Students participating in Astro-Journeys will find encouragement to pursue their own ideas and will certainly perceive the explored curriculum topics with a different attitude.

Resources:

- Student’s Profile by the end of Compulsory Schooling that the OECD is using as a reference document <https://cidadania.dge.mec.pt/sites/default/files/pdfs/students-profile.pdf>
- Universal Design for Learning (<https://udlguidelines.cast.org/>)

- https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/digcompedu/digcompedu-framework_en
- https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/greencomp-european-sustainability-competence-framework_en
- <https://www.oecd.org/education/cei/social-emotional-skills-study/beyond-academic-learning-92a11084-en.html>
- <https://astro4dev.org/oad-projects-and-their-link-to-sdgs/> (SDG)

The Role of Natural Effects of the Earth and Man-Made Structures in Learning Astronomy

Speaker: Hossein Khezri, Associate of Commission C5 Cultural Astronomy, Iran

Today, learning astronomy becomes more interesting for children when it is combined with other sciences. After three years of activity and photographing terrestrial phenomena such as: squares, alleys and mountains around the city during sunrise and sunset, I was able to teach the movement of the sun during different seasons to my elementary school students. At first, this topic was new to them and after learning mobile photography, they were able to use newer ideas in a scientific and attractive way to understand the concept of seasons, the length of days in different days of the year and the size of their shadow in different seasons.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/mlSOEb5W1eg>

Today, with the advancement of science and technology, especially in the field of artificial intelligence, we see that children and teenagers spend a lot of time on computer games and social media. Here, the role of a teacher becomes more challenging than before, and they must use new and attractive methods for teaching astronomy to students in order to have a positive impact. Having taught elementary schools for over ten years, I have noticed that elementary students have a greater thirst for learning and if they are on the right path, they can enjoy their knowledge well in the future. In our country, there is no special book or course about astronomy for elementary school students. We have a heavy duty to teach astronomy to elementary school students because, at this stage, students are not familiar with astronomical formulas and concepts, and methods that are simple, attractive and effective should be used. I used several methods to solve this problem that I mention below: 1. The start of schools in our country coincides with the September equinox. I asked the parents of the students to gather

Figure 1: Left: The statue of Rostam and his horse (Rakhsh)-Bushehr-Iran. Center: Angular distance between the Moon and Venus. Right: A four-arched structure from three thousand years ago – the Sasanian Empire period.

next to a statue near the beach a week before the start of the school year, and all the students take pictures of the sunset with their mobile phones at a certain point. We repeated this activity two weeks later. Besides watching the beautiful sunset and the play of colors on the horizon, I showed the students some interesting results:

1. Finding east.
2. Knowledge of planets, stars and angular distances: I divided the students in groups of three. One student is responsible for taking pictures, the second is responsible for measuring, and the third is responsible for recording information. This method created empathy between them, and I compared the angular outputs without competition or grading. They realized that they do not need advanced tools to learn astronomy at first, and they can get to know the sky above them better by doing teamwork.
3. Recognizing astronomical monuments and trying to preserve our heritage: In coordination with the school principal, I took my students on a camp trip to historical places that had astronomical uses. Thus seeing the precision in astronomical structures made students' minds more involved in the application of astronomy in life and the question arose in their minds of how and why they built their structures with such precision in the past?

In the end, it is important to mention that students do not need a complex device to better understand the sky and know their environment. In order to stay away from mobile phones and computer games, they need affection, empathy, and group activities. We teachers can strengthen this issue with practical work and help spread it.

Astronomy and Children's Literature in the Early Years of Elementary School

Speaker: Elizandra Daneize Santos, São Paulo State University (UNESP), Brazil

Collaborator: Rodolfo Langhi (UNESP)

The approach to Astronomy is essential in the Early Years of Elementary School, as it is present in our daily lives, it is perceived by the curious eyes of children who usually observe the sky and the stars visible during the day and night. The objective is to highlight children's literature as an important methodological resource in the teaching and learning of Astronomy, and to report some strategies developed for this stage of teaching. The qualitative approach allowed an analysis of some theoretical frameworks to realize a "state of knowledge". The results show that children's literature favors interdisciplinary work, enabling the student to construct knowledge with the pleasure of listening to stories, making discoveries and relating to what is observed daily.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/fmulR2b1ezI>

The approach to Astronomy is essential in the early years of Elementary School, as it is present in our daily lives, it is perceived by the curious eyes of children who usually observe the sky and the visible stars during the day and night. The objective is to highlight children's literature as an important methodological resource in the teaching and learning of Astronomy and to report some strategies developed for this stage of teaching. The qualitative approach allowed an analysis of some theoretical references on the subject. The results show that children's literature favours an interdisciplinary work, enabling the student to build knowledge with the pleasure of listening to stories, making discoveries and relating to what is observed daily.

Children's literature can enable a dialogue between the disciplines that make up the curriculum of the early years of Elementary School, providing interdisciplinary work with many possibilities. In the teaching of science, which encompasses the contents of Astronomy, children's literature can help in the construction of meanings and attribution of meanings to the facts that the child observes and presents curiosities to know more about. The use of children's stories enables the student to interpret facts with main consequences for society, providing a new view of reality. It can also lead to a problem, which has the potential to be solved through a process with some approximations with methodological proposals regarding investigative work.

Learning Astronomy implies understanding celestial phenomena, which despite being observable daily and arousing curiosity, are abstract for students at this stage, which intensifies the need for interdisciplinary, playful work that enables participatory reflection and meaningful learning. Astronomy allows the individual to know themselves, understand the dimensions of the universe and act consciously on our planet.

We developed methodological guidelines for a class of the 3rd year of the initial years of

Elementary School. The starting point was a children's story book, as we consider that children's literature is a great teaching strategy to assist in the introduction and approach of the contents that will be worked on. The book is "Here We Are – Notes on Living on Planet Earth" by Oliver Jeffers. The author proposes a reflection on aspects of the planet we live on from different points of view and the life we lead on it, takes on the voice of a father who talks to his newborn son, giving small pieces of advice that value life and passes on simple and fun lessons of survival on Earth. Among so many important reflections, one of them is about not being alone on the planet, because like a drop in the ocean, we are just one among the billions of living beings that live on Earth and we must understand the importance of sharing, tolerance, and respect (JEFFERS, 2018).

The teaching strategies involved the Science Curricular Component with the thematic unit "Earth and Universe", the Objects of Knowledge "Characteristics of the Earth" and "Observation of the Sky", and the Skills: Identify characteristics of the Earth (such as its spherical shape, the presence of water, soil, etc.) based on the observation, manipulation and comparison of different forms of representation of the planet (maps, globes, photographs, etc.); Observe, identify and record the daily periods (day and/or night) in which the Sun, other stars, Moon and planets are visible in the sky (BRASIL, 2018). The Mathematics curricular component in the same class is also involved, with the thematic unit "Quantities and Measures", the Knowledge Object "Time measurements: reading time on digital and analog clocks, duration of events and recognition of relationships between units of time measurement", and the Skills: Reading and recording measures and time intervals; Using clocks (analog and digital) to inform the start and end times of an activity and its duration; Reading time on digital and analog clocks and recognizing the relationship between hour and minutes and between minute and seconds (BRASIL, 2018).

The specific objectives were: to understand and analyse the characteristics of planet Earth; observe the Sun using an appropriate filter; observe the apparent movement of the Sun using one's own body as a gnomon; understand the movements of the Earth, relating day and night and the length of the year, as well as the four seasons, establish relationships between the length of the day and the hours when working with sundials and conventional clocks, and relate the contents of Science and Mathematics, establishing an interdisciplinary work.

The contextualization began with oral questions to introduce the contents, the questions are broad and enable the teacher to understand the students' previous knowledge: Where do we live? What is this place like? Do you know what it is made of? What is in it? What can we do in the different spaces that exist? Some questions were sent for the students to dialogue with their families, and in the next class, in a conversation circle, everyone was able to expose information from the dialogue, such as: What do we usually do during the day? And during the night? What do we see in the sky during the day? What do we see in the night sky? What are the family's habits, what do they usually do daily? These questions were asked again at the end of the sequence with all the strategies that will be addressed below. The aim was to analyse whether the students went through a conceptual evolution during the process of knowledge construction with the strategies developed. And, through the final answers, we probed that the students learned the knowledge explored in a useful and positive way.

By relating children's stories with the skills of the Science discipline, students were presented with some representations of planet Earth, such as the use of a terrestrial globe, maps and real photographs. For this stage of teaching, the notion of belonging to the planet may be

Figure 1: Observation of the shadow of one's own body from exposure to the Sun and observation of the Sun using a suitable filter (Source: Authors' collection).

a little abstract for students to understand. Therefore, the demonstration and exploration of the location in Google Earth of the place where the student was, at that moment, was of fundamental importance. It is necessary to understand starting from the micro to the macro, that is, the place where the student is inserted (school, streets near the school, neighbourhood of the school and neighbouring neighbourhoods, city – which is part of daily experiences), to understand what is more abstract (neighbouring municipalities, state, country, until obtaining the visualization of other countries, continents and the entire planet).

The students understood the concept of representation aimed at up to this stage of development of the planned strategies. The notion of size, in which we cannot observe our planet as a whole, because its size is much larger than our eyes can reach, and because we are inserted in it, was understandable. Therefore, the use of terrestrial globes, maps, and photographs, and even Google Earth, which are representations smaller than reality, is justified, so that we can observe and understand what planet Earth is like.

To observe, identify, and record the daily periods (day and/or night) in which the star Sun and other stars are visible in the sky, the following activities were developed: 1. Observation of the shadow of their own body from exposure to the Sun - the students played with their own shadow, performing movements; 2. Sun observation with filter: we use an appropriate filter with the necessary guidelines to make a safe observation, so that there is no damage to visual health; 3. Observation of the apparent movement of the Sun: markings were made at various times during the class period, in which the student's own body was represented as a gnomon, and the markings made on the floor made it possible to observe the apparent movement of the Sun during a certain time; 4. Rotation and translation/revolution movements: we use a globe and a lamp to simulate the movements of the Earth and relate it to day and night.

These activities were well appreciated by the students, as moments of play and relaxation were provided that differ from the profile normally experienced at school, which is to spend much of the time inside the classroom space. The simple fact of leaving the room and going to an open and spacious place already awakens in the student a feeling of curiosity and desire to learn new things. The intention was precisely to provide moments of playfulness so that scientific concepts could be approached and incorporated gradually.

All the data collected during the development of the aforementioned teaching strategies, involv-

ing oral reports, written and pictorial records, contributed to analyse the students' understanding and the conceptual evolution through which they passed, from the beginning, with the initial and common sense conceptions, to the final conceptions, imbued with scientific knowledge. The way in which the skills of the curricular components of Science and Mathematics were approached highlights the importance of interdisciplinary, objective, and meaningful work.

In addition to being a tool that facilitates the cognitive and social development of students, children's literature can mediate the understanding of concepts related to the universe, becoming an important methodological resource allied to the teaching and learning process of Astronomy. In addition to the curiosities presented by individuals in the early years of Elementary School, it can also awaken the desire to know new things, question more about the observable sky and clarify information disseminated by the electronic media or by common sense knowledge.

References:

- BRASIL. Ministério da Educação. Base Nacional Comum Curricular: Educação é a Base. Brasília/DF, 2018.
- JEFFERS, O. Aqui estamos nós: notas sobre como viver no planeta Terra. Tradução de Yukari Fujimura. São Paulo: Salamandra, 2018.

The Penn State Inservice Workshops in Astronomy (PSIWA)

Speaker: W. Niel Brandt, Penn State University, USA

The PSIWA, now operating for 20+ years, are week-long summer workshops for Pennsylvania high-school physics and Earth/space science teachers aimed at helping them teach their students about stars, black holes, cosmology, and other topics. They serve as a high-leverage method of improving understanding of astronomy; each of the attending teachers will teach hundreds of students. Teachers from diverse, under-served school districts are specifically recruited with scholarship funds. The PSIWA programs include lectures on subject material, discussions of pedagogical approaches, hands-on activities, nighttime observing, and guest presentations. I will describe the accomplishments of the PSIWA, their future prospects, and broader lessons learned.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/vE5bY60mZbg>

The Penn State Inservice Workshops in Astronomy (PSIWA), now operating for almost three decades, are week-long summer workshops for high-school (and sometimes middle-school)

teachers aimed at providing content and activities that help them teach their students. The PSIWA serve as a high-leverage method of improving participation in and understanding of astronomy across Pennsylvania; each of the attending teachers will teach hundreds of students. Teachers from diverse, underserved school districts are specifically recruited with scholarship funds.

I have served annually as the lead instructor for one intensive PSIWA workshop (with about 12-18 attending teachers) for about 25 years. Critical PSIWA teaching is also done by Dr. Chris Palma, an experienced outreach leader and author of astronomy education articles, and Mr. Glenn Goldsborough, a master teacher of physics/astronomy at Pennsbury High School. The PSIWA programs include lectures on subject material, discussions about pedagogical approaches, hands-on activities, examinations of curricular materials, nighttime observing, and guest presentations. My recent workshops have been titled “Black Holes: Gravity’s Fatal Attraction”, “The Origins and Fate of Our Cosmos: Understanding Big-Bang Cosmology”, and “The Lives and Deaths of Stars”. The first, for example, introduces teachers to the predicted properties of black holes (BH) and the astronomical evidence for their existence. Topics covered include the fates of massive stars, stellar-mass and supermassive BHs, active galaxies, cosmic jets, BH-galaxy connections, gravitational waves, Hawking radiation, and singularities. We also regularly detail exciting astronomical facilities and ongoing/upcoming surveys, including the Sloan Digital Sky Survey and the Vera C. Rubin Observatory. In my talk, I review the basic nature of the PSIWA, the audience served, instructors and standards, the details of our 2024 BH workshop, and assessment and follow-up. I end by covering broader lessons learned that may be useful to others aiming to develop such workshops.

Bridging Scientists and Students with Regional School Partnerships

Speaker: Jackie Bondell, University of Melbourne, Australia

The ARC Centre of Excellence for Dark Matter Particle Physics has developed a partner school program to build long-term collaborations with traditionally underserved regional and rural schools in Australia. Now in its fourth year, this program has expanded to seven schools across two states. Here, we discuss: The inspiration, drive, and support behind the development of the program; The structure of the program and its alignment with the centre's scientific research; An overview of the scaffolded and curriculum-aligned lessons covering topics such as gravity, the galaxies, the nature of science, and particle models; and an update on the evaluation of the efficacy of the program in conjunction with the University of Melbourne Faculty of Education.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/lZokBEYJo3I>

The ARC Centre of Excellence for Dark Matter Particle Physics has developed a partner school program to build long-term collaborations with traditionally underserved regional and rural schools in Australia. Now in its fourth year, this program has expanded to seven school across two states.

Here, we discuss: The inspiration, drive, and support behind the development of the program; The structure of the program and its alignment with the centre's scientific research; An overview of the scaffolded and curriculum-aligned lessons covering topics such as gravity, the galaxies, the nature of science, and particle models; and an update on the evaluation of the efficacy of the program in conjunction with the University of Melbourne Faculty of Education.

What is an ARC Centre of Excellence? The ARC Centre of Excellence for Dark Matter Particle Physics (CDM) brings together experts from across Australia and internationally to unlock the secrets of dark matter and foster the science and engineering leaders of the future. The [ARC Centre of Excellence for Dark Matter Particle Physics](#) aims to: Discover the particle nature of dark matter using state-of-the-art experiments based in Australia; Develop new technologies for the next generation of dark matter experiments and spin-off wider applications; and Create new theories of Nature that contain dark matter particles and describe their interactions. It is a multi-university research collaborative with scientists across seven universities in Australia and in partnerships with international research organisations such as INFN and CERN. One key project is the construction of the Southern Hemisphere's first underground physics lab, which was built a kilometer underground at the bottom of Stawell Gold Mine in regional Victoria. The [CDM Outreach and Education](#) portfolio leads the Centre's strategic approach to school partnerships and public engagement programs. The vision is to share the excitement and benefits of Australia's hunt for dark matter to inspire and train a new generation of innovative thinkers. The Dark Matter Partner Schools program is part of this portfolio and focuses on the

Image 1: Map of Partner schools

goals of increasing the uptake of and access to STEM opportunities for traditionally underserved groups while developing programs and resources to support educators.

What is the Dark Matter Regional Partner Schools Program? A core component of the education program is the development of long-term engagements with regional schools in regional and rural areas of Australia. The goal is to meet with students at all year levels over multiple years at select regional and rural schools to increase diversity in science by creating more pathways for student engagement. It also provides the opportunity to bring CDM's ECRs into the classroom to meet with large groups of students. We have developed interactive lessons and piloted these curriculum-aligned education activities at Stawell Secondary College in Victoria, home of the Stawell Underground Physics Lab. This program has expanded to schools across Victoria and New South Wales. The Centre also collaborates with the University of Melbourne Faculty School of Education to study the impact of these contemporary physics lessons on students' science belonging. This program also offers opportunities for Year 11 and 12 students from our partner schools to take on year-long research projects in conjunction with our universities under the mentorship of CDM PhD students and early career researchers.

This summary focuses on three main components of this program: The structure of the scaffolded lessons; the extended investigation opportunities for upper-level students, and the impact study by the University of Melbourne Faculty of Education.

The goal of the program is to engage students with multiple touchpoints over their secondary learning to connect them with contemporary Australian science and identify pathways to continued engagement, education, and possible careers in STEM. Secondary school in Australia traditionally starts in Year 7, when students are around 12 years old. With each partner school, CDM begins by delivering interactive, curriculum-aligned, and hands-on sessions with each of the school's Year 7 classes. This session looks at how we can learn about things we cannot see. Students discuss ways they learn about and measure stuff they cannot see. This lesson uses the CERN 3-D printed Mystery Box activity expanded to align with how scientists collaborate to learn about challenging new science. In the second year with each partner school, we will see the new Year 7 students and Year 8 students, who will get their second touchpoint with the centre's scientists. The Year 8 activity focuses on gravity and forces, using a gravity well to understand the basics of mass, distance, and orbits, and how this applies in the Solar System.

Image 2: Gravity Well

Image 3: Research Students

Then they will learn about the rotation of stars in spiral galaxies and discuss the contrast to what was expected. The pattern will follow over the next two years, with the students getting their third and fourth touchpoints in Years 9 and 10, with lessons on using light to map dark matter and the structure of matter, respectively. These themes and activities were developed in conjunction with teachers at the partner schools. At all schools, CDM also runs lessons for Year 11 and 12 Physics students in areas such as the Standard Model, Gravitation, Muons and Special Relativity, and General Relativity. A summary of these activities have been presented to teachers across Australia and published in education journals.

Another unique feature of this program is the opportunity to provide research opportunities for Year 11 and 12 Physics students to complete year-long research projects with mentorship from CDM scientists. There is a particular focus on muon detection as part of the underground laboratory and this topic aligns well with learning goals for Physics students. Additionally, a startup called mDetect is a spinoff from the Dark Matter Centre. [mDetect](#) has developed a robust and portable muon detector for educational purposes. CDM provides muon detectors and mentoring to allow regional students to study muons, special relativity, data analysis, and other related topics as an extended investigation project. Additionally, CDM is collaborating with educators and scientists in the US for a project to team Australian and American students in projects looking at high-altitude physics with muon detectors on high-altitude balloons.

The third aspect of this project in this summary is the education research study in conjunction with the University of Melbourne Faculty of Education. The study is to look at the impact of longitudinal programs that link scientists with students in regional and rural locations. The education researchers leading the study are using surveys, focus groups, and interviews with teachers, students, and administrators over five years to learn more about impacts from the program. COVID restrictions on allowing researchers into schools delayed to project. However, after a few of years some trends are starting to emerge. Early evidence shows that this has a positive impact on the students' sense of science belonging. Year to year students remember the previous visits, the activities they did, and welcome the regular visits from the 'Dark Matter people'. A second trend is that there is a sense of pride associated with the regional Stawell Underground Physics Lab and students and teachers associate positively with the locality connection of the science to the school.

This is an ongoing project and CDM looks forward to providing future updates. Please reach out to Jackie.bondell[at]unimelb.edu.au to further discuss this program.

Reference: Bondell, J. (2023) Dark Matter Detection: From the Lab to the Classroom. SASTA Journal Number 1 & 2 2023

Experiences in Creating and Implementing a Course for Astronomy as its Own Subject in High School

Speaker: Melissa Solares, NAEC Guatemala, American School of Guatemala, Guatemala

Astronomy education is the perfect area of opportunity to inspire the next generation of scientists. This talk showcases the work, educational strategies, and experience gained through developing and implementing the first program in Guatemala for teaching Astronomy as its own subject in High School. Starting in the year 2018, it has successfully run in two different schools and more than 400 students have successfully completed the course. As a result, students have asked for astrophysics as a follow up course to run this year as part of their science electives. Following the implementation, there have also been students that chose to join aerospace engineering and astrophysics programs as their college majors, proving to be successful in engaging young adults towards studying science.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/zQSPAorW-eY>

Figure 1: Astronomy course content distribution by units.

1. How to get started: Setting a foundation for your Astronomy Course.

Framework: Getting the initial background knowledge through diplomas, open ed. courses, self-study and mentorships. Be a student before teaching your students. In my experience, I did this through: Astronomy courses in college + teaching degree + Astronomy Diploma.
Explore other curricula: Take ideas from already existing and implemented curricula around the world. Document your findings, find connections, ask for expert revisions. Peer evaluation is key. In my experience, I did this through: Phenomenological Research + State of the Art.

Adapt and create: Your expertise and knowledge is the most valuable tool in the artistic process of creating your own curriculum! Set high standards, assess and then adapt. This is an exciting ongoing process! The final course has five units of content described in Figure 1.

2. First steps and trials: Experiences during the first years running the course

<p><u>2018 - 2019</u> Small groups (12 to 15 students); 13 through 15 years old</p> <p>Highly conceptual for a low-tech population</p> <p>I struggled looking for Hands-on activities</p> <p>Difficulties keeping squirmy students engaged</p>	<p><u>2020 - 2022</u> Larger groups (20 to 25 students); 16 to 18 years old Hands-on, inquiry and research driven</p> <p>high-tech population Hybrid and Virtual classes</p> <p>I focused mostly on individual learning strategies, found success in summative group projects</p>
<p><u>2023 to present day</u> About 120 students sign-up for Astronomy every year A new teacher joined the course! 25 students per class Astrophysics running as a New course! Students choosing Astrophysics and Aerospace engineering as their college majors!</p>	

3. Strategies for Teens: How to engage Gen Z teenagers in Science. Universal Design for Learning as a framework for planning my Astronomy classes:

Engagement	Representation	Action and Expression
Theoretical classes with specific note-taking templates	Vocabulary Slides	Interviews as a way of assessment
Jig Saw-like reading guides	Flashcards Articles, podcasts, videos	Communicating astronomical information/news/concepts through social media
Edpuzzles, Nearpods, Quizlets, Kahoots	Students researching using AI tools	Students teaching students from lower grades
Models!!!	Completing CER charts with the use of simulations	Comic book making, memes and children's books
Observation and documenting phenomena		Creating and playing board games

Figure 2: Students reading their comic books about eclipses to a Kindergarten class (left) and playing a board game they creating about the stellar life cycle in their High School class (center). A student from an after school Astronomy club holding a book she wrote on observational astronomy in Guatemala (right).

4. ECAs and Star Pupils: How to provide opportunities outside the course. Astronomy clubs are an amazing starting point! National and international contests: Catch a Star hosted by the EAAE, Space Art contest by the EAAE, Astronomy Olympiads - OGA & OLAA. Conferences and college level talks. LISTEN to students, let them inspire you!

Every step we take towards including Astronomy education counts: every little astronomical example or analogy we include in our practice, every small talk after class, every question we decide to respond to instead of dismissing, and every student we inspire to follow their passion. What we do today counts, so why not start now?

Authentic Research Experiences for High School Students in Astronomy

Speaker: Heidi Schran, Talawanda High School, USA

Collaborator: Joanna Hohn (Miami University)

Authentic research experiences for young people (women especially) in astronomy is rare; however, it is exceptionally meaningful and inspiring. My team of students and I were fortunate to participate in a unique research experience where we collected data during the recent total solar eclipse and live streamed our images to the NASA Edge website and the DEB Initiative. An NSF grant allowed for our team to receive the equipment needed and be trained to collect this data. We met throughout the winter and spring to practice, learn more about the science behind eclipses, and to do outreach events in our community. The students' relationship to the process of conducting scientific research became much more positive than before, and their knowledge of astronomy increased.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/JnNQxI5-mGI>

Providing research opportunities to High School students in Astronomy is extremely rewarding but can be challenging for many reasons. Much of naked-eye astronomy occurs at night when school is not in session, and equipment can be expensive or difficult to use. Therefore, many lessons are textbook or worksheet based. Laboratory activities can help with conceptualizing concepts (such as with creating a scaled Solar System to size and distance, or simulating impacts and crater formation); however, original research is difficult for students to experience. Last year's total solar eclipse across North America allowed me to provide this opportunity to my students.

I was chosen to participate in a National Science Foundation (NSF) funded citizen science research opportunity to collect data on the Sun's corona during the total solar eclipse. The grant funded the equipment and training as well as some expenses for 20 team leaders that worked with high school aged students and resided in the path of totality. We were trained on the equipment and then were instructed to choose a team of students and train them in time for the eclipse. I selected and trained a group of nine students, ranging from 15 to 19 years of age. This training took place from November up to the weekend prior to the eclipse. Many of the training sessions were only with our group; however, there were multiple whole group sessions to allow the people collecting all of the information to rehearse and identify any issues.

Late winter, our team was identified as one of seven different teams to livestream video feed from our telescope through Southern Illinois University (SIU). There it would be selected at various times throughout the eclipse and streamed on the NASA Edge website. This required new equipment and programs (that were provided), as well as a separate set of large group

practices. Two of my students were eager to be in charge of this and mastered the setup and use of the streaming equipment quickly.

The students learned more about eclipses during these practice sessions, in part due to multiple outreach events where they were asked to be an authority on the subject. They shared their knowledge and excitement at various venues and to people of all ages. The month before the eclipse, the students and I conducted multiple interviews with the local newspapers as well as television news shows. By this time the students were experts in what they were doing and very excited about the upcoming eclipse, therefore they were more confident and continued to improve their communication and public speaking skills.

The eclipse day provided us with multiple challenges, each handled by the team. The NASA team at SIU had some technical difficulties and our stream was never shown; however my students did an excellent job and handled this disappointment with professionalism. The images taken and uploaded to SIU were of high quality and used as the baseline for processing all of their eclipse data. This meant that the students did their job - the images were in focus, had appropriate light exposure, centered and oriented correctly.

The team was given surveys to take at the beginning (first practice) and at the end of the experience (our data party), aimed at identifying if there were any ways the students' relationship to science and any STEM careers and subjects changed. The final survey was conducted by a member from the Rockman Group during a Data Party about two weeks following the eclipse. The results indicated that all of the students involved in my group completed the project with more enjoyment and confidence working in science and conducting scientific research, as well as had a wonderful experience. During the Data Party, the students were able to be social and relaxed, share photos from the day in a common folder and take some home on a USB drive. We also examined the data we had as of that time, and students had the opportunity to make copies of the files and run various programs to try to "clean up" the images. A few of the students chose to use their experience with the group as the subject and data for a capstone project required in one of my classes.

Authentic research experiences are difficult to execute in the typical secondary school classroom despite it being one of the best ways for students to truly learn the science and to be inspired beyond the school year. Through outside grant funding I was able to acquire equipment that can be used for years to come for future students and other citizen science opportunities. Having used it to take images of the sun, I train my students to use it during my Astronomy classes to capture images of the sun and track the movements of sunspots over time. This opportunity through a citizen science research grant allowed not only for an amazing memorable experience, but empowered me with a tool for students to conduct their own research in my classes.

Recreating the Early Universe in Classrooms: Leveraging Augmented Reality and ChatGPT in Astrophysics

Speaker: Aishwarya Girdhar, Ludwig Maximilian University, Germany

Collaborators: A. Çoban (LMU), M. Warkentin (LMU), C. Hoyer (LMU), J. Kuhn (LMU)

The ALICE particle detector at CERN's Large Hadron Collider studies quark-gluon plasma to gain insights into the early Universe and dark matter. To bridge this advanced research with secondary education, a learning module is being developed that incorporates augmented reality (AR) for effective visualisation, ChatGPT as an AI tutor for personalized learning and LEGO models as educational aids for haptic interaction. The module educates students about ALICE's collaboration with the International Space Station in dark matter research. The learning module uses AR and AI to enhance learning while balancing for cognitive load. The talk introduces the module, discusses its development, and explores the interdisciplinary collaboration aimed at advancing science education.

Bringing the Universe into the Classroom: Integrating Astronomy Through Math Problems

Speaker: Eleen Hammer, Friedrich Schiller University Jena, Germany

Collaborator: Holger Cartarius (Friedrich Schiller University Jena)

It is unfortunate that not all school students have access to Astronomy education. To address this gap, this project develops mathematics problems centered around astronomy, aimed at students in grades 5 through 10. By using astronomical facts and laws as the basis for these problems, it is ensured that students engage with celestial concepts, even if astronomy is not part of their formal curriculum. In the talk exemplary problems are shown to illustrate how astronomical content can be integrated into math problems. The problems are created to be accessible for teachers with minimal or no background in astronomy, allowing them to use them with confidence. Additionally, the mathematics problems have been tested in schools, and the results are presented.

Talk link: https://youtu.be/Vv6WD76_85Q

Figure 1: Astronomical topics used for the math problem. (Credit: Solar System: rwarnbick/iStock unter <https://www.scinexx.de/wp-content/uploads/s/o/solarhighwayg.jpg>, Exoplanet: <https://user-images.githubusercontent.com/24231101/38481586-60ea1a90-3b80-11e8-8c1c-3d60a4309a73.jpg>, Black Hole: http://www.nasa.gov/mission_pages/nustar/multimedia/pia16695.html, SpaceX: https://static3.seekingalpa.com/uploads/2016/10/9932311_14762033139782_rId4.jpg, Abell 2744: <https://sci.esa.int/web/hubble/-/53574-hubble-frontier-fields-view-of-abell-2744>

Why Astronomy in mathematics lessons?

Astronomy often struggles to secure a spot in school timetables. Unfortunately, many schools offer only very few lessons per week on the subject, if any at all. In some instances, astronomy is incorporated into the physics curriculum, while in others, it's entirely absent from formal education. Germany is no different in this regard. For this reason, I chose to introduce some astronomical concepts into my mathematics lessons.

In Germany, only three out of the 16 federal states offer astronomy as a separate subject in lower secondary school (grades 5 to 10). As a result, some students finish school without even a basic understanding of the universe or the celestial objects they see every day. On the other hand, mathematics is a compulsory subject across all grades, with students attending four to five lessons per week.

During math lessons, students typically encounter applied or word problems, which present a scenario (often loosely based on real life) that must be broken down. These applied problems involve an additional subject matter beyond just mathematics. An analysis of math textbooks reveals what these topics are and shows that astronomy is the least used topic for applied math problems in the series studied. By creating applied math problems focused on astronomy, students can be introduced to various astronomical facts and laws. Using real-world data for these problems also enhances the experience, offering a more authentic alternative to the often contrived scenarios found in traditional math exercises.

After the PISA shock in 2001, the German education system was re-evaluated, leading to a new focus in curricula and teaching approaches: competence-based education. Although these guidelines have been in place for over 20 years, there was little material in mathematics instruction up until the 2000s that aligned with these standards and effectively fostered the development of mathematical competencies. There is, therefore, a clear need in this area.

Goal: The goal is to integrate astronomical concepts into mathematics lessons by adapting them as the context or subject of math problems for lower secondary school students, specifically in grades 5 to 10. This approach aims to introduce both fundamental knowledge – the contents that usually get taught in the separate Astronomy subject, if it exists – and modern astronomical topics.

Adapting astronomical content for mathematics lessons involves aligning it with the students'

age, skills, and the relevant mathematical topics. Astronomical topics can be drawn from basic astronomy, recent research, or media highlights. Depending on the selection, either a fact, data set, or astrophysical law is used. If a fact is chosen, the problem requires focus on the conveying of this fact, while if data sets or laws are chosen, the problems may need a more detailed explanation. Once the topic is chosen, it is paired with appropriate mathematical content. In competence-based curricula, problems are designed to foster specific skills and can be open or closed. Including a teacher's comment helps clarify the astronomical topic and any necessary simplifications of the Astronomical content made in the problem's explanation. It also helps alleviate any hesitation teachers may have in using the problems, particularly for those who are not specialized in astronomy.

Arithmetic/Algebra	Statistics	Geometry
points in coordinate system	statistical parameters	angle types and sizes
spacetime diagramme	sunspots and solar activity	Mars rovers

in part group work
partner work

Figure 2: Three exemplary problems that are shown in the presentation. (Credit: picture of Perseverance rover: <https://www.facebook.com/NationalSpaceCentre/posts/missionmars-art-attack-get-your-colouring-pencils-out-and-learn-all-about-nasas-/10157327500116003/>, edited by Eleen Hammer)

Examples: Three examples from grade 5 and 6 will be presented during the talk. The examples come from different areas of mathematics.

The first example focuses on plotting points in a coordinate system and is a closed problem. Astronomically, it explores spacetime diagrams – how to read them and what information a point in the coordinate system provides.

The second example deals with solar activity, using monthly or yearly averages of sunspot numbers to perform statistical analysis. By working with this real data, students learn about the variability of the Sun and independently reconstruct the Schwabe cycle. This problem is also closed but includes a subtask best suited for group work or whole-class collaboration.

The third example comes from geometry and covers types of angles and angle measurements. Astronomically, it focuses on the Mars rovers Perseverance and Curiosity. The task's introduction explains to students the missions of these rovers, their achievements, and discoveries. Through solving the problem, students gain an understanding of the rovers' components and hopefully come to appreciate the technological feat they represent. This task is a completely open problem

designed for pair work. You are welcome to try it out in your own lessons!

Pupils' Feedback: The developed problems were tested in schools, with 185 pupils from grades 6, 8, and 10 participating. For each 45-minute class, I used a learning station approach, allowing students to choose which problems to work on. In the talk the feedback is presented from 47 sixth graders who tried the Mars Rover problem and others of similar level as the other two problems shown. The evaluation form was simple, with students rating their experience on a scale from most negative to most positive.

The results of the student survey are quite positive and support the project. First, students were asked how much they knew about the astronomical topic before working on the problem. Following that, they were asked to assess their learning progress. Approximately 94% reported that they had learned something new, with the extent of this learning varying. The feedback on how the problems were received by students was also favorable. The majority found the astronomical topics interesting, and, especially when compared to traditional textbook problems, the developed problems were rated highly.

POSTER CONTRIBUTIONS

STEM+A@Astronomy: Integrating Astronomy into Curriculum by Engineering Design and Science Inquiry

Presenter: Exodus Chun-Long Sit, Starrix, Hong Kong, China

With the increasing popularity of astronomy education and space science, teaching astronomy has emerged as a new feature in formal education within schools, fostering learner's astronomy literacy and creative problem-solving skills. By applying engineering design cycles and scientific inquiry, teachers can facilitate the application of astronomical knowledge to real-world situations. STEM+A@Astronomy, as an interdisciplinary project, aims to cultivate learner's incentives and curiosity about night sky observation, space science, and planetary science through experiential learning and hands-on experience. It can also apply to modular lessons in formal primary education to provide an intensive learning experience for students in their daily life.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14321146>

STEM+A@Astronomy represents an innovative interdisciplinary endeavor to enrich public comprehension of astronomical science while tackling critical environmental concerns, notably urban light pollution, and excessive outdoor lighting. The initiative seeks to raise awareness about the detrimental effects of artificial light at night (ALAN) on nocturnal skies and ecological systems (Sit, 2021). Engaging a wide array of targeted learners, including students, educators, and community members, STEM+A@Astronomy go beyond merely showcasing the marvels of the cosmos. It emphasizes the significance of safeguarding dark skies for astronomical observations and environmental well-being.

As an astronomy educator and science communicator, I am deeply committed to advancing science education in Hong Kong, particularly in astronomy and the natural sciences. Our educational approach revolves around two distinct learning frameworks that align with the local mainstream science education paradigm. We focus on enhancing curriculum development through the integration of the PDIR (Plan, Do, Improve, and Review) engineering design model. This framework underscores problem-solving in real-life contexts, akin to the design thinking approach, and incorporates hands-on experiences. Students are involved in constructing prototypes, refining them based on user feedback, and presenting their findings to wider audiences, nurturing their scientific communication skills and promoting scientific literacy and self-reflection.

Utilizing an inquiry-based learning strategy (science inquiry learning), which involves planning, doing, analyzing, and reflecting (PDAR), students learn to gather evidence, conduct experiments,

Figure 1: 3 core elements of astronomy education in the process of popular science communication and classroom, proposed by Exodus Chun-Long Sit.

Figure 2: Activities about design thinking and social innovation in the STEM+A@Astronomy Project.

and formulate hypotheses. They analyze outcomes by comparing controlled and experimental setups, consistently posing questions to deepen their comprehension. By developing their prototypes, students have the chance to exhibit their projects at STEAM education fairs and science communication venues. These experiences foster social innovation, enabling students to apply their knowledge to address real-world challenges, cultivate empathy, and provide support to those in need. Through this dynamic learning journey, students can not only explore their passions, but they can also make meaningful contributions to society.

Reference: Sit, E.C.L. (2021). Decoding the Starry Night: A Guide to Stargazing and Astrophotography. (1st ed., pp.134-145). Cosmos Book

Equipping Educators Through a Train-the-Trainer Mental Health Initiative

Presenter: Dominic Vertue, Office of Astronomy for Development, South Africa

Collaborator: Kelly Blumenthal (Office of Astronomy Outreach)

This abstract provides an overview of a Train-the-Trainer program designed to equip outreach practitioners with the skills to implement astronomy-based mental health activities in educational settings. Developed in collaboration with psychologists and outreach professionals, this three-day workshop integrates psychological principles with practical astronomy, guided by the IAU Office of Astronomy for Development's Mental Health Workbook. Core topics include human behaviour, communication, ACT, group facilitation, ethical considerations, and monitoring strategies. The program emphasizes fostering STEM identity in adolescents while promoting well-being and explores potential longitudinal studies to assess impact.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14479724>

The "OAD x OAO Train-The-Trainer Workshop" aims to equip participants with tools and knowledge to promote mental health through astronomy-based activities. This workshop is part of the larger "Astronomy for Mental Health" initiative, a collaborative effort between the Office of Astronomy for Development (OAD) and the Office of Astronomy Outreach (OAO). This initiative explores how astronomical concepts and activities can support well-being, mental health awareness, and stress management.

Workshop Overview: The workshop's flow is designed to ensure gradual introduction and practical engagement with the Astronomy for Mental Health tool, which is grounded in psychological principles such as Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT). Participants are guided through a series of activities that enable them to familiarize themselves with the tool and explore its practical application.

1. **Introduction and Overview:** The workshop begins by introducing participants to the concept of using astronomy to promote mental health. This introductory session covers the background and goals of the "Astronomy for Mental Health" initiative, explaining how astronomical activities—such as stargazing and cosmic storytelling—can be used as mindfulness practices and reflection tools to improve mental well-being.
2. **Tool Introduction & Demonstration:** Participants will learn about how astronomy-based activities can encourage mindfulness, reflection, and emotional regulation. For instance, stargazing activities can promote mindfulness, while cosmic storytelling can help individuals clarify and reflect on their personal values. As an engaging demonstration, the "Toilet Paper Solar System" activity—a hands-on exercise that visualizes planetary distances—can be incorporated to foster both fun and reflection. During this session, participants are

encouraged to think about how they can apply these activities in their own lives or work environments.

3. Hands-On Activity – Using the Tool: The core of the workshop involves a hands-on group activity, where participants practice using the Astronomy for Mental Health tool. Breaking into small groups, they engage with one of the astronomy-based mental health activities introduced earlier. This allows them to apply the ACT principles they have learned and think creatively about incorporating these practices into their outreach work or personal life.
4. Group Reflection & Feedback: Following the hands-on session, participants come together for a group reflection. This is an opportunity to gather insights on their experiences with the tool and its ease of use. Participants discuss the challenges they faced, the impact they observed, and how confident they feel in applying the tool within their professional or personal settings. Feedback is a crucial component of the workshop, as it will guide future improvements to the tool. Participants can provide their reflections through open discussion or a brief self-evaluation questionnaire.

This workshop provides participants with a foundational understanding of how astronomy can be used as a tool to support mental health. By introducing psychological principles such as ACT alongside astronomy-based activities, the workshop equips outreach practitioners with a new set of tools for promoting mental well-being. Through practical engagement, reflection, and feedback, participants gain the confidence and insight needed to integrate these methods into their work, making astronomy not just a subject of scientific inquiry but also a means to improve quality of life.

References:

- Berto, R. (2014). The role of nature in coping with psycho-physiological stress: A literature review on restorativeness. In Behavioral Sciences (Vol. 4, Issue 4, pp. 394–409). MDPI Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs4040394>
- How stargazing is good for your health and well-being | RITUALS. (2022). Retrieved September 7, 2022, from <https://www.rituals.com/en-nl/mag-spirituality-benefits-of-stargazing.html>
- Miller, M. M. F. (2020). Stargazing: A Magical Way to Escape. <https://www.shondaland.com/live/body/a33419686/stargazing-a-magical-way-to-cenchanting-r despite/>
- Piff, P. K., Dietze, P., Feinberg, M., Stancato, D. M., & Keltner, D. (2015). Awe, the small self, and prosocial behavior. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 108(6), 883–899. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pspi0000018>
- RUSS HARRIS. (2009). ACT made simple. New Harbinger Publications, Inc. <https://www.newharbinger.com>
- Stargazing Is Good For Your Mental Health | Nature Makes Us Better. (2022). Retrieved September 7, 2022, from <https://naturemakesusbetter.co.uk/stargazing/>

Where Did the Stars Go?

Presenter: Ekaterini-Maria Rozi, 3rd Junior High school of Glyfada, Greece

Collaborators: Eleftherna-Katerina Bassi (2nd Model Junior High School of Athens, Greece), Aspasia Koutsouli (3rd Junior High school of Argiroupolis, Greece), Maria Panousi (4th Junior High school of Glyfada, Greece), Evgenia Loumpardia (3rd Junior High school of Glyfada, Greece), and Alexandros Kofteros (Apostolos Loukas Primary school, Cyprus)

Engaging students with science and its complex terminologies through traditional teaching methods can be challenging. This poster recounts our collaborative eTwinning project involving 3rd and 4th Junior High School students in Glyfada, Athens, Greece, and the Primary School of Apostle Lucas in Strovolos, Cyprus. Our primary aim was to familiarize them with Light Pollution, a topic often overlooked in our school curricula. Additionally, we aimed to break away from traditional classrooms, fostering cooperative skills, intensifying interest in extracurricular learning, and addressing societal challenges through research and innovation. The conclusion underscores the importance of broader public awareness and governmental action, advocating for a future with darker and starrier skies!

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14321485>

The eTwinning Program: Where Did the Stars Go? is a transnational educational initiative aimed at raising awareness about the issue of light pollution. Through a network of schools from Glyfada, Greece, and Strovolos, Cyprus, the project emphasizes the importance of preserving the natural night environment and promotes the development of informed, responsible citizens. By engaging in educational and scientific activities, students investigate light pollution and collaborate with local authorities to propose practical solutions.

The project seeks to raise awareness about light pollution and its impacts on human health, natural ecosystems, and astronomical observations. It fosters a sense of environmental responsibility, encouraging students to recognize the consequences of environmental neglect while developing respect for nature. The program also aims to enhance essential skills, such as collaboration, digital literacy, and scientific inquiry, through hands-on activities. By promoting active civic engagement, the project empowers students to take part in community efforts to address light pollution, blending scientific research with practical solutions to inspire responsible citizenship.

Project Phases:

1. Defining the Project: Students were organized into teams to explore the issue of light pollution, engaging in activities such as expert-led video conferences and webinars. Observational sessions of the night sky were conducted in Greece and Cyprus, allowing students

to study constellations and measure light pollution in real-world settings.

2. Project Design: Students, guided by teachers, collaboratively planned the project, distributing tasks and conducting research on the local effects of light pollution.
3. Executing the Project: Students collected data on sky brightness through the "Globe at Night" program and used the Nightlights app to analyze streetlight characteristics. They also built models of local public areas and proposed solutions to mitigate light pollution, with plans to present their findings to local authorities.
4. Presentation of Results: Results were shared through the Twinspace platform, allowing interaction between schools, and future presentations to local stakeholders are planned to raise community awareness and prompt action.
5. Evaluation and Dissemination: Educators and students will evaluate the project, with the findings disseminated through school websites and public platforms to engage a broader audience.

International Recognition: This project has garnered international attention, being presented at the COSPAR 2024 conference and the ESA ESEC 2023 event. These presentations underscore the project's scientific and educational significance, further contributing to global discussions on sustainability and environmental awareness.

Light pollution is a pressing issue that not only affects human health and ecosystems but also contributes to the greenhouse effect, with significant economic consequences. This project equips students with the knowledge and skills necessary to understand and address this issue, empowering them and their communities to advocate for sustainable solutions. By fostering scientific literacy and civic engagement, the program contributes to the larger goal of preserving the natural darkness of the night for future generations.

Galaxy Formation for School Students

Presenter: Rahul Chudji, DG Khetan International School, India

The obstacle of understanding will explain the formation of different types of galaxies and their evolution with the help of models and activities. 1. First Model: Bucket and Whirlpool model. The slow addition of different colors will explain mergers and acquisitions. 2. Second activity: Clay and soldering wire. Elliptical and Spiral galaxies and their respective shapes. How do they evolve and form? Students can make their galaxies with clay and wires. 3. Third model: Scaled down flow chart of galaxy formation. A flow chart explaining galaxy formation to 14-year-olds. This study will first include their ideas about galaxy formation. The responses will forecast the residual knowledge about galaxies. At the final stage, students will take two assessment tests after this intervention.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14319124>

The space component of the Physics textbook focuses on crucial topics like the Solar System and the formation of stars and planets. The main goal of this topic is to introduce galaxy formation in the curriculum. The poster includes three key aspects: Formation, evolution and classification of galaxies.

Formation of Galaxies: After the Big Bang, the Universe starts expanding. Due to small density fluctuations in the inflationary model, gravitational instabilities grow. The region with higher density starts attracting more matter. A high-density region will attract matter from the surroundings, making it more rarefied. This matter comprises dark matter and gas called 'halos'. Small halos grow in size due to gravitational growth. These halos merge to form large halos. These halos are a mixture of gas, dust, and dark matter—the collapse of large dark matter haloes forms galaxies. The concept of dark matter for 13-15-year-olds might be challenging. Depending on the intensity and spin (initial angular momentum) of the halos, the collapse can form an elliptical or spiral galaxy. In my poster, I have explained the galaxy formation process and the essential ingredients needed for it in 3 steps. The illustration below considers the previous concepts learned by the pupils in space physics.

Evolution of Galaxies: Further classification of galaxies is made based on angular momentum. The ones with less angular momentum or rotation are elliptical. To keep things simple, we will not discuss lenticulars or spheroidal galaxies.

Classification of Galaxies: Elliptical Galaxies: Massive elliptical galaxies form their stars immediately after the collapse. Elliptical galaxies have old and metal-rich stars. The high-density region will have a higher star formation rate and population. Elliptical galaxies are 'redder'. Two possible reasons behind the formation of elliptical galaxies: Short Burst Collapse (Monolithic Collapse) – Star formation took less time than the actual collapse and formed along with the assembly of the host galaxy. The surrounding environment plays a vital role in the formation.

Figure 1: Formation of Galaxies (left), Ingredients for Formation (right)

The merger scenario – Two galaxies merge to form elliptical galaxies. Here, the two individual galaxies have their independent star formation. As an example, two spiral galaxies can merge to form an elliptical galaxy. They are further classified as E0 to E7 (based on their eccentricity).

Spiral Galaxies: Many models explain the formation of disk/spiral galaxies. Gas clouds with initial angular momentum collapse. The gas accretion and angular momentum will give a disk shape.

The classification study will only include elliptical and disk galaxies. The initial phase would be to assign an initial condition and boundaries. Gravitational instability in dark matter halos will lead to cooling. Further classification is based on angular momentum. The presence of gas accretion and angular momentum will give a disk/spiral galaxy. The absence of angular momentum will lead to elliptical.

Class activity: Students will first take a pre-test and write/draw down their ideas regarding the formation of galaxies. Students will try to identify different types of galaxies. Post-test: They will perform a class activity where students will use clay to show different types of galaxies. Demonstration: Whirlpool: Spiral formation, Differential velocity, Angular momentum.

References:

- H. Mo, F. van den Bosch & S. White 2010. Galaxy Formation and Evolution.
- E. Tempel, E. Saar, L. J. Liivamägi, A. Tamm, J. Einasto, M. Einasto, and V. Müller, Galaxy morphology, luminosity, and environment in the SDSS DR7
- <https://skyserver.sdss.org/dr1/en/proj/advanced/galaxies/tuningfork.asp>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5SIWeNVXFrU>

Closer to the Sky: Co-Creating Astronomical Knowledge in the PPG Favela of Rio de Janeiro

Presenter: Larissa Okiyama, Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

Collaborators: Arianna Cortesi (Federal University of Rio de Janeiro), Cláudia Mignone (National Institute for Astrophysics) and The Closer to the Sky team

This project co-produces scientific knowledge with astronomers and artists/educators in PPG, targeting children, teenagers, and young adults. In partnership with 'Ninho das Águias', we offer classes and night sky observations. Many PPG students face academic challenges and lack extracurricular opportunities, leading to disadvantages in higher education and employment. Our extracurricular courses aim to enrich their education and promote continued learning. By providing positive role models from Afro-descendant backgrounds and creating decolonial, context-based science materials, we support local culture and share resources as Open Educational Resources.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14319576>

Overview of the Project: "Closer to the Sky" is a unique initiative that unites astronomers, artists, and educators in the Cantagalo-Pavão-Pavãozinho (PPG) favela of Rio de Janeiro. The project aims to provide scientific knowledge, cultural experiences, and English language education for children and young adults in the community. Activities include extracurricular courses, night sky observations, and highlighting role models among Afro-descendant scientists to inspire participants. While primarily focused on Brazil, the project has a partner initiative in India and collaborations with teams in Argentina, Chile, Italy, and the United Kingdom. Funding comes from FAPERJ (Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado do Rio de Janeiro), the Office of Astronomy for Development of the International Astronomical Union (OAD, IAU), and voluntary donations.

Ninho das Águias: A Transformative Learning Space: The project's activities take place at the "Ninho das Águias" (Eagle's Nest), a cultural and educational space located at the highest point of the Pavão-Pavãozinho favela. Previously an open-air dump, this area was transformed in 2011 by artists Acme and Iani into a vibrant community learning environment. Today, it hosts various activities, including tutoring, literature classes, English lessons, and breakdance. In 2014, the space expanded to include the PPG Community Library, a dedicated area for studying and educational initiatives. Astronomy classes for children began in 2022. In 2023 classes were also opened for adolescents and young adults, with plans for a three-year program to certify students as astronomical guides through the OAD, IAU. The curriculum covers essential topics in astronomy, such as the Solar System, stars, cosmology, and cultural astronomy, with a focus on diverse cultural understandings of the cosmos. This approach broadens the traditional Eurocentric narrative often found in science education. Currently, four students are part of

Figure 1: A group of students participating in the "Closer to the Sky" project.

the program, including one who has an intellectual disability. They have access to tablets to enhance their studies and learn programming. Field trips, such as visits to the Planetarium of Rio de Janeiro, are planned to further immerse them in the scientific community.

Learning Beyond the Classroom: The program not only teaches astronomy but also fills gaps in traditional school curricula by introducing topics that encourage critical thinking and exploration, for example how to create astronomical colour images. Although preparing students to approach complex subjects can be challenging, this method fosters a deeper understanding of scientific knowledge. The initiative also aims to ignite students' curiosity and motivate them to excel academically. Learning English is emphasized as vital for academic success and future career opportunities. The project introduces programming skills to equip students for a field with promising professional growth. A dedicated website is being created, and plans are underway to publish a physical resource, such as a book, that thoroughly covers the project's content. Beyond academic knowledge, "Closer to the Sky" fosters a passion for learning and a sense of belonging within the scientific community. Participants have reported increased happiness and motivation to pursue their studies.

Integrating Science and Daily Life: The program's approach integrates scientific inquiry with students' personal experiences, creating a learning environment that extends beyond academic settings. By connecting scientific concepts to their everyday lives, the project encourages a lifelong appreciation for knowledge and a critical understanding of the world. This model empowers students by showing them that science is not an abstract field but a vital part of their lives.

Bridging the Gap in Scientific Understanding: "Closer to the Sky" also tackles a significant issue: the disconnection between science and society, particularly in Brazil. There is a growing gap between scientists and the public, leading to misunderstandings about scientific processes and a decline in trust in science. This situation is further complicated by systemic challenges in education and economic disparities that hinder access to quality scientific resources. By bringing science directly to underserved communities, "Closer to the Sky" aims to bridge this gap and emphasizes the importance of understanding the scientific method as a critical thinking tool.

Figure 2: Students during the visit to the Rio de Janeiro Planetarium (left) and night sky observation using a telescope at "Ninho das Águias" (right).

A Movement for Change: Ultimately, "Closer to the Sky" aspires to be more than just an educational program; it seeks to redefine science's role in society by fostering a culture of inclusivity, curiosity, and lifelong learning. The initiative aims to cultivate a new generation of thinkers and leaders who are not only scientifically literate but also culturally aware and socially responsible.

Qatar Astronomy Olympiad for Schools 2024

Presenter: Hani Dalee, the Arab Union for Astronomy and Space Sciences,
IAU-NOC, Qatar

Collaborator: Bashir Marzoke (Qatar Calendar House)

Under the affiliation to Qatar Astronomy Olympiad for School 2024, educators have gone through a unique activity that allows students to get a good idea about sunspots and the solar cycle activity. In that aspect, schools were asked to purchase (or borrow) telescopes to be used for sunspots observations. Educators have formed an Astronomy Team at each school, this team has received the basic training about the project and how to convey it to other students at their school. Between 200-300 students from each school (69 schools) have attended the activity, which was divided into two parts; observing sunspots via projection method and listen to an interactive "lecture" from all team members. More than 10,000 students have gone through this project in less than two weeks.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14320934>

Under the theme “The Sun & the Extended Shadow”, the Arab Union for Astronomy and Space Sciences in cooperation with Qatar Calendar House and the Qatar Ministry of Education, has launched the Qatar Astronomy Olympiad for Schools 2024. Students will measure the rotational period of the Sun. Sixty-nine (69) national and international schools participated in the Olympiad, with each school team consisting of 3-5 students and a supervising teacher. All schools were required to purchase a telescope, as we are currently in the 25th Solar Cycle, and most projects will be related to the Sun. More than 55 schools have acquired telescopes so far.

To measure the rotational period of the Sun, we set four objectives for this project: Introduce the solar cycle; Learn how to observe the Sun safely; Study the behavior of sunspots; Calculate the rotational period of the Sun using direct and indirect methods.

Additionally, the Olympiad included outreach tasks. Students were asked to educate 300 of their peers about the 25th Solar Cycle and to let them observe sunspots through telescopes. Nearly 10,000 students across Qatar participated in these activities, marking the highest number of students ever involved in an astronomical event in Qatar.

About the Olympiad: The Olympiad began as an activity in Doha, Qatar, and is now in its 9th consecutive year, having started in 2016. It is dedicated to helping students gain knowledge and skills in astronomy, a subject that is not typically taught in schools. The idea for the Olympiad was initiated by Dr. Khalid Al-Subai, an astronomer and head of the Qatar Exoplanet Survey (QES) at Hamad Bin Khalifa University (HBKU) in Doha, with the assistance of astronomer Hani Dalee (IAU-NOC-Qatar), who proposes the projects and supervises the competition.

Projects of the Olympiad: Students are often assigned two to three Astronomy Projects to be completed during the first semester and the beginning of the second semester of each academic year. Results and hands-on projects are showcased during a national festival called "National Week for Science Research" (NWSR), which typically takes place in April. All winning schools are honored at the closing ceremony held (in 2024) at the Qatar Calendar House festival hall. At the beginning of the academic year, a three-day training workshop is conducted for teachers (and sometimes students) in October or November. This workshop trains participants on how to carry out the assigned projects.

Social Media and Communications: A WhatsApp group is typically created for Olympiad teachers to provide updates and address their questions and inquiries. To encourage greater student involvement in the competition, “Astro-Talks” are organized at many of the participating schools. It is believed that listening to a guest astronomer is more effective for students than hearing from their teachers.

A student discusses the 25th Solar Cycle at Rawda Bint Jassim School during the Qatar Astronomy Olympiad 2024.

Students at Al-Salam School observe sunspots using the projection method during the Qatar Astronomy Olympiad 2024.

A student delivers a lecture on the 25th Solar Cycle at Birla Public School during the Qatar Astronomy Olympiad 2024.

Students at Ahmad Bin Thani School observe sunspots using a solar filter during the Qatar Astronomy Olympiad 2024.

Collaboration Among High Schools, Universities, and High-Tech Enterprises to Jointly Develop Courses

Presenter: Xinrong Shen, Jiangsu Tianyi High School, China

Collaborator: Jianying Zhou (Wuxi Liaison Office of Jiangsu Astronomical Society)

Based on the collaboration between "high schools and high schools", "high schools and universities", and "high schools and high-tech enterprises", the Astronomical Society of Jiangsu Tianyi High School has jointly developed high school astronomy courses in partnership with these institutions and achieved significant results. We have not only jointly established in-school laboratories such as observatories and meteor monitoring stations, but also constructed a number of off-campus practical bases. We have joined the Informationization Working Committee of the Chinese Astronomical Society and initiated the establishment of astronomy alliances for middle school students in Jiangsu Province and Wuxi City. We collaborate with top-tier universities to develop astronomy courses and conduct research projects. We have established Popular Science Courses, including astronomy popularization lectures, exhibitions, and observations. We have developed Subject Competition Courses, contributing a number of outstanding students to the Chinese national team for the International Olympiad on Astronomy. We have developed Project Research Courses, Many student papers have been published in domestic and international academic journals, including SCI-indexed journals, and student research achievements have won awards in various science and technology competitions. In collaboration with universities, we have developed University-High School Joint Courses, a number of students have been admitted to astronomy departments at top universities both domestically and internationally, such as Peking University and Cornell University.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14316878>

1. Platform Construction

- **Innovation Laboratories:** By leveraging the talent and intellectual advantages of universities and high-tech enterprises, we have co-established astronomical laboratories, remote-controlled observatories, meteor monitoring stations, and urban night sky photometric monitoring stations.
- **Off-campus Practice Bases:** Utilizing the resource advantages of universities and high-tech enterprises, we have jointly established off-campus practice bases, such as

the Purple Mountain Observatory of the Chinese Academy of Sciences, Anji Jiangnan Tianchi Observatory, and Wuxi Urban Night Sky Photometric Monitoring Network.

2. Mechanism Construction

- **Organizational Structure:** We have established a school astronomy learning center to plan and coordinate school astronomy curriculum, and a Wuxi Liaison Office of the Jiangsu Astronomical Society to coordinate astronomical science popularization and education activities in Wuxi, while actively promoting the establishment of the Wuxi Astronomical Society.
- **Project Collaboration:** Participating in the "Talent Plan" of the China Association for Science and Technology, we collaborate with other high schools and universities on astronomy-related project research, develop courses with universities like Nanjing University, and invite university professors to give students lectures regularly at our school.

3. Curriculum Development

- **Popular Science Courses:** We have established connection with universities and high-tech enterprises, inviting experts to give science popularization lectures at our school. We also cooperate with other high schools to organize astronomy popularization activities for teenagers and the general public.
- **Subject Competition Courses:** In collaboration with other high schools and universities, we offer competition courses such as "Introduction to Astronomy" and "Introduction to Earth Sciences". Our school has contributed outstanding students to the Chinese National Team for the International Astronomy Olympiad.
- **Project Research Courses:** Together with other high schools, universities, and high-tech enterprises, we conduct research projects in areas such as solar science, lunar and planetary science, microlensing, asteroid searches, and dark sky protection. Many student papers have been published in domestic and international academic journals, including SCI-indexed journals, and student research achievements have won awards in various science and technology competitions.
- **University-High School Joint Courses:** In partnership with Nanjing University, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, Peking University, and other universities, we offer courses such as "Earth and Space Science Exploration", "From Newton's Gravity to Cosmic Accelerated Expansion", and "Introduction to Earth Sciences" to guide and enhance students' interest in astronomy. A number of students have been admitted to astronomy departments at top universities both domestically and internationally, such as Peking University and Cornell University.

Advancing Astronomical Literacy via Student Writing Contests

Presenter: William Waller, Endicott College, The Galactic Inquirer, and
IAU-OAE-NAEC, USA

Scientific literacy encompasses the ability to read scientific literature and to effectively communicate scientific knowledge and reasoning via writing, speaking, and other means. This skill comprises a key goal of K-12 education, as borne out by educational standards worldwide (cf. [The Next Generation Science Standards](#) followed by U.S. schools). Advancing astronomical literacy provides a compelling gateway to advancing scientific literacy overall, as the subject of Astronomy is both interdisciplinary and very popular. In this poster, I discuss the motivation and development of an astronomical writing contest for high-school students. Progress on a pilot astronomical science writing contest being hosted by The Galactic Inquirer will be presented.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14317074>

Motivation: It is tempting to say that any well-educated person should know what it takes to be scientifically literate. But what does scientific literacy really involve? Given that scientific literacy is a key goal of most science education standards and frameworks, considerable ink has been dedicated to utilizing the term in pedagogical papers. But what is scientific literacy? While others have attempted to articulate the term's meaning, I offer the following more “literal” definition.

Scientific literacy encompasses the ability to read scientific literature and to effectively communicate scientific knowledge and reasoning via writing, speaking, and other means.

Here, the goal is to cultivate an informed citizenry capable of engaging with evidence-based scientific discourse. By extension, astronomical literacy involves those aspects of scientific literacy that pertain to astronomy and space exploration. Motivated to advance the cause of astronomical literacy (so defined), I have pursued the development of an astronomical science writing contest for high-school students. Among the physical and natural sciences, Astronomy holds a special place within the educational lexicon. It is often regarded as the “gateway science”, as it is both interdisciplinary and very popular. Consider that more than 100 million people flock to planetariums each year. Even greater numbers of people marvel at the latest astronomical images and video presentations via a myriad of media platforms. Amateur astronomers spread the love on every continent. And then there is the allure of robotic and human space missions that continues to captivate people by the billions.

Developing an Astronomical Science Writing Contest for High School Students: Together, Astronomy and space exploration are most fitting subjects for student writing projects, including the astronomical science writing contest considered here. Students have a strong affinity for

contests in general, and such a writing contest should be no different. The contest being piloted will engage high-school students in active writing projects suitable to their grade levels.

A similar contest might also work well in middle school, but I wanted to pilot it at the high-school level first where I have more experience as an educator. In my own high-school and college science classes, I have obtained impressive results with the student writing that I assigned and mentored (cf. <https://sites.google.com/site/sciencegazette/ap-physics?authuser=0>, and <http://galacticinquirer.net/>). From these experiences, I highly recommend that teachers allow sufficient time to mentor their students in finding a suitable topic, taking useful notes, outlining, drafting, and refining their written pieces. For the piloted competition, students are welcome to work in a variety of writing genres such as research reports, essays, book reviews, speculative fiction, dramatic scripts, poems, and musical lyrics. In this way, a diversity of students in both science and English classes can pursue this competitive project.

As currently configured, the contest is being hosted by [The Galactic Inquirer](#) – a free online journal that covers a wide range of astronomical topics. Partners include the [American Astronomical Society](#), North America’s largest organization of astronomers, the International Astronomical Union’s Office of Astronomy for Education, and the [Slooh remote telescopes service](#). The contest is for high-school students interested in Astronomy and space exploration. Finalists receive [prizes and publishing opportunities](#). Submitted pieces should be 500 to 2,500 words in length, depending on the genre. Information on [submissions](#) includes topical prompts. The deadline for submissions is March 15, 2025. If you wish to partner on this project, please contact Bill Waller at [williamhwaller\[at\]gmail\[dot\]com](mailto:williamhwaller[at]gmail[dot]com).

Astronomy Education in Tanzanian Secondary Schools

Presenter: Elineema Nassari, Mount Meru Astronomical Observatory, Tanzania

Astronomy in Tanzanian secondary schools remains underdeveloped due to limited resources, teacher training, and curriculum focus on this subject. While Tanzania’s national curriculum includes general science, it rarely emphasizes space science, leaving astronomy mostly unexplored in classrooms. However, the Mount Meru Astronomical Observatory, established to provide educational outreach and public stargazing sessions, offers a unique resource for students and teachers interested in space science. This observatory, along with initiatives from organizations like the African Astronomical Society and local universities, aims to spark student interest through workshops, telescope access, and hands-on learning.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14321234>

The Mount Meru Astronomical Observatory (MMAO), located near Arusha in northern Tanzania, plays a crucial role in promoting astronomy education and outreach in the region. As the first private observatory in Tanzania, MMAO has made significant contributions to raising awareness about astronomy and inspiring interest in space sciences, especially among students and educators. Here are some of its key contributions:

1. Educational Programs for Students

- **Hands-on Learning:** The observatory offers students from local schools' opportunities to engage with astronomy through hands-on activities. This includes using telescopes to observe celestial objects like the moon, planets, and stars.
- **Workshops and Seminars:** MMAO regularly organizes workshops and seminars for students and teachers to deepen their understanding of astronomical concepts. These programs are tailored to introduce foundational knowledge in astronomy, astrophysics, and space science.
- **Inclusion of Local Schools:** By inviting students from Arusha and surrounding areas, MMAO fosters a culture of scientific curiosity, giving young learners exposure to a field that is not traditionally covered in-depth in the Tanzanian curriculum.

2. Outreach and Community Engagement

- **Public Observing Nights:** MMAO hosts public observing nights where members of the community can visit the observatory to view the night sky through high-quality telescopes. These events demystify astronomy and help spark interest in the general public.
- **Astronomy Clubs:** The observatory works with local schools to support the formation of astronomy clubs. This has created a sustained interest in the subject by allowing students to continue exploring astronomy after their visits.
- **Astronomy Camps:** Through partnerships with local and international organizations, MMAO organizes astronomy camps that bring students together for immersive learning experiences, combining astronomy with environmental science.

3. Teacher Training and Curriculum Support

- **Professional Development for Teachers:** MMAO provides training for science teachers in the Arusha region, equipping them with the knowledge and resources to teach astronomy in schools. This ensures that the impact of the observatory extends beyond just direct student engagement.
- **Resource Creation:** The observatory contributes to the development of educational materials, such as guides and textbooks, that teachers can use to integrate astronomy into the science curriculum.

4. Collaboration with International Organizations

- MMAO works in collaboration with various international astronomical bodies, such as the International Astronomical Union (IAU) and the Galileo Teacher Training Program. These partnerships help bring global expertise and resources to support astronomy education in Tanzania.
- Through these collaborations, the observatory has also been able to access more advanced telescopic equipment and educational tools, further enriching the experiences it offers to students and the community.

5. Promoting STEM Education

- MMAO's focus on astronomy is part of a broader effort to promote Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) education in the region. By introducing young people to astronomy, the observatory encourages critical thinking, problem-solving, and curiosity—skills that are transferable to other STEM fields.
- It also helps challenge stereotypes, particularly encouraging girls and young women to consider careers in science and technology.

6. Inspiring Future Generations

- The observatory's outreach efforts have the long-term goal of nurturing the next generation of Tanzanian scientists. By inspiring students to look up at the stars, MMAO hopes to cultivate a culture of scientific inquiry and encourage Tanzanian youth to pursue careers in fields such as astronomy, physics, and engineering.

In summary, the Mount Meru Astronomical Observatory has significantly impacted the Arusha region and Tanzania in general by promoting astronomy education, providing hands-on learning opportunities, engaging the community in science outreach, and fostering a greater appreciation for STEM subjects among students and educators. Through its programs and collaborations, MMAO continues to be a vital hub for astronomy education in Tanzania.

Building a Sky Observation Activity in a School Context

Presenter: Gleice Kelen Dornelles Costa, Inter-Unit Post-Graduation in Science Teaching, University of São Paulo, Brazil

Collaborators: Elrismar Auxiliadora Gomes Oliveira (Federal University of Amazonas), Cristina Leite and Antônio Carlos da Silva (University of São Paulo).

This poster presents a sky observation activity, applied in a school environment and developed based on references constructed by researchers in the field of Astronomy Teaching. These indicate three distinct moments: before, during and after sky observation. In the pre-observation phase, the student is prepared for the task and what elements should be taken into account when carrying it out: investigation of previous conceptions, the star/phenomenon to be observed, the objectives to be achieved, the period, duration and space where the activity will take place. During observation, data is collected, taking into account the strategies for observing and monitoring the stars. In the post-observation phase, the content is systematized, the data is analyzed and the objectives are verified.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14321026>

Since the dawn of civilization, the starry sky has attracted the gaze of mankind. However, the constant growth of cities has meant that artificial night lighting has spread over large areas. Combined with clouds of water vapor and suspended solid particles, these factors have gradually obscured our night vision of the starry sky (PICAZZIO, 2011).

The first astronomical observations were made with the naked eye and described countless stars and phenomena. With the advent of technology, it has become possible to perceive details of these objects, see more distant regions, and discover new celestial bodies/events.

In the school context, observation requires an attentive and systematic look at the firmament, so that not only the occurrence of celestial phenomena but also their regularity can be perceived. This can be encouraged through activities designed specifically for this purpose.

With a view to bringing students closer to their astronomical surroundings, making it possible to build knowledge and dialogue between theory and practice, an observation activity was created that goes through three different stages: pre-observation, observation and post-observation, which is aimed at secondary school students (2nd and 3rd grade). The activity takes place in a formal educational space, in the courtyard of a private school in the city of Brasília, during the student's time at school and guided by the teacher. The Sun was chosen as the star to be followed, as well as the shadow of a gnomon and the presence of sunspots. This activity is currently being implemented.

When produced, these practices must take into account certain factors, which, if present, can interfere with the quality of the observation, such as certain phenomena - clouds, humidity, rain, and/or light and atmospheric pollution. In addition, attention must be paid to the conditions related to pedagogical aspects, such as when there are classes with large numbers of students and the length of time they spend in the school environment (morning, afternoon or evening), which sometimes prevents them from observing some regularities in the phenomena. In addition, attention must be paid to the physical/structural conditions of the place where the observation activity will be carried out (COSTA, 2018).

The pre-observation stage investigated the students' knowledge of the subject. This stage made it possible to understand the students' conceptions of the phenomenon/astro-accompaniment. It is important to note that the answers to the questionnaire showed the existence of alternative conceptions, but this aspect is already widely discussed in the literature, especially when the subject is the formation of shadows when the Sun is at its zenith and the occurrence of the seasons. However, this moment is rich in providing elements for the construction of more appropriate didactic strategies, guiding the subsequent stage, observation.

The observation stage was carried out in two stages. The first, in a short space of time (20'), consisted of observing sunspots, using binoculars to project images of the Sun onto a sheet of paper. In the second instance, observation was carried out systematically at different times during the morning. The students were able to follow the variation in the length of the gnomon's shadow, recording the time of the observation on a piece of paper until the Sun reached its zenith.

The data collected is analyzed with the students during the post-observation period through discussions, and it will be possible to assess whether the objectives of the activity have been achieved. The data can lead to a deeper understanding of the topic: by recording the length of the gnomon's shadow and tracking the Sun's movement in the sky there is the possibility of determining the local celestial meridian (cardinal points - north and south) and the Sun's angular velocity. The activity will also be evaluated to see what aspects need to be improved.

The motivating nature of the activity could be seen in the students' interest in carrying it out, as evidenced by their surprise when they saw that at local noon there is a shadow or even when they saw small sunspots projected on the paper, associating them with something they had read in the newspapers, since we are going through the period of maximum solar activity.

When observation activities move from contemplative to systematic, they can help students perceive details of the star/phenomenon that can only be achieved with attention and dedication (Silva, 2021). Each stage of the process, if planned and analyzed, can provide the educator with information to enhance learning and improve each moment, especially the post-observation feedback, which can evaluate everything from the initial moment - checking the student's knowledge/experience of the sky - to the execution of the observation and subsequent discussions and in-depth studies. This shows the interrelationship between the three moments, each underpinning the other.

References:

- Picazzio, E. (2011). Movimento Aparente do Céu. In: Enos Picazzio. (Org.). O Céu que

nos envolve: Introdução à Astronomia para educadores e iniciantes. 1ª ed. São Paulo: Odysseus Editora, v. 01, p. 55-78

- Costa, G. K. D. A observação do céu nos livros didáticos de Ciências aprovados no PNLD/2017. 2018, 128p. Dissertação (Mestrado) – Programa de Pós-Graduação Interunidades em Ensino de Ciências. Instituto de Física, Instituto de Química, Instituto de Biologia e Faculdade de Educação, Universidade de São Paulo, São Paulo, 2018.
- Silva, A. C. A observação do céu nos livros didáticos de Ciências das séries iniciais do Ensino Fundamental aprovados no PNLD/2016. 2021, 148p. Dissertação (Mestrado) – Programa de Pós-Graduação Interunidades em Ensino de Ciências. Instituto de Física, Instituto de Química, Instituto de Biologia e Faculdade de Educação, Universidade de São Paulo, São Paulo, 2021.

Advancing Astronomy Education in Indonesia Through NASE: Insights from the 2022 and 2024 Courses

Presenter: Nindhita Pratiwi, Institut Teknologi Sumatera, Lampung, Indonesia

Collaborators: H. L. Malasan (Institut Teknologi Sumatera, Lampung, Indonesia), R. M. Ros (Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain), R. W. Romadhonia (Universitas Negeri Surabaya, Surabaya, Indonesia), M. I. Ikhsan, R. Muztaba, D. M. Noor, E. R. Kencana, A. Fitriawati, and N. Resfita (Institut Teknologi Sumatera, Lampung, Indonesia), R. Fahdiran (Universitas Negeri Jakarta, Jakarta, Indonesia), B. A. Subagyo (Institut Teknologi Sepuluh Nopember, Surabaya, Indonesia), R. Syamara (PT. Rekreasindo Global Utama, Jakarta, Indonesia), E. Fitri, M. Dewi, C. Kunjaya, and E. Soegiartini (Institut Teknologi Bandung, Bandung, Indonesia)

NASE continues to make significant strides in Indonesia, with recent courses held by ITS and UNJ. In 2022, ITS hosted a hybrid NASE course from December 12-13, featuring 3 IAU instructors, 4 local instructors, and 20 participants. Building on the success of this event, the 2024 NASE course was held by UNJ from September 9-12, featuring 6 IAU instructors, 7 local instructors, and 40 participants from Jakarta. The program was expanded to include 4 lectures, 11 workshops, and 2 working groups. The NASE courses in Indonesia contribute significantly to the development of astronomy education in Indonesia, fostering both academic growth and public interest in the field.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14319414>

Network for Astronomy School Education (NASE) courses in Indonesia was held by Ma Chung University (2016), Institut Teknologi Sumatera (2018 and 2019), Institut Teknologi Bandung

Figure 1: Model of the revolution motion that explains seasons.

Figure 2: Solar eclipse simulation

(2020) [1], and Universitas Ahmad Dahlan (2021). NASE continues to make significant strides in Indonesia, with recent courses held by Institut Teknologi Sepuluh Nopember (ITS) and Universitas Negeri Jakarta (UNJ). In 2022, ITS hosted a hybrid NASE course from December 12-13, featuring 3 IAU instructors, 4 local instructors, and 20 participants, including educators, students, and community members from Surabaya, East Java [2]. The course included two lectures on cosmology and stellar evolution and seven workshops over two days, fostering engagement with both theoretical and practical aspects of astronomy [3].

Building on the success of this event, the 2024 NASE course was held by UNJ from September 9-12. It attracted 50 participants, ranging from primary and secondary school teachers, astronomy enthusiasts, students, and amateur astronomers from across Indonesia. This event was supported by 2 international instructors (from Spain and Philippine), 3 lecturers, 9 local instructors, and 50 participants. The program was expanded to include 4 lectures covering topics such as the Evolution of the Stars, Cosmology, the Solar System, and Astrobiology. Additionally, 11 workshops and 2 working groups were conducted, focusing on practical skills and the integration of astronomy into the high school curriculum. Participants also had the opportunity to visit Skyworld Indonesia, to explore space education through interactive exhibits, and take part in night-time astronomical observations supported by Himpunan Astronomi Amatir Jakarta (HAAJ) [4]. The NASE courses in Indonesia have proven invaluable in enhancing the teaching abilities of educators and improving the understanding of astronomical concepts among students, teachers, lecturers, and community members. These efforts contribute significantly to the development

of astronomy education in Indonesia, fostering both academic growth and public interest in the field.

References:

- [1] Malasan, H. L., Ros, R. M., Kunjaya, C., Soegiartini, E., Aprilia, & Romadhonia, R. W. (2019). Empowering Science Teachers in Indonesia through NASE Workshops. Proceedings of the International Astronomical Union, 15(S367), 30–33. doi:10.1017/S1743921321000582
- [2] <https://www.its.ac.id/fisika/agenda/workshop-nase-12-13-desember-2022/>
- [3] Ros, Rosa M. & Hemenway, M. (editors) 2015, 14 Steps to the Universe: Astronomy course for teachers and science graduates (2nd ed, Network for Astronomy School Education NASE, International Astronomical Union IAU, Albdeo-Fulldome
- [4] <https://www.unj.ac.id/gaungkan-internasionalisasi-fmipa-unj-gandeng-network-for-astronomy-school-education-nase-dalam-bidang-astronomi/>

Teaching High School Astronomy Through Scientists' Biographies

Presenter: Dmitrii Ostriakov, École Jeannine Manuel, France

To get students motivated one needs to establish a personal connection with subject, show its beauty, and deliver amazing facts. From our experience, implementing elements of biographies of researchers into the curriculum has been a successful approach. References to misconceptions that are now considered ridiculous but once seemed like promising conjectures may attract students through humor and advance the critical thinking skill. Can we assume common personal traits of Johannes Kepler and Andrea Ghez, who made observations of the same objects over many years in a row? How ingenious were the ancient philosophers in laying the foundation of astronomical science without any computational tools? What moral choice did discoveries in nuclear physics in the mid-twentieth century lead to?

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14479904>

The poster is based on more than 15 years of in-person teaching experience of the presenter. It summarizes the main findings of astronomy curriculum implementation in 2006-2022 at The School for Physics and Technology after Zh.I.Alferov in St Petersburg, Russia. At the early stages

of the curriculum implementation, astronomy was hardly taught as a separate subject at Russian high schools, and therefore there was a significant lack of learning materials. However, some institutions with advanced training in the STEM field had the privilege of teaching it. We are going to discuss how we dealt with the lack of materials in our 2-years introductory course on General astronomy for future scientists, programmers and researchers (grades 10-11). One of the approaches that has proven to work well was teaching through biographies of astronomers. But how can we do that in an engaging way?

It is no secret that the vast majority of students who are interested in astronomy want to learn right away about quite complicated things, namely what a black hole is, how the Big Bang happened, or what's beyond the boundaries of the Universe. This challenges teachers as we are supposed to teach the core concepts first to build on later on. The introductory chapter of the course we implemented at The School for Physics and Technology was related to history of astronomy. Having watched educational series by Carl Sagan as a newly qualified teacher, we were inspired by his way of communicating science to the general public and included Eratosthenes' measurement of the Earth's radius into the lesson plan. Motivational questions that might be beneficial to discuss at this point: how could have a person with hardly any measuring devices or computational tools come up with a brilliant idea to measure the portion of the meridian and difference of angles of incidence of sunlight at different cities to further derive the Earth's radius? This discussion in stronger classes should lead to further exploration, whether it is possible to perform similar experiment at points that do not belong to the same meridian. What conditions do we need to set to still get the Earth's radius? The conversation might be rounded out by a discussion of Snellius' invention of geodetic triangulation. It is beneficial to put these two names, separated by almost two thousand years, side by side. It is no coincidence that Snellius is called the Dutch Eratosthenes.

Another fruitful conversation might be linked to Aristarchus' accomplishments. Every child is excited, when they close one eye and observe how the perception changes compared to two open eyes. Biology teaches us that to correctly estimate distance to an object one needs to process signal from two distinct points, namely eyes. How powerful the researcher should have been to make such a bold and global generalization and to relate this observation every human has in their experience to the concept of distance to stars! This idea was so far ahead of its time that it was first observationally confirmed only 2000 years later by Thomas Henderson, Friedrich von Struve, and Friedrich Bessel. Isn't everyone capable of great achievements if we all have the same sensory experience?

Having discussed purely observational concept of the celestial sphere, we transition in our course to Kepler's laws of planetary motion. It is known from history of science that Kepler was first considering planets to orbit the Sun on circles, but then, after having carefully studied Tycho Brahe's observational data and after having observed the Martian trajectory for decades, he finally concluded that our Earth and other planets orbit the Sun on ellipses. We discussed many times with students, what personal traits should a dedicated researcher possess to carry out meticulous observations over many years? As another example of a researcher of this kind it might be beneficial to discuss the case of one of the most recent Nobel prize winners, Andrea Ghez, who has been observing since 1995 a star called S2, and this name does not say much at first. Yet it is a good point to start our conversation about black holes. Now we can relate this phenomenal dedication to years of observations, which eventually yielded the stunning result confirming that there is a black hole at the center of the Milky Way.

Going back to Kepler's contribution to science, we emphasize that scientific inquiry is impossible without hypotheses, which inevitably leads to the rejection of some of them. At this point it is great to elaborate on Kepler's reference to the dark night paradox as an argument against the infinity of the Universe. It is great to discuss how a misconception can lead even a successful scientist to a dead-end. Here we make this loop in the curriculum and discuss along with Kepler's laws the objects and patterns that are the most interesting for students – namely black holes and the evolution of the Universe.

Another fruitful connection could be found in learning about Arthur Eddington. As students learn the concept of force in physics, they are applying it to many real-world problems. By analogy with the consideration of Ernest Rutherford's experiment in which alpha particles were scattering on atomic nuclei, we can consider the light beam deflection in a gravitational field. In 1919 Arthur Eddington found that during a solar eclipse, the position of stars in the sky near the Sun is distorted, thus brilliantly confirming the ideas of the general theory of relativity. In addition to discussing Eddington's contributions to science, we focus on a little-known fact of his life: he was a conscientious objector to military service during the World War I, which even caused him substantial problems at university. How brave a scientist should have been and how firm should have him stood on his ideas? Was his moral choice right or should he has served the military? The discussion continues with a biography of Karl Schwarzschild, renowned for the solution of Einstein's equations in the case of a non-rotating black hole, as he left as a volunteer for the army in the very beginning of the World War I and shortly after he became deathly ill.

This biographical approach gives us the opportunity to build the curriculum in a non-linear way, linking together the topics that are usually taught first to quite complicated concepts. The biographical references allow us to state personal questions that motivate students, establish connection to the subject of astronomy through fostering their reflection and, finally, discuss complicated concepts ahead of the lesson plan.

References:

- Carl Sagan. Cosmos. Eratosthenes: The man who measured the world.
- Albert Einstein über Kepler. Frankfurter Zeitung. 9. November 1930

Experiential Workshop: Integrating Astronomical Data Sonification with STEAM Education

Presenter: Lai Xinyu, Shandong University, China

The study integrates the interdisciplinary nature of astronomical data sonification with STEAM education concepts, designing a series of workshops to explore new teaching models for astronomy education. Conducted in middle schools, the workshops involve students selecting galaxy images that interest them and resonate with real-life contexts after learning about relevant astronomical knowledge and sonification techniques. Students then create their own simple musical pieces with the guidance of teacher. A post-workshop survey revealed students' positive attitudes toward the sonification of astronomical data. The workshops not only deepened students' understanding of astronomy but also fostered creativity and interdisciplinary problem-solving skills.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14319808>

Professional researchers' understanding of astronomy is often based on scientific knowledge itself, but it is not practicable for the public to learn these abstract concepts and formulas through their intellect [1]. Especially for younger secondary school students, they are likely to misunderstand these concepts or find it difficult thus losing confidence in continuing to learn about astronomy.

It has been shown that the use of sensory experiences has important positive effects in science education, especially in understanding abstract concepts [2]. Astronomical data sonification and related derivative creations show a new approach to learning by representing data in sound. Through sound audiences can intuitively and comprehensively experience astronomical concepts while using intuitive thinking to catalyze further reflection [3]. This not only improves understanding and increases engagement, but also gives people an emotional connection to the subject matter, which is important in helping them learn astronomy in a sustained and spontaneous way [4].

Therefore, going beyond traditional visual and textual approaches, this project attempts to explore the effects of data sonification in secondary astronomy education. As an interdisciplinary field, astronomical data sonification provides students with a unique perspective to explore the universe, which not only promotes scientific learning and fosters a spirit of practice and research, but also stimulates creativity and enhances artistic appreciation. This is highly compatible with the STEAM education concepts. Therefore, this project integrates astronomical data sonification with STEAM education concepts, and collaborates with Shandong University to conduct a series of experiential workshops in secondary school. In the class, students create their own "cosmic music" while learning astronomical knowledge. Student feedback was obtained through post-course questionnaires as well as interviews, which led to preliminary results on the multifaceted positive effects of astronomical data sonification in education.

The experiential workshop is entitled “Symphony of Galaxies” and is divided into four sections. The first section begins with a showcase of sonification works from NASA’s “The Universe of Sound” project. I chose three of these works with very different moods and feelings. The cheerful and cozy “Stephen’s Quintet”, the cold and solemn “Pillars of Creation”, and the grand and sumptuous “Carina Nebula”. Through the discussion of the musical atmosphere, students were able to understand the contextual and evocative nature of sound, and were encouraged to make their own contextual associations in the following production section.

The students are already very interested in the topic of this workshop through the viewing of the sonification work. At this point, the second part of the workshop introduced some knowledge about galaxy. Taking the Milky Way as a starting point, we talked about the evolutionary stages of galaxies with different shapes and characteristics, and the principles behind the different colours in the pictures of galaxies. Students are also encouraged to make associations with these galaxies, laying a foundation of knowledge and emotional resonance for designing their own soundscapes in the following steps.

The third part began with a period given to students to freely search the internet for pictures of galaxies that they want to sonify. Further introductions were also given to how to make associations with life situations and how to combine different sound elements to form moods and an overall feeling. Students then conceptualised the sound design of their pieces and write initial ideas on sticky notes.

Finally, the fourth part is the production of the sonification work. Students try to simply operate the data sonification software *sonoUno* to understand the mapping relationship between picture features and sound features, and then get preliminary sound results. After that students can choose to play the sound results with different instruments, divided into different groups the TA will process the audio in the music production software through MIDI technology. Finally, students can choose the suitable background music for their work and complete the design of the musical atmosphere.

Such an experiential workshop design incorporates several STEAM education concepts such as Contextual Learning, Technological Integration, Collaboration, Hands-on Learning, and Art Integration in each section. Instead of just teaching students isolated and abstract scientific concepts, this workshop allows students to bring the knowledge back to their own lives, deepening their understanding and creating an emotional connection.

The post-course questionnaire was organized into two parts, open-ended questions and multiple-choice questions (scales). In the answers to the open-ended questions, almost all the students agreed that sonification works were more appealing than pictures and words alone because they were “accessible to different senses”, “more interesting”, and “thought-provoking”. Regarding attitudes toward the sonification of astronomical data, “interesting”, “incredible”, and “novelty” were the most frequently mentioned words, which shows that students accept and enjoy the auditory way. The multiple-choice questions’ design was guided by 5-point Likert scale. It can also be obtained that students hold a very positive attitude. The level of enjoyment, the willingness to continue to participate in related activities in the future, and the willingness to recommend this experience to friends were all very high. It’s worth noting that, astronomical data sonification demonstrated a very strong attraction among the students, obtaining an average score of 4.92 on the 5-point scale.

References:

- [1] Trotta R, Hajas D, Camargo-Molina J E, et al. Communicating cosmology with multisensory metaphorical experiences[J]. JCOM: JOURNAL OF SCIENCE COMMUNICATIONS, 2020, 19(2): 1-17.
- [2] Shapiro L, Stolz S A. Embodied cognition and its significance for education[J]. Theory and Research in Education, 2019, 17(1): 19-39.
- [3] Zanella A, Harrison C M, Lenzi S, et al. Sonification and sound design for astronomy research, education and public engagement[J]. Nature Astronomy, 2022, 6(11): 1241-1248.
- [4] United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. Sonification: a tool for research, outreach and inclusion in space science[R/OL] (2023-4)[2024-10-20]. https://www.unoosa.org/documents/pdf/Space4PersonswithDisabilites/UNOOSA_Special_Report_on_Sonification_2023.pdf

Astronomy in Amateur Rocket Competition

Presenter: Arthur Miquelito Lopes, Fluminense Federal Institute, Brazil

Collaborator: Ana Cecília Soja (Instituto Federal Fluminense)

Amateur rocket competitions are very popular events, attracting students from different levels of primary and higher education. Among them, the Brazilian Rocket Show (MobFog) stands out for its pioneering nature and national reach. In the two most advanced levels of the competition (4 and 5), whose target audience is high school and higher education students, the rockets are made of plastic bottles and propelled by the chemical reaction of baking soda and vinegar. They are a great opportunity to teach concepts of Physics, Chemistry, and Astronomy, but studies show that their pedagogical potential is little explored by teachers. This work aims to share successful strategies for teaching Astronomy to students aged 14 to 16 through rocket launches.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14479994>

This work aims to share Astronomy teaching strategies from amateur rocket competitions. Amateur rocket competitions are very popular events, attracting students from different levels of primary and higher education. Among them, the Brazilian Rocket Show (MobFog) stands out for its pioneering nature and national reach. It occurs annually and involves over 100,000

students in all stages (MOBFOG 2023). In 2023, there were more than 300,000 students and the expectation is that in 2024 there will be around 500,000 participants. To participate, students must develop their own launch pads and rockets, respecting the guidelines for their level (1 to 5, from Elementary School to Higher Education). In all the levels the participants have the common goal of achieving the greatest reach in their category.

The division into levels gives a type of rocket to be built. The simplest levels (1 and 2) are intended for Elementary School students (6-11 years old), who explore the theme playfully by building paper rockets and propellants first with their hands (level 1) and then using catapults (level 2). In the final years of Elementary School (12-14 years old), the process is sophisticated, using water pressure as fuel and inside PET bottles (level 3). Level 4, aimed at high school and college students, follows the same homemade rocket model as the previous level, but now they use gas generated from the chemical reaction between baking soda and vinegar inside the insulated bottle as fuel. Finally, level 5, introduced in the competition last year, uses solid fuel combustion and requires greater care.

In this work we analyze the two most advanced levels of the competition (4 and 5), because they are a great opportunity to teach concepts of Physics, Chemistry, and Astronomy, but studies show that their pedagogical potential is little explored by teachers. Comparing level 4 and 5 rockets, we conclude that the first, despite being simpler, offers more freedom and options for educational work. The first is based on the challenge of rocket design and precise control of the reaction. The second demands more creativity in the elaboration of the base.

Aware of these characteristics and correlating them with rocket physics, especially those taught in high school and the first years of engineering courses, it is clear that the level 4 rocket is more suitable as a learning object. This is because students have more control over the chemical reaction, and can (and should!) test different shapes and proportions. Thus, beyond the physics and chemistry involved, there is plenty of room for learning scientific and engineering methods (e.g., Baldissera et. al 2016, Lapolli & Coelho 2024). There is also the possibility of relating the development of the rocket to the maker culture, one of the demands of current education.

On the other hand, level 5, despite being interesting, presents itself more as a demonstrative experiment, since due to its safety restrictions, there is little freedom for testing and creativity. Thus, when developing projects at this level, students often act as spectators at the launch, with little room to actually develop skills beyond engine-building techniques.

Therefore, the research presented here serves as a reference for teachers and students who are just starting out or even those who already have some experience in the competition to make an informed decision about which level best suits their pedagogical expectations.

References:

- MOBFOG - Mostra Brasileira de Foguetes. Regulamento da MobFog. Rio de Janeiro: OBA, 2024. Disponível em: <http://www.oba.org.br/site/?p=conteudo&idcat=6&pag=conteudo&m=s>. Acesso em: 05 jun 2024.
- BALDISSERA, Rafaela; SOARES, Douglas; GEDOZ, Tiago; MORELATTO, Tânia; SEVERO, Tiago; POLLETO, Matheus. Propelentes sólidos para foguetes Avaliação teórica do desempenho

da mistura nitrato de potássio/açúcar. Revista Interdisciplinar de Ciência Aplicada, Bento Gonçalves, Rio Grande do Sul, vol 2, 2016.

- LAPOLLI, E. L.; COELHO, Sara E. Análise da pressão em recipientes de plástico devido à reação do ácido acético com bicarbonato de sódio. Revista Brasileira de Ensino de Física, v. 42, 2020. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1806-9126-rbef-2019-0352>. Acesso em: 27 mar. 2024.

DISCUSSION SUMMARY

This session brought together an impressive array of innovative ideas and practices aimed at integrating astronomy into the classroom. Featuring eleven speakers and fourteen posters, this session provided a comprehensive and inspiring overview of how astronomy can serve as a gateway to foster scientific literacy and STEM engagement for students around the world. The contributions highlighted the transformative power of astronomy education, demonstrating its potential to inspire curiosity, enhance interdisciplinary learning, and make science more accessible.

A central theme across the session was the transformative power of innovative technologies and methods in enhancing astronomy education. For example, the Discovery Space Project, presented by Maria Luísa Almeida, showcased how AI-driven tools can create personalized learning experiences for students, allowing them to explore complex concepts such as the causes of seasons, the phases of the moon, and the challenges of landing on Mars. Similarly, Aishwarya Girdhar introduced a groundbreaking educational module that combines augmented reality, ChatGPT, and LEGO models to teach astrophysical concepts like quark-gluon plasma and dark matter. These projects highlighted how cutting-edge technology can be leveraged to make abstract and advanced topics more accessible and engaging for students.

Hands-on learning emerged as another key focus, with speakers emphasizing the importance of experiential activities in fostering a deeper understanding of astronomy. Juan Ángel Vaquerizo presented simple, classroom-friendly experiments to teach students about astrobiology, enabling them to grasp the scientific processes involved in the search for extraterrestrial life. In a similar vein, Heidi Schran detailed an authentic research experience where high school students collected and analyzed data during a solar eclipse, significantly enhancing their appreciation for the scientific process and its real-world applications. Melissa Solares shared her work in Guatemala, where she developed the country's first high school astronomy course, successfully inspiring students to pursue careers in science and related fields.

The role of interdisciplinary approaches and storytelling in astronomy education was another prominent topic. Eleen Hammer demonstrated how astronomy can be integrated into math education through the creation of astronomy-themed math problems. These problems not only introduced students to astronomical concepts but also allowed teachers with minimal astronomy training to engage confidently with the subject. Similarly, Elizandra Daneize Santos highlighted the use of children's literature as a methodological resource in teaching astronomy to young students, illustrating how stories can spark curiosity and make learning both enjoyable and effective.

Collaboration and teacher empowerment were also emphasized as vital components of successful astronomy education programs. W. Niel Brandt discussed the Penn State Inservice Workshops in Astronomy (PSIWA), a 20-year initiative that has trained high school teachers to effectively teach astronomy topics like black holes and cosmology. These workshops, particularly aimed at educators from underserved communities, have had a cascading impact, as each teacher reaches hundreds of students. Jackie Bondell shared her experience with a partnership program in Australia that connects scientists with rural and regional schools, creating long-term relationships and delivering curriculum-aligned lessons on topics such as gravity, galaxies, and

the nature of science. Both initiatives underscored the importance of equipping teachers with the knowledge and tools they need to inspire their students.

The session also offered insights into new collaborative and project-based approaches in astronomy education. Emmanuel Rollinde presented AstroJourneys, an upcoming Erasmus project that will integrate “big ideas in astronomy” with inquiry- and project-based learning to create personalized, inclusive educational experiences for students and educators. Hossein Khezri demonstrated how the use of terrestrial phenomena, combined with mobile photography and festivities with astronomical origin, could effectively teach students about the sun’s motion and seasonal changes, highlighting the importance of creative, localized methods in engaging students.

Complementing the talks, fourteen posters provided additional perspectives on the challenges and opportunities in astronomy education. These posters explored topics ranging from light pollution awareness and the integration of mental health initiatives into educational programs to the development of interdisciplinary and collaborative courses between schools, universities, and high-tech enterprises. The posters underscored the adaptability of astronomy education to diverse cultural and institutional contexts, showcasing efforts to address educational inequities and inspire students in under-resourced areas.

The session provided a comprehensive overview of the innovative ways educators and researchers are using astronomy to inspire curiosity, build scientific literacy, and promote interdisciplinary learning. With its blend of talks and posters, the session illustrated how astronomy can serve as a gateway to science, encouraging students and teachers alike to explore the universe. The efforts showcased during this session are a testament to the potential of astronomy education to shape the next generation of learners and educators, ensuring that the wonders of the cosmos remain a source of inspiration for all.

Compiled by: Eduardo Penteado

Astronomy Education Research

Session organisers: Tshiamiso Makwela (OAE Heidelberg/ University of Cape Town), Julia Plummer (Director of Curriculum, Department of Curriculum & Instruction, College of Education, Pennsylvania State University), Saeed Salimpour (Deakin University/OAE Associate), Joanna Holt (Faculty of Education of the Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences), Moupiya Maji (Astronomy Education Postdoc Fellow Inter-University Centre for Astronomy and Astrophysics, Pune, India)

Editing supported by: Tshiamiso Makwela

SESSION OVERVIEW

This session focuses on the methodology and frameworks that are used in Astronomy Education Research. The session also incorporates research into astronomy learning, teaching, and knowledge creation in astronomy, drawing connections to education, cognitive science, neuroscience and psychometrics.

TALK CONTRIBUTIONS

Mixed Methods Designs for Astronomy Education Research

Speaker: Janelle Bailey, Temple University, USA

Mixed methods research designs bring together both quantitative and qualitative components to maximize the strengths and limit the weaknesses inherent to either alone. Research questions addressed by mixed methods can vary widely, and the three most common designs—convergent, exploratory sequential, and explanatory sequential—serve different investigative purposes. Convergent designs typically collect different data types at the same time and allow for a comparison across them. Exploratory sequential uses qualitative methods to get an initial idea of the scope of the problem, which can then lead to more meaningful development of quantitative measures. Explanatory sequential designs incorporate surveys or other quantitative approaches followed by in-depth qualitative data collection to explain features of the quantitative results.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/o0IMpk1BKz4>

Mixed methods has become increasingly popular in social sciences, and as such, is a viable research design for astronomy education research (AER) studies. Mixed methods is defined as a methodology and a method to research in the social, behavioral, and health sciences in which the investigator gathers both quantitative (closed-ended) and qualitative (open-ended) data, integrates or combines the two, and then draws inferences (called 'metainferences') from the integration that provides insight beyond what can be learned from the quantitative or qualitative data (Creswell, 2022, p. 2). This approach allows us to access the best features of quantitative and qualitative methods while also compensating for their weaknesses by pairing them together. Mixed methods is more than just gathering both types of data; although this is a critical component, perhaps even more important is the integration of the two types together in order to go above and beyond what either could do alone. It is also distinguished from multiple methods (which uses both but does not integrate) or mixed models research (a specific quantitative approach).

Quantitative data are typically numerical and include responses to closed-end questions and other measurements that represent variables in some way. These data are well suited for statistical analyses, although which specific analyses are appropriate will depend upon the nature and extent of the quantitative data. In contrast, qualitative data are primarily textual, obtained through open-ended questions, interviews, audio or video, artifacts, or observations. These data are often understood through an iterative process of thematic coding and analysis.

There are three primary mixed methods designs: convergent, explanatory sequential, and

exploratory sequential. The convergent (sometimes called concurrent) design is when both data types are collected at (approximately) the same time; even if collected at different times, the two data strands are analyzed independently, then brought together afterward to merge or compare the results. This sometimes involves data transformations, such as converting written responses to rubric scores after identifying themes or quality. An example of a convergent design might be a professor who includes both closed-ended (such as a Likert scale) and open-ended questions on a survey to gauge students' perceptions of a new class design, comparing the results of each set of questions to gather greater understanding. Colleagues and I used a convergent design in a survey of physics teachers to understand how and how often they integrated Earth and space science concepts into their physics courses (Vieyra et al., 2020).

In an explanatory sequential design, quantitative data are collected and analyzed first and then qualitative data are collected and analyzed second. This design is often used when the quantitative results are unexpected or unclear, and the qualitative data allows the researcher to explain the quantitative results. A hypothetical study using the explanatory sequential design might involve a researcher who interviews departmental leaders in order to better understand the barriers to using active learning strategies that were highlighted in the results of a survey of faculty in an astronomy department. In my own work, we used this design to understand conflicting results in changes in students' self-efficacy for learning about and knowledge of stars in different courses (Bailey et al., 2017).

Finally, in the exploratory sequential design, qualitative data are used to first understand the variety of perspectives in a smaller sample before collecting quantitative data from a larger group. This design is often used for instrument development to inform item creation or to adapt an existing instrument into a new context, culture, or language. For example, perhaps a researcher in Uganda is curious about students' interest in different astronomy events; she uses an existing survey from the United Kingdom as a starting point, first interviewing local students to see what kinds of opportunities for astronomy learning they have and then following the UK survey format adapted to local events and resources. The Star Properties Concept Inventory was developed using an exploratory sequential design (Bailey, 2007).

Regardless of the mixed methods design you use, integrating the two data strands is key to understanding the phenomenon more fully. Integrating may involve data transformations, such as when you produce frequency counts of thematic codes or apply a rubric to open-ended questions. A different approach could be when you use qualitative data to highlight or explain quantitative results, such as clusters of participants who respond in similar ways. Plano Clark (2019) provides some examples of how integration might occur.

Mixed methods designs can provide powerful opportunities to explore complex ideas in astronomy education research. Careful attention to the design, data collection, data analysis, and integration strategies can allow you to make meta-inferences that go above and beyond what you could infer from either data strand alone.

References:

- Bailey, J. M. (2007). Development of a concept inventory to assess students' understanding and reasoning difficulties about the properties and formation of stars. *Astronomy Education Review*, 6(2), 133–139. <https://doi.org/10.3847/AER2007028>

- Bailey, J. M., Lombardi, D., Cordova, J. R., & Sinatra, G. M. (2017). Meeting students halfway: Increasing self-efficacy and promoting knowledge change in astronomy. *Physical Review Physics Education Research*, 13(2), 020140. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevPhysEducRes.13.020140>
- Creswell, J. W. (2022). *A concise introduction to mixed methods research* (2nd ed.). SAGE.
- Plano Clark, V. L. (2019). Meaningful integration within mixed methods studies: Identifying why, what, when, and how. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 57, 106-111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2019.01.007>
- Vieyra, R. E., Bailey, J. M., Lopez, R. E., & McAuliffe, C. (2020). Integration of Earth and space science contexts for teaching physics. *Physics Education*, 55(5), 055026. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6552/ab9f92>
- Fetters, M. D. (2018). Six equations to help conceptualize the field of mixed methods. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 12(3), 262-267. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1558689818779433>
- Fetters, M. D. (2020). *The mixed methods research workbook: Activities for designing, implementing, and publishing projects*. SAGE Publications. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research* <https://journals.sagepub.com/home/mmr>

Beyond the Stars: Investigating Student Reasoning in Astronomy

Speaker: Chad Luekes, University of Cape Town, South Africa

The present work forms part of a broader programme of research aimed at understanding how pre-instruction introductory astronomy students reason when engaging with astronomy concepts. We developed an instrument, designed to probe student thinking by eliciting detailed written responses. Here we present details of the instrument and selected results from the analysis of student writing. The analysis revealed that the central idea(s) the students used to underpin their reasoning about the day-and-night cycle, was largely in agreement with the accepted astronomical explanations. However, they expressed these ideas in diverse ways. With regard to the question that probed areas that had not been formally taught (stellar twinkling), the key observation was that the majority of students drew on ideas that were deemed plausible. Additionally, where the ideas expressed did not coincide with the concepts that are central to the canonical explanation, it was clear that “sense-making” was driving student reasoning.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/xIa-ducJxOU>

Astronomy education researchers, who are often instructors themselves, generally conduct research to measure the effectiveness of (1) their teaching and (2) their course design and structure. To achieve this, the research focusses on assessing what students have learnt throughout the course and therefore seeks to document (a) what students know (i.e., what they have successfully learnt) and (b) the common areas and themes where students have underperformed. Researchers design and make use of Concept Inventories (CIs) to probe students' conceptual understanding of concepts in astronomy (Madsen et al., 2020). To date there exist several CIs, which successfully surveyed what students know about aspects of astronomy, including earth related phenomena, stars, galaxies, and the big bang.

CIs often make use of multiple-choice type questions (MCQs) to probe student conceptual understanding. These questions usually provide four or five options from which to choose (Slater et al., 2015). Of these options, one is scientifically correct whilst the others generally consist of established alternate understandings, or "distractors". Bardar et al. (2006) noted that well-designed distractors should be identifiable as incorrect by someone who fully understands the concept that is being tested, while at the same time appearing reasonable by someone who lacks understanding of the concept.

Insights gained from the use of these concept inventories have the potential to guide the formative feedback instructors provide to their students and have led to instructional approaches, which have been used at various education levels. For example, conceptual change has been documented where the "misconceptions approach" gave rise to examples of active learning curricula, including Ranking Tasks and Lecture-Tutorials for introductory astronomy. This in turn gave rise to large learning gains (Prather et al., 2004; Hudgins et al., 2006). However, I note that the information one can obtain on student reasoning is often limited when comparing typical CIs to free-writing style item-response instruments (also known as open-ended). This is particularly the case when the purpose of a study is to probe the nature of student reasoning and which begins with documenting the range and frequency of student ideas, necessitating that they (the students) describe their ideas in their own words and in as much detail as possible. Alternatively, CIs typically only document what students know in a summative form.

This work forms part of a broader programme of research aimed at understanding how pre-instruction introductory astronomy students reason when engaging with astronomy concepts. As I could find no suitable resources (CIs) from which to draw on in the literature, I developed an instrument, designed to probe student thinking by eliciting detailed written responses. The instrument covered eight topics, listed as follows: (1) day-and-night cycle, (2) seasons, (3) differences between the luminosities (apparent brightness) of stars, (4) why stars appear to twinkle, (5) dark energy and dark matter, (6) the expanding universe, (7) differences between stars and planets, and (8) black holes. In my masters dissertation, I analyzed student responses to the first four of these topics and I explore student responses to topics 1 (day-and-night cycle) and 4 (why stars appear to twinkle), respectively, in this presentation.

I followed a grounded analysis, more specifically, the Constructivist Grounded Theory Method (Charmaz, 2003). The analysis revealed that the central idea(s) the students used to underpin the reasoning behind the phenomenon of the day-and-night cycle, were largely in agreement with the accepted astronomical explanations. However, they expressed these ideas in diverse ways. With regard to the questions that probed areas that had not been formally taught (stellar twinkling), the key observation was that the majority of students drew on ideas that were

deemed plausible. Additionally, where the ideas expressed did not coincide with the concepts that are central to the canonical explanation, it was clear that “sensemaking” was driving student reasoning.

In my conclusionary remarks of this presentation, I note that reasoning (sense-making) is the hallmark of scientific thinking. I encourage practitioners to foster spaces wherein students are encouraged to engage in logical reasoning and wherein their reasoning abilities are praised. Lastly, I note that when students come to incorrect conclusions, practitioners may find pedagogically useful to look deeper into the ideas that students built their arguments upon. Simply stating that a student is “wrong” may result in the student concluding that their reasoning is flawed, where-in actuality, they may have made use of “sound” logical reasoning, however grounded on incorrect “starting” ideas.

References:

- Bardar, E. M. et al., 2006. Development and validation of the light and spectroscopy concept inventory. *Astronomy Education Review*, 5(2), pp.103–113. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3847/aer2006020>.
- Charmaz, K., 2006. *Constructing grounded theory a practical guide through qualitative analysis*. Los Angeles: Sage Publications.
- Hudgins, D. W., et al., 2006. Effectiveness of Collaborative Ranking Tasks on Student Understanding of Key Astronomy Concepts. *Astronomy Education Review*, 5(1).
- Madsen, A., McKagan, S., & Sayre, E., 2020. Best practices for administering concept inventories. *The Physics Teacher*, 55(9), pp.530-536.
- Prather, E. E., et al., 2004. Research on a Lecture-Tutorial Approach to Teaching Introductory Astronomy for Nonscience Majors. *Astronomy Education Review*, 3(1).
- Slater, S., Price Schleigh, S. & Stork, D., 2015. Analysis of Individual Test Of Astronomy Standards (TOAST) Item Responses. *Journal of Astronomy & Earth Sciences Education (JAESE)*, 2(2), p.89.

The Impact of Questions on Students' Estimations of Astronomical Sizes and Distances

Speaker: Willem Keppens, KU Leuven, Belgium

Collaborators: Mieke De Cock (KU Leuven), Hans Van Winckel (KU Leuven), Wim Van Dooren (KU Leuven), and Jan Sermeus (KU Leuven & Planetarium, Royal Observatory of Belgium)

Literature shows that students have a hard time making estimations of astronomical scales, and very often underestimate the vastness of space. In this research, we constructed and deployed an interactive online survey to probe students' ideas of sizes and distances in the Solar System. It was found that the relative distances between celestial bodies were strongly underestimated overall, while the same did not hold for the relative sizes of those bodies. Moreover, as we used two different formulations to question student estimations, a systematic impact of the type of question on the magnitude of the answers was uncovered. Lastly, we also had students (dis)agree with a customized visualization and self-assess their certainty after every answer. Our findings are discussed.

By making observations and interacting with the world, children gain so-called intuitive or naïve knowledge. This knowledge contributes to the construction of mental models, which are thought to be present in all individuals. The debate on whether children form a rather coherent framework or theory of intuitive knowledge or whether this is more fragmented is still ongoing (see, e.g., [1]). However, regardless of their structure, it is very clear that pieces of intuitive knowledge are often at odds with most recent scientific viewpoints. In such cases, they are usually referred to as misconceptions, also in astronomy [2]. An extensive report on astronomical misconceptions can be found in, e.g., the works of Bailey & Slater [2] or Comins [3].

Several astronomical misconceptions are related to scale [4], which is why many researchers have already investigated students' estimates of astronomical sizes and distances. While a general conclusion is that most people find it very difficult to make these estimates, more specific results often differ between authors. For example, Sadler [4] showed that most participants tend to underestimate the distance between the Earth and the Sun, while Mant [5] reports that half of his participants instead overestimated that distance. As Miller & Brewer suggest, such discrepancies are likely to be due to differences in the assessment methods used. For example, results from multiple-choice questions are always affected by the set of provided options, especially when no option larger or smaller than the correct answer is given. Also, questions about actual physical distances in terms of miles or kilometers are hardly ideal and limit the validity of the results, as they confound the students' intuitive perception of distances with their ability to understand and interpret large numbers [6]. In this work, we therefore attempt to evaluate the reliability and effectiveness of different assessment questions by administering an interactive online survey.

Participants & Methodology: We constructed an online, interactive survey using JavaScript code, linked to an online server and database. This survey was administered with N=201 students in their last year of high school, between 16 and 18 years old. The distances of interest were those between the Earth and the Moon (EM), between the Sun and the Earth (SE), between the Sun and Neptune (SN) and between the Sun and the nearest next star (SS). We chose to only probe estimates on these distances relative to each other, that is, on the ratios SS/SN, SN/SE, and SE/EM. Not only does this approach alleviate the issues with large numbers discussed before, it has also been shown that conceptions of relative scale are generally more accurate than those of absolute scale. In addition to distances, also the relative sizes of the Moon (M), the Earth (E), and the Sun (S), i.e., S/E and E/M were probed in a similar relative manner. At the beginning of the survey, students were asked to rank these sizes and distances from smallest to largest. Based on this ranking, students were then asked to pairwise quantify these ratios.

After every answer, participants were presented with a customized visualization of their answer. Students could then either agree with the visualization and move on to the next question, or disagree and revise their previous answer. When the student eventually agrees with the visualization, a self-assessment of certainty was required. We included a 'pure guess' option to distinguish those from very uncertain (but not random) answers.

Every student answered each question in two formulations: a fraction formulation and a travel time formulation. An example of a question in the fraction formulation would be: "How many times smaller is the distance Earth-Moon compared to the distance Sun-Earth?". The corresponding question in the travel time formulation would read: "If a spacecraft takes one month to travel the distance Sun-Earth, then how long does that spacecraft take to travel the distance Earth-Moon?". The effect of those different formulations was the main interest of this study, together with the impact of the customized visualizations.

Results and Discussion: Roughly two thirds (67%) of the participants ranked the sizes correctly, while only 60% placed the distances in the correct order. Only slightly more than half of the participants (54%) placed both the distances and the sizes in the correct order.

Roughly half of the quantification answers were marked as pure guesses, indicating that students had a hard time making these estimations. The estimations resulting from the questions on the ratio SE/EM are shown in Figure 1. The range of collected answers spans several orders of

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

magnitude, which was a recurring result for all questions. There is much more underestimation than overestimation for this question, as can be seen from the red horizontal line indicating the correct value of roughly 400. The trend of overall underestimation was found to occur for every distance-related question, as can be seen from the striped boxplots in Figure 2. For the size questions, indicated by the fully colored boxplots, we see both over- and underestimation, although for the ratio S/E the underestimation starts to dominate as well.

Roughly one third of all answers were altered after seeing a visualization. This number was significantly higher for size-related questions (40%) than for distance-related questions (25%), with $p < 0.001$, from which we conclude that the visualization with two disks was more effective than that with one simple line. For some but not all questions, adjusting the original answer significantly improved the students' answers.

There was a measurable difference in the estimations resulting from questions in the fraction formulation compared to those from the travel time formulation. Fraction formulation questions lead to significantly higher estimations than travel time questions. An example of this effect is shown in Figure 3. This trend was found for all assessed ratios, both before and after the visualizations were shown. However, we did not find any difference in the self-assessed certainty

scores between the two formulations, nor did one formulation lead to more numerous or more drastic adjustments after visualization. Moreover, the two datasets resulting from the two formulations had very similar internal consistency scores. Therefore, we cannot conclude that one formulation leads to better or more trustworthy results than the other, only that the precise formulation influences the magnitudes of the resulting estimations.

Conclusion: Students express their mental models of astronomical scales in ways that are susceptible to external factors. One such factor, as we showed in this work, is the precise formulation of the assessment question. Although some students were quite consistent, with only small differences between their answers to fraction and travel time questions, others often had multiple orders of magnitude between both answers. Another influential factor could be the presentation of visualizations, as was explored in this work as well. While most answers were either unaltered or only slightly modified, some students adjusted their initial answer by a factor 10 or greater. The question on how to build further on these inherently unstable models will be a challenging theme in future research.

References:

- [1] di Sessa, A. A., Gillespie, N. M., & Esterly, J. B. (2004). Coherence versus fragmentation in the development of the concept of force. *Cognitive Science*, 28(6), 843–900.
- [2] Bailey, J. M., & Slater, T. F. (2003). A Review of Astronomy Education Research. In *Astronomy Education Review* 2(2), 20-45.
- [3] Comins, N. F. (2001). *Heavenly Errors: misconceptions about the real nature of the Universe*. Columbia University Press.
- [4] Sadler, P. M. (1992). *The Initial Knowledge State of High School Astronomy Students*. [Doctoral dissertation, Harvard University].
- [5] Mant, J. (1995). A survey of British primary school teachers' understanding of the Earth's place in the universe. *Educational Research*, 37(1), 3–19.
- [6] Miller & William, W., & Brewer, F. F. (2010). Misconceptions of Astronomical Distances. *International Journal of Science Education*, 32, 1549–1560.
- [7] Tretter, T. R., Jones, M. G., Andre, T., Negishi, A., & Minogue, J. (2006). Conceptual Boundaries and Distances: Students' and Experts' Concepts of the Scale of Scientific Phenomena. *J Res Sci Teach*, 43(3), 282–319.

Framework for the Use of the Celestial Sphere as an Educational Tool

Speaker: Judith Vandewiere, Planetarium of the Royal Observatory of Belgium and KU Leuven, Department of Physics and Astronomy, Belgium

Collaborators: Jan Sermeus (KU Leuven Department of Physics and Astronomy, KU Leuven Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences) and Mieke De Cock (KU Leuven Department of Physics and Astronomy)

Explaining the apparent motion of the Sun and stars is challenging for students. To help students reason about it and support them in switching between different perspectives, educators use various representations of the celestial sphere (e.g., the planetarium or a celestial globe). However, we suspect that students (and perhaps educators) may not fully grasp the underlying model of the (representations of the) celestial sphere, as well as its possibilities and limitations. This lack of understanding can lead to misinterpretations or over generalizations. As a first step in studying students' understanding of the celestial sphere, we constructed a framework to categorize different representations of the celestial sphere model according to the perspectives and reference frames they use.

Positional astronomy, one of the oldest branches of astronomy, continues to pose challenges when it comes to teaching the apparent motion of the Sun and stars. Research has shown that people of all ages, not just students, hold various alternative conceptions about this phenomenon (Bekaert et al., 2022; Plummer, 2009; Slater & Stork, 2015; Trumper, 2001). Common misconceptions include beliefs that the Sun is always directly overhead at noon or that stars remain stationary in the sky.

Several studies (Bekaert et al., 2024; Plummer et al., 2011; Yu et al., 2015) suggest effective teaching must consider motions of celestial bodies both from an observer's point of view on Earth and from space. Focusing solely on Earth's rotation is often insufficient for a complete understanding of the diurnal motion of the Sun and stars. Therefore, one must be able to switch perspectives in order to fully connect actual and apparent motion, emphasizing the role of spatial thinking in astronomy education, as highlighted by Plummer (2014) and Cole et al. (2018).

Bekaert et al. (2024) used the celestial sphere, represented by a globe and a planetarium projection, to guide students in thinking about the apparent motion of the Sun and stars. Despite a careful instructional design, students still struggled to answer questions about the apparent motion of stars compared to the Sun. Bekaert et al. (2024) hypothesize that students, may not fully grasp the underlying model of the celestial sphere, as well as its possibilities and limitations. This lack of understanding can lead to misinterpretations or overgeneralizations. Despite the widespread use in education, little is known about how well students understand the celestial sphere as a model.

Perspective \ Reference frame	Earth-based (view from Earth)	Space-based (view from space)	'Out of space'-based (beyond the stars)
Earth-based (fixed Earth, moving stars)	Planetarium (classic) "Observable" Reality	Planetarium (digital)	Celestial globe (rotating sphere)
Space-based (moving Earth, fixed stars)	???	Planetarium (digital) "Actual" Reality	Celestial globe (rotating Earth)

Table 1: Framework. The arrows illustrate different pathways to navigate between perspectives and reference frames.

In this work, we summarize the celestial sphere model, discuss several representations of the model and present a framework to categorize the different representations of the abstract celestial sphere model.

The celestial sphere model: The celestial sphere is an imaginary sphere with an arbitrarily large radius, centered on the Earth, onto which celestial bodies are projected. Since the radius is large, the observer can be considered positioned at the center, making the visible sky appear as the upper half of the sphere above the horizon plane. The sphere appears to rotate due to the Earth's rotation. This model supports reasoning about the positions and movements of celestial bodies in the sky. However, like any model, it makes assumptions and simplifications. One key assumption is that astronomical objects are equidistant from Earth, as their actual distances are too great to determine through simple observation. Another simplification is that stars can be treated as fixed points, as their proper motions are typically negligible over the span of a human lifetime. However, not all celestial objects behave this way; the Sun and planets shift position relative to the "fixed" stars over the course of a year, making the explanation of the apparent motion of the Sun more complex than that of the stars. Therefore, for now, we only consider the stars as part of the model.

Representations of the celestial sphere model: To help students reason about celestial motion and to support them in alternating between perspectives, educators use various representations of the celestial sphere, such as celestial globes, planetariums, or drawings. However, these representations inevitably introduce additional considerations due to their physical nature. Since it is impossible to create a model with an infinitely large radius, these representations often depict the Earth as disproportionately large, with the observer no longer at the center. Drawings are two-dimensional representations of a three-dimensional object, which introduces further difficulties (Parker & Heywood, 1998). Planetariums typically display only half of the celestial sphere, and not all students can be positioned at the center where the zenith is directly above them.

Framework – perspective versus reference frame: Given the variety of representations and their affordances, we need to be able to clearly refer to its different aspects when discussing the celestial sphere as a model and educational tool. Therefore, we developed a framework that categorizes different representations based on their perspective and reference frame (see Table 1). Here, perspective refers to the specific location from which a student observes the system, while reference frame refers to the inertial system that determines what is considered

stationary. Objects in motion are perceived as moving relative to this reference frame. Note that in literature (Bekaert et al., 2024; Plummer et al., 2011; Yu et al., 2015), the terms “perspective”, “reference frame”, and “point of view” are often used interchangeably.

We distinguish three different perspectives regarding the celestial sphere. In an Earth-based perspective, students observe the stars from Earth, while for a space-based perspective, students take the position of an observer in space, looking down at the Earth. In the ‘out of space’-based perspective students are positioned beyond the stars, effectively outside the celestial sphere. We differentiate between two different frames of reference: the Earth-based reference frame in which the Earth is considered stationary and the stars are moving, and the space-based reference frame, where the opposite is true. Note that a reference frame becomes relevant only when there is motion involved, which means when there is a change in position over time.

Representations of the celestial sphere can be mapped within this framework (see Table 1). For example, a classical planetarium might use an Earth-based perspective with an Earth-based reference frame, allowing students to observe the stars as they move during a normal night.

Future: We will use this framework to investigate which transitions are particularly challenging for students and whether these involve shifting between different perspectives, reference frames, or between model and reality. Moreover, we can assess whether certain transitions occur spontaneously or are easier for students. This is a first step in studying students’ understanding of the celestial sphere and in developing evidence-informed learning paths that result in a better understanding, supporting students in switching between the ‘observable’ and ‘actual’ reality (as indicated by the full grey arrow).

References:

- Bekaert, H., De Cock, M., Van Dooren, W., & Van Winckel, H. (2024). Investigating students’ insight after attending a planetarium presentation about the apparent motion of the Sun and stars. *Physical Review Physics Education Research*, 20(1), 010141.
- Bekaert, H., Van Winckel, H., Van Dooren, W., Steegen, A., & De Cock, M. (2022). Identifying students’ mental models of the apparent motion of the Sun and stars. *Physical Review Physics Education Research*, 18(1).
- Cole, M., Cohen, C., Wilhelm, J., & Lindell, R. (2018). Spatial thinking in astronomy education research. *Physical Review Physics Education Research*, 14(1).
- Parker, J., & Heywood, D. (1998). The earth and beyond: Developing primary teachers’ understanding of basic astronomical events. *International Journal of Science Education*, 20(5).
- Plummer, J. D. (2009). A Cross-age Study of Children’s Knowledge of Apparent Celestial Motion. *International Journal of Science Education*, 31, 1571–1605.
- Plummer, J. D. (2014). Spatial thinking as the dimension of progress in an astronomy learning progression. *Studies in Science Education*, 50(1), 1–45.

- Plummer, J. D., Wasko, K. D., & Slagle, C. (2011). Children learning to Explain daily Celestial Motion: Understanding astronomy across moving frames of reference. *International Journal of Science Education*, 33(14), 1963–1992.
- Slater, S. J., & Stork, D. J. (2015). Analysis of Individual Test Of Astronomy Standards (TOAST) Item Responses. In *Journal of Astronomy & Earth Sciences Education-December* (Vol. 2, Issue 2).
- Trumper, R. (2001). A cross-age study of junior high school students' conceptions of basic astronomy concepts. *International Journal of Science Education*, 23(11), 1111–1123.
- Yu, K. C., Sahami, K., Sahami, V., & Sessions, L. C. (2015). Using A Digital Planetarium For Teaching Seasons To Undergraduates. *Journal of Astronomy & Earth Sciences Education (JAESE)*, 2(1), 33.

Innovation in Astronomy Teaching: A Study of Astronomical Peripateticism and the Flipped Classroom

Speaker: José Antonio D'Santiago García, Rafael María Baralt National Experimental University, Mene Grande, Venezuela

This study explores the effectiveness of Astronomical Peripateticism combined with the Flipped Classroom methodology in teaching astronomy. Through workshops and night observations, students acquire theoretical knowledge at home and apply it in practical outdoor sessions. The research focuses on how this methodology enhances the understanding of astronomical concepts and fosters a personal connection with the universe. Preliminary results indicate a significant increase in student engagement and interest, as well as their ability to apply theoretical knowledge in practical contexts.

Talk link: https://youtu.be/SdJo_u1Vx94

This study explores the combination of two innovative methodologies: the Flipped Classroom and Astronomical Peripateticism, as tools to transform astronomy teaching. The main focus of this research is to evaluate how these methodologies influence students' learning, participation, and interest. In our Astronomy Club, we have implemented these methodologies in order to create a learning environment that not only favors the acquisition of theoretical knowledge, but also the practical and reflective experience of astronomy.

Flipped Classroom: In this methodology, students take on an autonomous role in acquiring theoretical knowledge at home, through digital resources such as videos, readings, and online quizzes. This prior preparation allows them to arrive at face-to-face sessions with a solid theoretical foundation, ready to be applied in practical activities.

Astronomical Peripatetism: Inspired by Aristotelian teachings, Astronomical Peripatetism takes instruction outdoors, where night hikes and sky observations facilitate immersive teaching. Students use telescopes, star charts, and mobile apps to observe constellations and other celestial bodies, allowing for a direct connection between theory and practice in a real-world setting.

Implementation in our Astronomy Club: Club sessions are organized into three key phases:

1. **Theoretical Preparation at Home:** Students access online teaching materials covering essential astronomical concepts. This fosters their autonomy and allows them to arrive better prepared for practical activities.
2. **Outdoor Practical Sessions:** In these meetings, night walks and astronomical observations are carried out under the sky, where students apply what they have learned, identifying celestial bodies and discussing the astronomical phenomena observed in real time.
3. **Discussion and Reflection:** After practical activities, students participate in group discussions and reflections, where they share their observations and ask questions, promoting collaborative learning that deepens their understanding.

To evaluate the impact of these methodologies on student learning, we used a combination of qualitative and quantitative techniques:

- **Pre- and Post-Session Questionnaires:** We apply questionnaires before and after the practical sessions to measure progress in understanding theoretical concepts and their practical application.
- **Direct Observation:** During the outdoor sessions, systematic observations of student participation were conducted. Students' ability to identify celestial bodies, the quality of their contributions in discussions, and their ability to connect theoretical concepts with observations were documented.
- **Learning Portfolios:** Each student kept a portfolio where they recorded their observations, reflections, and practical work. These portfolios were reviewed and analyzed to identify learning patterns and recurring difficulties.
- **Semi-structured interviews:** At the end of each cycle, we conducted interviews with students to collect their perceptions about the methodologies implemented, the relationship between theory and practice, and the impact these had on their motivation and interest in astronomy.

Our goal was to observe how these methodologies foster not only a better understanding of astronomy, but also a greater emotional connection with the cosmos. We wanted to identify

areas for improvement in the learning process and explore how the natural environment and autonomy of students influence their ability to apply complex concepts in real-life situations. Preliminary data collected from this implementation indicates the following results:

- **Increased Participation:** Students show greater enthusiasm and commitment to club activities, actively participating in both observations and discussions.
- **Improved Understanding:** The integration of theory and practice has significantly strengthened understanding of complex astronomical concepts. Students are able to apply theoretical knowledge in practical contexts, demonstrating deeper and more sustainable understanding.
- **Personal Connection with the Universe:** The outdoor context and astronomical observations have awakened a deeper and more emotional interest in astronomy, generating a personal connection with the universe that goes beyond the classroom.

The combination of the Flipped Classroom and Astronomical Peripatetism has been shown to be an effective methodology for improving both student engagement and understanding in astronomy. Our research at the Astronomy Club suggests that these methodologies not only increase student interest and motivation, but also provide them with a deeper understanding of astronomical concepts. We will continue to refine and explore these tools to maximize their impact on astronomy education.

References:

- Becerra, M. (2014:96) Participatory, critical and transformative action research Group for Research and Dissemination in Education (GIDE) Editorial Vlladoi-España.
- Brehier. (2014), Epistemology and Qualitative Research: Educational approaches in current education. Editorial la Muralla, S.A. 2nd Argentine edition.
- Buchetti A (2016), Mayéutics and Peripatetics for its application as a learning technique - XVI Academic Reflection Conference in ISSN: 1668 1673 Year IX, Vol. 9, Buenos Aires, Argentina.
- Cerda, A. (2015), Educational, participatory and critical research, in the classroom, Editorial Alfar Sevilla Spain.
- D'Santiago García, JA (2023). Exploring the secrets of the cosmos on foot: Astronomy clubs and Peripatetism. 5th Shaw-IAU Workshop on Astronomy for Education (5th SIW), virtual. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10445237>
- Fernández, A. (2014), The qualitative paradigm in socio-educational research. Central American Educational and Cultural Coordination pp105 (CECC) San José, Costa Rica.
- Hurtado, de B. (2000) Holistic Research Methodology, SYPAL- in Barrera. Educational services and projections for Latin America- Caracas.

A Study Discussing How to Get the Most out of Collaboration Between Scientists and Teachers

Speaker: Oriel Marshall, Universities of Copenhagen & Antwerpen, Denmark & Belgium

Collaborators: Jesper Bruun and Anja C Andersen (University of Copenhagen, Denmark), Katrien Kolenberg and Peter Van Petegem (University of Antwerp, Belgium)

Including contemporary science research in the classroom can help students to understand the scientific landscape. One method of introducing cutting-edge topics into schools is Scientist Teachers Partnerships (STPs); using the input of both parties to create scientifically and pedagogically sound materials. In this study, we use STPs to develop lessons about Exoplanet climates. One-on-one initial interviews were conducted with 13 international exoplanet PhD students and five science teachers from Flanders. Co-creation sessions were then conducted with groups of teachers and scientists. In this study, we use the Model of Educational Reconstruction to breakdown the process of bringing modern astronomy topics into the classroom with STPs.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/IQn9btpA0sw>

Scientist Teacher Partnerships: One way of bringing modern scientific concepts and methods into the classroom is to include researchers in the development of classroom resources through scientist-teacher partnerships (STP) (Brown et al., 2017; Trautmann & Makinster, 2005). It has been found that pairing scientists and teachers together may help teachers to adapt curriculum content, particularly when their confidence and content knowledge are lacking (Lee, 2004), which is often the case when it comes to teaching astrophysics (Angell et al., 2004). The inclusion of teachers in the material development may help to increase teachers' feelings of ownership over the materials (Ball & Cohen, 1996), which is hypothesised to, in turn, lead to an increase in confidence in the teachers.

For this article, STP was used during the co-creation process. Individually, the teachers' and scientists' input and feedback provided valuable insight based on their perspectives and experience, and then facilitating interaction between the two groups allowed for interesting and unexpected discussions and outcomes that may not have occurred if each group had been worked with separately.

The Model of Educational Reconstruction: The model of educational reconstruction (MER) (Duit et al., 2012; Reinders et al., 2012) provides a methodological framework for developing educational materials and environments. This framework is based on three pillars of educational research. The first pillar is the analysis of the scientific content that will be taught in order to find key concepts. The second pillar is the analysis of both students' and teachers' perspectives

and learning processes. The third pillar is the design and evaluation of learning environments and activities. MER was chosen as a framework for this project as it is an appropriate model for modern science topics that have not been established in teaching curricula yet, and each pillar of the model maps suitably to an element present in the STP process.

Method: This project was developed using Design Based Research (Hoadley, 2004) and so the data was collected and analysed iteratively over multiple cycles. The participants that provided voices for this lesson development were; thirteen exoplanet researchers from the CHAMELEON research network and four secondary school teachers from the Antwerp region of Belgium. The exoplanet researchers were selected as they are part of the same research network as the principal author. The teachers were chosen from a number of volunteers who were informed about the project through outreach activities organised by members of the CHAMELEON research network. The students selected were students through the classes taught by the selected teachers.

The process began with individual interviews with the scientists, during which we familiarized ourselves with the scientist's research areas and interests. These interviews were semi-structured and conducted online for practical purposes. This was followed up by a consolidation of the science behind the key topics. We then conducted individual interviews with the teachers. These interviews were also semi-structured and held online, and the questions were inspired by the results from the initial interviews with the scientists. We identified two topics with an appropriate overlap of teacher interest, curriculum topics, and scientific research: cloud formation and lightning occurrence on exoplanets. Based on this, we then consulted online resources to see what educational resources already existed in the field.

We then formed two groups of teachers and scientists based on subject. The cloud formation group was made up of one geography teacher and three exoplanet cloud scientists, and the lightning group was made up of one physics teacher and two exoplanet lightning scientists. In these groups, we conducted group co-creation sessions through which a set of lesson materials were developed. These materials were then tested by both the scientists and teachers, with both groups providing feedback to us. We tested and improved the materials over multiple iterations, resulting in a set of lessons about clouds and lighting on exoplanets that is pedagogically and scientifically sound, and in line with current cutting-edge exoplanet research topics. The resultant materials from these rounds of STP development can be found [here](#).

Conclusion: This study is still underway, and further data analysis will be conducted in the future. We have learned from the process so far that Scientist-teacher partnerships (STPs) are a useful approach to integrating contemporary astronomy into the classroom, allowing for the creation of materials that make use of this versatile and interdisciplinary field. When used effectively, STPs can bring forth overlaps in topics and skills between the three players (teachers, scientists, educational researchers), and allow for all three to utilise their particular skillset. Through the use of the Model of Educational Reconstruction, these STPs ensure that both the scientific accuracy and pedagogical effectiveness of materials are carefully considered. STPs provide an innovative pathway for enhancing science education and allowing for future student engagement with cutting-edge astronomical topics.

References:

- Angell, C., Guttersrud, Ø., Henriksen, E. K., & Isnes, A. (2004). Physics: Frightful, but fun. Pupils' and teachers' views of physics and physics teaching. *Science Education*, 88(5), 683–706. <https://doi.org/10.1002/SCE.10141>
- Ball, D. L., & Cohen, D. K. (1996). Reform by the Book: What Is—or Might Be—the Role of Curriculum Materials in Teacher Learning and Instructional Reform?: *Educational Researcher*, 25(9), 6–14. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X025009006>
- Brown, J. C., Bokor, J. R., Crippen, K. J., & Koroly, M. J. (2017). Translating Current Science into Materials for High School via a Scientist–Teacher Partnership. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 25(3), 239–262. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10972-013-9371-Y>
- Duit, R., Gropengießer, H., Kattmann, U., Komorek, M., & Parchmann, I. (2012). The Model of Educational Reconstruction – a Framework for Improving Teaching and Learning Science¹. In *Science Education Research and Practice in Europe* (pp. 13–37). SensePublishers. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6091-900-8_2
- Hoadley, C. M. (2004). Methodological alignment in design-based research. *Educational Psychologist*, 39(4), 203–212. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15326985ep3904_2
- Lee, O. (2004). Teacher change in beliefs and practices in science and literacy instruction with English language learners. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 41(1), 65–93. <https://doi.org/10.1002/TEA.10125>
- Reinders, D., Harald, G., Ulrich, K., Michael, K., & Ilka, P. (2012). The Model of Educational Reconstruction – a Framework for Improving Teaching and Learning Science. In D. Jorde & J. Dillon (Eds.), *Science Education Research and Practice in Europe* (Vol. 5, pp. 13–37). SensePublishers. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6091-900-8_2
- Trautmann, N. M., & Makinster, J. G. (2005). Teacher/Scientist Partnerships as Professional Development: Understanding How Collaboration Can Lead to Inquiry. AETS International Conference, Colorado Springs, CO. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/239763626_TeacherScientist_Partnerships_as_Professional_Development_Understanding_How_Collaboration_Can_Lead_to_Inquiry

POSTER CONTRIBUTIONS

To Make Astronomy Education a Compulsory Subject for All High School Students

Presenter: Hidehiko Agata, NAOJ & IAU OAO, Japan

This study examines from various perspectives a high school science curriculum that can be implemented in Japan's next Courses of Study. The competencies to be addressed are under discussion. In addition to "analytical, critical, and evaluative skills", "risk response", and "problem-solving skills", which are directly related to agency, we would like to emphasize "the ability to express one's own opinions on science and technology" as a compulsory subject for "Fundamentals of Science" in high school. A questionnaire survey of Japanese high school students revealed that "understanding the universe" was a content they wanted to learn.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14489783>

Aiming to integrate astronomy into the government curriculum guideline, our research team designed a new curriculum of science education in Japanese high school that smoothly connects to junior high school content. Social problems that we face today require interdisciplinary scientific comprehension to be addressed while students learn each science subject, which is physics, chemistry, biology, and geology in Japanese science curriculum, independently. Considering the purpose of science education and its role in society, we reconsider compulsory subject for science education that should be comprehensive and foundational in order to nurture problem solving skills. Our goal is to implement "Big Ideas in Astronomy" into the Japanese high school science curriculum.

In this poster, we present the progress of our research. The survey asked whether the curricula of various countries include a comprehensive or integrated mandatory basic science course. This survey was conducted during the international conferences in 2022, specifically GA/IAU, GHOU2022, CAP2022, & Shaw-IAU WS etc. The results showed that among the countries that responded, Taiwan and Singapore had a curriculum structure that was close to the ideal. Many countries that responded had comprehensive courses, but in many cases, they were not mandatory or were not university entrance exam courses.

Next, a survey of a total of 500 high school seniors and graduates in Japan revealed the following order of the science content they wanted to learn during their high school years. 1. Climate Change, 2. Understanding humans, 3. Understanding the universe, 4. Infectious disease, 5. Understanding life, 6. Understanding the Earth, 7. Water pollution, 8. Energy problems, 9.

Biodiversity, 10. Technology & Life, and 11. History of science. Thus, among these options of what students would like to learn, astronomy ranked third. As a result of this and various other related studies, our research group has identified the following seven topics to be covered in the mandatory science courses. Responding to global warming and other climate change (SDG 13); Understanding biodiversity and maintaining ecosystems (SDGs 14+15); Addressing energy issues (SDG 7) Fighting infectious diseases (SDG 3); Addressing water pollution and securing water resources (SDG 6); Science, technology and human life (AI, medicine/health, food shortage, disaster prevention/mitigation, bioethics, etc.); Understanding the universe, the earth, life, and humans. Based on the results of the aforementioned research, we have also included the study of Universe, or astronomy, as a required content.

In my personal opinion, I consider the understanding of globalization and universalisation in the last chapter of “Big Ideas in Astronomy” to be a mandatory Big Idea in the high school curriculum. In June 2024, our research group proposed three new curriculum proposals to the Japanese Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology based on these analyses and findings. These proposal includes about 20 hours of astronomy education in Japanese all high schools. It is not clear if they will be implemented. A conclusion will be reached within a few years.

Reference: For more information on this study, see [here](#) (Japanese version only).

Clarifying Uncertainty in the Nature of Science Through Astronomy Examples

Presenter: Stepanovic Jakub, KU Leuven, LUCA School of Arts, Belgium

Collaborators: Sandy Claes (KU Leuven, LUCA School of Arts) and Jan Sermeus (KU Leuven, Royal Observatory of Belgium)

The Nature of Science (NoS) (Lederman et al., 2002) includes several aspects, but uncertainty is usually not mentioned explicitly. Yet, uncertainty is inevitable in astronomy and science in general. Uncertainty is a driving force for curiosity, reducing uncertainty is a crucial challenge in instrument development, reporting uncertainty is expected and necessary in the academic community. Moreover, honest and accurately portraying uncertainty in education and science communication is needed to uphold scientific transparency and credibility. As such, our study examines the elements of NoS to clarify and define uncertainty among them, supported by examples from astronomy. We conclude with recommendations for astronomy instruction.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14483210>

Uncertainty is common in science. In fact, absolute certainty is not only epistemically unachievable but also undesirable, as it would block science from exploring new ways of understanding [1]. While scientists are generally aware of uncertainties, the lay public can link uncertainty with failure, contributing to the challenge of communicating scientific uncertainties [2]. Many formal and informal educators have naive views on certainty in science themselves [3,4], so it is not surprising that children and adolescents continue to believe that forming scientific knowledge is a certain, clear-cut process, e.g., [5].

Uncertainty is broadly captured in the scientific literacy concept Nature of Science (NoS), which discusses students' understanding of science beyond the body of knowledge by specifying science as a process and a way of knowing and by including its limitations [6]. Advancing the NoS understanding is a major goal of science education [7]. Moreover, an informed understanding of NoS is essential for countering scientism and skepticism [8]. Research on NoS defines the characteristics of scientific knowledge through seven core pillars: (1) Science includes perspective and subjectivity; (2) Laws have no hierarchy above theories; (3) Science involves human imagination and creativity; (4) Science is empirical; (5) Science embeds social and cultural elements; (6) Science is tentative; and (7) There's not one scientific method. Uncertainty is included in the pillar of tentativeness. It describes science as being subject to change and never absolute or certain. However, the tentativeness definition is inconsistent across the literature and only highlights one aspect of uncertainty. Also, in science education standards, sometimes based partly on NoS research, the uncertainty is present in a vague form or omitted altogether [9]. Because of the unclear definition, teaching tentativeness has been criticized for possibly misleading [10] and reducing trust in science [11].

As there are calls to make the NoS elements explicit [12], and researchers advocate teaching uncertainty as inherent in science [13], we aim to clarify various forms of uncertainty in science through illustrative astronomy examples. As such, we want to contribute to the NoS construct.

Example 1: the shift in the view of the universe from geocentric to isotropic demonstrates how scientific theories evolve and become increasingly reliable over time. It illustrates the tentative nature of science: as the evidence grows, it not only reveals what the universe is but also clarifies what it is not by ruling out incorrect assumptions, e.g., that we are the center of the universe.

Example 2: Here, we map uncertainties in an ongoing research project that integrates and processes data on the atmosphere of Venus and communicates it to scientists and the general public [14]. In this project, the scientists use data that already includes uncertainties in the accuracy and precision due to the technical limitations of the instruments used in the data collection. After integrating data from different sources (each with their format, syntax, units, and reported uncertainties), the scientists are also using machine learning (ML) to process the data, which was sparse and suffered from missing data (two additional forms of uncertainty). Furthermore, ML also introduces aleatoric and epistemic uncertainties [15]. Finally, communicating the results of their work can add uncertainties due to unclear writing and a lack of transparency. Yet, throughout all these stages, the scientists employ methods to manage uncertainty, such as building on prior research, instrument calibration, ensuring study repeatability, and peer review. While never complete, such processes reduce uncertainty and increase the reliability of the data and the science.

Our second example shows that tentativeness does not capture the full extent and importance

of uncertainties in science. We suggest including uncertainty as a stand-alone pillar in NoS to mitigate the shortcomings.

References:

- [1] K. Kampourakis and K. McCain, *Uncertainty: How It Makes Science Advance*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2019.
- [2] S. Schneider, "Communicating uncertainty: A challenge for science communication," in *Advances in Natural and Technological Hazards Research*, vol. 45, 2016.
- [3] N. G. Lederman and J. S. Lederman, "Teaching and Learning of Nature of Scientific Knowledge and Scientific Inquiry: Building Capacity through Systematic Research-Based Professional Development," *J Sci Teacher Educ*, vol. 30, no. 7, 2019.
- [4] G. M. Holliday and N. G. Lederman, "Informal Science Educators' Views about Nature of Scientific Knowledge," *Int J Sci Educ B Commun Public Engagem*, vol. 4, no. 2, 2014.
- [5] M. Schroeder, A. McKeough, S. A. Graham, and S. P. Norris, "Students' views of uncertainty in formal and personal science," *Research in Science and Technological Education*, vol. 37, no. 2, 2019.
- [6] N. G. Lederman, F. Abd-El-Khalick, R. L. Bell, and R. S. Schwartz, "Views of Nature of Science Questionnaire: Toward Valid and Meaningful Assessment of Learners' Conceptions of Nature of Science," *J Res Sci Teach*, vol. 39, no. 6, 2002.
- [7] K. Kampourakis, "The 'general aspects' conceptualization as a pragmatic and effective means to introducing students to nature of science," *J Res Sci Teach*, vol. 53, no. 5, 2016.
- [8] M. Ferkany and C. Kendig, "Countering Scientism and Scepticism in Teaching the Nature of Science Through Its Virtues," in *Virtues as Integral to Science Education: Understanding the Intellectual, Moral, and Civic Value of Science and Scientific Inquiry*, 2020.
- [9] J. K. Olson, "The Inclusion of the Nature of Science in Nine Recent International Science Education Standards Documents," *Sci Educ (Dordr)*, vol. 27, no. 7-8, 2018.
- [10] I. Galili, "Towards a Refined Depiction of Nature of Science: Applications to Physics Education," *Sci Educ (Dordr)*, vol. 28, no. 3-5, 2019.
- [11] W. W. Cobern, B. A. Adams, B. A. S. Pleasants, A. Bentley, and R. Kagumba, "Do We Have a Trust Problem? Exploring Undergraduate Student Views on the Tentativeness and Trustworthiness of Science," *Sci Educ (Dordr)*, vol. 31, no. 5, 2022.
- [12] N. Lederman and F. Abd-El-Khalick, "Avoiding De-Natured Science: Activities that Promote Understandings of the Nature of Science," in *The Nature of Science in Science Education*, 2005.
- [13] Z. E. Buck, H. S. Lee, and J. Flores, "I Am Sure There May Be a Planet There: Student

articulation of uncertainty in argumentation tasks,” Int J Sci Educ, vol. 36, no. 14, 2014.

[14] “VAMOS Project.” Accessed: Oct. 21, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://vamos.aeronomie.be/>

[15] C. I. Yang and Y. P. Li, “Explainable uncertainty quantifications for deep learning-based molecular property prediction,” J Cheminform, vol. 15, no. 1, 2023.

Investigating the Efficacy of Experiential Learning Through Observatory Internships for Studying Astronomy

Presenter: Chandrsekaran Annal Deva Priya Darshini, Madras Christian College, India

Astronomy is a course in Madras Christian College for the students of BSc mathematics. The course includes understanding the celestial sphere, the celestial coordinate system, the movement of the Sun, and the diurnal motion of stars. Students are taught using ICT tools supported by a practical exposure to the actual night sky through observation sessions. Students are allowed to intern at an observatory to gain a first hand experience of setting up telescopes and recording observations. In this poster, we showcase the effectiveness of night sky observation and training at an observatory as experiential learning tools for the students, the challenges faced, the outcome, and impact of the initiative. This study is in line with SDG 4.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14489887>

Background of the study: Experiential learning is considered to be a progressive method of instruction, which allows students to understand topics taught in class through tasks in the real world. This study is an investigation into the efficacy of experiential learning in Astronomy through an internship at a private observatory. Astronomy is taught at the under-graduate level to students of Mathematics. The learning objectives for the experience were formed based on the topics in the syllabus. The actual experience was carefully designed keeping in mind the age, gender mix, and understanding of students. Reflection was an important part of the experience in learning process. The reflection stage was assessed through a questionnaire given to the students. The four stages in this study were (1) Design of the experience/Developing the experiential learning exercise (2) Internship/Practicum at the observatory (3) Questionnaire and Discussion, and (4) Report and conclusions/Analysis and Contemplation.

- **Planning and Execution:** The internship was planned with the collaboration of an amateur astronomer and the college's faculty. After a lecture by the astronomer, discussions were held to finalize logistics. 14 out of 57 students were selected for participation, following parental consent due to late evening commutes.
- **Learning Objectives (LOs):** Students were expected to learn hands-on skills like assembling and operating telescopes, identifying celestial objects, understanding cardinal points, and studying the moon's surface. These objectives were reinforced through simulations and preparatory lectures using apps like Stellarium and star charts.
- **Internship Experience:** Students attended ten days of training at the observatory, learning about celestial coordinate systems, telescope operations, lens grinding, and maintaining observational logs. The experience complemented their classroom learning, deepening their understanding of both theoretical and practical aspects of astronomy.
- **Assessment and Results:** A questionnaire compared the learning outcomes between students who attended the internship (Group A) and those who didn't (Group B). Group A demonstrated superior understanding and confidence in using telescopes and applying astronomical concepts.
- **Challenges and Concerns:** These included logistical challenges, especially for female students needing permission to stay late, and the focus on responsibility and avoiding distractions during the internship.
- **Impact and Reflection:** The experiential learning process greatly enhanced students' engagement, confidence, and interest in astronomy. Students appreciated the hands-on experience and expressed interest in further studies. The course teacher highlighted the importance of such internships in bridging theory with practical application, fostering patience, precision, and systematic observation skills in students.

Future Directions: The success of the program encourages the possibility of making it an annual event, expanding collaborations with other observatories, and possibly initiating outreach programs for schools and the general public. A skill development course can also be designed based on the Internship experience.

References:

- Lewis, L. H., & Williams, C. J. (1994). Experiential learning: Past and present. In L. Jackson & R. S. Caffarella (Eds.), *Experiential learning: A new approach*, (pp. 5-16). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Cantor, J. A. (1995). *Experiential learning in higher education*. Washington, DC: ASHE-ERIC Higher Education Report No. 7.
- <https://www.suffolk.edu/madrid-campus/academics/experiential-education> Retrieved on 18 March 2024
- Hutchinson, S., and Lawrence, H. *Playing with Purpose. How Experiential Learning Can Be*

More Than a Game. Taylor & Francis, 2017.

- Munge, B., Thomas, G., & Heck, D. (2018). Outdoor fieldwork in Higher Education: Learning from multidisciplinary experience. *Journal of Experiential Education*, 41(1), 39-53.
- <https://www.wgu.edu/blog/experiential-learning-theory2006.html> Retrieved on 18 March 2024
- <https://experiencelearning.utk.edu/about/types/> Retrieved on 18 March 2024

Cultural Astronomy: Transformative Potential in Basic Education

Presenter: Enrico Chiosini, Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil

Cultural Astronomy examines how different cultures interpret and integrate celestial knowledge into their social systems, revealing a rich diversity that is often overlooked in traditional education. By analyzing the relationship between education and culture and considering legal measures that promote multicultural education, we explore the challenges of assimilationist and differentialist perspectives. This research underscores the transformative potential of Cultural Astronomy in basic education, encouraging deeper cultural awareness, critical thinking, and a more inclusive understanding of science, enriching students' worldviews and preparing them for life in a multicultural society.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14489477>

Astronomy, one of the oldest sciences, traditionally studied from a Western perspective, reveals transformative potential when examined through cultural diversity. This work explores the integration of Cultural Astronomy into basic education, proposing a reconfiguration of teaching to incorporate an intercultural understanding that values the celestial knowledge of various cultures.

The educational system often faces challenges in dealing with cultural differences, especially in the inclusion and recognition of those who do not fit hegemonic standards. These challenges are evident in traditional approaches that tend to overlook the rich cultural plurality and the valuable contributions that non-hegemonic knowledge can offer to student development. Intercultural perspectives challenge these dominant norms, seeking to overcome assimilationist and differentialist approaches that, as discussed by Candau, often result in the homogenization of knowledge from marginalized cultures or in the intensification of cultural segregation by excessively emphasizing differences without promoting effective dialogue [1].

Within the disciplines associated with the teaching of Natural Sciences, Astronomy stands out for its intercultural potential. The varied interpretations of the sky and the different ways of relating to it provide a rich field of intercultural study. Cultural Astronomy, specifically, investigates how different societies perceive and interact with celestial phenomena within their cultural and social contexts [2]. This field of study seeks to integrate the knowledge of various cultures through the observation of the sky and its influence on the lives of cultural groups, enhancing a science education that is more inclusive and representative of global diversity.

Integrating Cultural Astronomy into basic education is not limited to expanding the science curriculum but involves reorienting pedagogy so that cultural diversity becomes an essential component of teaching. According to Lima et al., this intercultural approach promotes respect and appreciation for diversity, which are fundamental in pluralistic societies [2]. Through Cultural Astronomy, a bridge is established between scientific and cultural knowledge, revealing how science is intrinsically linked to diverse historical and cultural contexts.

Moreover, by exploring astronomy through a cultural lens, students can perceive that scientific knowledge is just one of multiple ways of understanding the world. This view aligns with the ideas of Jafelice, who advocates for a holistic approach in science education, where different perspectives are valued and integrated into learning [3]. This holistic perspective is further reinforced by legal guidelines, such as Federal Law No. 11.645/08, which encourages the inclusion of Afro-Brazilian and indigenous history and culture in school curricula. As pointed out by Oliveira, these guidelines not only promote more inclusive and representative education but also ensure that students recognize and value cultural diversity as an essential enrichment to their academic and personal formation [4].

However, the inclusion of Cultural Astronomy faces significant challenges, from institutional resistance to a lack of adequate educational resources. As observed by Candau, many schools still adopt assimilationist or differentialist perspectives, which can dilute or marginalize non-hegemonic knowledge [1]. Assimilationism, for example, tends to homogenize cultural contributions, framing them within a dominant framework that does not reflect the true richness of diversity. In contrast, the differentialist approach can inadvertently promote segregation by overly emphasizing differences without encouraging constructive dialogue between cultures.

The intercultural proposal seeks to balance the appreciation of diversity with the promotion of shared understanding and mutual respect among different cultural communities. Implementing this approach involves reexamining and possibly reinventing pedagogical practices and curricula to ensure that education in Cultural Astronomy not only adds to the educational environment but transforms it to incorporate and value all voices. As Rodrigues points out, it is crucial for educators to develop teaching materials and methods that reflect the plurality of astronomical and cultural knowledge, paving the way for a richer and more inclusive understanding of science [5].

Education in Cultural Astronomy has the potential to profoundly transform students' perceptions of the universe and their social interactions, fostering mutual respect and intercultural understanding. By integrating various interpretations of the cosmos, students are encouraged to challenge the Western-dominated view in science. Jafelice highlights that learning about cultural connections with celestial phenomena allows students to perceive science as a narrative intertwined with culture, religion, and philosophy, not just as a collection of decontextualized facts [3].

In conclusion, integrating Cultural Astronomy into basic education not only meets legal guidelines that promote multicultural education but also redefines the parameters of how science is taught and understood in a globalized context. This work has shown that the intercultural approach of Cultural Astronomy can substantially enrich the educational curriculum while preparing students to be global citizens, aware, and respectful. By exploring a variety of cultural perspectives on celestial phenomena, this educational approach challenges traditional paradigms and fosters a learning environment that values diversity and intercultural dialogue. Thus, Cultural Astronomy emerges as a crucial element not only in promoting tolerance and empathy but also in developing profound critical thinking, preparing students to face and positively contribute to an increasingly diverse and interconnected society. Therefore, more than an addition to the curriculum, Cultural Astronomy is an essential educational necessity to cultivate a more comprehensive and inclusive understanding of the world we live in.

References:

- [1] V. M. Candau, "Multiculturalismo e educação: desafios para a prática pedagógica", in *Multiculturalismo: Diferenças culturais e práticas pedagógicas*, Candau, V. M. and Moreira, A. F. B. (Eds.), 10th ed., (Editora Vozes, Petrópolis, 2013), pp. 13-37.
- [2] F. P. Lima et al., "Sky-earth relations among indigenous peoples in Brazil: distinct skies, different views", in *History of Astronomy in Brazil*, Matsuura, O. T. (Ed.), (Companhia Editora de Pernambuco, Recife, 2013), pp. 85-128.
- [3] L. C. Jafelice, "The teaching of Cultural Astronomy: For whom, by whom, how, and why?", *Proceedings of the IV National Symposium on Astronomy Education (SNEA)*, (Goiânia, 2016).
- [4] É. de Oliveira, "Multiculturalismo e Ensino de Ciências na Educação Básica: Desafios e Potencialidades da Astronomia Cultural", Master's Thesis, University of São Paulo, (São Paulo, 2020).
- [5] M. de S. Rodrigues, "The diversity of knowledge about the sky and astronomy teaching: didactic proposals and potentialities of cultural astronomy", Master's Thesis, University of São Paulo, (2015).

Misconceptions on Astronomy Topics in Science Education: A Case Study for Secondary School Students

Presenter: Yelkenci Aysegul, Istanbul Kültür University, Turkey

Collaborator: Seda Türker (Istanbul Kültür University)

This research aims to determine the misconceptions of secondary school students about astronomy topics. A total of 119 students from private and public schools participated in this study while an astronomy achievement test was applied to 12th grade students. According to the analyses, misconceptions were found in some questions. The 12th grade students' level of understanding of basic astronomical concepts appears to be low. No statistically significant difference was found between male and female students in terms of the level of understanding astronomy concepts. The private school was observed as the institution with a low rate of success. These results show the difficulties in students' ability to understand and apply certain concepts related to astronomy in science education.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14489977>

A misconception in education occurs when students connect one notion incorrectly with another, or when they confuse new ideas with ones they already know, leading to the formation of false conceptions. In general, what students understand differs from what scientists think. There are five kinds of misconceptions, namely: (a) preconceived notions; (b) non-scientific beliefs; (c) conceptual misunderstandings; (d) misconceptions of local languages, and (e) factual misconceptions (Suprpto, 2020). Misconceptions about astronomy are generally considered to fall into the category of "conceptual misunderstandings". This research aims to determine the misconceptions of secondary school students about some astronomy topics.

A total of 119 students from one private high school (21), one vocational and technical high school (38), and two one public high school (60) participated in this study while 57 of them were female and 62 were male students. A 15-question Astronomy Achievement Test (AAT) was applied to the sample group consisting of 12th grade students. 'The Astronomy Diagnostic Test' (Hufnagel, 2002) and the Astronomy Achievement Test (ABT) developed by Türk (2015), which has been previously conducted validity and reliability studies were used as the main reference sources for the questions. The Astronomy Achievement Test (AAT) was administered after the consultant opinion of an expert academician in the field of Astronomy and Space Sciences and necessary permissions were obtained from the Ministry of Education. While determining the method to be used in quantitative data analysis, it was checked whether the data were suitable for normal distribution. It was determined that the scale data did not show normal distribution. Therefore, non-parametric analysis methods were used in IBM SPSS v.23 software. The maximum score obtained after the application of the 15-question AAT test is 9 out of 15. The average score of 119 participants is $5,3697 \pm 1,9904$. According to the analyses, misconceptions were found in the

Figure 1: Number of correct answers for each question (left) and Correct answers female/male (right)

answers to some questions. It can be said that they are misconceptions for questions 1, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, and 14. These results show the difficulties in students' ability to understand and apply certain concepts related to astronomy in science education. As a result of the Mann Whitney U analysis, it was determined that the number of correct and incorrect errors did not show a statistically significant difference with the gender variable.

Looking through Turkish education system, in primary school astronomy content is found in Science lesson plans starting from grade 3 increasing in grades 5-6-7 up to 8. In secondary education astronomy is covered in physics courses but it is also offered as a selective course in grades 9 and 10. We assume as a last year high school student a 12th grade student should be able to understand many topics related to astronomy. But according to the results of this study, secondary school 12th grade students' level of understanding of basic astronomical concepts appears to be low. No statistically significant difference was found between male and female students in terms of the level of understanding astronomy concepts. The private school was observed as the institution with a low rate of success in the test. There is a statistically significant difference in the level of understanding of astronomy concepts between students in public high schools and students in private high schools. Students should be made aware of their misconceptions and motivated to make an effort to correct them.

References:

- Hufnagel, Beth. (2002). Development of the Astronomy Diagnostic Test. *Astronomy Education Review*. 1. 10.3847/AER2001004.
- Suprpto, N. (2020). Do We Experience Misconceptions?: An Ontological Review of Misconceptions in Science. *Studies in Philosophy of Science and Education*, 1(2), 50-55. <https://doi.org/10.46627/sipose.v1i2.24>
- Türk, C. (2015). Efficiency of the teaching of astronomy through models. PhD Thesis, Samsun: Ondokuz Mayıs University, Graduate School of Educational Sciences.

Continuing Teacher Education: Comets as a Pedagogical Strategy for Teaching Astronomy

Presenter: Jaqueline de Souza Valdemiro Campos, São Paulo State University (UNESP), School of Sciences, Campus Bauru, Brasil

Collaborators: Dr. Enos Picazzio (Institute of Astronomy, Geophysics and Atmospheric Sciences, University of São Paulo) and Dr. Rodolfo Langhi (UNESP, School of Sciences, Campus Bauru)

Astronomy teaching needs to be sensitive to the needs of teachers, encouraging and adding to their routines and pedagogical practices. Comets are a potential interdisciplinary approach to insert Astronomy concepts. The development of concept through workshops and virtuals simulator contributed significantly to the construction of teacher knowledge in a continuing teacher training through of the D. Shön's practical-reflective, J. Dewey's progressive education, and D. Ausubel's meaningful learning. The Bardin's Content Analysis revealed that training centered on a single topic favors the teacher's teaching and learning process. Teachers demonstrated a change in their pedagogical, professional practice, and motivational like a research news themes and use a new teaching tools.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14489668>

Continuing Teacher Education: Continuing Teacher Education is a resource that contributes significantly to the professional training of teachers in practice, promoting, in addition to knowledge, new teaching and learning practices in the classroom. It is well known that the initial training of education professionals does not have the necessary time to develop more specific scientific content (PRADO, A.F.; NARDI, R. 2020; LANGHI, R. 2011). This makes continuing training extremely important for teaching, especially for higher education courses in pedagogy.

Astronomy Teaching: According to Soler and Leite (2012), the teaching of astronomy contributes to historical-philosophical discussions, as well as promoting an understanding that society is not distant from science and technology, which are so necessary and valued today, as well as the interdisciplinarity that is inherent to astronomy. In Brazil, the Common National Curriculum Base sets out the guidelines for the competences and skills to be developed in students in Basic Education. It includes Earth and Universe content in Nature Sciences, such as the apparent movement of the Sun, characteristics of the Earth, observation of the sky and the Moon, Cultural Astronomy, the calendar, and optical instruments (BRASIL, 2017).

Methodology: The process of continuing education needs to meet the needs of practicing teachers and not be limited to updating knowledge or training. In order to achieve this goal, the priority was to lead teachers to reflect on their practice and interdisciplinary action, thus developing practical-reflective training (SHÖN, D. 1987, apud ALARCÃO, I. 1996), together with David Ausubel's Significant Learning, which values the teacher's prior knowledge, and Jhon

Figure 1: Comet 1P/Halley - Celestia and Stellarium simulators. Campos, J.S.V. (2022) (top). Cometary core workshop - sublimation and surface. Campos J.S.V. (2022) (bottom).

Dewey's Progressive Learning (2018. apud MOREIRA, 2022), where the teacher, in a student position, took the center of his learning process. As an interdisciplinary theme, we worked on comets, considering these objects as a differential in arousing curiosity, such as their observation, history and the myths and omens involved, their peculiarity among the small bodies of the Solar System, which contributed to the formation of the planets, the supply of water on Earth and the existence of its biosphere, fundamental in the teaching of Life and Evolution and Matter and Energy. To make the teaching of astronomy meaningful to the theoretical content and teaching proposals, the use of simulators such as Stellarium and Celestia were used to show some comets, identifying their physical and orbital characteristics, as well as their observation in the sky.

A "cometary core" workshop with dry ice was also held, in which the teacher could mediate the main characteristics of a comet. However, this one was adapted, where the dry ice was not mixed with the other substances used in the workshop, but served to show the sublimation process undergone by the comet as it approaches perihelion, as well as mediating the main characteristics of a comet.

A virtual visit was also made to a private observatory in the city of Bauru, SP, the Sagittarius Observatory, where the amateur astronomer makes observations of comets, thus recognizing

the importance of the actions of Amateur Astronomy for Science and its dissemination and teaching.

Results: During the lessons, the teachers expressed surprise at the relationship between their prior knowledge and the content presented. According to Ausubel, previously acquired knowledge serves as the basis on which new information is related. Using Content Analysis (BARDIN, 2008), it was possible to identify a change in the teachers' behavior towards the content and the teaching of astronomy in the classroom. The analysis generated three categories: Recognition of the need for research, where the teacher understands the importance of research for their teaching practice; the adoption of new methodologies and teaching tools, such as the use of simulators; motivation, where a motivated teacher plans and reflects on changes in their lessons. The analysis also raised points that can promote this behavioral change in teachers when it comes to teaching astronomy. These are contextualizing the curriculum base within the proposed theme; showing the paths of interdisciplinarity; exploring the theme and its resources; and positioning the teacher as the protagonist.

References:

- ALARCÃO, I. (1996). Reflexão crítica sobre o pensamento de D. Shön e os programas de formação de professores. *Revista da Faculdade de Educação*, v. 22, n. 2. São Paulo: USP. p. 11-42.
- BARDIN, L. (2008). *Análise de Conteúdo*. Tradução: Luíz Antero Reto, Augusto Pinheiro. 4. ed. Lisboa: Eduções.
- BRASIL. (2017). *Base Nacional Comum Curricular*. Ministério da Educação. Brasília, DF.
- CAMPOS, J. S. V. (2022). *Formação Continuada de Professores: os cometas como estratégia pedagógica interdisciplinária para inserir conceitos de Astronomia nos anos iniciais do Ensino Fundamental*. (Dissertação). Mestrado Profissional em Ensino de Astronomia. Instituto de Astronomia, Geofísica e Ciências Atmosféricas. Universidade de São Paulo. São Paulo, SP, 2022.
- LANGHI, R. (2011). Educação em Astronomia: da revisão bibliográfica sobre concepções alternativas à necessidade de uma ação nacional. *Caderno Brasileiro de Ensino de Física*, v. 28, n. 2: p. 373-399.
- MOREIRA, M. A. (2022). *Teorias de Aprendizagem*. 3. ed. ampl. Rio de Janeiro, RJ: LTC. E-book.
- PRADO, A. F.; NARDI, R. (2021). Formação de professores dos anos iniciais e saberes docentes mobilizados durante um curso de formação em Astronomia. *Revista Latino-Americana de Educação em Astronomia*, n. 29, p. 103-116. DOI: 10.37156/RELEA/2020.29.103.
- SHÖN, D. (1987). *Educating the reflective practitioner: Toward a new design for teaching and learning in the professions*. San Francisco: Jossey Bass.
- SOLER D. R.; LEITE, C. (2012). *Importância e Justificativa para o Ensino de Astronomia*:

um olhar para as pesquisas da área. II Simpósio Nacional de Educação em Astronomia. Anais... São Paulo, SP, 24 a 27 jul. 2012. p. 370-379.

Teacher-Centred Approach: Study of Profiles, Needs, and Practices in Astronomy Education in Primary

Presenter: Olivier Bonneton, S2HEP Universite Claude Bernard Lyon 1, France

Collaborators: Juliette Tuillon-Combes and Philippe Loutesse (S2HEP Universite Claude Bernard Lyon 1)

This study engages in the exploration of astronomy education in France within primary schools, adopting a perspective centred on school teachers. Its primary objective is to analyze the profiles, needs, and pedagogical methods of teachers working in this field. It is noteworthy that in France, few recent studies have delved into this research area, with the majority of available surveys dating back more than two decades (MERLE 2003, FREGE & VENTURINI 2006). Thus, the study initiates an approach to create a state-of-the-art review and to characterize profiles primarily. In this poster we discuss the initial results of the questionnaire distributed to all schools (36 000) from January to May 2024. To date, over 1730 feedback responses are being analysed.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14483299>

In this poster, I have presented the initial results of my first year of doctoral research, focused on the teaching of astronomy at the primary level in France. The main aim of this study is to provide a detailed overview of the profiles, needs, and teaching practices of primary school teachers. In this summary, we discuss the initial results of the questionnaire distributed to all schools (36 000) from January to May 2024. To date, over 1730 feedback responses are being analyzed. The goal of this research is to provide a solid foundation for understanding and improving the teaching of astronomy in primary schools.

Methodology: We developed and distributed a detailed questionnaire aimed at collecting data on the perceptions, needs, and practices of current teachers. This questionnaire was specifically designed to target primary school teachers. The questions were crafted to be both quantitative and qualitative in order to capture a comprehensive range of data: The closed-ended questions include multiple-choice questions and Likert scales, a psychometric tool used to measure attitudes such as the degree of agreement or disagreement among individuals. These allow us to obtain quantifiable and easily analysable data on aspects such as the frequency

and type of astronomy-related activities conducted in the classroom. Regarding the open-ended questions, they provide teachers with the opportunity to express in detail their opinions, experiences, and specific needs, thus enriching our data set. The analysis of these responses is currently underway. The method of distributing the questionnaire was rigorously planned to reach a broad, representative sample of primary school teachers across France.

Regarding the selection of participants: To build our participant database, we used a Python script that automatically extracted email addresses from a public school directory. This process allowed us to target approximately 36,000 French primary schools, ensuring comprehensive and balanced distribution of the questionnaire.

On the procedure for sending the questionnaire: To maximize the response rate and manage the data efficiently, the questionnaires were sent in a staggered manner over a four-month period, from January to April 2024. Prior to this extensive phase, a test was conducted in the Lyon region in December 2023 to refine and validate our sending and response processing protocol. Managing a data collection campaign of this scale involved challenges and the rigorous implementation of response processing, including daily email dispatch maintenance and return management, ensuring that data was collected systematically and ethically to guarantee the quality and integrity of the data collection.

The questionnaire: The questionnaire enabled us to gather data from over 1,700 primary school teachers, providing a rich database for our study. The collected data is currently being analyzed using advanced statistical and computational tools to ensure accurate and in-depth interpretation: specialized software such as R, Tableau, and specific Python libraries (Seaborn, Plotly, or Matplotlib) are used for the quantitative analysis of the data. These tools facilitate the detection of trends, the establishment of correlations, and the generation of other essential descriptive statistics. As for the qualitative data analysis from open-ended responses, analysis techniques are being implemented to code and interpret the numerous text responses.

Regarding the questionnaire itself: it contains 64 questions and it is structured into four distinct sections, each targeting complementary aspects of teachers' knowledge, attitudes, expectations, and teaching practices. The first section collects data on the affiliated educational region (academie), the type of school, years of teaching experience, and other basic demographic information. The aim is to contextualize the responses within a variety of geographical and institutional frameworks. The second section explores the respondents' educational background, including their academic training and personal interest in astronomy and science in general. It also inquires about their participation in astronomy-related activities (sky observation activities or astronomical events, planetarium, visit of observatory, etc.) both in school settings and personally. The section also focuses on basic knowledge of astronomy (for example, explaining the phases of the Moon and the phenomenon of the seasons). In the third section, the questions focus on teaching methods in astronomy, assessing the teachers' comfort level with teaching this subject, the frequency of lessons, the resources used, and the assessments conducted with students. And the final section focuses on teachers' needs and expectations regarding continuing education and specific educational resources for astronomy. It aims to determine opportunities for improving teacher training.

Perspectives: The methodological approach of this research combines strategies to provide a deep and nuanced understanding of astronomy teaching practices at the primary level in France.

It ensures the validity and reliability of the data, thereby supporting the main objective of developing tailored educational resources that meet the real needs of teachers. The preliminary results of this survey will allow us, by next years, to propose, develop, and analyze tailored educational materials aimed at improving the quality of astronomy teaching in French primary schools. The continuation of this study will focus particularly on examining the numerous resources already available. We will question their accessibility and how they are appropriated by primary school teachers. Many teachers have contacted me following the questionnaire and have expressed interest in further experimentation. The development of a research protocol is currently underway.

Acknowledgement: We thank Emmanuel Rollinde (Universite de Cergy-Pontoise, ESPE de Versailles, LDAR) for his valuable advice.

References:

- Girault, Y., & Merle, H., 2003, *Aster*,36,3-14
- Frege, V., & Venturini, P., 2006, Analyse des conceptions en astronomie de futurs professeurs d' école. *Didaskalia*, 29, 41-65 Likert R., 1932, A technique for the measurements of attitudes. *Archives of psychology*.1932, 140(22), 5-55

Investigating Teachers' Integration of Astronomy and Space in Formal Learning

Presenter: Christine Hirst Bernhardt, University of Maryland, USA

Many teachers have acted upon the inclusion of space topics in NGSS to embed space experiments into their courses. Consequently, various space entities provide low or no cost launch services and activities for K-12 classrooms. There has never been a holistic investigation of: a) Which programs teachers use, b) How they use them, c) How teachers' perceive impacts on science learning, and d) Impacts on teachers' practice. Further, these teacher-led initiatives have not made significant roads into education literature. This qualitative study coded a survey instrument to ground student space experiments in science education literature by connecting the agentic opportunities of learning with and through space topics.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14489240>

For over 100 years, Earth and Space were the most neglected realm of science education (Hirst Bernhardt & Bailey, 2024; Orion, 2019). Yet the robust inclusion of these areas within the Next

Generation Science Standards (NGSS), combined with the rapidly changing space economy, has prompted many teachers to embed dynamic Earth and Space content in their courses, which embody the Science and Engineering Practices (NRC, 2012). In response, a myriad of entities in aerospace, industry, and the non-profit sector have begun providing low cost or free launch services and space experiments for students in K-12 formal education settings. Teachers nationwide are exploring innovative means of teaching science through the lens of space, which embody the science and engineering practices. Programs which allow students to design space experiments or analog space missions embody the elements for robust science experiences as defined in much of the science education literature (Ko and Krist, 2019; Miller et al, 2018; Stroup, 2014; 2018), however there has never been a research study documenting such efforts. Space experiments offer students the unique ability to do science, as scientists. This study is a first step towards grounding student space experiments and other space lessons in the corpus of science education.

Rationale: While many of these initiatives have individual evaluation and assessment components, there has never been an investigation of which programs teachers use, how they use them, and how they perceive the programs to impact their students and their professional practice. Further, the use of such educational opportunities has not yet made any roads into the science education literature. Salimpour and colleagues (2021) conducted the first multinational astronomy curricular study to highlight the occurrence of astronomy topics, while Hirst Bernhardt and Bailey (2024) conducted a follow-on qualitative study to document examples of astronomy in classrooms and communities. There has never been a large-scale national study to document teachers use of space programs in their classrooms. Student designed space experiments such as aboard high-altitude balloons, and programs such as Peppers in Space, Plants in Space, MixStix, and Student Space Flight Experiments offer students the unique ability to do science, as scientists, and act with epistemic agency (Miller et al., 2018; Stroup 2014; 2018). This study is a first step to grounding student space experiments into the literature, and then to explore the opportunities for epistemic agency afforded by such experiments.

Research Question: This study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What resources do teachers deploy for students to authentically engage in space sciences through experimentation?
2. How, if at all, do teachers perceive the impact of space experiments on students?
3. How, if at all, do teachers perceive the impact of space experiments on students?

Preliminary Findings: This study included a survey instrument administered via social media groups and mailing lists. Participants were asked a variety of questions, including if they used student space experiments or observations. At the time of this submission, only two respondents did not use such experiments. These two indicated greater barriers to bringing astronomy into their coursework, and frustration with recitation-based astronomy lessons and rote skills. Teachers who did not use space experiments were less likely to use materials if they were uncomfortable with the underlying science content. Conversely, the teachers who used space experiments cited engagement, career connections, love of learning and piqued interest amongst students. The teachers noted their own increased networks and professional value as a result of participating in space experiments. Activities included rocketry, NASA's Grown Beyond Earth, high altitude balloon experiments, and student activities in the Limitless Global Educator program.

Figure 1: One word to describe space activities with students (world cloud).

Respondents who use space experiments

Respondents do not use space experiments

Figure 2: How comfortable are you using a new lesson if you do not know all of the background science?

Use of Astronomy Concepts Within Comics to Motivate Physics Classes

Presenter: Marcos Rincon Voelzke, Cruzeiro do Sul University, Brazil

The aim of this work is to use Astronomy concepts within comics to motivate Physics classes. It was applied at the Casimiro Silva State School, in Brazil, with 40 high school students. For the development of the Learning Object, software for comics was used. The pre-test was applied on the dates of August, 2021 and then interventions were carried out on the subject of electromagnetic wave, spectral bands, and radio waves and with the delivery and explanation of the Comics, as a Learning Object, addressing communication between planets and between Earth with Voyager 1 and 2. After a period of four months, the same questionnaire, was repeated to verify the potential significant learning. It was verified that the methodological strategy reflected in the improvement of the performance.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14489362>

The Physics teacher in High School (HS) finds alternatives so that the student can easily understand the concepts of radio waves and microwaves with a didactic resource, the Comics, which makes the discipline of electromagnetic waves more modifying with the Teaching of Astronomy. The objective of this work is to build a Learning Object (LO) for the discipline of Physics in HS through Comics as a support for the teacher in the classroom.

Methodology: For the development of the LO, a textbook by Godoy (2018) was used. Supported by a software HagáQuê (Bin, Tanaka and Rocha, 1999) from Campinas University (UNICAMP-Brazil), bringing together drawings, figures, and information from Greicius (2020, 2021) and Wild (2021) from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) website in the context of the story (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Communications (Source: <https://mars.nasa.gov/mars2020/spacecraft/rover/communications/>).

Figure 2: Communication between Mars and Earth (Source: https://www.nasa.gov/mission_pages/msl/index.html).

Results and discussion: The results of the Comics production generated two episodes with nine Comics. Evidencing the communication between Mars and Earth (Fig. 2). With Curiosity and Perseverance rovers on the Martian surface and by satellites in orbit. They use the transmission of radio waves in Ultra-High Frequency (UHF) in the range from 300 to 3,000 MHz, being part of the microwave range from 1,000 MHz to 10,000 MHz. With terrestrial receivers in the United States, Spain and Australia to receive scientific data from Mars. Hence production of the comic book made it possible to improve the teaching by the teacher about electromagnetic waves.

References:

- BIN, S. A.; TANAKA, E. H.; ROCHA, H. V. 1999, Software HagáQuê. Version 1.01. [S.I.]. UNICAMP. Available [here](#) - Accessed on 24 May 2021.
- GODOY, L. P. 2018, Ciência Vida e Universo. Ensino fundamental: anos finais. 1 ed. São Paulo: FTD, 77, 78.
- GREICIUS, T. 2020, Curiosity Rover. National Aeronautics and Space Administration. Available [here](#) - Accessed on 23 May 2021.
- GREICIUS, T. 2021, Perseverance Rover. National Aeronautics and Space Administration. Available [here](#) - Accessed on 23 May 2021.
- WILD, F. 2021, Commercial Crew Program. National Aeronautics and Space Administration. Available [here](#) - Accessed on 23 May 2021.

DISCUSSION SUMMARY

In this edition of the 6th Shaw IAU workshop on astronomy for education, the session on Astronomy Education Research was focused on “how to carry out astronomy education research effectively”. This highlighted the key research methodologies, paradigms, and theoretical approaches often used in the AER domain.

AER is an interdisciplinary field that draws on other disciplines to draw inferences on how people make sense of astronomy content and phenomena. The speakers in this session shared their different research approaches, different frameworks as well as astronomy content focus. The session had an invited speaker Professor Janelle Bailey, who has over 20 years of experience in Astronomy Education Research. Her talk provided an overview of the mixed method methodology in AER. This highlighted three mixed methods designs from Creswell (2019), (i) Convergent, (ii) Explanatory sequential, and (iii) Exploratory sequential, which can be employed when using the mixed method design, that would yield useful results.

The following talks covered different ways of probing students’ knowledge of astronomy content. From Leukes’ talk, it was highlighted that we tend to focus more on the correct answers, rather than exploring students’ answers (correct or incorrect), as the reasoning behind their answers reflects their sense-making process. Keppens’ exploration of astronomical scales (size and distances), yielded results consistent with the current research, showing the need for more rigorous intervention that would assist the students with understanding this better. Veandewiere has developed a framework for teaching the celestial sphere, which combined all the models of the celestial sphere including visualisations and planetarium. While this is still in its preliminary phase, the framework promises to be effective.

The other talks focused on the interventions that could be employed in aiding student understanding of concepts, one from Marshal, on developing theory-based activities, with scientists, and practitioners as well as research, to provide a richer student engagement. Dr. García covered the aspect of assessing the impact of the learning environment, with a focus on the flipped classroom and peripateticism, which have since shown positive learning outcomes.

An important aspect of the AER session is also on how people can be equipped with skills to carry out the research in their context. The range of speakers we had allowed a flow of discussion where the new PhD candidates can showcase their initial research work, as well as to locate it in the big picture of astronomy education research. Our speakers, also reflected much on their practices as researchers, while providing insight on AER topics that are not well explored.

Compiled by: Tshiamiso Makwela

● Teaching Methods and Tools

Session organisers: Niall Deacon (OAE Heidelberg), Beatriz García (Network for Astronomy School Education – NASE), Shylaja B S (Jawaharlal Nehru Planetarium)

Editing supported by: Niall Deacon

SESSION OVERVIEW

This session will focus on the many innovative ways astronomy is being taught, with practical tips on how to implement them.

TALK CONTRIBUTIONS

In Praise of Raw Data: Sustainable Printing Techniques to Engage Students with Astronomical Images

Speaker: Melanie King, Canterbury Christ Church University / Royal College of Art, UK

Collaborator: Claudia Mignone (INAF)

Telescopes return almost daily images of celestial bodies that communicate science through colours, shapes and structures, contributing to our collective imagination of the Universe. The goal of this project is to bring back the “material” aspect of astronomical observations by exploring images from James Webb Space Telescope, discovering the richness of raw data, from artifacts like cosmic rays and bad pixels to the actual scientific information about planets, stars, galaxies. Images will be printed using sustainable analogue photographic techniques, acknowledging the importance of using materials wisely on a planet with limited resources. Two formats are being developed: an advanced printing workshop for art students and a basic version for secondary schools.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/kWvTIjG7Jyg>

How do we, as humans, picture the vast nature of the Universe? Telescopes on Earth and in orbit, along with spacecraft exploring the Solar System, return almost daily a wealth of images portraying planets, stars, and galaxies, which populate all realms of print and digital media, contributing to our collective imagination of celestial bodies, the cosmos, and outer space. The most recent addition to this fleet is the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST), the most powerful astronomical observatory ever launched into space, whose first images in July 2022 captured audiences worldwide with their sheer beauty and cosmic grandeur (Pontoppidan et al. 2022). JWST observes the cosmos in infrared light, wavelengths that are not perceived by human eyes, prompting the question of how those images are produced. This question is actually relevant for all observations of the cosmos, whether in visible light or any other wavelength of the electromagnetic spectrum: astronomical image processing is a data visualisation exercise that involves several parameters to provide a factual, possibly also aesthetically pleasant visual representation of the measurements collected by telescopes.

Is there a best combination of these parameters for the general public to appreciate these views of the cosmos? Astronomers and science communicators have been investigating this question (Smith et al. 2010, Rector et al. 2017). In Science and Technology Studies, scholars have been exploring materiality in science communication, pointing out the role of objects,

structures, spaces and places in the public perception of science, as the effects that are tied to these elements have the potential to elicit positive emotions towards the scientific process (e.g., Davies, 2014). Addressing questions such as “How are scientific visuals produced?” or “Where do these images come from?”, which abound in online news and forums, makes it possible to connect with learners in an affective, disembodied fashion, recentering the engagement around emotions of pleasure and delight. The authors decided to investigate whether it becomes easier to grasp these concepts when learners can enjoy a direct involvement in the processing of images from outer space, and chose to do so by exploring different printing techniques to convey the behind-the-scenes processes that are involved in the creation of astronomy images for public consumption.

As a first step, in July 2024, Dr. Claudia Mignone and Dr. Melanie King met with Alyssa Pagan and Joe De Pasquale, Science Visuals Developers at the Space Telescope Science Institute. The aim of the meeting was to discuss how astronomical images from JWST are processed, also in relation to Hubble photographs. King was particularly keen to understand raw data artefacts within the images. King and Mignone also met with Prof. Mark McCaughrean, who is a JWST interdisciplinary scientist and former Senior Advisor for Science & Exploration at the European Space Agency. With decades of experience analysing and processing astronomical images, especially in the infrared domain, McCaughrean has his own way of processing astronomical images which differ to those produced at NASA.

Following these meetings, King wanted to make a feature of the raw data artefacts in the astronomical images as they can tell us about the process of producing the image. For example, some astronomical images from the Hubble Telescope feature trails from cosmic ray interactions. With JWST images, there are artefacts which include six pointed stars or diffraction spikes, which arise from the six mirrors of the telescope. In the raw files, there are also overexposed dots which resemble black holes, and trails on the edges of images from software processing. King was keen to print the images using sustainable printmaking processes. Firstly, Melanie King worked with Park Press to produce risograph prints of the Carina Nebula and Pillars of Creation images by JWST. Risographs are produced using otherwise obsolete machines, and the technology is both similar to screen printing and photocopying. A digital image is loaded onto a computer and split into colour channels, in a manner which mirrors astronomical image compositing processes. A master or ‘screen’ is produced, which allows one colour of ink to be selectively applied to paper. In this session, King was only able to print 2 colours due to availability of ink, but it is theoretically possible to build up to a full colour image. Many elements of the risograph process are sustainable, as the masters are based from starch and are biodegradable. The inks are made from a soya base, and the paper is made from recycled fibres.

In addition to this, King worked with photographer Clare Hewitt, botanical ink maker Carolyn Morton and paper maker Danielle Phelps to produce a screen print of the Tarantula Nebula. Hewitt, Morton, and Phelps have been working to produce a fully sustainable photography book and have spent months researching their individual processes to find a combination that works. For the Tarantula Nebula image, paper was made with recycled cotton fibres by Danielle Phelps. In addition to this, the team used paper made from recycled coffee cups and an ink was made from foraged oak gall by Carolyn Morton.

In future, King would like to work with the cyanotype process, building up colours through selective toning processes. This is work in progress: eventually, King and Mignone would like to

produce an easily replicable technique that can be reproduced in an educational environment. This will familiarise students with astronomical imaging techniques, whilst simultaneously educating students on sustainable printmaking techniques. The aim of this project is to empower people by providing a stepwise, facilitated approach to scientific data via the use of photographic techniques, researching the best resources and communication tools to achieve this. We wish to encourage a change in perspective of people with no previous experience in photography and/or astronomy, presenting these topics as approachable rather than distant, ethereal, almost intangible.

References:

- Davies, S. R. (2014). Knowing and Loving: Public Engagement beyond Discourse, *Science & Technology Studies*, 27(3), pp. 90–110
- Pontoppidan, K. M., Barrientes, J., Blome, C., Braun, H., Brown, M., Carruthers, M., Coe, D., DePasquale, J., Espinoza, N., Garcia Marin, M., Gordon, K. D., Henry, A., Hustak, L., James, A., Jenkins, A., Koekemoer, A. M., LaMassa, A., Law, D., Lockwood, A., . . . Nota, A. (2022). The JWST Early Release Observations. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 936, 1
- Rector, T. A., Levay, Z. G., Frattare, L. M., Arcand, K. K., & Watzke, M. (2017). The Aesthetics of Astrophysics: How to Make Appealing Color-composite Images that Convey the Science. *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, 129, 975
- Smith, L. F., Smith, J. K., Arcand, K. K., Smith, R. K., Bookbinder, J., & Keach, K. (2011). Aesthetics and Astronomy: Studying the Public's Perception and Understanding of Imagery From Space. *Science Communication*, 33(2), 201-238

The Mediterranean Co-Design: The Sabir Project. Towards Co-Designed IBL Activities for High School

Speaker: Dunja Fabjan, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

Collaborators: Stefano Sandrelli and Gloria Tirabassi (INAF, OAE Center Italy), Nayra Rodríguez Eugenio (NAEC Spain, Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias), Alejandra Goded Merino (Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias), Aysegul Yelkenci (NAEC Turkey, Istanbul Kultur University), Jean-Pierre Saghbini (President of the Association UniversCiel, NAEC Lebanon), and Hassane Darhmaoui (School of Science and Engineering, Al Akhawayn University in Ifrane)

The Sabir project is a co-design initiative fostering the network of NAECs in the Mediterranean. It was held both online (March-July 2024) and in person during a one-week residency in Milan. NAECs from Lebanon, Morocco, Spain and Turkey were invited. We discussed the framework and meaning of an Inquiry Based Learning (IBL) approach during the kick-off meeting. Each NAEC then selected some 'standard' activities to be rethought as IBL ones. The project included three cycles of discussion, offline implementation according to the suggestion of the group, and presentation of improved activities. The final versions of the activities were eventually co-designed together during the residency. In this presentation, we will illustrate the challenges, difficulties, and opportunities of this approach.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/08iBFqcyeyS>

Sabir is a project aimed at producing activities for high school students and fostering innovative, open and critical learning in the Mediterranean. The project is addressed to the IAU National Astronomy Educators community, and it involves six different Mediterranean countries: Italy, Lebanon, Morocco, Slovenia, Spain, and Turkey.

The project is organised by Stefano Sandrelli (OAE Center Italy), Gloria Tirabassi (OAE Center Italy), and Dunja Fabjan (NAEC Slovenia), and it is conducted through a co-design method in all its phases: it stands on a previous co-design project led by the OAE Center Italy (I-OAE), the MIRTO-STEAM-Med (2022) project.

The general social goals of the project were to support the NAECs network in the Mediterranean, exchanging best practices, building and reinforcing the community and enhancing the co-design implementation process.

The name *Sabir* refers to a contact language used as a lingua franca in the Mediterranean Basin from the 11th to the 19th centuries. It was neither a formal language with written rules nor a language tied to a specific country. Instead, it emerged from the will of people—primarily sailors and traders—to communicate, share, and coexist.

Figure 1: From left to right: The Sabir project team in Milano: Stefano, Nayra, Jean-Pierre, Gloria, Dunja, Hassane, Aysegul.

Goals of the Sabir Project: Sabir aims at promoting and encouraging innovative, open, critical learning by producing Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL) activities for high-school students. Although the IBL variety is very rich and complex, scientific literature defines IBL as: the essence of inquiry is learning science in ways that mirror authentic scientific research practices, or “learning science as science is done” (Hunter et al. 2010).

Since our basic idea was to select some non-IBL activities and to transform them into inquiry-based ones through a collaborative process among peers, our first challenge was to establish how we defined IBL in Sabir and how we would like to design it in principle. This was one of the main efforts throughout the whole process.

Development of the Sabir Project: Sabir was designed to be held both online and in-person: six online recorded meetings from February to July were followed by a one-week residency in Milan.

Before starting with the online phase, we collected our own ideas and practices about this topic. During the meetings, we discussed the general meaning of IBL, our different experiences and which level of IBL should be considered appropriate in our case. Then we tried to rebuild our own scheme of an IBL activity, which could help us in designing the activities.

We chose to adopt the framework sketched in Pedaste et al. (2015) after analysing hundreds of IBL activities. After a long work of synthesis, they eventually identify five major phases that characterise an IBL activity, which they choose to identify as: Orientation, Conceptualisation,

Figure 2: The Sabir project team discussing during the residency in Milan.

Investigation, Conclusion and Discussion. Every phase can be subdivided into sub-phases. A similar analysis was done in Duran and Duran (2004).

In the following meetings, the NAECs proposed some candidate activities to be developed as IBL co-designed activities. At this stage, activities could already be tested (non-IBL or partially IBL activities) or new ideas were suitable to become an IBL activity. The suggested activities were:

- Aysegul (Turkey): “Asteroid Mining” (mostly new activity)
- Jean-Pierre and Marc (Lebanon): “3,2,1... Water Rockets” (well tested in a non IBL context)
- Hassane and Zakaria (Morocco): “ Exploring Exoplanets: The Transit Method” (mostly new)
- Nayra and Alejandra (Spain): “Our Place in the Universe” (well tested in a not totally IBL context)

We then started to transform the activities into IBL ones. Each NAEC presented his/her group’s activity and together we discussed about the main idea, the link to the national curricula, how to engage the students in the scientific challenge, what inquiries could the students choose to conduct, what would be the necessary materials/software/real data to foster an interdisciplinary approach, and so on. In the following meetings, we repeated the process of presenting, discussing, and proposing further developments.

The **in-person phase** consisted in a one-week residency, from the 2nd to the 6th of September 2024, hosted by INAF-Osservatorio Astronomico di Brera, in Milan.

During the in-person phase, the NAECs discussed the activities in pairs, with the help of a facilitator. The facilitator had the role to help the sparring-partner NAEC to raise questions, to push the discussion towards an IBL approach, and to pinpoint the most relevant issues to solve. The facilitator did not take part in the discussion itself. The presenting NAEC collected the suggestions and implemented his/her activity before the following bi-lateral meeting. At the end of the week, all NAECs were requested to write down the final version of the activity in the astroEDU (the IAU educational platform) format, including images and everything needed. As a final product, we are publishing the IBL activities on astroEDU, together with the translations into all languages of the participating NAECs and facilitators.

The Evaluation of the Sabir Project: One of the crucial aspects of this project is the evaluation, which will be done both on the process and on the activities. Regarding the co-design process, our goal is to evaluate if the “translation” of activities into IBL-like activities had an impact on the Mediterranean community involved. On the other hand, we aim to determine whether the activities were designed as inquiry-based and to assess the relevance of inquiry when these activities are conducted in different countries. For this purpose, we will test the activities in schools with questionnaires and interviews in the following months. In this phase, we will also write the “Teacher’s guide” and the “Student’s guide”, which are necessary to properly evaluate the activities in different environments.

Conclusions: The co-design process, that we implemented and used in the I-OAE led projects, is not straightforward. From our past and present experiences we saw that it can be very slow, especially when happening online. On the other hand, the pair discussions during the in-person residency were more efficient, facilitated by the fact that NAECs already knew each other from previous collaborations on past projects. Which confirms that working on the community (and as a community) has a strong impact on the outcome of such a project.

References:

- Sabir project webpage, https://edu.inaf.it/oea_italia/sabir-2024/
- AstroEDU, <https://astroedu.iau.org/en/>
- Hunter et al., Cultivating Scientist- and Engineer-Educators 2010: The Evolving Professional Development Program, 2010, ASP Conference Series, Vol. 436
- Pedaste et al., Phases of inquiry-based learning: Definitions and the inquiry cycle, Educational Research Review, 14 (2015), 47-61
- Duran, Lena Ballone and Emilio Duran. “The 5E Instructional Model: A Learning Cycle Approach for Inquiry-Based Science Teaching.” (2004)

Engaging Students in Astronomy Through Learner-Driven Questions

Speaker: Arwen Hubbard, USA

Centring education around learner-driven questions empowers students and deepens their understanding of astronomy. By focusing on what students are curious about, educators can foster a sense of ownership in their learning, leading to greater engagement and independent exploration. In this presentation, I will share strategies from “Found in Space: A Science Podcast for Kids and Teens,” which uses listener questions to spark curiosity and ownership in their learning. Participants will gain practical tips on integrating learner-driven questions into their teaching, creating a dynamic and engaging astronomy education experience.

Talk link: https://youtu.be/3_2aKV3q0Q

This presentation explores learner-driven questions as a method for engaging students in astronomy. Encouraging students to ask their own questions fosters curiosity and deeper involvement in learning. Educators have shifted from being providers of knowledge to guides, helping students explore and seek answers. By responding to questions in a way that boosts self-efficacy and empowers learners to take ownership of their education. By acknowledging and expanding on student inquiries, educators can connect specific questions to broader scientific concepts, promoting better retention and understanding. This approach prepares students for future scientific inquiry.

Engaging PreK - 2nd Grade Students Using Storybook Style Lessons to “See What’s Out There!”

Speaker: Paul Sirstins, Clark Planetarium, USA

Collaborators: Jason Trump and Thomas Quayle (Clark Planetarium)

For pre-K through 2nd grade students, distance and size are concepts that are often beyond their experience. Using something that all kids enjoy, having a book to share and read together, we introduce these concepts along with imagery and tactile objects to involve students in their own learning. Students explore the natural world around them, learning how the Sun gives light and heat to help things grow and live. This includes how the Sun is essential to the plants and animals that the Earth supports, and the ways the Sun and sky move water around to help things thrive. We designed our Storybook lesson to be presented using NOAA’s Science on a Sphere at our venue. In this session, we will explore ways in which it can easily be adapted to the classroom and available technology.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/yxN03MXP5o8>

Tips and Tools for Teaching Astrobiology

Speaker: Chris Impey, University of Arizona, USA

The search for life beyond Earth is a compelling quest of modern science. Astrobiology appeals to a wide audience, including those who might not otherwise be engaged with science. It is just one subfield of astronomy but it has connections to geology, chemistry, biology, and even sociology. This interdisciplinary context creates both challenges and opportunities for educators. For non-science students, “Life in the Universe” is popular as a follow-up to an introductory astronomy course. Examples of teaching materials are given, with an emphasis on classroom demos, small group activities, and pedagogy that promotes engagement and active learning.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/pNrY29HqLLA>

The astrobiology course for non-science majors encourages pedagogy that is innovative and takes full advantage of the range of disciplines involved in understanding life in the universe. The Center

Figure 1. Menu of options for a portfolio used in an introductory astrobiology class. Students critique science articles they find online, study how science really works to address questions, and they get to be creative and utilise their other skill sets (Courtesy: Chris Impey).

for Astronomy Education, hosted by NASA's Jet Propulsion Laboratory, has extensive astronomy materials, with many on astrobiology (Center for Astronomy Education 2024). The group led by Ed Prather has pioneered lecture tutorials to enhance student learning in a traditional face-to-face classroom. Lecture tutorials are worksheets of carefully designed questions to make students think about a challenging subject. After a brief lecture, students work together in groups of two or three to complete the worksheet. Lecture tutorials scaffold learning and specifically address typical misconceptions. The activities often use a debating strategy where hypothetical students express opinions about a topic, and students in the class must say who they agree with, and why. Lecture tutorials for an introductory astrobiology class have been published as a workbook (Prather, Offerdahl, and Slater 2006). Lecture tutorials constitute a low-technology solution to learner-centred engagement in large classes.

The use of portfolios to monitor the training of pre-service science teachers is increasingly common, however, their implementation in an undergraduate science classroom is limited (Collins 1992). For large introductory classes like "Life in the Universe" the assessment is usually multiple-choice tests and perhaps term papers. Portfolios offer a more authentic mode of assessment and a way to build multiple writing assignments into the class. The learning goals were to assess scientific claims in the popular media, to recognise science as a dynamic and iterative process, and to communicate science content to peer audiences. The four interrelated units of the assessment are shown in Figure 1. Each one echoes the process scientists follow when they do research and gain new knowledge. Where appropriate, students worked in pairs and small teams. The assignments are designed to attach to the highest levels of the Bloom taxonomy. More than half the students in this class agreed that portfolios provided a better assessment of learning than standard exams (Offerdahl and Impey 2012).

The following sampling of astrobiology activities is designed for a large class of non-science majors, but the materials work equally well at a high-school level or for outreach to the public. They are small, bite-sized activities that can be inserted into any class, distinct from the portfolio approach discussed earlier, which is a holistic, writing-intensive pedagogy across an entire

semester. When talking about life on Earth, a fundamental issue is how life is defined. An activity that generates thought and discussion is four different “Mystery Boxes,” with five to six of each placed up front so a large class can experience them all (London Science Museum 2024). I use small, sealed cardboard boxes with holes that can only be inspected by smell, sound, or feel. The contents should each weigh the same and sound similar when shaken. One box contains something inert and non-living, such as gravel. The second has something formerly living, such as peanuts. The third has something potentially alive, like yeast pellets. The fourth has a living object, where an ideal choice is Mexican “jumping beans,” seed pods inhabited by the larva of a small moth. Mystery boxes teach the essence of the scientific method.

It’s useful to tether the idea of DNA as an information storage mechanism, using a text metaphor. For example, a base pair is one bit of information, or analogous to a letter. A codon is 6 bits, like a word. A gene is about 1000 bits, like a sentence (i.e. you have brown hair, you are prone to a particular disease). Simple organisms like bacteria have a million bits of information, analogous to a short book. The human genome of six billion bits is an encyclopedia. To make this visible in class, use a plastic egg to represent a human cell, with a long roll of dental floss inside to be the DNA. In a scale model where 0.03 mm is a base pair, a codon is 0.1 mm, a gene is 0.5 meters, a chromosome is 500 meters, and the genome is 20 km. Unspooling the floss in the classroom, it’s easy to imagine “reading” a sentence and the enormity of reading 20 km becomes clear. A great hands-on activity is extracting DNA from a strawberry. All that’s needed are strawberries, water, salt, rubbing alcohol, dish detergent, stirrers, plastic cups, and sealable plastic bags (National Institutes of Health 2024). Multiple stations can be used to serve a large class. For students it’s an aha moment when they draw clumpy strands of DNA out of the solution.

An excellent source of small group activities that use pedagogy that lets students construct their own learning is the previously mentioned *Life in the Universe Activities Manual* (Prather, Offerdahl, and Slater 2006). One example is “The Evolving Earth,” where students establish a timeline with six major eras, and then match cards of geological and biological events on Earth to the correct era. They learn about the complex interplay between the diversity of life and the evolving geological and atmospheric conditions. Another is “The Drake Equation,” which makes an analogy between the small fraction of planets that host intelligent life and the small fraction of a college student population that would be female psychology majors with long hair studying in the library at a particular time. The activity teaches the skill of estimation using large numbers. For SETI, the Search for Extraterrestrial Intelligence, another good activity is to have the class work in pairs to decide what they would put into a cubic meter payload sent beyond the Solar System, a “message in a bottle” to represent humanity and our civilization and technology. A second version follows the SETI methodology by having students design messages in a binary code, beamed as pulses by a transmitter at a radio telescope. This, and many other activities, can be found in Project Haystack (SETI Institute 2010).

Finally, there is an activity that is more related to space travel than astrobiology, although it does convey the challenge of surviving off-Earth. The scenario is that you have survived a crash landing on the Moon and must decide which of the items in the spacecraft you would carry on a perilous journey to safety at a Moon base. The 15 items range from obviously useful (a first aid kit), to potentially useful (a rope), to useless (a compass, which is no use because the Moon has no magnetic field). The items are ranked by each student on a worksheet, not talking to any of their neighbours. Then they are ranked on a second worksheet by students working in pairs or small groups. The model answer derives from NASA astronauts who were given the same

Figure 2. Students decide which are the most and least useful items to bring on a hazardous trip across the lunar surface to safety after a crash landing. They are ranked, in this view, in an online interface. In the classroom a worksheet is used, and students do the ranking individually and then in small groups, aiming to mimic astronauts ranks of the same items (Courtesy: NASA).

task (NASA 2024). The sum of differences in ranks by students and astronauts is the measure of success, where a lower number is better. Students get very animated and fully engaged by the activity. Results can be displayed in class, and they invariably show that groups come closer to astronauts on average than individual students, illustrating the power of collaborative learning.

References:

- Collins, A. 1992. Portfolios for Science Education: Issues in Purpose, Structure, and Authenticity. *Science Education* 76: 451-463.
- London Science Museum 2024. Science Museum Group Mystery Boxes. <https://learning.sciencemuseumgroup.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/SMG-Academy-Mystery-Boxes.pdf>
- NASA 2024. Landing Humans on the Moon. Activity Three: Priority Packing for the Moon. https://www.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/ps-03283-landing_humans_on_the_moon_0.pdf
- National Institutes of Health 2024. How to extract DNA from a strawberry. National Human Genome Research Institute. https://www.genome.gov/sites/default/files/media/files/2023-04/How_to_extract_DNA_from_a_strawberry_508.pdf
- Offerdahl, E. and Impey, C.D. 2012. Assessing general education science courses: A portfolio approach. *Journal of College Science Teaching* 41: 19-25.
- Prather, E.E., Offerdahl, E. and Slater, T.F. 2006. *Life in the Universe: Activities Manual*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- SETI Institute 2010. Project Haystack: The Search for Life in the Galaxy. <https://www.seti.org/sites/default/files/litu-files/ProjectHaystack.11.pdf>

Astronomy, Language, and Cultural Continuity: Nurturing Connection for Iranian Migrant Youth

Speaker: Shahrzad Mirsoltani, Astronomy Educator and Director of Kargahe Setare Project, Iran

The migration of children and youths from underprivileged countries to advanced nations is a pressing issue. The Kargahe Setare Project aimed to promote astronomy among young Iranians through an online platform, reaching over 10,000 children. It then expanded to provide astronomy education for Iranian migrant children. A major challenge was the language barrier, as the project was initially in Persian. To address this, the project used astronomy to teach both scientific knowledge and the Persian language, integrating new worksheets, traditional Iranian drama, and storytelling. This approach underscores astronomy's potential in language learning, helping migrant children stay connected to their cultural heritage.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/msVA0ksUy7E>

Home is a complex concept. When we observe our planet from a distance in space, it appears that everyone shares just one home: Earth. However, upon closer examination, we realise that for a significant portion of the world's population, finding a place to call home is a considerable challenge. This struggle often leads to the migration of people from one country to another in search of safety, opportunity, and a sense of belonging. Migration can occur for a variety of reasons, including economic opportunities, conflict and violence, environmental factors, education, family reunification, and political persecution. Iran, a country with one of the highest rates of migration, is also an ancient civilisation rich in history, culture, and literature. This raises important questions: How will this new generation abroad stay connected to their homeland? How will they learn their mother tongue and preserve their roots?

The Kargahe Setare Project is a pioneering initiative dedicated to advancing astronomy education for children and young learners, both in Iran and for Iranian children worldwide. Established in 2017 by Shahrzad Mirsoltani, the project distributes astronomy-related educational content via digital platforms, making learning accessible to a broad audience. Key features of the project include the creation of educational content that fosters a love for science, a global reach to provide quality resources to Iranian children regardless of location, and a range of online courses that deliver interactive astronomy education. Beyond courses, Kargahe Setare conducts workshops and activities that actively engage students, while focusing outreach efforts on underserved communities to bridge gaps in educational access. With digital tools enhancing the learning experience, Kargahe Setare has reached over 10,000 students worldwide, contributing significantly to astronomy education and inspiring a new generation of young scientists and enthusiasts.

When the project launched its dedicated course for Iranian children living abroad, several new

Figure 1. The official logo of Kargahe Setare Project. Logo credit: Sahar Mirsoltani

challenges emerged, offering valuable learning experiences and insights. Some of the most notable challenges included:

Language: Teaching astronomy to children with diverse linguistic backgrounds required multilingual resources and customised language support.

Available Resources: Access to educational materials and technology varied significantly between countries and families, influencing the quality and type of learning experience possible.

Age Group: Different age groups required distinct approaches, content levels, and engagement methods to make astronomy accessible and exciting for all learners.

Different Educational Systems: Aligning astronomy lessons with the diverse educational standards of each country presented challenges due to varying curricula and teaching methods.

Time Zones: Coordinating live classes and events across multiple time zones limited real-time interaction, necessitating flexible scheduling.

Knowledge Levels: Students came with varying levels of prior knowledge, requiring a careful balance of introductory and advanced content to ensure effective learning for all.

Over time, through adapting teaching methods, tailoring content for different age groups, and learning how to teach astronomy to students for whom Persian was often a third language (after English and sometimes another language), we found ways to overcome language barriers. At first, language seemed like a limitation, but it actually became a motivator for families, as students learned both Persian and astronomy simultaneously. We incorporated diverse methods, such as game-based learning, storytelling, and puppet shows, to make learning engaging and accessible. Astronomy even became a tool for teaching the Persian alphabet.

In conclusion, astronomy education holds great potential for educating migrant children about indigenous knowledge. Online education provides a unique way to transcend borders and reconnect migrants with their homeland. Astronomy subjects serve as powerful tools for language learning, especially for those who have migrated. Through online astronomy education and global classes, young migrant generations can connect with art, history, literature, indigenous science, and culture. These classes also allow students from the same nation, living in different parts of the world, to engage and build connections with one another.

Opening Windows, Revealing Meanings: Instrumental Reading of Scientific Texts in English

Speaker: Ana Cecilia Soja, Fluminense Federal Institute, Brazil

Collaborator: Priscila Célia Giacomassi (Federal Institute of Paraná)

Astronomy, like all sciences, uses English as its language. While this is a challenge for native speakers of other languages, it also opens up the opportunity for an interest in astronomy to be used as a tool for teaching English. In this study, we explore the potential of the joined teaching English as a second language and science. The aim is to demonstrate that texts that seem inaccessible to students in a first contact can be understood by them through specific reading and interpretation techniques. We chose scientific texts about major discoveries, such as gravitational waves, because of the interest the students demonstrated in such subjects. Our results showed that reading scientific articles with high-school students is a great way to teach English and promote scientific literacy.

Astronomy, like all sciences, uses English as its language today. While this is a challenge for native speakers of other languages, it also opens the opportunity for an interest in astronomy to be used as a tool for teaching English.

In Brazil the native language of most of the population is Portuguese. English as a second language teachers faced a reality where only 5% of students had a basic level of English, despite the subject being mandatory for all. One of the strategies to address this challenge is to use topics that interest students as a catalyst for language learning—Astronomy being a prime example.

To test this strategy, we proposed using English for Specific Purposes (ESP) tools to help students read scientific texts. We know that these texts are not specifically written for this public, but they are primary sources and a perfect example to show how English is important in science.

For example, we applied our techniques to the paper “Observation of Gravitational Waves from Binary Black Hole Merger” (Abbott et al., 2016), a famous work that presents the first detection of a Gravitational Wave (GW), and that won the Nobel Prize in 2017. The first step was to present the structure of the article to the students since they are not used to read this kind of texts. We show the title, the authors, the institutions, the abstract, the journal where it was published, and the year. The idea was to teach the rules, that could seem basic for those who are used to them but were new to the students.

The second step was to read the title and translate it if necessary. In the case of Abbott et al. (2016), it presents concepts as “merge” and “black hole”, that can be discussed in the moment. Next, we identified the authors. This is a particularly significant moment in this paper, as it includes more than one hundred contributors. It is a good example of how collaboration is

important in science and it shows how the team is composed of people from around the world. This highlights the importance of a common language—English, in this case—that enables effective communication. The same applies for institutions, including two research centres in Brazil.

Applying the reading strategy, students begin by identifying cognates and words whose meaning they already know. This collaborative approach helps them gradually understand the text. Once the language barrier is addressed, their focus shifts to the scientific content, such as understanding frequency in astronomy and discussing objects like stars. The key question becomes: What knowledge is needed to fully comprehend the text?

This method proves effective in teaching English and subjects such as astronomy, while also offering opportunities to explore how knowledge is produced and the importance of primary sources. However, it is important to remind students that reading a text does not mean to fully understand it right away. Students should not feel pressured to know everything. This approach should be collaborative between language and science teachers, encouraging students to see challenges as part of the learning process.

In summary, the approach is a combination of language learning and scientific inquiry that emphasises collaboration and gradual understanding. Our results showed that reading scientific articles with high-school students is a great way to teach English and promote scientific literacy.

Reference: Abbott, B.P.; Abbott, R.; Abbott, T.D.; Abernathy, M.R.; Acernese, F.; Ackley, K.; Adams, C.; Adams, T.; Addesso, P.; Adhikari, R.X.; et al. Observation of Gravitational Waves from a Binary Black Hole Merger. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 2016, 116, 061102.

POSTER CONTRIBUTIONS

Advancing Astronomy Education Through Dark Sky Initiative on Design Thinking and Social Innovation

Presenter: Exodus Chun-Long Sit, Chair of IAU-NAEC & Co-NOC Hong Kong, Starrix, Hong Kong

Despite light pollution poses significant challenges to observational astronomy, nocturnal animals, and energy consumption, it has rarely been discussed in formal education. This raises the question of how we can integrate dark sky education into science learning. This presentation highlights the interdisciplinary project “ASTROx”, with the student-led social innovation team “The Starlight Squad,” which focuses on dark sky advocacy and science communication. By addressing real-life issues in the community, the project aims to raise awareness about urban light pollution. Students explored interdisciplinary methods and experiential activities, including outdoor classrooms, design thinking lessons, and hands-on experiences, to effectively communicate the importance of preserving our night skies.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14544028>

ASTROx represents a groundbreaking educational initiative focused on dispelling stereotypes surrounding astronomy and seamlessly integrating them into everyday life. This program aims to cross-media collaboration, integrating astronomy with diverse disciplines to enhance scientific communication and education effectively. Central to ASTROx is its interdisciplinary goals, which intertwine astronomy with environmental conservation efforts, promoting public awareness about dark skies. Moreover, the initiative forges connections between astronomy and space technology, especially the practical implications of space advancements in daily routines. Encouraging the fusion of astronomy with the arts, ASTROx invites individuals from varied backgrounds to partake in astronomy education and outreach, including learning about stargazing manners and observational practices.

Over the past five years, ASTROx has orchestrated over 100 astronomy outreach lectures, workshops, and conferences, facilitating inclusive and accessible knowledge dissemination. By transcending geographical and language barriers, ASTROx ensures diverse audiences can engage with astronomy across various platforms. Through collaborative endeavours, ASTROx aspires to engender a more profound appreciation for astronomy, rendering it relevant and accessible to all. By arousing public interest in astronomy, the initiative aims to inspire a new cohort of astronomy enthusiasts and advocates for scientific literacy.

Figure 1. Three stages of astronomy development in popular science communication and astronomy education, proposed by Exodus Chun-Long Sit.

Figure 2. Future framework of STEM+A@Astronomy with core mission of “IDEAS”.

Aligned with the STEM+A@Astronomy project, ASTROx is a pivotal component that focuses on advancing science communication, interdisciplinary education, and IDEAS—Inclusion, Diversity, Equity, Access, and Special Education. This innovative initiative seeks to transform astronomy education by exploring its intersections with various disciplines and fields of study.

Employing the Development Framework, ASTROx identifies and expands avenues for effective astronomy education and outreach by integrating astronomy with diverse subjects. This holistic approach aims to create an engaging learning experience that resonates with diverse audiences, fostering a deeper appreciation for astronomy’s relevance in the daily life. By promoting an inclusive environment where individuals from all backgrounds can actively participate in and benefit from astronomy education, ASTROx strives to enhance educational outcomes and ensure equitable access to scientific learning opportunities for everyone.

Reference: Sit, E.C.L. (2021). Decoding the Starry Night: A Guide to Stargazing and Astrophotography. (1st ed., pp.134-145). Cosmos Book

Building Visualisations of Objects in Space from Ground Based Observations and Using Technology

Presenter: Noorali Jiwaji, Marian University College and Open University of Tanzania, United Republic of Tanzania

The progress of science has relied on keen observers noticing changes that follow patterns humans are inclined to explain. Observations of events in the sky form the basis of astronomical knowledge. Building accurate mental models of how phenomena occur in space has been essential for advancing our understanding of the vast universe. We describe the challenges faced by students to understand ground observations, and how technology can assist in filling up observational gaps so as to build a complete picture of these observations and explain them by building a mental picture of how this phenomena happens in space. We illustrate this approach using examples of daytime observations of the Sun and nighttime observations of planets.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14541937>

Astronomical Peripatetism and Flipped Classroom: The New Horizon in Astronomy Education

Presenter: José Antonio D'Santiago García, Universidad Nacional Experimental Rafael María Baralt, Venezuela

In a hybrid world, we combine Astronomical Peripatetism and the Flipped Classroom to teach astronomy. Students acquire theoretical knowledge at home through videos and digital resources. During face-to-face sessions, we use the night sky as a blackboard to reinforce and apply this knowledge through live observations and interactive discussions. This approach promotes active and participatory learning, extending education beyond the physical classroom and fostering a personal connection with the Universe. Our project integrates innovative pedagogical strategies and technological tools to make astronomy accessible and meaningful for a diverse audience.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14542241>

In a contemporary educational context that demands innovation and adaptability, this work explores the integration of two significant methodologies in the teaching of astronomy: the Flipped Classroom, and Astronomical Peripatetism. Both methodologies not only revitalise the learning of astronomy, but also promote students' emotional and practical connection with the universe.

The Flipped Classroom is an innovative approach which has gained popularity in recent decades as an effective way of teaching. This technique inverts the traditional classroom structure, where students acquire theoretical content at home through videos, readings, and digital resources, and use class time for practical and collaborative activities. This strategy is based on the premise that students learn best when they have the opportunity to interact and apply their knowledge in a practical environment.

The implementation of the Flipped Classroom in our Astronomy Club allows students to prepare in advance, providing them with a solid foundation for face-to-face activities. This approach not only promotes student autonomy, but also makes them the protagonists of their own learning. By taking responsibility for their training, students are more engaged and motivated to explore astronomical concepts and actively participate in practical sessions.

A holistic approach to teaching astronomy: Traditionally, the flipped classroom focuses on acquiring theoretical knowledge at home, reserving face-to-face time for activities in a physical classroom where doubts are discussed, debated and clarified. However, what is innovative about our proposal is that face-to-face time does not take place in a traditional classroom, but outdoors, where Astronomical Peripatetism comes to life. This change transforms the educational approach, allowing students to observe the night sky in real time and apply the knowledge acquired at home in a practical and immersive context.

Peripatetism: A legacy from antiquity, the term peripatetism comes from the philosophy of Aristotle, who taught his students while walking and discussing outdoors. This pedagogical approach emphasised the importance of direct observation and interaction with the environment. In ancient times, peripatetism was not only a form of teaching, but also a method of encouraging critical thinking and debate among students. Aristotle believed that learning was enriched by experiencing the world directly, which is essential in the study of astronomy, where observation is fundamental.

Astronomical Peripatetism: An innovation of our club, the term Astronomical Peripatetism was coined in our Astronomy Club to reflect the combination of the peripatetic teaching tradition with the study of astronomy. Using the night sky as our "blackboard," students can observe astronomical phenomena in real time, such as constellations, planets, and other celestial bodies. This method not only strengthens their theoretical understanding, but also generates a sense of wonder and personal connection to the cosmos.

Using the night sky as our blackboard and nature as our classroom allows students to experience astronomy in an immersive way. Instead of being limited to theory in a closed classroom, students become explorers, observing and discussing what they see in the sky. This approach promotes active and participatory learning, where the natural environment becomes an invaluable educational resource.

During outdoor sessions, students not only look at the night sky, but also have the opportunity to interact with their peers, ask questions and share discoveries in a natural environment. This methodology encourages active and participatory learning, where the environment becomes an integral part of the educational process. The fusion of Astronomical Peripatetism with the Flipped Classroom highlights the innovative and significant nature of our proposal, offering students a unique and enriching learning experience.

The integration of the Flipped Classroom and Astronomical Peripatetism into astronomy teaching represents an innovative and effective approach that transforms astronomy education. Our research at the Astronomy Club indicates that these methodologies not only increase student engagement and interest, but also improve their ability to understand and apply astronomical concepts in practical contexts. We will continue to explore and refine these methodologies to maximise their impact on astronomy education and foster a new generation of enthusiasts and explorers of the universe.

References:

- Amilburu, M. G.(2015) Educating with life In the classroom and out of it: Edetania - Edition, Barcelona.pp.43.
- Buchetti A (2016), Maieutics and Peripatetics for their application as a learning technique - XVI Conference of Academic Reflection in ISSN: 1668 1673 Year IX, Vol. 9, Buenos Aires, Argentina.
- D'Santiago García, JA (2023). Exploring the secrets of the cosmos on foot: Astronomy clubs and Peripatetism. 5th Shaw-IAU Workshop on Astronomy for Education (5th SIW), virtual. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10445237>
- Fritz, M. (2014), Die Schule des Aristoteles, text and commentaries on ancient philosophy.10 Hefte und 2 Supplemente, 2. Aufl. 2014 Brasilea.

Facilitating Celestial Navigation Through Artistic Visualisation of Constellations Using Artsterism

Presenter: Nurul Syahirah Binti Nazarudin, International Association of Astronomical Artists (IAAA), Infant Jesus Convent Primary School, Malaysia

For centuries, humanity has used creativity to visualise constellations, making art essential in celestial navigation. The Artsterism Kit facilitates learning by helping students recognise “asterisms” through artistic visualisation. This kit includes a star map base, seasonal star map, brass fastener, and compass, which students draw on, label, and assemble before guided observation. Research with 6th grade pupils from the Infant Jesus Convent Primary School showed they enjoyed and engaged in learning about constellations. Pre- and post-test results indicated significant improvement in celestial navigation knowledge. The Artsterism Kit, a STEAM-integrated tool, enhances interest in astronomy and science through creativity, demonstrating the value of a multidisciplinary teaching approach.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14541918>

For centuries, humanity has applied creativity and imagination in visualising constellations, making celestial navigation an essential guide across the Earth. However, this subject is often perceived as complicated due to its abstract concepts and interdisciplinary nature. The Artsterism Kit is designed to facilitate the learning process of recognising bright stars and the prominent shapes of constellations, known as "asterisms," through artistic visualisation. This kit includes a star map base, a star map, a brass fastener, and a compass, which students draw on, label, and assemble before participating in a guided observation.

Research conducted with 34 6th grade pupils from the Infant Jesus Convent Primary School in Johor Bahru assessed the effectiveness of integrating creativity and artistic skills in recognising constellations and stars while facilitating celestial navigation in an astronomical observation session. From the initial data collection, a questionnaire using Likert Scale assessed five aspects of pupils' familiarity with the night sky in general, which encompasses their personal experiences, stars and constellations identification, familiarity with utilising astronomical tools, engagement in astronomical events and awareness of light pollution in their respective locations. Question 1 pertains to the pupils' experience with the night sky, and the findings showed that most of the pupils occasionally observe the night sky for constellations, and another 20% rarely or never do so. In question 2, most pupils can sometimes identify the constellations in the sky, and only 3.4% of the pupils were able to identify the constellations. In terms of using astronomical tools based on question 3, more than half of the class never used tools such as star maps or mobile stargazing apps when they look up at the night sky. Meanwhile, the results from question 4 indicated that 58.6% of the pupils have never participated in stargazing events or astronomy related activities. Lastly, the majority of pupils can spot street lights and artificial lights in their

neighbourhood, implying that most of them live in urban areas under the glow of light pollution that hinders them from being able to see dimmer stars. The pre- and post-test results indicated improvement in the pupils' comprehension of constellation patterns and their ability to identify bright stars. The pupils were tested about the prominent constellations and stars of the spring's night sky based on three sections: Section A - Celestial Navigation, Section B - Constellations, and Section C - Stars. The mean for pre-test was 36.06 meanwhile the mean for post-test was 62.81. The pupils showed improvement from limited knowledge about celestial navigation, constellations and stars to being able to recognise the prominent constellations and stars of the spring's night sky.

Research findings showed the pupils' knowledge about the constellations and stars before the lesson, was limited. Most of the pupils received knowledge related to astronomy from the previous 5th grade science lesson. The teaching and learning of celestial navigation using the Artsterism kit opened the opportunity for the pupils to learn more about the dynamic night sky, while expressing their inner artist. Learners are able to enhance their interest, motivation, understanding and involvement about science through creative visualisation (Ursyn and Sung, 2007). The pupils draw and connect the group of stars based on the objects, animals or characters that are visually familiar to them. This process of connecting and drawing based on their imaginations fosters a personal relationship with the constellations in the night sky as the pupils created their own meaning based on the patterns of groups of stars. While drawing, the pupils shared the stories behind their illustrations with the teacher and friends, allowing themselves to be vocal in expressing their creativity. Engaging in imaginative conversation through the art making process can further stimulate the pupils' cognitive abilities and facilitate other fields of learning (Duh, 2016). Teaching and learning constellations and stars through Artsterism was conducted as an out-of-class lesson at night, whereby the pupils learned how to use the Artsterism to locate prominent constellations in the spring season along with their bright stars. The out-of-class practice not only emphasise on the knowledge itself, but more importantly relates the concept to the environment or situation where the pupils are placed, in this case under the starry night sky, hence increasing their motivation to learn (Sulaiman & Azlan, 2011). Through Artsterism, the pupils were able to have a glimpse of how celestial cartographers produced star maps that served both functional and aesthetic purposes.

In conclusion, the Artsterism Kit serves as an effective STEAM-integrated tool for young learners, enhancing their interest in the basics of astronomy and science through creativity and ingenuity. By integrating the arts into STEM education, this kit allows learners to be expressive and imaginative, making the learning process exciting and unlocking a wealth of knowledge and curiosity. This approach not only enriches students' educational experiences, but also has the potential to influence future educational practices by demonstrating the value of a multidisciplinary approaches in teaching complex subjects.

References:

- Brooks, M. (2009). Drawing, visualisation and young children's exploration of "Big ideas." *International Journal of Science Education*, 31(3), 319-341. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500690802595771>
- Duh, M. (2016). Art appreciation for developing communication skills among preschool children. *Center for Educational Policy Studies Journal*, 6(1), 71-94. <https://doi.org/>

10.26529/cepsj.105

- Sulaiman, W. I., & Azlan, M. H. (2011). Learning outside the classroom: Effects on student concentration and interest. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 18, 12–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.05.003>
- Ursyn, A., & Sung, R. (2007). Learning science with art. *ACM SIGGRAPH 2007 Educators Program*, 8–12. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1282040.1282049>

Young Scientific Explainers - A Museum Perspective on Designing an Astronomy Educational Program

Presenter: Xiaoxi Wu, Shanghai Astronomy Museum, China

Collaborators: Zhang Yao and Yin Quanyu (Shanghai Astronomy Museum)

Intending to shape well-rounded individuals through astronomy education, the annually hosted program “Young Scientific Explainers” at the Shanghai Astronomy Museum offers a distinctive scientific exploration experience. Students transform from learners into researchers by utilising the resources and tools provided, and progressive guidance from astronomers. They sharpen their presentation and communication skills with the help of museum educators. The program culminates in a student-curated exhibition, in which they manifest their findings creatively through posters, models, and direct communications with the public. With varying astronomical themes each year, the program has evolved and enhanced over the past three years, becoming an integral part of the summer offerings at the museum.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14541897>

"Young Scientific Explainers" is an educational program offered by the Shanghai Astronomy Museum for primary and secondary students during every summer vacation. It has been three years since we first launched it in 2022, and the program has evolved and upgraded year by year. We have chosen three different themes for each year: 2022 focused on creating cosmic roaming videos with the World Wide Telescope; 2023 centred on investigation and research into light pollution and dark sky protection situations and solutions; 2024 is a Sun journal written by all participants during the solar maximum year.

This program is designed especially for museum learners. It aims to unlock the potential of these young minds by giving them the tools to research and study, equipping them with skills to design

their posters and exhibit booths, and enabling them to communicate scientific content to the public like professional museum guides. To accomplish this, we collaborate with astronomers from observatories and institutions, as well as curators and professionals from the museum. We provide theoretical lectures and practical astronomical observations and fieldwork training both online and offline, and utilise the museum's telescopes and exhibits.

When designing this program, we keep certain concepts in mind. We do not aim for systematic astronomy courses; instead, we find topics related to the latest astronomical and social changes/situations in which everyone can participate. We try not to gather students in classrooms but use multiple methods to help students from various places learn according to their schedules. This includes online lectures, live-streaming observatory tours, online chat groups for questions at any time, and offline museum tours, practical outdoor astronomical observations, and self-organised study and research. Students may not necessarily see their test scores raised in schools, but they will gain a deeper understanding of scientific research, the local community, and astronomy that can be observed in our daily lives.

At the end of this program, we provide a space in the museum for exhibitions where students can display and explain their research and findings to the public. The museum's strengths in curation, interpretation, and science communication enable us to cultivate students' skills in this regard which is also an important goal of this program.

Each year, we are delighted to see their enthusiasm and creativity developed through this program. This year, we have extended the exhibition to online social media platforms ([Wechat link](#)).

We see "Young Scientific Explainers" as an effective educational program for teaching astronomy in a museum setting. Therefore, we are willing to share our approach with schools, organisations, and communities to make astronomy education more accessible and inclusive. Through such measures, we hope to increase young learners' social involvement and make science and astronomy a lifelong passion for everyone.

From Real-Life Astronomy Research Questions to Olympiad Problems

Presenter: Catalina-Ana Miritescu, Institut de Física d'Altes Energies (IFAE), Spain

Data analysis tasks are part of the Astronomy Olympiad in Romania. I created three problems based on real-life research projects. One problem presents noise sources characterisation in gravitational wave detectors while it also assesses students' ability to comfortably use a logarithmic scale and to perform a linear fit. Another exercise uses real spectra of galaxies in the COSMOS field for Doppler shift and spectral line calculations. Data from the citizen science website Zooniverse.org is used in the third problem, presenting this novel way of research while testing pupils' knowledge about error propagation and exoplanets. Although the short-term goal is to select the best competitors, the long-term aim is to teach all participants about current topics and methodologies in astronomy research.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14545237>

Romania has a long history of taking part in the International Olympiad on Astronomy and Astrophysics (IOAA), with the number of participants in the national exam steadily increasing since the first edition in 2007. Part of the selection process is the data analysis task which consists of the analysis and interpretation of the astronomical data provided, such as plots, tables, images, light curves, and spectra. My efforts have been focused on developing problems that will not only test for the necessary skills the high-school students need to master in this field, but will also familiarise them with some current research questions and workflows in astronomy. The work presented here details three such problems, two of them based on my own research projects, with the third one based on a citizen science project.

The problem titled “The Reionization of the Universe” is based on a 10-week summer undergraduate research project. The aim of the project was to investigate the possibility that primordial galaxies were the source of reionizing UV photons by studying some similar close-by galaxies with high oxygen III to oxygen II emission flux ratios, as this type of galaxies were recently observed to have a high fraction of escaping UV photons [1]. The pupils were given five galaxy spectra showing both OIII and OII emission lines (example Figure 1a) plus zoom-in on the lines (example Figure 1b,1c). They were asked to calculate the redshift of these objects, the strength of the lines by estimating the area under the curve, and to identify these objects on a COSMOS field picture based on the coordinates of the objects and the coordinates of the bottom left of the picture. Thus, we wanted to test their ability to correctly read a spectrum, to utilise suitable approximations to determine the area under a curve and the physical meaning this quantity has, and to correctly transform celestial coordinates into millimetres on an image. At the same time, the students learned from this exam question about the ongoing research in the evolution of the universe field and about a recent observational result involving the oxygen emitting galaxies.

Figure 1. (a) Example spectrum of a galaxy showing both the OII and OIII emission lines. (b) Zoom in on the OII line. (c) Zoom in on the OIII line.

The second problem is based on a six-week research stay at the gravitational waves detector Virgo in Pisa, Italy. The problem follows closely the work we did there in order to find the frequency dependency of the magnetic noise. It starts by introducing the importance of noise hunting campaigns before observations, the equipment used for magnetic noise injections (coils, amplifiers, single-axis magnetometers) and the procedure for these injections. The concept of a coupling function and its upper limit between the magnetometers – witness sensors labeled by X , and the gravitational waves channel – labeled by Y , is then explained. These formulas are:

$$TF(f) = \sqrt{\frac{Y_{inj}^2(f) - Y_{bkg}^2(f)}{X_{inj}^2(f) - X_{bkg}^2(f)}} \text{ and,}$$

$$TF_{UL}(f) = \frac{Y_{bkg}(f)}{\sqrt{X_{inj}^2(f) - X_{bkg}^2(f)}}, \text{ both dependent on frequency } f \text{ [2].}$$

Based on the given values for f , X and Y , the students then needed to calculate these transfer functions and upper limits (they could use limits instead of values), to plot their results on a logarithmic scale and to determine the slope of the graph in order to extract a power dependency $TF(f) = A \times f^{-\alpha}$. The end goal of the problem was the plot shown in Figure 2. This way we tested students' understanding of a logarithmic scale and how a power dependency looks like in this scale, their ability to fit a dataset using the least squares method and to adequately determine the slope of the fitted line.

The third problem is based on the Planet Hunter Tess citizen science project found [here](#). The project allows people to observe and mark exoplanet transits in light curves from the TESS space telescope. The question uses five light curves of exoplanet transits (example light curve in Figure 3). The task is to determine each planet's orbital period T and the ratio R_{Planet}/R_{Star} for each case, including associated uncertainties. Through this problem, the students learned

Figure 2. Frequency dependency of the magnetic transfer function.

Figure 3. The transiting light curve of exoplanet WASP-126b.

about citizen science and what can be accomplished by involving a large number of people in research, while they also showed their understanding of the transiting method used to detect exoplanets.

By transforming cutting-edge research topics into engaging competition questions as outlined above, my aim is to nurture the curiosity for astronomy in high school and middle school students and to introduce them to topics that are difficult to explore otherwise.

References:

- [1] Kimihiko Nakajima, Masami Ouchi, Ionization state of inter-stellar medium in galaxies: evolution, $SFR-M^*-Z$ dependence, and ionizing photon escape, Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society, Volume 442, Issue 1, 21 July 2014, Pages 900–916, <https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stu902>
- [2] Fiori, I. et al. The Hunt for Environmental Noise in Virgo during the Third Observing Run. Galaxies 2020, 8, 82. <https://doi.org/10.3390/galaxies8040082>

Engaging the Public with Astronomy Through Interactive Museum Experiences

Presenter: Ruoying Chen, Shanghai Astronomy Museum, China

Shanghai Astronomy Museum, the world's largest astronomy museum, offers a wide view of astronomical fields. However, complex topics like cosmology are hard to grasp through exhibitions alone. To address this, the "Star Navigation" program was launched as China's first regular educational live-streaming event focused on museum exhibits. This monthly program, held within the museum, integrates exhibitions with current topics and features "star" scientists for thematic explanations. It has held 28 sessions, attracting 2.27 million viewers and 3,500 online participants through live-streams. The program transforms exhibits into an engaging "online classroom," enhancing public understanding of astronomy and has achieved tremendous success.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14541910>

The Shanghai Astronomy Museum, recognised as the world's largest astronomy museum by building size, offers an extensive array of exhibits beyond its planetarium dome. Through its three main exhibition areas—"Home," "Universe," and "Odyssey"—the museum provides a comprehensive panorama of various astronomical fields, helping the public shape a holistic understanding of the cosmos. However, topics such as cosmology and multi-wavelength astronomy are difficult for the general public without a foundation in mathematics and physics to immediately comprehend, turning the exhibition into a mere backdrop for photos. We aim to provide an interactive exhibition experience that allows visitors to engage with and understand the content, thereby deepening their knowledge of astronomical science.

Against this backdrop, the "Star Navigation" science outreach program was developed. It is currently China's first regularly scheduled, series-based educational live-streaming event focused on exhibits within an astronomy museum. Departing from traditional lecture formats, this program is set within the Astronomy Museum itself, integrating the museum's permanent exhibitions, temporary exhibits, and trending topics. It invites prominent "star" scientists from relevant fields to provide thematic scientific explanations that connect the exhibits, offering the public opportunities to interact with scientists and learn about astronomy while exploring the museum. The program is conducted monthly, and to date, 29 sessions have been held, with each session lasting about one hour. While guiding offline audiences, the events are simultaneously live-streamed on the Shanghai Astronomy Museum's official online platforms, accumulating a total of 2.27 million views, with approximately 3,500 offline participants. Additionally, the recordings and highlights of the live streams are published on the museum's social media accounts, garnering approximately 100,000 replays and receiving highly positive feedback.

Several factors contribute to the success of the "Star Navigation" program. First, the diverse and highly interactive exhibits in the Shanghai Astronomy Museum provide a solid foundation for

engaging activities. Second, the strong background of experts is crucial. The Shanghai Astronomy Museum has its own astronomy research department, conducting scientific research such as meteorite studies and solar monitoring. The integration of science and education not only allows for science popularisation that is unique to the museum but also ensures that the latest developments in the field are showcased. Additionally, we invite experts from various fields, including observatories, universities, aerospace engineers, and science film directors, to create interdisciplinary connections with astronomy. Third, the timeliness and regional relevance of the event themes are important. Hot topics are selected in response to current astronomical events, such as the solar maximum or the return of lunar samples by Chang'e 5, which draw greater public interest. For example, the "Dream Building in Space" event held on the 30th anniversary of China's manned spaceflight program attracted approximately 580,000 live-stream views. The "Shanghai Native Xu Guangqi" event, commemorating the 390th anniversary of Xu Guangqi's death, also attracted around 900,000 live-stream viewers. Lastly, leveraging the strong influence of the Shanghai Astronomy Museum, the live broadcasts are distributed to several mainstream domestic media outlets, creating a new media matrix that extends the reach of the activities.

In the 29 sessions conducted so far, we have vividly narrated the exhibits of the Shanghai Astronomy Museum in various forms. We are currently exploring opportunities beyond the museum, collaborating with satellite manufacturers, chemical companies, and other organisations to enter their laboratories, seeking intersections between astronomy and other sciences. This approach helps the public realise that astronomy is not just about gazing at the stars but is closely related to everyday life.

The "Star Navigation" program has achieved tremendous success. It transforms the exhibits of the Shanghai Astronomy Museum from static displays into an "online classroom" that is dynamically connected through scientific knowledge, vivid narration, and interactive demonstrations by numerous experts. By systematically answering the questions of "What is it?", "Why is it important?", and "How is it useful?", the program builds a knowledge tree for the audience, making the museum less intimidating and astronomy more engaging.

Sustainable Methods for Teaching Astronomy: Educational Camera Obscura in Non-Formal Spaces

Presenter: Mayana Vitória Oliveira e Sousa, Observatório Didático de Astronomia “Lionel José Andriatto”, Brazil

Collaborators: Kennia Karina da Silva Varine (Observatório Didático de Astronomia “Lionel José Andriatto”, Universidade Estadual Paulista “Júlio De Mesquita Filho” - UNESP campus Bauru), Sioneia Rodrigues da Silva (Observatório Didático de Astronomia “Lionel José Andriatto”, UNESP), and Rodolfo Langhi (Observatório Didático de Astronomia “Lionel José Andriatto”, UNESP)

This work adapts the construction of an educational camera obscura using recyclable, low-cost materials for a non-formal educational setting, such as the Observatório Didático de Astronomia at UNESP. This approach offers a practical way to demonstrate and complement optical concepts in astronomy education. The camera obscura allows students and visitors to understand the basic principle of the optical telescope and its relation to the functioning of the human eye. By observing image formation and principles like light refraction, interactive and deep learning can be promoted. This practical and accessible approach facilitates the observation of astronomical phenomena and stimulates discussions about optics and the history of scientific instruments.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14541958>

The Observatório Didático de Astronomia “Lionel José Andriatto”, project at the Universidade Estadual Paulista “Júlio de Mesquita Filho” (UNESP) stands out for applying sustainable methodologies in the teaching of astronomy in non-formal spaces. Among its main activities is the service to schools, which includes visits from students to the observatory to participate in three activities: a lecture, a practical activity, and nighttime sky observation, all conducted by the project’s monitors.

This work focuses on constructing a didactic camera obscura using recyclable and low-cost materials to promote the understanding of optical and astronomical concepts. The activity also proposes a discussion on these concepts, highlighting the similarities between the camera obscura and the functioning of telescopes.

For the activity, the materials are provided by the observatory and include: an aluminium can, black cardboard, tracing paper, a small nail, white glue, and a magnifying glass (converging lens). The students are organized into groups of four to five participants, and the activity lasts approximately 30 minutes. The groups follow a step-by-step guide with the assistance of the observatory monitors.

The process begins with a small hole being made in the bottom of the can using the nail. Next, the black cardboard is glued to the inside of the can to darken it, and the tracing paper is

attached to the opening of the can, functioning as a screen. To prevent light from entering, the external part of the can is sealed. Finally, the magnifying glass is used in front of the small hole, allowing students to observe the difference in the image seen with and without the lens.

This interactive approach facilitates the understanding of the concepts of image formation and light refraction, relating them to the functioning of optical telescopes, the human eye, and cameras. Additionally, the use of recyclable materials reinforces sustainable practices, promoting discussions about the role of science in environmental preservation and the conscious use of resources.

We would like to thank the Observatório Didático de Astronomia “Lionel José Andriatto” and the Faculdade de Ciências for their continuous support, the Centro de Meteorologia de Bauru (IPMET) for providing the space, and Universidade Estadual Paulista “Júlio de Mesquita Filho” (UNESP) for the institutional support that made this work possible. Finally, we thank the 6th Shaw-IAU Workshop on Astronomy for Education for the opportunity to present this work.

References:

- DUARTE, A. R.; ALMEIDA, A. A. A construção da câmara escura como instrumento de ensino de óptica e astronomia. *Revista Brasileira de Ensino de Física*, v. 40, n. 3, p. 1-10, 2018.
- GOMES, E. F. et al. Sob o olhar das lentes: uma proposta de divulgação científica na escola a partir do Projeto Banca da Ciência. *Revista Interdisciplinar de Tecnologias e Educação*, v. 3, n. 1, p. 1-8, 2017.
- LÓPEZ, G.; OCAMPO, J. *Astronomia e Educação: uma abordagem interdisciplinar*. São Paulo: Editora da UNESP, 2019.
- MELO, M. R.; SOARES, A. Aprendendo astronomia com material reciclável: um estudo de caso. *Educação em Questão*, v. 15, n. 1, p. 123-135, 2021.
- RIBEIRO, F. A.; SANTOS, A. M. *Educação e Sustentabilidade: práticas pedagógicas sustentáveis em sala de aula*. Brasília: Editora UnB, 2020.
- ROSSATTI, C. et al. Oficina de fotografias com câmara escura: uma atividade multidisciplinar. *Revista de Cultura e Extensão USP*, v. 2, p. 33-39, 2009.
- SILVA, D. B.; DA SILVA, T. S.. Experiência do “faça você mesmo” nas séries: 3º ano e EJA (Educação de Jovens e Adultos) do ensino médio. In: CONEDU-Congresso Nacional de Educação. 2015.
- UNIVERSIDADE ESTADUAL PAULISTA (UNESP). Observatório Didático de Astronomia - Projetos e Atividades. Disponível em: <https://www.fc.unesp.br/#!/observatorio>. Acesso em: 10 de outubro de 2024.

Transforming Science Education in Informal Settings with Astronomy and Meteorology: The Role of Astrometeorology

Presenter: Kennia Karina Silva Varine, Observatório Didático de Astronomia “Lionel José Andriatto”, Universidade Estadual Paulista “Júlio De Mesquita Filho” (Unesp-Bauru/SP), Brazil

Collaborators: Mayana Vitória Oliveira e Sousa (Universidade Estadual Paulista “Júlio de Mesquita Filho” - UNESP campus Bauru-SP) and Rodolfo Langhi (UNESP)

Astronomy and meteorology are valuable interdisciplinary tools for enriching science education in informal settings, such as the Unesp Didactic Astronomy Observatory. Comparing Earth’s atmosphere with those of other planets in the Solar System helps to understand complex concepts like planetary morphology and atmospheric dynamics, making them more accessible and engaging for diverse audiences starting from high school. Didactic lectures, images, animations, and astronomical observations are effective resources for illustrating these topics clearly and attractively. The use of data from scientific literature and connections with historical events also enhance learning. Astrometeorology can be a powerful tool in this context, promoting both theoretical and practical understanding.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14542238>

Through the "Lionel José Andriatto" Didactic Observatory of Astronomy at the "Universidade Estadual Paulista Júlio de Mesquita Filho" (UNESP), many students serve as volunteer monitors, gaining the opportunity to apply the concepts learned in their undergraduate courses. This experience also allows them to engage with astronomy, expanding their knowledge while providing services to schools and the community of Bauru, in the interior of São Paulo, as well as participating in various events. School visits are conducted weekly for elementary and high school students, featuring informative lectures, expository activities, and workshops.

This poster presents one of these lectures, in which physical concepts and terrestrial meteorology were explored in relation to the other seven planets of the Solar System. During the presentation, the same concepts were discussed, with an emphasis on the characteristics of Mercury, Venus, Mars, Jupiter, Saturn, Uranus, and Neptune. Delivered to high school students, the lecture lasted 40 minutes, followed by 10 minutes for questions. It began with a brief introduction to astronomy and meteorology, followed by explanations of the Earth’s characteristics and then those of each planet in the Solar System and their peculiarities.

Earth is a rocky planet, the third closest to the Sun, with an atmosphere composed mainly of nitrogen and oxygen, and an average temperature of 15°C. It has a protective ozone layer that filters solar radiation, while water vapour retains heat near the surface, creating a greenhouse effect that maintains mild and stable temperatures. Mercury is rocky and has a surface similar

to that of the Moon; being the closest planet to the Sun, it is impossible for an atmosphere to exist. Venus, the second planet in the Solar System, is also rocky and has a dense atmosphere composed of sulphur. Sulphur, like water vapour, captures heat, resulting in temperatures exceeding 400°C, with no significant variations between day and night. Additionally, Venus has one of the slowest rotations in the Solar System, with a day equivalent to 243 Earth days. Mars, the fourth rocky planet, has an atmosphere predominantly composed of carbon dioxide, with an average temperature of -60°C. However, temperatures can vary between 20°C in summer and -125°C in winter, depending on the region of the planet.

The first four planets of the Solar System are known as terrestrial or rocky planets, while the last four are classified as gas giants, having very small cores compared to their vast atmospheres. Jupiter, the fifth planet and the largest in the Solar System, can accommodate about 1,300 Earths. Due to its distance from the Sun, the average temperatures in its outer layers reach -145°C. Additionally, Jupiter has a rapid rotation, with a day lasting less than 10 hours. A notable feature is the "Great Red Spot," an immense and long-lasting storm that raises various hypotheses about its origin. Saturn, the sixth planet of the Solar System, has temperatures in its outer layers of around -178°C and also has a rapid rotation, with days lasting just over 10 hours. Like Jupiter, Saturn features a storm known as the "Great White Spot," which appears every 30 years. Moreover, its density is lower than that of water, which is an intriguing characteristic. Uranus and Neptune, the two planets farthest from the Sun, are known as ice giants and have cold, dense atmospheres. Uranus has an average temperature of -224°C and a rapid rotation, with a day lasting approximately 17 hours. Neptune, on the other hand, is relatively warmer, with average temperatures of -214°C, even though it is farther from the Sun, and has a day lasting just over 16 hours.

Through a mix of curiosities and information, it was possible to enrich knowledge about astronomy, meteorology, and physical concepts, facilitating the understanding of complex topics and promoting scientific and academic dissemination.

References:

- Bengoa, Jesus Arregi. Estudio de la Dinámica Atmosférica en la Región Ecuatorial de Júpiter. 2013. Tese de Doutorado. Universidad del País Vasco= Euskal Herriko Unibertsitatea.
- Correia, Helena Isabel da Costa. Estrutura e Morfologia Dos Planetas Telúricos: O Exemplo de Marte. 2002.
- González, Víctor Manuel et al. Curiosidades Atmosféricas de Saturno. Revista de Ciências, N. 2, P. 41-42, 2013.
- Hueso, Ricardo; Sánchez-Lavega, Agustín. Atmospheric Dynamics and Vertical Structure of Uranus and Neptune's Weather Layers. Space Science Reviews, V. 215, N. 8, P. 52, 2019.
- Hunten, D. M.; Morgan, T. H.; Shemansky, D. E. The Mercury Atmosphere. Mercury, V. 562, 1988.
- López, G.; Ocampo, J. Astronomia e Educação: uma abordagem interdisciplinar. São Paulo: Editora da UNESP, 2019.

- Peixoto, José Pinto. A Estrutura da Atmosfera da Terra. Finisterra, V. 14, N. 28, 1979.
- Universidade Estadual Paulista (UNESP). Observatório Didático de Astronomia - Projetos e Atividades. Disponível em: <https://www.fc.unesp.br/#!/observatorio>. Acesso em: 18 de outubro de 2024.

Enhancing Student Impact Through Innovative Astronomy Teaching Methodologies

Presenter: Adriana Victoria Araujo Salcedo, Centro de Estudios en Astrofísica, Gimnasio Campestre, Colombia

Astronomy builds bridges between mathematics, physics, statistics, and nowadays data analysis. Astronomy allows us to create awareness of our environment, especially the physical-chemical reasons that allow life on Earth. Teaching astronomy as part of the vertical axis of the curriculum has been implemented since a few years ago at the GC school in Bogotá. Through the centre of studies in Astrophysics and the Astronomical Observatory of the school, a subject called “Explora” has been developed, facing astronomy’s basic concepts, history, and even exploration of topics in astrobiology, exoplanets, and planetary sciences. This talk will summarise the activities, the corresponding data on published articles in the area, and the number of students impacted by this methodology at the school.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14545299>

In 2006, Gimnasio Campestre School launched a research-oriented curriculum for students in grades one through nine, with a particular focus on teaching research skills through the lens of astronomy. This initiative began with a fourth-grade course, structured around three key topics: the origin of the universe and matter, the behaviour of light and stars, and the principles of gravitational force. By sixth grade, the curriculum expanded to include stellar astronomy, solar and stellar evolution, planetary atmospheres, and astrobiology. These courses were carefully designed to align with the students’ developmental stages, incorporating mathematics and hands-on laboratory skills to enhance learning.

The program identified students with a strong interest and aptitude for scientific inquiry, especially in astronomy, leading to the creation of a student research group called "Jóvenes Investigadores" (Young Researchers). This group enables students to conduct independent astronomy research projects, applying the knowledge and skills acquired in the classroom.

Figure 1. Julio Garavito Astronomical Observatory, Gimnasio Capestre.

The research group focuses on three key areas: the evolution of the solar cycle, the history of Colombian astronomy, and planetary science. The students' work has been featured in the school's research journal, *Astrolabio*, and has also been published in external, indexed journals. Additionally, they have presented their findings at national and international conferences.

This initiative showcases how structured research programs can cultivate critical research skills, contribute to the generation of new knowledge, and guide students in discovering their long-term academic and professional interests.

References:

- Freedman, R. & Kaufmann, W. (2002). *Universe*. W. H. Freeman and Company. New York.
- Schatz, A., Fraknoi, A. (2016). *Solar Science*. NSTA Press. Arlington Virginia.
- Beck, R., Hilbrecht, H., Reinch, K. & Volker, P. (1995). *Solar Astronomy Handbook*. Willmann-Bell. Virginia.

We are All Residents of the Milky Way

Presenter: Nir Dubrovsky, Israeli space agency, Israel

Collaborators: Victor Bar, Osnat Eldar, Majd Thabt

Using a unique online platform with multilingual space lectures and space oriented PBL missions as a tool to bridge between alien sectors, a case test that I managed in Israel between Jewish and Arab students.

This initiative is a focused, hybrid set of meetings conducted by a different ethnic groups and sectors, sometimes on the background of rivalry, under the wide imaginary theme of space, that is taking place physically and online simultaneously.

The idea is that our collective identity extends far beyond sectors, ethnic groups, religious minorities and similar divisions. It encompasses the galaxy we belong to—the Milky Way—and this shared heritage defines us as boundary-crossing equals, regardless of nationality or ethnicity.

This initiative includes a lecture by space specialists delivered in both languages (e.g. Hebrew and Arabic). Following the lecture, two lessons are conducted for each sector in their respective language, guided by students from our program. Finally, the activity concludes with a workshop (e.g. building water rockets) or an interactive game like “Space Treasure Hunt”, designed to gather the group in a collective physical mission.

This initiative has been running in Israel since the spring of 2021, against the backdrop of clashes between Jews and Arabs. It has already held a series of online and offline meetings involving a wide range of schools and specialists.

The highlight of this program was an event held at the prestigious Oranim College in Israel. It featured a series of lectures, workshops and games, led by Jews and Arabs instructors, with over a 1000 participants in attendance. The main goal of the event was to foster a shared foundation that reduces differences and rivalry, promoting a collective identity and a common purpose.

More information can be found on our page: <https://www.horizon-space.com/residents-of-the-milky-way/>

Satellite Radio Reception Experiment Using SDR as a Teaching Material for High School Physics

Presenter: Hideki Uchiyama, Shizuoka University, Japan

Collaborators: Akari Sugiyama (Shizuoka University), Masaya Kamio (Nihon University Mishima Senior High School), and Tomoyuki Uchiyama (High School Misawa)

Some artificial satellites transmit radio waves that can be received using amateur radio equipment. Satellite radio reception experiments allow students to observe satellite movements and study high school-level physical phenomena. Kobayashi et al. (2020) showed that these experiments effectively motivate Japanese high school students to learn science. We propose using Software-Defined Radio (SDR) instead of analog receivers for the experiments. SDR enables direct visualisation of frequency changes, allowing for the quantitative measurement of satellite velocity using the Doppler effect formula. It offers valuable material for studying Kepler's motion and the Doppler effect in high school physics. We conducted classes with SDR-based experiments and will report our findings.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14542247>

Radio waves from artificial satellites can be received by tracking the satellite's movement with an antenna and adjusting the Doppler shift of the receiving frequency. In this experiment, students can observe the rapid passage of satellites over their heads, as calculated using the physics principles they have previously studied. They can also undertake a quantitative study of physical phenomena, such as Keplerian motion and wave phenomena, which they may have encountered at the high school level. Consequently, it can be utilised as a physics experiment with excellent educational effects. Furthermore, students can discern the connection between the technologies that support society, such as artificial satellites, and the physics they learn in school. From this perspective, Kobayashi et al. (2020) studied and implemented this experiment as a teaching material, reporting that it increases motivation to study science (Journal of the Physics Education Society of Japan, 68/2, 79-86, in Japanese).

We propose to use software-defined radio (SDR) for satellite radio reception experiments as a teaching material. In the previous study (Kobayashi et al. 2020), analog receivers were used for the experiment. It is expensive (about 20,000 yen ~130 USD) or more at least, and can only output audio information, and what we can do with it is limited. The SDR is a receiver in which a computer processes signals digitally instead of analog circuits. It can be employed in reception experiments easily and inexpensively (although a personal computer is required). Furthermore, it can be used to view radio spectra with free software (e.g., [HSDR](#)), and we can see the change in frequency directly. Using SDR, the velocity of a satellite can be measured quantitatively based on the Doppler effect formula. This measurement can be good experimental material for

Figure 1. Photos of the experiment in this trial.

Figure 2. The result of the co-occurrence network analysis on the post-survey descriptions.

Keplerian motion and the Doppler effect in high school physics. Accordingly, we conducted an educational trial with this material (see Figure 1).

The educational trial was conducted at a s high school in Shizuoka, Japan. The lecture was conducted as a special lecture over two days, with each session lasting 150 minutes for those who wished to attend voluntarily. A total of 14 high school students, comprising second-year students aged 17 years, participated in it. They had previously studied circular motion, gravity, and the Doppler effect. The radio signal from the NOAA-18 satellite was received with SDR. On the initial day of the lecture, the students employed the theoretical framework of Kepler’s motion to calculate the velocity of the NOAA-18 satellite, which was found to be 7.4 km/s. To confirm the velocity experimentally, the students formulated an equation to determine the velocity from the received frequency based on the Doppler effect. On the second day, the students conducted the radio reception experiment of the NOAA-18 satellite using SDR. They calculated the satellite velocities from the observed frequencies and shared and discussed the results. The calculated satellite velocities were found to agree with the theoretical value to within 8%. This trial demonstrates the potential of this material to facilitate understanding of both the physical phenomena themselves and the associated measurement uncertainty.

Following the lecture, a survey was conducted, requesting participants to respond in writing to the question, "What was interesting or memorable about the lecture?". Text mining (co-occurrence network analysis) was performed on the descriptions using the KH coder (Higuchi 2001, <https://kncoder.net/>). The results indicate that the experiment was highly satisfy-

ing to the students and demonstrated their understanding of the importance of quantitative reasoning and units.

In the future, we intend to construct additional trials, assess the efficacy of the educational program, and improve the material. We will publish manuals and guides for teachers and students that can be readily utilised in schools on a website accessible in English and other languages, including Japanese.

This work was supported by JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number 24K06356. Part of this work has already been reported in Global Hands-on Universe Conference 2023 (<https://ghou2023.hansonuniverse.org/>) and its proceedings.

Further Adventures with Gee Whizz Astronomy Modelling

Presenter: Fraser Lewis, Faulkes Telescope Project, GWAM, UK

Collaborators: The GWAM Team

I provide an update on a successful year for Gee-Whizz Astronomy Modelling (GWAM), an online astronomy 'club' giving our students, teachers and educators opportunities in astronomical research. GWAM was founded during the pandemic by Carl Pennypacker (UC Berkeley, GHOU) and Elizabeth Villanueva (University of Chile) who developed open-ended astronomy projects for students. Our team lives in Chile, Pakistan, the United States, Colombia, and Wales and we meet online for an hour each week at a time suitable to all (typically Fridays ~ 18 - 20 UT). Students collect and analyse astronomical images and datasets (such as Gaia DR3), use astronomical software along with Python, and observing time from Las Cumbres Observatory. Students study topics such as transiting exoplanets, eclipsing binaries, open clusters, and blazars. Find out more at our [website](#).

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14542255>

The Gee-Whizz Astronomy Modelling (GWAM) project was set up by Professor Carl Pennypacker (UC Berkeley) and Elizabeth Villanueva (Colegio Alberto Perez, Santiago) in mid-2020 as a way of keeping educators active and productive during the pandemic. Meeting weekly on Zoom at ~ 18 - 19 UT enabled us to keep in touch with students from all around the world at a time when most of the world is awake.

With the support from LCO's network of 40-cm telescopes, students were able to take images of objects that interested them from spectacular galaxies, to planetary nebulae and supernovae remnants.

Students were encouraged to develop their own research projects and collected data both using telescopes and interrogating existing data archives. They used photometry packages to reduce the data and tools such as MS Excel, Python, and [TOPCAT](#) to analyse their results. Their data was used to build colour-magnitude diagrams allowing us to look at stellar evolution and the life cycle of stars, something that appears in many curricula around the world.

Other projects involved datasets collected over different timescales to search for variability - a property inherent to nearly all astronomical objects. Notably, transiting exoplanets, blazars, and microlensing systems are both accessible to our telescopes and of particular interest to our students. We are currently preparing several papers to present the methodologies and tools our students use in their work, as well as the results of their initial studies.

I want to acknowledge the students I have the privilege of working with, who often take these research projects in unexpected and innovative directions. We are always eager to collaborate with new students, educators, teachers, and explore fresh project ideas.

In addition to our regular meetings, we are developing a set of resources for teachers, initially available in Spanish and English. More information can be found at <https://sites.google.com/view/gwamcl/>.

Journey Alongside the Centreline

Presenter: Deborah Skapik, Friends' Central School/St. Joe's University, USA

This presentation focuses on teacher training in advance of the Great American Eclipse on April 8, 2024. I document my cross-country journey to prepare underserved communities along the eclipse path and how I followed up with them as they reflected on their incredible eclipse experiences. In fall 2022, I self-published an educator's guide to solar eclipses. In summer 2023 I distributed *Look UP, Below!* to educators in Title 1 schools (large concentrations of low-income students) alongside the centreline of the eclipse, providing science educators in these schools with a free resource and workshops, encouraging them to get their students outside viewing the eclipse safely. I will share advice to those planning similar teacher training along eclipse paths in other countries.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14545222>

Figure 1.

In the weeks leading up to the Great American Eclipse of April 8, 2024, teachers needed a reliable resource they could access quickly to provide their students with a firm foundation in eclipse literacy. I published a book that offered K-12 teachers background material on eclipses, not only as natural world phenomena, but as historical and cultural events. It included ready-to-go activity pages that teachers could duplicate and enjoy with their classes. Additionally, it gave step-by-step guidelines for each teacher to determine eclipse timing according to their geographic location. In July 2023, I drove alongside the eclipse path from Indiana to Vermont in order to distribute this book to teachers in Title 1 eligible schools.

Contents of the Book: “Look UP, Below!” was designed with K-12 teachers in mind. For the novice, I included basic, distilled descriptions of the shadow geometry causing eclipses, and a glossary defining complex scientific terms in simple language. For teachers already well-versed in astronomy who were seeking fresh ideas for demonstration or labs, I included workbook pages with permission to reproduce. Table 1 lists the activities sorted by age-appropriateness. There is a little something for everyone—there is even a section on folklore and an eclipse music playlist.

Planning the Journey: From July 29 to August 5, I drove west from my home near Philadelphia to Indiana, then turned to drive north-east along the eclipse path. My goal was to distribute the book to as many educators as possible near the centreline, with special attention to those in underserved communities. To identify them, I looked for counties along the path containing high percentages of schools eligible for Title 1 funding. According to the US Department of Education, Title 1 “...provides financial assistance to local educational agencies (LEAs) and schools with high numbers or high percentages of children from low-income families.” In the counties I selected, 80-100% of the schools are Title 1 eligible. Figure 1 demonstrates the distribution of Title 1 eligible schools by county in Indiana, for example. Next, I reached out to the county libraries via letter or email, offering to give them a copy of the book and asking for their help setting up a distribution event to their local educators.

Though I started plotting the journey in January 2023, I did not have a full itinerary planned for the trip until early July. The majority of the libraries did not answer my letter, and many of them did not return my phone messages, either. On the other hand, some were absolutely delighted and let me set up hands-on workshops with demos and a slide show. Doors seemed to open more easily when I introduced myself as a NASA Partner Eclipse Ambassador, so I am very grateful for the credential that the Astronomical Society of the Pacific provided.

Figure 2. Four steps on the journey.

Figure 3. Locations on/off centreline.

Figure 4. Entire journey path.

Journey Alongside the Centreline: The adventure began far off the eclipse path in Wheeling, West Virginia. Wheeling is in Ohio County, where 50% of its seven public schools are eligible for Title 1 funding.

From Wheeling, I headed west to the Greater Indianapolis area and from there followed the north-east section of the eclipse path. Figure 2 shows the first four stops along the path at libraries in Indiana and Ohio, and Figure 3 demonstrates how some of the locations were closer to the centreline (Kenton, OH), while others just skirted the path (Canton, OH). And, yes, the irony of these two similar-sounding locations having very different eclipse experiences is not lost on me! Table 2 lists my destinations, the number of Title 1 eligible schools served by the public libraries in each place, the minutes of totality each experienced, number of people who attended my workshop and number of books donated.

Generally, I visited two libraries each day. Some requested a formal slide show and presentation on eclipses. Others requested hands-on workshops about Moon phases or sizes and scales in the Solar System with attention to eclipses. In some places, I only had time to distribute books and do a short Q&A before heading to my next destination. The entire journey is mapped in Figure 4.

Follow-up: At these events, I collected contact information from over 100 educators. In March 2024, I reached out with a pre-eclipse survey to see how they were using my book to prepare their classes for the eclipse. I also sent a post-eclipse survey to hear how they implemented the activity pages from “Look UP, Below!” and their students’ reactions to the eclipse. Only 10 educators responded to my first survey and of those only six responded to my second. Of those six, only four had a copy of my book, three teaching primary grades and one K-12 teacher. All four of these teachers reported using the activity pages with their classes in days preceding the eclipse as well as on eclipse day itself (Table 3). Most of the teachers noted that schools were closed for the eclipse, so they had prepared eclipse day packets for their students to take home. One teacher commented, “Thank you for the information you shared in Erie, PA in the summer. It inspired me that day to plan activities on the 8th of each month leading up to the eclipse!”

Reactions to the Eclipse: There are, of course, untold numbers of awesome stories about people experiencing the 2024 eclipse in the USA. This alone is valuable and thrilling for me to hear, as my motivation for writing the book and taking my distribution journey was to make sure that the experience of 2017—where a lot of people were caught unaware or unprepared—was not repeated. But I was especially happy to hear a couple of teachers report specific things to me about their experience. First, one teacher said, “Many of the students didn’t understand what the fuss was all about until it happened.” This teacher, from Massillon, Ohio, also reported to me observing the strange behaviour of animals (deer, bats, and crickets) during the eclipse, something I had instructed folks to watch for during my workshops. Another very satisfying story came from a teacher in Canton, Ohio, who said about the students, “...it was very exciting to hear them use proper vocabulary and understand what they were seeing and why.”

Future Plans: Over the next few months, I intend to share the more detailed story of my journey—the places I went, the people I met— in a book called Journey Alongside the Centreline.

Acknowledgments: I would like to thank Friends’ Central School for partial support through the Hendrie Fund and the Farraday Fund to write and distribute this book.

Number	Activity	Primary	Middle	Secondary
1	Eclipse Colouring	X		
2	Interview an Adult		X	X
3A	Lunar Phases			X
3B	Lunar Phases and Time of Day			X
4A	Shadow Boxes			X
4B	Shadow Bodies		X	
5A	Partial Eclipses and Orbits			X
6	Pinhole Projectors	X	X	X
7	How Images Form			X
8	Eclipse Observations Worksheet	X	X	X
9	Creativity Page	X	X	X

Table 1. Activity page contents.

Destination	Title 1 Eligible Schools	Minutes of Totality	Attendees	Books Donated
Ohio County, WV	4	O (97% partial)	4	3
Fayette County, IN	8	3m 47s	1	1
Adams County, IN	9	2m 43s	8	3
Hardin County, OH	11	3m 55s	6	3
Marion County, OH	20	3m 35s	22	9
Stark County, OH	91	O (99.8% partial)	25	29
Trumbull County, OH	61	O (99.7% partial)	3	2
Erie County, NY	155	3m 46s	28	22
Clinton County, NY	21	3m 34s	10	5

Table 2. Destinations and donations.

Location	Book activities pre-eclipse	Book activities on 4/8
Massillon, OH	3A Lunar Phases	Eclipse Colouring, Pinhole Projectors
Canton, OH	3A Lunar Phases, 4A Shadow Boxes, Pinhole Projectors	3A Lunar Phases, 4A Shadow Boxes, 5A Partial Eclipse Phases, Pinhole Projectors
Erie, PA	Eclipse Colouring, Interview an Adult, 3A Lunar Phases, 4A Lunar Phases and Time of Day, 4A Shadow Boxes, 4B Shadow Bodies, 5A Partial Eclipse Phases, 5B Partial Eclipses and Orbits	Eclipse Colouring, Interview an Adult, 3A Lunar Phases, 4A Lunar Phases and Time of Day, 5A Partial Eclipse Phases, 5B Partial Eclipses and Orbits
Nile, OH	4A Lunar Phases and Time of Day, 4A Shadow Boxes	4A Shadow Boxes

Table 3. How educators used "Look UP, Below!".

References:

- [US Department of Education](#)
- Greatamericaneclipse.com
- <https://www.zipdatamaps.com>
- timeanddate.com

The Knowledge that Emerges from Shadows

Presenter: Álvaro Folhas, University of Coimbra, NUCLIO, CITEUC, Portugal

Interdisciplinary learning is crucial for the 21st century, promoting the construction of a meaningful and holistic view of the Universe. Astronomy, in addition to the interest it arouses, offers a unique platform to integrate physics, chemistry, mathematics, biology, geography, ICT and arts. By exploring the cosmos, students develop a scientific and aesthetic understanding of the organisation and mechanics of the Universe, and they also gain awareness of the fragility of our existence on Earth. To implement this, I conducted a teacher training, focused on astronomy and shadow analysis and measurement activities for students. This experience reinforced physics, mathematics, geography and biology concepts, demonstrating how astronomy enables interdisciplinary learning in schools.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14545262>

The challenges posed to science education are increasing to build a scientifically informed society, capable of decisions based on knowledge, prepared to respond to the needs of the future [1]. In this context, it is important to construct meanings that link different subjects to the reality of students. Thus, interdisciplinarity emerges as a beacon capable of allowing knowledge to be explored more broadly and deep. Through it, we break the artificial boundaries between subjects, weaving a rich tapestry of knowledge that gives us a way to understand the world, holistically, with greater clarity and more enthusiasm. In addition to the cognitive domain, interdisciplinarity also stimulates critical thinking, and promotes the development of transversal skills, essential for the 21st century.

Astronomy, as a scientific area that encompasses different areas of knowledge, offers unique opportunities for interdisciplinarity in science teaching, arousing students' interests, stimulating their curiosity and creativity [2], establishing connections between different subjects, brought together here for the construction of meanings about the reality experienced by students.

Developing activities based on astronomy is within the reach of any school, whether it has telescopes or not. The simple exploration of the behaviour of the shadow of a vertical stick throughout the day, allows us to determine a myriad of information such as solar noon, the maximum height of the Sun, the orientation of the North-South meridian, and the latitude of the place, just mobilising concepts from physics, but also mathematics, geography and even natural sciences. By adding tools like Stellarium and Google Maps, students can even determine the longitude and meridional perimeter of the Earth (Eratosthenes' experiment) on any day of the year.

Thus, it was proposed to carry out a teacher training project, using an action research methodology, to a pedagogical team formed by mathematics, natural sciences, physics and chemistry and

Figure 1. Group of students carrying out the experiment.

Figure 2. Some measurements obtained in the experiment.

geography teachers, who had three 7th grade classes in common in the Escola Básica Professor Nunes Vidal (Fermentelos, Portugal). In an initial phase, the knowledge based on the processes involved in the proposed activity were explored, as well as the 7th grade curricular contents in each of the subjects that would be mobilised by this activity.

The activity took place on a sunny day on June 11, 2024, and we used a horizontal plate on which a 4.90 cm nail emerged, perfectly vertical. A very simple setup. Once it was assembled, recording the maximum position of the shadow began, around 1.5 hours before solar noon, and continued around an hour later to verify the difference in size and orientation of the shadows.

Once the experimental phase was over, the exploratory analysis of the data began, starting by determining, on site, the orientation of the shortest shadow that points to the geographic North. This is the first determination that allows to establish the cardinal directions from the experiment. Checking the time of solar noon was another determination, realising that it was the instant in which, in its apparent movement, the Sun crossed the meridian, immediately mobilising curricular concepts in physics and geography.

Having the length of the nail and the minimum shadow, students reproduced a triangle with these dimensions and directly measured the maximum height of the Sun with a protractor, inferring the shadow angle. With this data, students learned how to determine the latitude of the place, realising the need to modify the result accounting for solar declination. Still using the support of Stellarium, they verified the validity of their results and also determined the longitude of the place. This analysis could also involve history, talking about how ancient navigators knew their position on the seas. With the same data and tools, they made the determination of the meridional perimeter of the Earth, using Eratosthenes' experiment, searching in Stellarium,

along the meridian, the place where the Sun, at solar noon, would be at the zenith. This approach helps to understand and give substance to the concepts involved.

An assessment was carried out, before and after the activity, with questions from the curriculum of the subjects involved, and there was a statistically significant improvement in reinforcing learning, demonstrating the effectiveness of this strategy.

We can only talk about learning when concepts acquire meaning for the students, allowing them to understand the world around them. As this reality is interdisciplinary, it is important to bring activities structured in this interconnection of knowledge to school - the whole is greater than the sum of its parts.

References:

- [1] OECD Future of Education and Skills 2030—OECD Future of Education and Skills 2030. (2021, julho 14). <https://www.oecd.org/education/2030-project/>
- [2] Folhas, A., Costa, A., Doran, R. (2023). “Campanhas de pesquisa de asteroides: aprender ciência fazendo ciência”. In Conselho Nacional de Educação (CNE) (Eds.), DICA: Divulgar, Inovar, Colaborar, Aprender – 2023 (pp. 262-275). https://www.cnedu.pt/content/DICA/DICA_2023/Vivencias_2023/Campanhas_de_pesquisa_de_asteroidesaprender_ciencia_fazendo_ciencia.pdf

Bridging Gaps in Ghana’s Astronomy Education for Exceptional Learners Through Innovative TTP

Presenter: Albert Forson, University of Mauritius / PRAGSAC, Ghana

Collaborators: Naomi Asabre Frimpong (GSSTI, NOC Ghana & PRAGSAC), Sarah Abotsi-Masters (NAEC Ghana & PRAGSAC), Sarah Boamah (GES & NRF Accra STEAM Centre), Joshua Kolognia (UCC & PRAGSAC), and Christiana Adorkor Kpakpo (TELECEL Ghana & PRAGSAC)

Teaching astronomy to exceptional learners, especially those with disabilities or socioeconomic challenges, is challenging globally. In Ghana, there is a significant lack of organised astronomy education for these students, particularly in schools for the blind and deaf, due to the absence of accessible learning materials. To address this, the Teacher Training Program (TTP) was introduced, providing workshops for science teachers of grades 7th-9th. The program equips them with hands-on activities and innovative methodologies, leading to a significant increase in their skills. Feedback shows 83.3% of participants improved their astronomy knowledge, marking TTP as crucial for equity and inclusivity in Ghana’s astronomy education.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14545285>

Teaching astronomy to exceptional learners, particularly those from underrepresented groups facing diverse learning challenges—such as the blind, deaf, or socioeconomically disadvantaged—presents significant global challenges. In Ghana, with a population of approximately 32.8 million (Ghana Statistical Service, 2023), there are an estimated 110,625 deaf individuals, representing 0.4% of the population (Asonye & Edward, 2022). Additionally, between 246,000 and 328,000 people, or 0.75% to 1% of the population, are blind (Ghana Blind Union and WHO estimates).

Ghana lacks organised astronomy education programs for schools that cater to exceptional learners, especially those for the blind and deaf. Despite past efforts to promote astronomy education in schools, institutions serving these groups have been largely overlooked. A primary obstacle in astronomy education for exceptional learners in Ghana is the absence of accessible learning materials tailored to their specific needs. Traditional visual aids are insufficient for visually impaired students, highlighting the need for innovative and inclusive teaching methods such as tactile models, interactive digital platforms, and multi-sensory experiences.

To address this gap, we introduced the Teacher Training Program (TTP), offering astronomy workshops for science teachers from grades 7th-9th in schools for the blind and deaf across Ghana. The three-and-a-half-day residential workshop covers key topics such as the Moon, Earth, planets, the Solar System, the Sun, and constellations, aiming to equip teachers with hands-on activities for effectively teaching astronomy to visually and hearing-impaired students.

This paper presents positive feedback and insights from participating teachers, as well as the challenges encountered, to guide future projects. Pre- and post-evaluation analysis showed a significant increase in participants' knowledge and skills in designing and using astronomy teaching materials related to the Earth, Moon, and Sun, with proficiency rising from 64.53% to 95.06%. Similarly, knowledge about the Solar System improved from 39.58% to 79.19% by the end of each lesson and two weeks after the training.

Additionally, 60.3% of teachers demonstrated increased proficiency in using simple teaching materials for the blind and deaf, highlighting TTP's potential as a powerful tool for promoting equity and inclusivity in astronomy education. This initiative contributes significantly to bridging the inequality gap in Ghana and supporting the country's growth and development.

Figure 1. Discover Earth's climate with a balloon activity.

Figure 2. Demonstration of the Earth-Moon Distance: Teachers wrap a string around the Earth ball 10 times to represent the distance between the Earth and the Moon when the string is fully extended.

Figure 3. The Sun and Planets Activities: Teachers compare the sizes of the Planets to the Sun.

Figure 4. Group photos of the participants and the organisers of the TPP.

Assessing Student Writing Assignments with Large Language Models

Presenter: Matthew Wenger, University of Arizona, USA

Collaborators: Chris Impey, Shahriar Golchin, Nikhil Garuda, and Sanlyn Buxner (University of Arizona), and Sarah Stamer (University of New Mexico)

Writing assignments is useful for promoting and assessing student learning. It is difficult to implement student writing in large classes, and nearly impossible to provide iterative feedback. For large online classes, such as Massive Open Online Classes (MOOCs), the only solution has been to use peer graders. Unfortunately peer grading can be unreliable as peer graders do not always leave useful feedback. We used Large Language Models (LLMs) to test whether they can accurately grade student writing assignments and provide feedback. Our results show that LLMs provide accurate feedback similar to instructors. We also found that the grades assigned by LLMs were consistent with instructor scores, and more accurate than peer graders.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14542100>

Although writing assignments is an excellent way to promote and assess student learning, it is difficult to implement student writing in large classes, and nearly impossible to provide iterative feedback. For large online classes, such as Massive Open Online Classes (MOOCs) peer grading has been the only solution. Unfortunately, peer grading can be unreliable as often peer graders do not leave any useful content-specific feedback. In this study we used Large Language Models (LLMs), GPT-3.5 and GPT-4, to examine whether current LLM's can evaluate student writing assignments and to test the use of Machine Learning as an alternative to peer grading and feedback. The research questions include:

1. Can Large Language Models (LLMs) evaluate student writing assignments in science courses?
2. Can LLM's accurately grade student writing?
3. How do the grades assigned by LLM's compare with those assigned by peer graders?
4. How do the grades assigned by LLM's compare with those assigned by instructors?

Research Context: Data was collected from three MOOCs with over 275,000 students enrolled. The courses are on the topics of Introductory Astronomy, Astrobiology, and The History and Philosophy of Astronomy. The writing assignments are currently peer-graded, but prior research has shown that peer-grades can be unreliable, and in our own courses we have found that

not everyone participates in peer-grading which results in some students never having their assignments graded. The two top performing models, GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 were compared.

Research Data: We identified writing assignments from each course and purposefully sampled them to get a range of scores so we could examine how the LLM's perform at the high- and low-ends of the grade range. An instructor graded each assignment and the peer grades were retrieved from Coursera. The grading rubric used by the peer-graders was provided to the LLM and a model "correct" answer was written by the instructor. LLM prompts were developed for each test scenario (model answer only, model answer and rubric, and model answer with LLM generated rubric).

Results and Findings: The results show that LLMs reliably provide comprehensive and accurate feedback similar to feedback from instructors. LLMs performed, statistically, as well as instructors and peer graders. No significant differences between instructor, peer, and LLM scores. LLMs were qualitatively a bit closer in performance to instructor grades than peers. Peer grades were slightly higher than instructor and LLM grades. GPT-4 had the best performance with the closest alignment to the instructor and less dispersion than peer-graders. LLMs performed best when provided with a model answer and the grading rubric. LLMs had some difficulty with edge cases (very long or very short assignments).

Our findings also show that LLMs assigned grades that were consistent with instructor scores. Automated grading is at least as good as peer-grading and would be more reliable. Open-ended questions, like those in the History and Philosophy classes, pose more challenges for current LLMs and they work best with "right" or "wrong" answers in science courses.

Limitations and Future Work: There is still work to be done before deploying LLMs as graders in high-stakes environments like college classes. LLMs can still be fooled, especially if students know that the grading process is automated. There need to be systems in place to address inaccurate grades. For example, students could be allowed to dispute inaccurate grades with an instructor.

We aim to explore the use of LLMs in the lower-stakes aspects of the writing process and asses their ability to provide accurate formative feedback. This would be particularly useful in large classes where instructors or teaching assistants cannot provide iterative feedback. We also aim to explore whether the results of LLMs can be improved by examining different models and enhancing their performance through additional training.

Multisensory Planetarium. The Universe as You Never Sensed It

Presenter: Federico Di Giacomo, INAF - Istituto Nazionale di Astrofisica, Italy

Collaborators: C. Mignone (INAF & IAU OAE Center Italy), R. Toniolo (Department of Physics and Astronomy, University of Bologna, INAF, & IAU OAE Center Italy), and S. Varano (INAF & IAU OAE Center Italy)

What if anyone could observe the night sky regardless of their physical abilities? This project means to offer a common perceptual and cognitive framework to all users, sighted, deaf, and blind or visually impaired (BVI) alike. The planetarium consists of a plexiglass hemisphere on which stars up to the fourth magnitude are represented by metal bars that, when touched, activate visual, tactile and acoustic stimuli. The acoustic stimuli (used to represent magnitude) are intended to introduce a perceptive equivalent for BVI users, while the haptic ones introduce quantitative features (distance and magnitude) that can only be known through instrumental observations. The multisensory planetarium opens new perspectives for inclusive education, offering everyone the opportunity to explore the sky.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14542259>

1. Introduction: The celestial vault is the apparent surface of the sky, which many cultures and myths intend as a sort of physical "dome" hovering above the observer. Even though it is an apparent feature, whose existence has been overcome by scientific studies and modern astronomical observations, it still represents a powerful idea. This concept is inaccessible to blind and visually impaired (BVI) users, who cannot experience the sensation of being under the starry sky.

To address this, various successful projects have utilised haptic (touch-based) and acoustic (sound-based) resources to make astronomy accessible to BVI users. These efforts include tactile star maps [1], audio descriptions for astronomical phenomena [2], sonification and even 3D-printed models of celestial objects [3]. Such multi-sensory representations have proven to be highly effective and have great potential to foster equal access to astronomy culture [4].

Following this approach, we created a multisensory planetarium, which, thanks to visual, acoustic and tactile stimuli, allows to show both the apparent and physical characteristics of the stars, to offer common perceptual and cognitive frameworks to sighted, deaf, and BVI users alike.

2. The Multisensory Planetarium: The multi-sensory planetarium consists of a plexiglass hemisphere on which stars are represented by a metal bar that when touched, activates visual, haptic and acoustic stimuli.

Among the approximately 6,000 stars visible in the sky to the naked eye, we decided to include

Figure 1. The picture on the left shows some constellations that you can see inside the planetarium. The red thread indicates the shape of IAU constellations. The picture on the right shows the electrical implementation that reproduces the stimuli.

in our multi-sensory planetarium only stars up to the 3.5 magnitude. This means that on the surface of the planetarium, users will be able to find about 80 stars. Using a fisheye projection of the night sky, we determined the positions of the stars on the plexiglass dome. Holes were then drilled at these positions to insert brass cylinders, threaded at the top to accommodate bolts. These bolts serve as a tactile representation of the stars' apparent magnitudes. A small vibration motor was attached to the base of each cylinder, and a 3mm LED was installed at the top.

2.1. The Mapping of Stimuli: The stars' physical characteristics that are represented in the planetarium are the apparent magnitude, the 2D position on the celestial sphere, and the distance from Earth.

1. **Position.** Information about the position of the stars on the celestial vault is provided both as tactile and visual stimuli, corresponding to the position of the bar on the dome.
2. **Apparent magnitude.** We use both acoustic and visual stimuli. The visual stimulus is determined by the brightness of the LED, which is proportional to the apparent luminosity of the star. The acoustic stimulus, on the other hand, is defined by a sound whose volume depends on the star's apparent luminosity. We selected this acoustic mapping because the senses of sight and hearing both operate on similar logarithmic scales. This approach ensures a consistent method for defining stellar magnitudes. Additionally, the magnitude was represented using a tactile stimulus: a variable number of bolts were added to the metal bars, corresponding to the magnitude of each star.
3. **Distance.** The distances of stars from Earth were represented through vibrations, with faster or slower shakes corresponding to shorter or longer distances, respectively. We used a vibrating motor operating at a fixed frequency of 240 Hz and increased the pulse interval by one millisecond for each additional light year of distance.

3. Discussion: The multi-sensory planetarium was presented for the first time during the Festival "Punti di Vista" (Viewpoints) held at Palazzo Esposizioni Roma, in Italy, on 16-17 March 2024. During the event, we asked some questions to the users to assess the impact and the validity

of the experience. The collected data indicate that users highly appreciated the inclusion of a perceptual equivalent not only for what is directly visible (position and magnitude) but also for what can only be observed through scientific measurements (distance).

During the first phase of exploration, acoustic and visual stimuli provided information based solely on the direct perception of nature, such as the position of objects and their apparent magnitude. However, information about the true (intrinsic) brightness or on distance of stars cannot be obtained by simple observation of the sky. In studying the celestial vault, observation alone is insufficient for a deeper understanding; various instruments, such as telescopes, and repeated measurements are required. Similarly, in our representation, sight and hearing are not enough for a complete understanding. Therefore, we incorporated an additional sense—touch.

This approach provides a richer cognitive experience, grounded in scientific data inaccessible through naked-eye observation. It enables equal perceptive enjoyment of the night sky as observed without instruments and offers representation of astronomical data on two cognitive levels, both accessible to all. In this way, the multi-sensory planetarium balances the direct perceptual experience of the night sky with a deeper scientific understanding, allowing users to explore and grasp the wonders of astronomy inclusively and comprehensively.

References:

- [1] Bonne, N. et al. 2020, “Tactile Universe makes outreach feel good”, *Astronomy & Geophysics*, 59(1), 1-30
- [2] Perez-Montero et. al 2022, “The Universe in Words: Astronomy for all through audio description within the outreach project Astroaccessible”, arXiv:2206.09703
- [3] Ortiz, G. A. 2020, “A Touch of the Universe”. Scientific Meeting of the Spanish Astronomical Society, p.265.
- [4] Varano, S. & Zanella, A. 2023, “Design and evaluation of a multisensory representation of scientific data”, *Frontiers in Education*, Vol.8

DISCUSSION SUMMARY

At the end of each session we hosted discussion panels with our speakers. The discussion panel for part 1 included a diverse range of topics ranging from how to treat scientific uncertainty and doubt when teaching cutting-edge topics in areas such as astrobiology, to how to teach astronomy in what might be a student's third language. During one of the discussion panels in part 1 we also heard from a range of people involved in the Sabir project about their experiences working through the co-design process. In the discussion panel for part 2 we dealt with using media and exhibits to teach astronomy. This included questions on how to treat artefacts when presenting images to students, and how to use questions to increase student engagement both in in-person and virtual environments. Several of the poster presenters for this session also joined at the end of the discussion panels to advertise their posters.

Compiled by: Niall Deacon

Evaluation

Session organisers: Sophie Bartlett (OAE Heidelberg), Noorali T. Jiwaji (Open University of Tanzania), Ayelet Weizman (NAEC Israel, Kibbutzim College of Education), Hakim L Malasan (NAEC Indonesia. Astronomy Division, Institute of Technology Bandung, Department of Atmospheric and Planetary Sciences, Institute of Technology Sumatra), Exodus Chun-Long Sit (NAEC and Co-NOC Hong Kong, China. International Committee, Dark Sky International President, Starrix Hong Kong. Educational Committee, Aurora Association), Jungjoo Sohn (NAEC Republic of Korea. Dept. of Earth Science Education, Korea National University of Education)

Editing supported by: Sophie Bartlett

SESSION OVERVIEW

This session will showcase diverse approaches to assessing the effectiveness of astronomy education initiatives. It will explore evaluation methodologies for assessing the impact of astronomy education projects on teachers, pupils, and broader communities.

Evaluating Without Words

Speaker: Federico Di Giacomo, INAF - Istituto Nazionale di Astrofisica, Italy

Collaborators: C. Mignone (INAF – Istituto Nazionale di Astrofisica & IAU OAE Center Italy), R. Toniolo, (Department of Physics and Astronomy, University of Bologna, INAF - Institute for Radioastronomy & IAU OAE Center Italy), and S. Varano (INAF – Institute for Radioastronomy & IAU OAE Center Italy)

The use of traditional written questions to evaluate astronomy education workshops in difficult contexts, marked by high rates of school dropout, low literacy and the presence of non-native Italian speakers, can be ineffective. In these situations, it is essential to adopt new and alternative methods. Direct experiences carried out in the outskirts of big Italian cities, where social marginalisation is marked, have shown that drawing and other non-verbal forms are powerful tools for evaluation. Through drawing, everyone can express their experiences, emotions and levels of learning, offering a valid tool to understand the impact of the activities. This approach allows for an inclusive and intuitive evaluation, capable of involving everyone regardless of their linguistic competencies.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/HP1-Z2fypeE>

1. The Context

As part of the virtual exhibition “Look up! Sfoggia il cielo con un dito”, organised by the Italian National Institute for Astrophysics (INAF) to share with the general public the historical astronomical atlases in the institute’s collections, a series of educational workshops were implemented in 2022/2023 to engage young children with the exhibition content. The workshops were conducted in collaboration with the NGO Save the Children Italia in the “Punti Luce” (Light points), community centres run by the NGO in the suburbs of many Italian cities, offering extracurricular activities to children living in situations of great social fragility and high school drop-out rate. Through the cultural heritage of Italian astrophysics, we aimed to provide an opportunity for growth and the development of new skills and passions to some of the most disadvantaged children. With the goal of promoting and supporting self-determination and individual expression, regardless of personal conditions, gender, ‘race’/ethnicity, socio-economic status or culture. The workshops involved the participation of over 300 children aged 6 to 15 in seven centres distributed throughout the national territory (Catania, Milan, Naples, Palermo, Rome, Turin, and Venice).

Two workshops were dedicated to stars, celestial atlases and constellations: *Stars in Perspective* (ages 6-10) and *Let’s Light Up Constellations* (ages 11-15). Another two workshops focused on the Moon and lunar atlases: *The Moon Phases Box* (ages 6-10) and *Let’s Build the Moon Soil* (ages

11-15). Solar System atlases and Mars were also covered, and finally, two workshops covered the topic of planetary images: *Long Live Resolution* (ages 6-10) and *Let's Observe the Mars "Canals"* (ages 11-15). In this presentation, we discuss the evaluation of the three workshops conducted with the youngest children group, corresponding to ages 6 to 10.

2. Evaluation Methodology

To assess both the effectiveness of the activities and the satisfaction level of children, a brief survey was administered to all participants before and after the activities, with a series of questions related to the topics covered in the workshops. The analysis of the collected data helped understand the participants' knowledge level and allowed for improvements to be made to the activities, enhancing their engagement and efficacy. Participation in the survey was fully anonymous and optional: children could choose to answer a few questions, all of them or none, as they pleased. Overall, all children found the activities interesting and fun. However, the initial evaluation questionnaires were heavily text-based, with multiple-choice answers. In some areas, children could read and answer questions easily, but in other areas, children's literacy was very low, making this evaluation unfitting to the context. During the first workshop, the facilitators realised that they needed to read the questions and multiple-choice answers to the children, breaking them down to their basic concepts but basically influencing the answer, with a high risk of introducing bias and false positives. To overcome this bias, we asked them to illustrate their answers to some questions related to the workshop content. Graphical representation is very powerful and widely used in evaluation with very young children and in cases of language barriers. In this case, we demonstrate that graphical evaluations allow us to overcome communication issues caused by low literacy and cultural barriers in contexts of social marginalisation. A total of 70 pre- and 45 post-activity questionnaires were collected at the end of the various workshops. Pre- and post-questionnaires had similar questions phrased in a different way, to make the activity less repetitive. All pre-questionnaires included the question "What does an astronomer do?" and all post-questionnaires included the question "Did you have fun?". Other questions varied depending on the content of the workshop (stars, Moon phases, planets). Moreover, the sample of children who completed the pre-activity questionnaire is not the same as (and is larger than) the post-activity sample. Therefore, a full pre/post analysis was not feasible. Instead, we conducted a case study analysis to compare responses and identify overall trends.

3. Case Study Analysis

One of the workshops, *Stars in Perspective*, explored the distances of stars and constellations. Contrary to common perception, constellations are not composed of stars that are close to each other but rather of stars located at different distances from Earth. An interesting result from the evaluation of this activity comes from comparing children's representations of a star before and after the workshop. In the pre/post questionnaires of this workshop, we asked children to draw a star. All pre-activity drawings featured the classical five-pointed star, reflecting a common misconception. However, in the two post-activity drawings, a new representation emerged. Whereas in one drawing the classical five-pointed star persisted, in the other drawing, a child reproduced what he or she perceived during the experience: stars are sphere-shaped objects (mounted on a stick). This shift in representation is rich in meaning and provides additional information on the child's understanding that cannot be captured through multiple-choice or open-ended questions.

Another workshop, *The Moon Phases Box*, explored the origin of Moon phases. At the start

(a)

(b)

Figure 1. On the left is a picture from the workshop. On the right is a representation of a star drawing after the workshop. On the left (a) the classical five-pointed star, aligned with the common misconception. On the right (b) the new representation, the star is a sphere-shaped object mounted on a stick.

Figure 2: The graph on the left shows how children's drawings are distributed. 34.6% of children drew a Moon with craters and/or maria, 11.5% a full Moon without craters, while 23.1% showed a Moon in its recent phase. On the right is an example of a drawing of the Moon with its craters.

of the activity, a questionnaire was administered to assess the children's initial understanding of the concept and to slightly tailor the activity. Only the pre-activity questionnaire included a drawing question, which provided valuable insights into the children's representations of the Moon. These representations fell into three main categories: the most common was a single circle with coloured dots representing craters and/or maria; the second depicted a full circle (without craters) alongside crescent moons; and the third consisted of a single crescent moon. The three types of drawings convey different conceptions about the Moon. The first one reveals the idea of the Moon as a single sphere-shaped object with irregularities on its surface that are clearly visible. The second and third ones unveil an idea of the Moon strictly correlated with its phases, which make it appear in different shapes.

The fact that some children chose to depict all of them in the same drawings (as opposed to the third representation) may raise some doubts about their knowledge of the Moon as a single object. Indeed, this kind of drawing can be interpreted as either distinct versions of the same object or different kinds of Moons. This reflection led us to emphasise during the activity that the Moon is a single spherical object whose appearance changes due to variations in its illumination.

Finally, the *Long live resolution* workshop, which focused on images of Solar System planets, included a graphical question asking children to draw a telescope or binoculars. Only pre-activity questionnaires were collected, which included seven drawings. Most of the drawings depicted a single tube-like instrument. In three cases, the drawings showed a more detailed shape,

suggesting the presence of distinct components such as an eyepiece or lenses.

Conclusions

Direct experiences from astronomy hands-on workshops conducted in communities on the outskirts of big Italian cities, marked by social marginalisation, high rates of school dropout, low literacy and the presence of non-native Italian speakers, have shown the power of drawing as a non-verbal form of evaluation. Through drawing, everyone can express their experiences, emotions, and levels of learning, offering a valid tool to understand the impact of the activities. This approach allows for an inclusive and intuitive evaluation capable of involving everyone regardless of their linguistic competencies.

The Challenges of Evaluation of Astronomy Activities in the Croatian Educational System

Speaker: Danijela Takac, astronomy and physics teacher, Croatia

Collaborator: Ana Marija Zazinović (physics and astronomy teacher)

This talk explores the complexities involved in teaching and evaluating astronomy in the Croatian educational system, where astronomy is primarily offered as an extracurricular activity at the primary and secondary school levels. The talk highlights the multifaceted role of educators who integrate astronomy projects into physics and technology curricula. By guiding students through experiential learning, teachers facilitate a deeper understanding of scientific principles. This research identifies challenges faced by educators in evaluating astronomy activities, particularly in primary and middle schools where formative assessments are predominant. We will present effective evaluation rubrics, tests, and examples of best practices adopted by teachers across various grades in Croatia.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/Nh84Qi31d8k>

The Croatian educational system comprises primary, middle, and secondary schools. Currently, astronomy is not a formal subject in primary and secondary education; instead, it is offered as an extracurricular activity. In secondary schools, astronomy may be included as a facultative subject.

One significant event in the realm of astronomy education is the National Astronomy Competition held in Croatia. Teachers endeavour to motivate students by integrating astronomy into the

physics and technology curricula. They emphasise that through hands-on projects, students can “become scientists” and gain insight into the exciting everyday work of real astronomers. Once students select their project topic, they conduct online research, develop a plan for experimental measurements, and prepare stargazing charts.

Teachers bear the responsibility of preparing students for both the written exam and providing mentorship throughout the project development process. High school students tend to be more independent and easier to mentor, whereas 5th and 6th graders require guidance through each step. A common challenge is the students’ mathematical background, particularly in statistics, alongside their limited understanding of the scientific method. Teachers often need to be creative when selecting project topics, simplifying concepts for younger students while ensuring the projects include necessary measurements, calculations, and error analysis. This aspect is more manageable in the final two years of middle school, where students have taken physics and chemistry classes that foster an understanding of the scientific process. Nevertheless, the project component of the competition is both demanding and rewarding. Students dedicate one to two months of intensive work, learning far more than they would in regular classes. In fact, the Astronomy Competition is one of the most rigorous STEM competitions within the Croatian educational system. In comparison, the National Physics Competition distinguishes between theoretical (exam-based) and project-based categories, while astronomy combines both elements.

Throughout our experience teaching science and astronomy in the Croatian educational system, we have identified significant gaps in the curriculum, particularly between middle school and the start of high school, as well as between high school and university. These gaps contribute to insufficient student knowledge of STEM subjects. However, students who participate in astronomy as an extracurricular activity demonstrate greater success in bridging these gaps. Our research shows that those who engage in astronomy classes starting from middle school excel even more. Teachers who integrate astronomy activities across various science subjects—such as physics, chemistry, technology, and biology—have noted an increased interest in STEM. Consequently, these students are more inclined to apply to technological and space-related universities.

Teachers face substantial challenges when evaluating astronomy activities in schools. In primary and middle schools, formative evaluations are primarily conducted, whereas high schools employ both formative and summative assessments. Through our research, we aim to present rubrics and methodologies for evaluating different activities across various grades in Croatia, along with examples of successful practices.

Perception Measurement Instrument on the Use of Real Astronomical Data in the School Classroom

Speaker: Irma Fuentes-Morales, Universidad de Santiago de Chile, Chile

Collaborators: Javiera Núñez (Universidad de Playa Ancha, Valparaíso) and Carla Hernández (Universidad de Santiago de Chile)

In this work, we present the design of an instrument to evaluate the perception of students before and after participating in an activity involving the use of astronomical data in the subject of physics, in order to determine whether teaching astronomy can motivate students in science learning. The instrument was validated through expert judgment. In addition, this test was initially applied to a 9th and 10th grade physics class. The test results aligned with expectations, indicating that students value the use of real astronomical data in the classroom.

Talk link: https://youtu.be/1RZ_ecNKIq4

Introduction

Astronomy has the potential to create interest in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) careers, and it involves many aspects of knowledge, such as cultural, technological and scientific, among others (Salimpour et al., 2021). In the Chilean context, astronomy becomes more relevant because we have the advantage of being one of the best countries for astronomical observation, however, the knowledge of astronomy in Chile at a general level is very low. Some studies have found that both eighth- and fourth-grade secondary school students, and even teachers, have alternative or erroneous conceptions of astronomy (Rabanales & Ortega, 2021).

Based on this background at the national level, the Interdisciplinary Center for Research in Astrophysics and Space Sciences (CIRAS) of the University of Santiago de Chile (USACH) developed a research initiative in Astronomy for Education in 2021. The initiative aims to address science education and understanding through the creation of didactic sequences that bridge the gap between astronomical research and the classroom. It seeks to strengthen didactics in accordance with the contents of the school curriculum, and using real astronomical data for its development in scientific subjects of secondary education.

Corroborating that the activities carried out in the classroom are effective is of paramount importance, as "evaluation not only indicates whether objectives have been achieved, but also explains why they have or not have been achieved" (Guerra, 2003). Therefore, this research focuses on developing a tool to accurately and consistently measure the effectiveness of these educational activities and assess whether they are fulfilling their intended purpose.

Methodology

Based on this background, the research question addressed in this work is:

What characteristics should an assessment instrument have to effectively measure students' perceptions and learning about science in activities based on real astronomical data?

To design the appropriate assessment instrument for the proposed activity and to ensure its effectiveness, it is crucial to consider and build on prior experience. We rely on the *Evaluation Framework & Toolkit* published by the International Astronomical Union (IAU) in 2024, which provides guidance for evaluating activities that use astronomy in education. This handbook offers a theoretical foundation and a set of data collection tools that "help astronomy educators to systematically evaluate their educational programmes and develop evidence-based practices that can be applied in a variety of contexts".

The manual highlights different data collection tools for assessing the impact of astronomy education activities. One of the recommended instruments is the *Astronomy and Science Student Attitudes (ASSA)* questionnaire: A short review and validation of a new instrument questionnaire by Bartlett et al. (2018). This tool measures students' attitudes towards astronomy and science across eight main categories: interest in astronomy, interest in science outside school, practical work in science, teacher actions in science, perceptions of science ability, future aspirations in science, benefits of science, and personal relevance of school science.

For this purpose, we based the creation of the instrument on the ASSA instrument by Bartlett et al. (2018), as it is the most relevant to the area being investigated. Additionally, it is validated, reliable, and recommended by the IAU in its manual for evaluating astronomical activities.

The questionnaire was selected as the evaluation instrument due to its ability to collect data systematically and in detail. To obtain comparative data, we designed a pre-test and a post-test that integrated closed, open, and Likert-type questions, enabling a wide range of responses while ensuring quick completion. Additionally, we incorporated recommendations from the IAU manual for evaluating astronomy education activities, specifically we considered the suggestions: "Include some open questions to give participants more freedom to express their answers", and to use the pre- and post-tests to "compare the data from the two time points to see if there are differences".

The pre-test consisted of 23 questions, including closed, open, and Likert-type questions, divided into the following categories: student characteristics, perception of science skills, perception of interest in astronomy, practical work in science, and future aspirations. The post-test consisted of 26 questions of the same style and covered the same categories, with the addition of an item gathering feedback on factors that may have influenced the activity's effectiveness. The questions focused on collecting information after the activity, however some questions were repeated in order to evaluate changes with respect to the pre-test. Examples of questions from the instrument are shown in Table 1.

Results

Validation by expert judgment and classroom implementation

To date, four experts in the areas of science education and physics teaching have been consulted. However, we still need to engage experts in astronomy didactics, which has proven challenging due to the limited exploration of this field in Chile.

Item	Question	Type of question	Source
Perception about science	Do you consider yourself good at science?	Close	Own <u>elab.</u>
	Do you consider yourself good at physics?	Close	Own <u>elab.</u>
	Science subjects are where I do best.	Likert	ASSA
Perception about Astronomy	I am very interested in astronomy	Likert	ASSA
	I would like to pursue a career in astronomy	Likert	ASSA
	People who study astronomy do complex work	Likert	Own <u>elab.</u>
	There is a relationship between physics and astronomy.	Likert	Own <u>elab.</u>
Practical work	Have you worked with real data in the classroom?	Close	Own <u>elab.</u>
	How often do you use real data as part of your classroom activities?	Likert	Own <u>elab.</u>
	I learn science better when I do practical work	Likert	ASSA
	I would like more practical work in my science classes.	Likert	ASSA
	How did you like working with real astronomy data in your physics course?	Open	Own <u>elab.</u>
Future aspirations	I would like to study something related to science in the future.	Likert	ASSA
	I would like to learn more science in the future.	Likert	ASSA
Feedback	Are there any factors that made it difficult for you to learn?	Close	Own <u>elab.</u>
	Describe in more detail the factors that hindered your learning, if desired	Open	Own <u>elab.</u>

Table 1. Categories and questions of both the pre- and post-instrument created to measure the impact of the application of activities using real astronomy data in the school classroom.

The judges expressed a lack of consensus, primarily due to their perception that the test was comprised of questions of a relatively generic nature. Nevertheless, we argue that the test should include general questions, as it is intended to be administered after a wide variety of activities across multiple science subjects at the secondary level.

Furthermore, a preliminary validation was carried out by implementing the activity in a classroom setting. The preliminary results suggest that the activity has the potential to positively influence students' perceptions of the relationship between physics and astronomy. Additionally, the use of real data has been observed to enhance students' understanding of the subject matter within the context of physics classes.

Conclusions

This work requires further validation before it can be considered as a tool for use in classroom activities involving real data. We aim to involve a larger number of judges who can review this test, and, given the limited number of specialists in Chile, we extend an open invitation to the OAE to assist us in this process. In addition, we are in the process of collecting data based on the implementation of a physics guide that applies Kepler's third law to exoplanets. By next year, we hope to have enough information to launch this instrument enabling educators worldwide to use it in their classrooms.

References:

- Bartlett, S., Fitzgerald, M. T., McKinnon, D. H., Danaia, L., & Lazendic-Galloway, J. (2018). Astronomy and Science Student Attitudes (ASSA): A short review and validation of a new instrument. *Journal Of Astronomy and Earth Sciences Education/Journal Of Astronomy & Earth Sciences Education*, 5(1), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.19030/jaese.v5i1.10190>
- Escobar-Pérez, J., & Cuervo-Martínez, A. (2008). Validez de contenido y juicio de expertos: una aproximación a su utilización. *Avances En Medición*, 6(1), 27-36.

- Guerra, M. Á. S. (2003). Una flecha en la diana: la evaluación como aprendizaje. *Andalucía Educativa*.
- Rabanales Loyola, Felipe, & Vanegas Ortega, Carlos. (2021). Concepciones alternativas sobre astronomía en estudiantes de educación básica y media de la Región Metropolitana de Chile. *Estudios pedagógicos (Valdivia)*, 47(2), 247-268.
- Salimpour, S., Bartlett, S., Fitzgerald, M. T., et al. (2021). The gateway science: A review of astronomy in the OECD school curricula, including China and South Africa. *Research in Science Education*, 51, 975–996.

Enhancing Skill Development in Digitally Instructed Hands-On - Minds-On Astronomy Lessons

Speaker: Ilham Bouisaghouane, Leiden University and Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences, The Netherlands

Collaborators: Bert Bredeweg (Centre for Applied Education Research, Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences & Informatics Institute, Faculty of Science, University of Amsterdam), Joanna Holt (Centre for Applied Education Research, Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences, Netherlands Research School for Astronomy), and Pedro Russo (Leiden Observatory, Leiden University)

Building on the Minds-On project, this study developed the online module “Celestial Bodies” to enhance hands-on and minds-on learning, providing students with individualised feedback prompts to monitor and identify weaknesses in their understanding. The lesson centred on classifying 14 celestial bodies based on three properties, with the guidance of the online module, a map, and cards. This study aimed to (1) enhance student engagement with the software, and (2) assess the impact of guided instructions and feedback prompts. We introduce our interactive lesson, present our findings, and discuss their benefits in upper primary education classes to enhance student engagement, concept learning, emphasising enhanced integration of minds-on and hands-on activities.

Embedded Participatory Evaluation to Assess Mission Embedded Education Outcomes

Speaker: Sanlyn Buxner, Planetary Science Institute, USA

Collaborator: Cherilynn Morrow (NASA PUNCH Outreach Director, Boulder)

The public engagement (PE) program embedded within the NASA PUNCH mission extends outreach to primary and secondary classroom students and educators. Our Ancient and Modern Sun-watching outreach theme helps to ensure that the science of heliophysics is more personally and cross-culturally relevant to a broader diversity of learners. The mission cultivates intentional collaboration with scientists, Indigenous and Spanish-speaking youth and families, Girl Scouts, and Blind and Low-Vision (BLV) learners. Evaluation is conducted collaboratively among PE team members, institutional partners including planetariums and science centres interested in reaching classrooms, and the external evaluator (S. Buxner), who is also an active astronomy educator. Aligned with research about how people learn, evaluation is conducted from a participatory framework and includes ongoing conversations and collaboration that are sensitive to new opportunities beyond traditional front-end needs assessments. The multi-institutional nature of the collaboration allows for pilot testing in classrooms in multiple communities and in different settings to best meet the needs of collaborating communities.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/MkBhHwDVfKc>

Introduction: The public engagement (PE) program embedded within the NASA PUNCH mission extends outreach to primary and secondary classroom students and educators.

The NASA PUNCH Mission Public Engagement Program is organised around an Ancient and Modern Sun-watching outreach theme to ensure that the science of heliophysics is more personally and cross-culturally relevant to a broader diversity of learners both inside and outside the classroom.

The theme portrays NASA exploration of the Sun as a natural extension of humanity's age-old dedication to observing and learning to live in harmony with the Sun's cycles. Our educational activities are centred on the personal solar observations of the learner and their interconnections with both ancestral Sun-watching and NASA Sun-watching missions including NASA's PUNCH Mission and the Parker Solar Probe.

The PUNCH mission cultivates intentional collaboration among scientists, Indigenous and Spanish-speaking youth and families, Girl Scouts, and Blind and Low-Vision (BLV) learners

on developing educational activities that are aligned with research on how people learn. Partners also include classroom educators plus planetariums and science centres that are reaching classroom teachers and students.

Traditional evaluation of educational activities involves front-end, formative, and summative components enacted by an evaluator who solely collects data for reporting purposes. Evaluation for PUNCH Outreach addresses these evaluative stages but with some novel twists worthy of sharing and discussing with the broader community.

Selecting a Participatory Evaluator who is also an Astronomy Education Professional: PUNCH Outreach leadership (author Morrow) selected an evaluator (author Buxner) who wanted to collaborate on enacting a non-traditional, participatory approach to evaluation. We needed a low-cost plan that was nevertheless effective in ensuring the development of high-quality products of benefit to all learners.

In our participatory model, the evaluator regularly attends team meetings and participates in mission activities, including first-person field-testing of educational products. Her extensive background and networking in space science and astronomy education offers a capacity for confidently gathering important data and insights from a wide spectrum of participants, from school children trying out our products to research scientists contributing to our outreach efforts. This participatory approach supports relationship development and ongoing conversations with diverse team members and advisors regarding opportunities to collaborate and amplify the impact of the project.

An evaluator who is well connected in astronomy education can advise on new synergies for the public engagement effort including places to present, publish, and partner.

Cultivating an Evaluation Mindset among Team Members: A benefit of an embedded evaluator is one who works closely with the rest of the PE team to ensure that evaluation is conducted by all members of the team for the good of the project. A sole evaluator cannot be in all the places needed to collect data, both for time and monetary reasons. Our evaluator helps support and train all members to collect needed data when visiting schools or conducting teacher workshops, along with helping them critically reflect on that data. Project leadership helps to cultivate an evaluative mindset among team members asking them to provide “after-action reports” that reflect on lessons learned and ideas for improvement while field testing prototype activities. Some results and insights can be shared across the team and immediately implemented.

Including Collaborators not Targeting Audiences: We collaborate with historically marginalised populations to create products of benefit for everyone. Mission outreach team members test activities in classrooms and with teachers to gather feedback about how they can be improved. By cultivating an ongoing relationship during activity design and revision, the mission ensures that field testing is not just perfunctory but is a central part of the relationship. By this means, what other projects may refer to as “target audiences” instead become NASA collaborators.

Moving Beyond “Front-End” Evaluation of Needs to Ongoing Conversations about Opportunities: Traditional “needs assessments” as part of front-end evaluation is a valuable way to strengthen proposals for funding. PUNCH Outreach moves beyond this traditional structure to include ongoing conversation and continuous relationship building by team members with

collaborators. Our participatory framework for evaluation includes attention to the team's ongoing conversations and collaborations with historically marginalised populations that are sensitive to new opportunities beyond the results of traditional front-end needs assessments. With support from the evaluator, team members are attuned to recognise needs and opportunities of collaborators in an ongoing way that moves beyond a single “front-end” assessment and allows for new opportunities to emerge while the project is ongoing.

Examples of Products Created and Revised Through Collaboration with Classrooms

Figure 1. Seeing with Your Hands: This is a set of thermoform tactile-art representations of the solar corona. These thermoforms were originally designed as an inquiry for blind and low vision learners. Through ongoing pilot testing in classrooms with blind and low vision students in two different communities, the thermoform tactiles have been adapted for use with an activity called *Seeing With Your Hands* that benefits not only blind and low vision learners, but also sighted learners.

Figure 2. PUNCH Team Cards: This is a set of cards (in both digital and physical formats) that feature diverse individuals who each support the NASA PUNCH mission. The team members featured help demonstrate to students the wide range of skills and backgrounds needed to make a NASA mission successful. Each person showcases not only what they do at work but also what they like to do in their free time. This broadens the humanity of team card participants, providing students with inspiring and relatable role models. The PUNCH Team cards have been carefully developed in collaboration with each person featured and with those who field-tested the cards in classrooms and Girl Scout troops. The Cards and associated activities have undergone several revisions to adapt for a variety of age groups. Alongside the cards are ways for students to engage by making their own “team card” on a template.

Leveraging Formative Evaluation Opportunities across a Multi-Institutional Collaborative: The NASA PUNCH Public Engagement effort is made up of multiple institutions across the Southwest

of the United States. Having multiple core partners with a spectrum of ongoing educational events, provides many more natural opportunities for field-testing of products with students and teachers in multiple states leading to products like our 3-Hole-PUNCH pinhole projector that have been used across the United States.

Taking Summative Evaluation Beyond the Numbers: Summative evaluation includes, but transcends, just reporting numbers of individuals reached. Our summative assessment is intentionally including attention to how the project is benefiting team members, partner institutions, consultants, advisors, and the broader community in an enduring way. Key insights and lessons learned are shared not only for the project but for the community at large.

Pedagogical Advisor and Couple for the Teaching of Astronomy at Elementary School

Speaker: Fernando Ariel Karaseur, Ministerio de Educación de la Ciudad Autónoma de Buenos Aires and Universidad del Centro de la Provincia de Buenos Aires, Argentina

Collaborators: María Cristina Iglesias (Escuelas Intensificadas en Actividades Científicas) and Alejandro Gangui (IAFE-CONICET / UBA)

We discuss the joint work between elementary school teachers and science teachers in the planning and implementation of interdisciplinary proposals motivated by astronomy content. We describe the advisory and pedagogical partner functions from the perspective of two technical-pedagogical assistant teachers from scientific-activities intensified schools in the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires. We present and discuss some of their proposals based on the results of an instrument for evaluating attitudes towards the teaching of astronomy by practising teachers and student teachers in which we link aspects of personal and school biography, especially during initial and continuous teacher training, with the aim of obtaining categories to analyse and contribute to the redesign of training devices.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/APp0hFYV09I>

Intensification in Scientific Activities (IAC) is part of the schools' program with intensification in one of the fields of knowledge offered by the Ministry of Education of the Government of the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires to primary school students (ages 6 to 12). The main objective of IAC is to enrich and deepen knowledge about natural science topics prescribed in

the jurisdiction's curricular design. It has its own curricular framework that provides guidelines for this intensification^[1]. With a history of about 20 years, it has undergone adjustments and reformulations in teaching proposals, work organisation, types of institutional support required, and other aspects. Since 2010, the hours allocated to intensification (five hours) have been combined with the four hours already dedicated to teaching natural sciences in any school in the jurisdiction, representing 20% of classroom time. Currently, the program includes 22 schools with Intensification in Scientific Activities distributed across the 24 districts of Buenos Aires. Within each IAC school, at least one new staff member is added: the Pedagogical Technical Assistant (ATP). This role is often filled by science teachers (primarily biology) or experienced primary school teachers. The ATP's main responsibilities include providing advice^[2] collaborating with classroom teachers, both inside and outside the classroom, and supporting the leadership team in developing training experiences and fostering the identity of the IAC.

Based on over 15 years of experience working in primary education, we can affirm that natural sciences generally have a limited presence in primary schools in our jurisdiction compared to subjects like Language and Mathematics. This disparity is more pronounced in the early years of primary education. Moreover, being a teacher at an IAC school does not necessarily mean dedicating more hours to teaching natural sciences. Within the subject, astronomical content is the most neglected compared to other topics, such as living beings or materials. From their early training stages in teacher training programs, surveyed teachers report feeling more confident with non-astronomical content, viewing astronomical topics as more challenging and abstract. This perception often translates into a fear of teaching astronomy incorrectly (from conceptual, didactic, or epistemological standpoints). Nevertheless, teachers also recognise astronomy as a science that engages, invites curiosity, and inspires enthusiasm. In this context, the following statements from a colleague in initial training stand out as exceptional:

“Given the training I received, I feel confident planning a sequence on astronomy, prioritising systematic observation and experimentation intertwined with the ways of knowing contemplated in the current approach.”

This situation becomes evident when new teachers join an IAC school and report having little experience in teaching astronomy, particularly in the final three grades of primary education. This is surprising given that, over the past decade, the Government of the City of Buenos Aires has produced and distributed teaching materials, such as didactic guides and workbooks, and implemented teacher training programs.

What happens when classroom teachers feel consistently supported in their classroom decisions, week after week? The ATP intervenes with direction and intention, seeking to expand and diversify teaching strategies to enhance learning. By proposing new perspectives and inspiring different approaches to teaching, we begin to notice changes in our colleagues' attitudes. These changes are much more evident among those colleagues who continue their roles in IAC schools. While some may initially approach the support system with apprehension, fear, or reluctance, they eventually develop a genuine pedagogical relationship of trust. As a result, they express willingness to explore content areas they might never have taught—such as astronomy—or to approach them in a less expository manner. This includes systematising problem-based activities, dedicating more time for children to engage with the sky and space through direct observation, recording, and analysis.

On this, some surveyed IAC teachers who have not had the opportunity to plan astronomical content in their initial training, state:

“Having support in planning from the ATP has helped with doubts I had. Reading texts, so the didactic transposition is not erroneous and gives children the opportunity to get closer to science, which many may not have known before, or at least to spark curiosity about it. One former student is currently studying space engineering.”

“Going through the IAC experience... expanded my knowledge and made me see natural sciences from a different perspective.”

“I learned a lot about astronomy as the topic was not covered in teacher training. The didactics of astronomy fascinated me! Incredible materials that I remember and try to implement, or I share with colleagues so they can use them.”

Even among those surveyed colleagues who have incorporated astronomical content into their teaching careers, many acknowledge the ATP's support in helping them deepen and enrich their instruction.

A colleague with 13 years of experience in an IAC school, now serves as a pedagogical coordinator in other schools in Buenos Aires. She provides testimony that highlights the importance of situated and periodic support she received during her time as an IAC classroom teacher, as well as the critical role of initial and ongoing teacher training in the area:

“Both topics (astronomy and forces and movements) are often overshadowed by others, usually ‘touched upon superficially,’ or not addressed at all, perhaps due to ignorance or fear. From my position as cycle coordinator, I see the need to support teachers in incorporating these topics into their planning.”

The same colleague, reflecting on her experience as an IAC teacher, said:

“(The ATPs) help think through the sequence, activities, and resources to be used, supporting the teaching work. Since we are generalists, we often do not possess knowledge of astronomy, and over the years, we gradually incorporate it into our teaching. I know teachers who have moved schools and continue to implement IAC sequences in their didactic proposals.”

Based on the examples provided, we pose the following questions: Would the support for practising teachers, as described by the previous teacher, be perceived as necessary if they had not experienced a work format like the IAC? Furthermore, is it possible to think of a new teacher training model that incorporates elements of the IAC format?

References:

- [1] Intensificación en actividades científicas : marco curricular, escuela primaria / dirigido por Gabriela Azar. - 1a ed. - Ciudad Autónoma de Buenos Aires : Ministerio de Educación del Gobierno de la Ciudad Autónoma de Buenos Aires, 2015. Available [here](#).
- [2] Nicastro, S. y Andreozzi, M. (2013). El trabajo de asesoramiento en Asesoramiento

pedagógico en acción. La novela del asesor. Paidós.

- [3] Porlán, R. (1999). Hacia un modelo de enseñanza-aprendizaje de las ciencias por investigación en Kaufman, M. y Fumagalli, L. (comp.). Enseñar Ciencias Naturales. Reflexiones y propuestas didácticas. Paidós.

Mediterranean Co-Design: Evaluating the Project FRESCO (Florence RESidency COdesign)

Speaker: Stefania Varano, Istituto Nazionale di Astrofisica (INAF), Italy

Collaborators: Silvia Casu, Sara Ricciardi and Alessandra Zanazzi (INAF and OAE Center Italy), and Sophie Bartlett (Cardiff University and OAE Heidelberg)

The FRESCO project co-designs playful resources for children up to 12 years old within an international community. It focuses on creative learning (specifically Game Based Learning and Playful Learning) in STEAM, Astronomy and Astrophysics. Our initial focus was on specific actions: building a community and evaluating participants' perceptions of their co-design and co-development experiences, and assessing their views on the value and effectiveness of these processes. To evaluate these aspects, we have developed a system that incorporates documentation (online activity recording and observation) and questionnaires. The system has been applied throughout the process, collecting pre- and post-activity evidence to track changes related to our research questions.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/Q61BRYIyph8>

The Project and its Organisation

FRESCO (Florence RESidency and Co-design) is a project promoted by the OAE Center Italy to co-design playful resources for children up to 12 years old within an international community. It builds on the OAE Italy's previous co-design experiences in the Mediterranean. The project included several rounds of co-design and a final residency. As the name suggests, the final residency was originally planned to take place in Florence, Italy, but it was ultimately held in Istanbul, Turkey, from October 13-16, preceding the Mediterranean regional Shaw-IAU Workshop on Astronomy for Education (MASTED).

Regarding the theme of the co-design, we decided to explore new approaches:

- Expanding the network beyond the Mediterranean to involve a larger community.

- Focusing on innovative child-centred educational practices such as Play-Based Learning (PBL) and Game-Based Learning (GBL). Our experience in these fields has shown that these activities are highly effective for enhancing the learning experience, as they actively engage children in the learning process.

We issued a call to all NAECs (national astronomy education coordinators) worldwide and formed a group of 10 participating countries: Turkey, Syria, Nigeria, Egypt, Pakistan, India, Portugal, Morocco, Greece, Lebanon.

We began our collaboration by hosting two seminars led by experts in the respective fields to set a common understanding for our future work and define our interpretations of PBL and GBL. After the initial meeting to discuss and share proposals, we divided into two groups: one focused on designing game-based learning activities, and the other on playful activities. From April to October, we held more than 10 online meetings. During the residency, we worked in person for three days, making significant progress in finalising the process and activities. Finally, we were able to conduct preliminary testing of these activities with other Mediterranean NAECs participating in MASTED.

Evaluating a Process

The evaluation presented here aimed to assess participants' perceptions of their personal experience of co-design and their views on the value and effectiveness of such a process. It was an ongoing and iterative process, since we were aiming at spotting and assessing possible changes in the participants' feelings and perspectives.

The main research questions that drove our evaluation were the following.

- Are participants feeling comfortable in the co-design process? Were they expecting something different? Is the process changing their perspective in any way?
- Is the process perceived as effective in producing somehow better resources than the ones that could have been developed separately?

To establish a baseline for our evaluation, we developed a method to assess the community's initial status concerning our research questions. The first was to assess the previous beliefs about what the co-design process was expected to entail. The second key assessment focussed on identifying expectations regarding how this process might alter the initially proposed activities, which served as the foundation for the entire process.

During the co-design process, we consistently ensured that the activities we were developing aligned with a collectively agreed-upon definition of PBL and GBL. To achieve this, we first assessed participants' initial knowledge of PBL and GBL methodologies, including their nature and objectives. Specifically, we aimed for all participants to have a comparable understanding of the methodologies we intended to implement in the co-design process. We approached this assessment in a non-interrogative and non-demanding manner, aiming to facilitate a process of community knowledge and experience building without being over instructional. Since participants indicated limited prior experience with the proposed methods, the seminars we provided served as an effective way to establish a common foundation.

The evaluation of the final product was not the focus of this work; it was envisioned as a

separate and subsequent step, to be conducted with different communities, specifically groups of students experiencing the activities in their classrooms across the participating countries. The groundwork for this product evaluation was laid during the MASTED workshop, where we tested our prototypes with the colleagues in attendance.

The Evaluation System

The FResCo project brings together many people who initially do not know each other and employs a working method (co-design) and a methodological approach (game-based and playful learning) that are not universally acknowledged. Evaluating such a process is a complex task. To address this, we designed an evaluation plan in collaboration with Sophie Bartlett, an evaluation expert from the OAE. We identified various evaluation tools tailored to different aspects of the project. The final choice of tools was influenced by the working strategy, which was conducted entirely online during its initial phase and only transitioned to in-person activities during the Istanbul residency in the final days.

To gather evidence and data on our co-design process we used the following tools:

Surveys: on pre-existing knowledge of the process and educational methodology. We use cumulative online 'jamboards' to collect disciplinary aspects proposed by participants, previous ideas and preconceptions about methodological approaches, and fundamental values on which to base the educational action. The survey was very useful to understand the initial level of confidence and/or experience of participants of PBL and GBL, as well as to build a shared perspective.

Questionnaires: to assess changes in participants' feelings, perceptions, knowledge, and expectations before, during, and after the process, we used reflective journals as a tool. We distributed four online questionnaires to participants, including a mix of unique and repeated questions (i.e. about comfort levels, inspirations, and changes during the process). The primary goal was to encourage self-reflection and identify strengths and areas for improvement.

Observations: throughout all phases (both online and in person), we recorded the sessions and took detailed notes to evaluate various aspects of the process, such as team dynamics, the flow of collaboration, decision-making processes, and any possible disagreements among participants.

Focus group: to gather qualitative insights into participants' experiences—particularly regarding the efficacy of network community building, collaboration, challenges faced, process efficiency, feasibility, and replicability—we dedicated a final session to a focus group with all participants. This session was limited to one hour to allow time for the concluding part of our in-person interaction and work. We started the open discussion with the following questions and recorded all audio from the interviews.

Preliminary Results

As of this presentation, we have just concluded the FRESCO residency and can share only very preliminary results.

The atmosphere in the online meetings has progressively become more positive and effective, while the in-person residency has undoubtedly facilitated the process, smoothing out some

challenges encountered along the way. A key challenge that emerged is the efficiency of this process, which requires patience and time for results to fully materialise. During the early stages of the co-design process, some participants felt overwhelmed by the variety and richness of the proposals, expressing doubt about the process' ability to produce a tangible outcome. Additionally, some participants shared that they had to make significant compromises on their initial ideas to contribute a shared, collaborative product.

As we approached the final stages, just before the residency, participants noted that meeting by meeting, the product was becoming more tangible. This progress was attributed to the impressive group effort and the rich exchange of ideas among all members. This collaborative dynamic allowed for the gradual emergence of a shared vision. One participant's diary entry stands out, capturing the group's general feeling during the conclusion of the online sessions: "I'm happy that we are getting somewhere. In the last round, we developed a draft of the final game and I felt confident that we can really do it. Co-design needs time and patience, but it's a great way to exchange ideas and learn from each other."

This reflection embodies the spirit of co-design: while it may be a slow and sometimes uncertain process, it fosters a collaborative environment where participants can learn, evolve, and ultimately create something meaningful for everyone. A particularly significant entry from one of the reflective journals states: "As a matter of fact not only my ideas are changing, my way of thinking, the way I research for certain definitions and topics, the way I discuss with my group members, and the way we convince each other. This co-design was a wonderful experience for me to develop and grow. So yes, a change for the better and for the more collaborative approach".

Beyond embracing the co-design process as a form of professional growth, participants also recognised its intrinsic value in improving educational design itself: "Yes of course, there's a considerable change in my initial idea! I improved the initial proposal based on the input from different colleagues, and the second version still needs new improvements based on their new input. Thanks to these co-design meetings, I learned a lot about educational game design".

Assessing Learning in Astronomy: Methods and Tools in the Context of Astronomical Peripatetism

Speaker: José Antonio D'Santiago García, Universidad Nacional Experimental Rafael María Baralt, Venezuela

This work presents an innovative approach to assessing learning in astronomy, utilising the Flipped Classroom methodology and Astronomical Peripatetism. Various assessment techniques are employed, including formative and summative evaluations, live observations, and interactive discussions. The goal is to measure the effectiveness of this methodology in students' understanding and retention of astronomical concepts. The collected data shows that students not only improve in theoretical assessments but also demonstrate a greater ability to apply their knowledge in practical and real-world situations.

Talk link: https://youtu.be/wchNtVS_xfs

The flipped classroom encourages students' autonomy and responsibility, as they are in charge of studying theoretical content on their own, using resources such as videos and readings provided in advance. In this way, students have the opportunity to acquire an initial understanding of astronomical concepts on their own, allowing them to develop a deeper and more personalised understanding of the material.

In-person sessions are transformed into active and experiential learning experiences through the Astronomical Peripatetism methodology, where the traditional classroom is moved to open spaces and the night sky, observed through telescopes, becomes the blackboard. In this context, students not only observe the astronomical phenomena they have previously studied, but they participate in debates and group discussions, reflecting on their observations and enriching their understanding through the exchange of ideas. This immersive experience connects theory and practice, promoting more meaningful and collaborative learning. Assessment is carried out at two levels: formative and summative, providing a comprehensive view of student progress.

Formative Assessments:

- *Online quizzes:* Before practical sessions, students complete quizzes covering the concepts studied at home, allowing difficulties to be identified and activities to be adjusted.
- *Live observations:* During walks and evening observations, instructors conduct real-time observations, assessing students' participation and understanding, providing immediate feedback.
- *Group discussions:* Group discussions that follow practical activities encourage collaborative learning and critical analysis.

Summative Assessments:

- *Written exams:* At the end of each module, students take exams that measure their theoretical

understanding and ability to solve astronomical problems.

- *Practical projects*: Students apply their knowledge in projects that link theory with practice.
- *Learning portfolios*: Students maintain a portfolio that is periodically evaluated, where they document their progress, reflections, and practical work.

Key Areas of Impact:

- *Improvement in theoretical assessments*: Students show a greater understanding of astronomical concepts.
- *Practical application*: Practical activities allow them to apply their knowledge in real-life situations, improving their critical thinking skills.
- *Greater motivation and participation*: The methodologies used have increased students' commitment and enthusiasm towards learning astronomy.

The combination of the Flipped Classroom with Astronomical Peripatetism has proven to be an effective educational strategy that favours both theoretical learning and the practical application of astronomical concepts. By transferring learning to a real environment under the night sky, students feel more connected and motivated to actively participate in their education.

References:

- Amilburu, M. G. (2015) Educating with life In the classroom and outside it: Edetania Edition, Barcelona.pp.43.
- Becerra, M. (2014:96) Participatory, critical and transformative action research Group for Research and Dissemination in Education (GIDE) Editorial Villadoi-España.
- Bordas, I. (2001): Educational evaluation: evaluating the teaching-learning process, in General Didactics for educational psychologists. UNED, Madrid.
- Brehier. (2014), Epistemology and Qualitative Research: Educational approaches in current education. Editorial la Muralla, S.A. 2nd Argentine edition.
- Buchetti A (2016), Mayéutics and Peripatetics for its application as a learning technique - XVI Academic Reflection Conference in ISSN: 1668 1673 Year IX, Vol. 9, Buenos Aires, Argentina.
- Cerda, A. (2015), Educational, participatory and critical research, in the classroom, Editorial Alfar Sevilla Spain.
- D'Santiago García, JA (2023). Exploring the secrets of the cosmos on foot: Astronomy clubs and Peripatetism. 5th Shaw-IAU Workshop on Astronomy for Education (5th SIW), virtual. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10445237>

Hands-On Experiments as Physical Analogies for Exoplanet Weather Phenomena

Speaker: Oriel Marshall, Universities of Copenhagen and Antwerp, Denmark & Belgium

Collaborators: Jesper Bruun and Anja C Andersen (University of Copenhagen), Katrien Kolenberg and Peter Van Petegem (University of Antwerp)

Models can help to convey and discuss abstract science concepts by comparing them to something more tangible or familiar. Existing research on metaphors and analogies as models tends to focus on language aspects. However, models can also be enacted physically. In this study, we investigate the use of student-led, hands-on experiments as physical analogies in inquiry-based science lessons. We conducted inquiry-based science education lessons about exoplanet clouds and lightning with 28 students aged 16 to 18. After these lessons, the students participated in peer-led focus groups in which they discussed the experiments they had conducted. We analysed these recordings to give insight into the ways that students use the experiments as analogies when discussing scientific topics.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/iW-ZDXCtL98>

Introduction

Models are a staple in science teaching and learning as they can help convey and discuss abstract concepts by comparing them to something more tangible or familiar. There is ample existing research into the use of metaphors and analogies as models in the classroom, the majority of which focus on the verbal aspects of these. However, it is also possible for these models to be enacted physically. In this study, we investigate the use of hands-on experiments as physical analogies, where students will interact with and manipulate the experiment themselves. The aim of this study is to observe and analyse the ways in which students talk about these experiments as physical analogies. The research questions for this project are; 1) In which ways do students utilise the experiment as an analogy during discussion? 2) How do the physical limitations of an experiment as an analogy impact the way that students discuss the concepts in this experiment?

Theoretical Framework

This study builds on conceptual metaphor theory, thinking of physical analogies as a multimodal instance of conceptual metaphor. In this study, we will consider hands-on experiments in inquiry-based science lessons as physical analogies. Analogies work by utilising a 'target domain' and a 'base domain'. The target domain is the (more abstract) topic or subject that we wish the students to be able to understand, and the base domain consists of experiences and ideas that students already have access to. Through analogies, we explicitly map aspects of the base domain onto the target domain in order to aid students' understanding of a subject.

	Finding	Example Data Excerpts
1	Students could map aspects of the base domain onto aspects of the target domain.	S1: "The cold water at the top of the jar could be like the outer cold atmosphere..." S2: "Yeah, and then the hot water at the bottom could be like the heat from the Earth, like the surface of the earth is warmer."
2	Students could identify elements of the base domain that did not map to the target domain.	S1: "I guess the dish soap is kind of irrelevant to experiment itself, because the only thing it did was to help us visualise the experiment."
3	Students were seen to switch between the target and base domains when explaining the concept.	S1: "There are two clouds - one is very positive and one is very negative." S2: "No... it was more like they split up, like with the metal container, the bottom got negative and the top got positive."
4	Students could use the base domain as a reference point to seek clarification in respect to the target domain.	S1: "I don't know how the hairspray works? Was that a..." S2: "No, that was a... um... aer..." S1: "Aerosol?" S2: "Yeah, so the little dust stuff."

Table 1: A summary of how students used the experiments as analogies during discussion.

Methods and Findings

This study is part of a PhD project that is focused on the translation of contemporary astrophysics research topics into teaching materials. We developed a set of lessons that use hands-on experiments to teach students about clouds and lightning on exoplanets. We tested these lessons with two groups of students aged 16 to 18 (n=28). After the lessons, the students participated in peer-led group interviews. We audio-visually recorded each student group and analysed the resultant data using thematic analysis and systematic metaphor analysis. The findings show that the experiments in these lessons were utilised by students as physical analogies in multiple distinct ways during discussions. A breakdown of these ways can be seen in Table 1.

Conclusion

These findings suggest that students, after engaging in a hands-on experiment in a lesson, will be able to discuss the topic of the lesson using the experiment as an analogy. Students are able to map the relevant aspects of the experiment to the relevant aspects of the topic they are learning during the discussion. In addition, they are able to identify which aspects of the experiment do not correlate to the topic they are learning about and are present purely for practical purposes. We observed the students using aspects of the analogy as a way to ask for clarification about the topic, and they were able to switch relatively easily between aspects of the experiment and the scientific topic. This suggests that using experiments as analogies for abstract scientific concepts in a lesson can provide a shared experience and therefore, a shared 'language' between students that can aid them in both sharing and seeking knowledge.

References:

- Lakoff G, Johnson M. *Metaphors We Live By*. The University of Chicago Press; 2003.
- Pedaste M, Mäeots M, Siiman LA, de Jong T, van Riesen SAN, Kamp ET, et al. Phases of inquiry-based learning: Definitions and the inquiry cycle. *Educ Res Rev*. 2015 Feb 1; 14:47–61.
- Podolefsky NS, Finkelstein ND. Analogical scaffolding and the learning of abstract ideas in physics: An example from electromagnetic waves. *Physical Review Special Topics - Physics Education Research*. 2007; 3(1).
- Braun V, Clarke V. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qual Res Psychol*. 2006 Jan;3(2):77–101.
- Schmitt R. Systematic Metaphor Analysis as a Method of Qualitative Research. *The Qualitative Report*. 2015 Jan 20;

Assessing Teachers' Perspectives to Develop Astronomy Learning Materials with Augmented Reality

Speaker: Aishwarya Girdhar, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich (LMU), Germany

Collaborators: Dr. Christoph Hoyer (LMU) and Prof. Dr. Jochen Kuhn (LMU)

Astronomy education has unique challenges due to the abstract nature of concepts. Teachers acknowledge the use of Augmented Reality (AR) in enabling visualisations that support learning. However, educational AR apps need to be developed for specific use cases, making the positive effects on student learning highly dependent on teachers' self-assessed digital skills. To enhance these skills, we developed teacher trainings based on the UTAUT2 (Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology) and TPB (theory of planned behaviour) theories. Teachers developed AR apps to accurately depict the size and distance scales of the Solar System. Through pre- and post-tests, self-assessments from 120 physics teachers were collected. I will present these AR apps, the survey methodology, and insights on factors that influence teachers' acceptance and integration of educational technology.

Teachers' professional knowledge and attitudes towards new technologies significantly impact students' performances, especially in astronomy which presents unique challenges due to the

abstract nature of physical concepts. This intangibility often hampers learning experiences. In this regard, teachers have come to acknowledge the use of augmented reality (AR) in supporting learning experiences by enabling visualisations of abstract concepts. Research indicates that AR can increase learning motivation, improve learning gains, and encourage the exploratory behaviour of students. One challenge, however, is that AR learning applications need to be developed for the specific use case in classrooms, making the positive effects on student learning highly dependent on teachers' self-assessed digital skills.

To foster teachers' perception of digital self-assessment skills, and equip them with required skills, we developed teacher training courses based on the 'Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology' (UTAUT) and the 'Theory of Planned Behaviour' (TPB). Focusing on AR as an example of a novel educational technique with proven benefits, we investigated the factors influencing teachers' acceptance and integration of this technology. We utilised AR to accurately depict the size and distance scales of the Solar System – a concept that is exceptionally challenging to convey in traditional classrooms. Through a pre- and post-test design, we collected the self-assessments from about 120 teachers involved in physics education at the high-school level in Bavaria.

In this talk, I will present the teacher training course, showcase the AR applications developed by the teachers, detail the survey methodology, and present preliminary findings from our research. Additionally, I will provide statistical insight into the factors influencing the acceptance of new technologies in education while also discussing possible avenues for enhancing their implementation in education.

Engagement: What Is It? How Is It Measured? How to Bring It to the Astronomy Course?

Speaker: Cuauhtemoc Mendez, Tec de Monterrey / TRIBU cultura astronómica, Mexico

Collaborator: José Luis Arreola (Tec de Monterrey)

This study defines 'engagement' as what students do beyond passing the course. This allows a clear idea of how to identify and measure it (Formanek, Buxner, Impey, & Wenger, 2019). The students mentioned having shared the learnings achieved in the course with their family and friends. This is one of the aspects that generate educational engagement (Fernández-Zabala, Goñi, Camino, & Zulaika, 2015). Using engagement measurement allows for continuous improvement of the course (both in its topics and in the strategies used).

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/t48Qo4zky6E>

We began by researching literature on what engagement is and the tools that measure it. This search was done in the contexts of education, online courses, and astronomy teaching. To validate the relevance of our findings in the context of the astronomy course, we implemented a simple tool that incorporated the key points identified in the literature.

We used this tool to measure the students' engagement in different activities, such as: exams, team projects, and final grades. We compared these grades with the use of various strategies recommended in the literature. In this way, we were able to recognise which strategies showed results in the numerical grade we obtained for engagement in each edition of the astronomy course.

A significant finding from our measurements was that when the course is not linked to a student's school grade, engagement drops by more than 90%. Activities that demonstrated the highest levels of student engagement included the use of class tutorials, inviting prominent figures in astronomy, participating in astronomical observation nights, and the influence of family and friends' opinions on astronomy topics. The activity that most effectively encouraged engagement involved students explaining astronomy topics to their guests. This highlights the importance of motivating students to invite others to the astronomical evenings they organise.

References:

- Appleton, J. J., Christenson, S. L., Kim, D., & Reschly, A. L. (2006). Measuring Cognitive and Psychological Engagement: Validation of the Student Engagement Instrument. *Journal of School of Psychology*, 427-445.
- Fernández-Zabala, A., Goñi, E., Camino, I., & Zulaika, L. M. (2015). Family and school context in school engagement. *European Journal of Education and Psychology*, 47-55.
- Formanek, M., Buxner, S., Impey, C., & Wenger, M. (2019). Relationship between learners' motivation and course engagement in an astronomy massive open online course. *PHYSICAL REVIEW PHYSICS EDUCATION RESEARCH*, 1-15.
- Fredricks, J. A., Wang, M.-T., Schall Linn, J., Hofkens, T. L., Sung, H., Parr, A., & Allerton, J. (2015). Using qualitative methods to develop a survey measure of math and science engagement. *Learning and Instruction*, 5-15.
- Prather, E. E., Rudolph, A. L., & Brissenden, G. (2009). Teaching and learning astronomy in the 21st century. *American Institute of Physics*, 41-47.
- Slater, T. (2019). Teaching with Lecture Tutorials and Small Group Activities. *Astronomy Teaching Summit*. Baltimore.
- Slater, T., & Adams, J. (2003). *Learner-Centered Astronomy Teaching: Strategies for Astro 101*. New Jersey: Pearson Education.

DISCUSSION SUMMARY

Evaluation was the special education topic for the 6th Shaw-IAU Workshop on Astronomy Education. The session showcased diverse approaches to assessing the effectiveness of astronomy education activities, resources, and programmes. We heard about different evaluation methodologies and theoretical frameworks to explore the impact of astronomy education practices on teachers, pupils, and broader communities. Presentations revealed both commonalities and unique perspectives and contexts, underscoring the value of innovative strategies in fostering engagement, overcoming barriers and improving learning outcomes.

Several presentations emphasised the importance of inclusive and innovative approaches to address linguistic, cultural, and socioeconomic challenges in astronomy education. For instance, Federico Di Giacomo showcased the value of using non-verbal tools, such as drawing, as an effective evaluation method among marginalised communities, enabling participants to express learning and emotions beyond linguistic limitations. Similarly, the NASA PUNCH mission's public engagement programme, presented by Sanlyn Buxner, showcased the value of culturally relevant education, incorporating Indigenous perspectives and tailoring strategies for diverse learners, including those with disabilities. Buxner also provided valuable insights into participant observation and researcher-participant approaches to evaluating implementation programmes. Additionally, the work of Ilham Bouisaghouane exemplified the integration of individualised feedback mechanisms to enhance engagement and learning in upper primary students.

The use of formative and summative evaluations, live observations, and interactive discussions in flipped classroom settings presented by José Antonio D'Santiago García, revealed how diversified evaluation techniques can provide comprehensive insights into student learning. Furthermore, the design and application of instruments to gauge students' perceptions before and after exposure to astronomy education initiatives reflect an ongoing commitment to evidence-based pedagogical practices. Cuauhtemoc Mendez also emphasised the challenges of defining 'engagement' and other latent constructs which have a bearing on how we evaluate these areas. These contributions collectively emphasised the importance of transcending beyond traditional evaluation methods and adopting innovative assessment tools that can validate and refine education programmes, whilst catering to varied learning environments.

The implementation of technological tools in astronomy education, such as augmented and virtual reality (AR/VR) and online modules also featured in several contributions. For example, Aishwarya Girdhar described the development of AR applications to depict the size and distance scales of the Solar System, the evaluation of which demonstrated its value in facilitating conceptual understanding. Girdhar also emphasised the role of established behaviour theories, The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology and the Theory of Planned Behaviour as a lens to assess teachers' ability to integrate these technologies into classrooms.

The value of interdisciplinary and experiential learning was a recurring theme. Collaboration between elementary and science teachers, using astronomy as a cross-curricular bridge, was demonstrated in Fernando Ariel Karaseur's work as a way interdisciplinary approaches can enrich learning experiences. Similarly, the PETeR project in Spain presented by Nayra Rodríguez Eugenio highlighted the impact of guided inquiry and project-based learning using robotic

telescopes. Evaluation of these methodologies demonstrated their ability to deepen conceptual understanding and foster STEM skills and student engagement.

Creative teaching and learning approaches, such as game-based learning and hands-on physical analogies, were presented as exemplary approaches to making abstract astronomical concepts accessible. The FRESCO project team, Stefania Varano, Silvia Casu, Sara Ricciardi, and Alessandra Zanazzi described the process and value of a co-design methodology in developing game-based and play-based resources. For older students, Oriel Marshall demonstrated the value of utilising physical analogies in inquiry-based lessons on exoplanet clouds and lightning, to foster deep understanding and peer-led discussions.

The diverse contributions to this special topic session provided a wide view of evaluation techniques in astronomy education, highlighting innovative approaches, theoretical frameworks, and the importance of inclusivity and interdisciplinary approaches. This session demonstrated the value of collaboration among educators, researchers, and communities to overcome existing challenges and advance evaluation practices across the field. By building on these insights, future initiatives can begin to embed evaluation more routinely in their astronomy education programmes.

Compiled by: Sophie Bartlett

JWST – the First Two Years

Session organisers: Samantha Brown-Sevilla (OAE Heidelberg), María Claudia Ramirez Tannus (MPIA), Łukasz Tychoniec (Leiden Observatory), Mike Boylan-Kolchin (University of Texas), Elizabeth Watkins (University of Manchester)

Editing supported by: Samantha Brown-Sevilla

SESSION OVERVIEW

In the two years since its launch, the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) has transformed our understanding of the universe. In this session, we heard from experts about remarkable scientific achievements made possible by the JWST, including star and galaxy formation, exoplanet characterisation, and insights into the early universe. Experts also discussed the telescope's advanced technology and its educational impact. Additionally, the session explored ongoing challenges and future directions for JWST's discoveries.

TALK CONTRIBUTIONS

Two Years of Cosmic Exploration with JWST

Speaker: Macarena García Marín, European Space Agency (ESA) and Space Telescope Science Institute (STScI), USA

Since the summer of 2022, JWST has been fulfilling its promise of making revolutionary discoveries across all areas of astronomy. From studies of the early Universe to detailed analysis of Solar System objects, JWST's groundbreaking capabilities continue to open new windows to the cosmos, capturing the imagination and wonder of both the scientific community and the public. This talk reviews the most impactful and unexpected discoveries of the observatory to-date, and looks at what JWST's future investigations may bring.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/0-PyL76xhh0>

Before the launch of the Hubble Space Telescope, the astronomical community was already discussing the science drive and design of the next big Observatory. The agreement was that the next mission should be a large, very sensitive infrared telescope, capable to observe the first galaxies and stars formed in the universe. More than 30 years later, on December 24th 2021, the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST), was on the launchpad. After a successful six-month commissioning period, which included many delicate operations such as observatory deployments, orbital injection, mirrors alignments, and readying the instruments for science, JWST started normal operations in July 2022. Webb's performance is truly remarkable (Rigby et al. 2023), and overall, it surpasses its pre-launch requirements: images are twice as sharp, optics are more stable, and most instrument modes are more sensitive. In addition, thanks to its highly optimized launch, JWST has fuel for more than 20 years.

Now in its third year of science operations, JWST is fulfilling its promise of revolutionizing all fields of astronomy. To achieve that the telescope relies on its four very capable science instruments: NIRCam, NIRSpec, and NIRISS, operating in the near-infrared regime, and MIRI, operating in the mid-infrared. We can think of infrared light as a way of detecting thermal emission, which allows JWST to observe cold structures (e.g. exoplanets, ices, and dust), objects that in the visible light are blocked by dust, and very distant objects whose light has shifted from the visible to the infrared. Another aspect that sets JWST apart is the many different observing modes its instruments have. Broadly speaking they can take images in many different infrared colors, block light of very bright objects and see what is around them, and decompose the light and create a spectrum (similar to how rainbows are made, when visible light is filtered through

Figure 1: Image comparison between three different infrared space telescopes. The mid-IR capabilities of JWST/MIRI are showcased here, with never seen before detail. Image credit: Andras Gaspar.

water droplets). JWST dedicates about 75% of its observing time to obtain spectra, which allow astronomers to understand the chemical composition, temperature, pressure, and dynamics of astronomical objects, as well as the distance at which they are. This, in turn, opens a new discovery space that we are just starting to probe. In summary, the combination of its size and infrared capabilities makes JWST a very powerful telescope to explore the universe around us, that reaches a level of detail and depth never seen before (see Figure 1).

JWST's discoveries in all fields of astronomy are far too many to summarize here. Instead, we will highlight some key results, beginning with the early universe down to Solar System objects.

On its exploration of the early universe, JWST has discovered that galaxies were already present less than 300 million years after the Big Bang (the age of the universe is about 13.8 billion years). At the time of writing this summary, the oldest spectroscopically confirmed galaxy is JADES-GS14-4, a luminous star forming galaxy that formed about 290 million years after the Big Bang (Carniani et al 2024). In line with the fast pace of JWST discoveries, there are already robust older galaxies candidates (Kokorev et al 2024) that will have to be spectroscopically confirmed. Overall, JWST has revealed that early galaxies are brighter, chemically richer, more developed, and more numerous than expected, and that in general the early universe evolved at a fast pace.

On the studies of galaxy evolution over time, JWST has revealed the physics of star formation in nearby galaxies, seen as a complex network of filaments and bubbles (Thilker et al. 2024). It is also bringing into new focus studies of nearby active galactic nucleus, and facilitating the study of local galaxies that are true analog to very distant ones.

Both local and distant galaxies contain large numbers of stars, born in massive clouds of gas and dust; JWST is revealing the rich chemistry of disks around stars, and unveiling new details of planet forming disks. This not only includes which materials are available in the disk to form planets, but the fact that some planet forming disks may just survive the harsh ultraviolet radiation environment from nearby stars a few million years (Ramírez-Tannus et al. 2023). JWST has also identified, for the first time, brown dwarf candidates outside our own galaxy (Zeidler et

al 2024). These are objects that straddle the line between the nature of stars and planets: they are not massive enough to fuse hydrogen in their core, hence are not stars, and are not orbiting around stars, and hence are not planets.

Exoplanets are planets that orbit stars outside our Solar system, and their study has become highly relevant: JWST has measured many molecules in the atmospheres of giant exoplanets (Rustamkulov et al. 2023), ruled out thick atmospheres in some rocky worlds (Greene et al. 2023), and discovered an atmosphere in one (Hu et al. 2024).

Finally, JWST has brought Solar System planets into new focus, and explored every class of object in our Solar System, with discoveries that include water peroxide at the poles of Ganymede (Trumbo et al. 2023), an endogenous carbon source on the surface of Europa (Villanueva et al. 2023), and a large water vapor plume from Enceladus (Villanueva et al. 2023).

In summary, JWST is delivering transformational science in all fields of astronomy, and its images manage to capture everyone's awe and imagination. With an expected mission life of over 20 years, many new and exciting discoveries are in the horizon, and we can't wait to unveil them.

References:

- The Science Performance of JWST as Characterized in Commissioning. Rigby, J. et al. 2023, 2023PASP, 135 d8001R.
- Spectroscopic confirmation of two luminous galaxies at a redshift of 14, Carniani et al. 2024, Nature 633 318C.
- A Glimpse of the New Redshift Frontier Through Abell S1063, Kokorev et al. 2024, 2024arXiv241113640K.
- MIRI's transformative view of ISM structure in nearby PHANGS-JWST galaxies: Extragalactic dust filament networks and their relation to star formation, galaxy dynamics, Thilker et al. 2024, AAS, 24342701T.
- XUE: Molecular Inventory in the Inner Region of an Extremely Irradiated Protoplanetary Disk, Ramírez-Tannus M.C. et al. 2023, ApJ, 958L, 30R.
- Discovering Subsolar Metallicity Brown Dwarf Candidates in the Small Magellanic Cloud, Zeidler P. et al. 2024, ApJ, 975, 18Z.
- Early Release Science of the exoplanet WASP-39b with JWST NIRSpec PRISM, Rustamkulov, Z. et al. 2023, Nature, 614, 659R.
- A secondary atmosphere on the rocky exoplanet 55 Cancri e, Hu R. et al, 2024, Nature, 630, 609H.
- Hydrogen peroxide at the poles of Ganymede, Trumbo M. et al, Science, 2023, AGUFM, P53A, O8T.

- Endogenous CO₂ ice mixture on the surface of Europa and no detection of plume activity, Villanueva G.L. et al. 2023, Science, 10.1126/science.adg4270. JWST molecular mapping and characterization of Enceladus' water plume feeding its torus, Villanueva G.L. et al. 2023, Nature Astronomy, 7, 1056V.

Blowing Bubbles in Galaxies: A Zoo of Bubbles from JWST

Speaker: Eric Koch, Center for Astrophysics, Harvard & Smithsonian, USA

Collaborators: Elizabeth Watkins (University of Manchester) and Erik Rosolowsky (University of Alberta, on behalf of the [PHANGS collaborations](#))

JWST's view of nearby galaxies has already produced some of the telescope's most iconic and widely shared images. Because of JWST's ability to peer into the mid-infrared, these images reveal the beautiful and rich structure of the cool gas in interstellar space, resolved on scales never before available. Among the most eye-catching features are the ubiquitous voids of gas. The hundreds of voids in each galaxy are "bubbles" driven by the energy and momentum imparted as massive stars form and (spectacularly) die. Their connection between the gas structure, galaxy structure, and massive stars make these bubbles invaluable for a wide array of open questions in star formation and galaxy evolution, including: How do massive stars reshape the galaxies they form in? Do bubbles trigger star formation, cease star formation, or both? How are heavy elements produced in massive stars mixed back into the galaxy? Previously, we needed sharper observations to reveal these bubbles, and robustly identifying them has long been an algorithmic challenge. Now, with JWST, we finally have the data to trace huge populations of bubbles. Our pilot study visually identifying the bubbles in a single galaxy yielded ~ 1700 bubbles, sufficient to provide new constraints on the size distribution of these structures (Watkins et al., 2023). Next, with imaging of 80 galaxies (and counting!) from treasury surveys led by the Physics at High Angular resolution in Nearby GalaxieS (PHANGS) collaboration, we are developing BubbleZoo: an upcoming citizen science project on Zooniverse to catalog and characterize 100,000s of bubbles. In this talk, I outline the BubbleZoo project, describe how this massive population of bubbles will shape the next generation of star formation models and simulations, and discuss the potential for future citizen science projects in the rich, complex, and rapidly advancing field of star formation.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/726sXr56TrA>

Figure 1. 19 nearby galaxies observed by JWST as part of the PHANGS survey (Credit: NASA, ESA, CSA, STScI, Janice Lee (STScI), Thomas Williams (Oxford), PHANGS Team).

Massive stars play a crucial role in regulating star formation in galaxies. Their intense energy output—known as “feedback”—combined with their short lives means that these rare massive stars have an outsized effect on their surrounding medium. In particular, the feedback from massive stars literally “blows bubbles” in their galaxies, ranging from few light-years to hundreds of light-years across [1].

Studying these bubbles has broad implications, including in our Solar neighborhood. The Sun is currently within a large “super-bubble” that formed about 14 Myr ago from a series of supernovae at the end of the lives of nearby massive stars. With the Gaia satellite, we now have evidence that all the nearest star formation to the Sun lies at the edge of the expanding Local Bubble [2], suggesting that these bubbles may also determine where the next generation of stars will form. However, we can only make this definitive connection within the Sun’s proximity, making it currently impossible to test whether our Local Bubble is normal or unique.

With JWST, we can now observe the bubbles in nearby galaxies instead, providing a unique top-down view to study whole populations. The mid-infrared bands traced by JWST are ideal for tracing the dust and gas swept up in shells at the edges of these bubbles. However, previous infrared telescopes lacked the resolution to distinguish individual bubbles clearly. Within the first months of JWST’s operations, its first images of nearby galaxies immediately and profoundly changed our view of these bubbles: JWST revealed galaxies are filled with a complex intersection of bubbles and shells everywhere in their disks!

Figure 2. Prototype view of BubbleZoo on Zooniverse.

As part of the Physics at High Angular resolution in Nearby Galaxy Survey (PHANGS), our team received some of the JWST’s first images of nearby galaxies (Fig. 1), which have now completed over the first two years of JWST operations to provide 89 galaxies [3]. In our initial work, Watkins et al. [4] identified 1694 bubbles in a single galaxy (NGC 628; the “phantom galaxy”), and Barnes et al. [5] find strong hints of new generations of bubbles forming along the edges of older, larger ones, consistent with predictions based on our Local Bubble in the Milky Way. With nearly 88 more galaxies already observed, we expect there are >100,000 bubbles waiting to be classified and have their properties measured. This bubble catalog will be >1000 larger than any other previous catalog. It will provide exciting insight into how bubbles vary with age. Such a large sample is necessary to identify these trends because each image provides only a single snapshot in time of each bubble as they evolve and grow over ~ 10 s Myr.

To create this vast treasure of bubbles, we introduce **BubbleZoo**, an upcoming citizen-science project on Zooniverse (anticipated in early 2025) that will create the definitive catalog of bubbles in nearby galaxies (Fig. 2). Please join us in exploring and interpreting the intricate beauty and complexity of JWST’s view of nearby galaxies!

References:

- Schinnerer & Leroy, 2024, ARA&A, 62, 369
- Zucker et al., 2022, Nature, 601, 334
- Lee et al., 2023, ApJL, 944, L17
- Watkins et al., 2023, ApJL, 944, L24
- Barnes et al. 2023, ApJL, 944, L22
- Link to press release version: [Webb’s Stunning Collection of 19 Face-On Spiral Galaxies](#)

JWST's Look into First Galaxies and Black Holes

Speaker: Jan Scholtz, Kavli Institute for Cosmology, University of Cambridge, UK

Collaborators: JADES collaboration (international)

The launch of JWST has opened a new window into the Universe, allowing us for the first time to observe the first galaxies and their black holes. Within the JWST Advanced Deep Extragalactic Survey (JADES) we focused on searching for these first galaxies and their black holes, as well as studying the galaxy population across the Cosmic epochs. In my talk I focus on the discovery of the most distant galaxy (GS-z14) and the most distant black hole (GN-z11) as well as overview of the capabilities of JWST in connection of galaxy evolution.

Talk link: https://youtu.be/_2yb0GASne8

One of the main questions of modern astronomy is the detection and study of the first galaxies and black holes in the Universe: the search for cosmic dawn. The launch of the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST), with its exquisite resolution and sensitivity at near-infrared wavelengths, allows astronomers to detect and study these early galaxies in great detail.

The launch of JWST on 25th December 2021 and the beginning of its scientific operations in July 2022 has opened a brand new window into studying the Universe. JWST was designed to operate at near and mid infra-red wavelengths (1-25 microns), optimal for studying the first galaxies in the early Universe.

JWST Advanced Extra Galactic Survey

JWST has a suite of instruments focusing on imaging and spectroscopy: NIRCam, NIRSpec, NIRISS and MIRI. Within the JADES collaboration (JWST Advanced Deep Extra-galactic Survey) we primarily use two instruments: NIRCam (imaging) and NIRSpec (taking deep spectra of galaxies). The aim of the collaboration is to find and study the first galaxies in the Universe as well as their black holes, growth, first stars, and shape (morphology).

Our observing strategy is to first observe a field with NIRCam imaging to map out the field on the sky and then identify targets for later spectroscopic follow-up with NIRSpec instrument. While the imaging allows us to study large amounts of galaxies at the same time, the follow-up spectroscopy enables us to study the galaxies in great detail. We can investigate their stellar population (pinpointing the ages and other properties of their stars), black hole properties as well as metal content (astronomers consider any element heavier than Helium as a metal).

There are too many new discoveries in galaxy evolution from JWST to list here, let alone describe in here. We find galaxies with overmassive black holes, massive red and dead galaxies (sometimes

Figure 1. Spectrum of GS-z14. The deep spectrum with JWST/NIRSpec with ~ 10 hours exposure time. The sharp break in the spectrum is called the Lyman break and its location is indicative of the distance to the galaxy. Credit: NASA, ESA, CSA, J. Olmsted (STScI), S. Carniani (Scuola Normale Superiore), JADES Collaboration.

called quiescent galaxies) that have grown to their mature state and then stopped forming stars within the first two billion years, evolved grand design spirals a few billion years after Big Bang as well as discovery of bright luminous galaxies, 400 million years after Big Bang. This can be summarized by a single overall result: the Universe has evolved significantly faster than we thought before the launch of JWST.

GS-z14 – Most distant Galaxy detected so far!

The discovery of the first galaxies and black holes have been one of the key goals of the JADES collaboration. Observing them is essential for us to understand the evolution of stars, gas and black holes in the everchanging early Universe. In October 2023 and January 2024, we observed GS-z14, a galaxy in the GOODS-S field with JWST NIRSpec instrument to get a spectrum of this distant galaxy candidate. The sharp break in the spectrum (Fig. 1) shows that this galaxy is observed only two hundred and ninety million years after the big bang. This corresponds to a redshift of about 14, which is a measure of how much a galaxy's light is stretched by the expansion of the Universe. Investigating its properties gave us a unique insight into the first galaxies in the Universe. The galaxy is \sim million light-years across with mass of \sim million times the mass of our Sun. It is remarkable that this galaxy has managed to grow to such size and mass in less than 300 million years.

GN-z11 – Most distant supermassive black hole

GN-z11, the most distant galaxy confirmed by the Hubble Space Telescope, has been a great puzzle for astronomers. It is incredibly bright for a galaxy from such an early epoch of the Universe (at a redshift of 10.6, just 440 million years after the Big Bang). JADES observations of GN-z11 surprised the entire team with its spectacular beauty but also the new puzzling properties that needed to be explained. First of all, our imaging has shown that it has multiple components: 1) an extremely compact unresolved component in the middle, 2) an extended disc; and 3) a small companion “Haze” on the side.

The spectroscopic data has shown spectacular emission lines from various different elements: hydrogen, helium, oxygen, nitrogen, neon, and carbon. These emission lines show a harsh

Figure 2. This image from James Webb Space Telescope NIRCам (Near-Infrared Camera) instrument shows a portion of the GOODS-North field of galaxies. At lower right, a pullout highlights the galaxy GN-z11, which is seen at a time just 430 million years after the big bang. The image reveals an extended component, tracing the GN-z11 host galaxy, and a central compact source whose color is consistent with those of an accretion disk surrounding a black hole. Credit: NASA, ESA, CSA, Brant Robertson (UC Santa Cruz), Ben Johnson (CfA), Sandro Tacchella (Cambridge), Marcia Rieke (University of Arizona), Daniel Eisenstein (CfA).

ionizing radiation with unusually strong nitrogen. Combining careful modelling of the emission from these elements with careful theoretical modelling revealed that the strong emission is coming from an extremely dense region around a black hole. The black hole scenario explains the unusual brightness of the galaxy, which allowed it to be first detected by the Hubble Space Telescope in 2010. We measured the black hole mass to be few million times the mass of the Sun, the earliest black hole ever to be detected by astronomers.

However, the black hole in GN-z11 is still not far back enough in time to help us answer the question: How did supermassive black holes come to be? In order to answer this question we need to push JWST further to discover black holes even earlier.

The JWST's spectacular capabilities have allowed for a completely new look into the Universe despite being operational for only two years. It is difficult to comprehend what we will discover with this amazing facility in the next 20 years of scientific operations and how much we will learn about the Universe we live in.

Creating the James Webb Space Telescope First Images

Speaker: Klaus Pontoppidan, NASA/JPL, USA

The first color images from the James Webb Space Telescope were designed with the understanding that a NASA/ESA/CSA flagship must explain its purpose and science to the public, and that to earn the opportunity to explain and educate, we must first inspire. I present some of the history behind the creation of the first JWST color images, reasons behind their design, and how public outreach astronomy images are generally made.

Talk link: https://youtu.be/4o_R1DD7QRE

Webb: Probing the Material that Builds Planets

Speaker: Ewine van Dishoeck, Leiden University, The Netherlands

The James Webb Space Telescope (JWST, or Webb) is the new flagship mission led by NASA. It is orders of magnitude more powerful than previous missions and will therefore push the boundaries of human knowledge even further, from the formation of the first galaxies in the universe to the building of new stars and planets. This talk highlights some of the exciting early science results from Webb, with a focus on characterising the material that makes planets and charting the horizons of other worlds. Could there be life outside our Solar System?

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/udNhABRk9PI>

Infrared observations with the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST, or Webb) open up new opportunities to study the formation of stars like our Sun and planets like Jupiter and Earth. We now know that planets around other stars are common, but how were they formed and why is there such a diversity in planetary systems? And how was our Solar System formed? With its ~ 6 m mirror and state-of-the-art detectors, Webb is orders of magnitude more sensitive than

previous missions. It also sees much sharper, having a spatial resolution comparable to the orbit of Neptune (30 astronomical units, 1 au=distance Sun-Earth) in nearby star-forming regions. Operating at long wavelengths, Webb can penetrate the dusty clouds, which are the nurseries of stars, but which are completely dark when seen with our own eyes. It is fascinating to realise that “our” origins started some 4.6 billion years ago in a dark cloud similar to those that we can see along the Milky Way on a clear night!

This talk and short summary gives a “taste” of some of the science that can be done uniquely with Webb. Beautiful images taken with the NIRC*am* instrument show irradiated clouds such as the Carina Nebula, as well as the powerful jets and outflows that accompany protostars in the earliest stages of their formation when they are only 10000 yr old. Most of our science comes from the spectrometers on Webb, especially the Mid-InfraRed Instrument (MIRI) built by a European-US consortium of institutes. The Netherlands built the spectrometer’s main optics. MIRI operates from 5-28 μm , a wavelength region that is almost entirely blocked by our own atmosphere on the ground. Hence astronomers need to go to space to observe the mid-infrared radiation from celestial objects. Most molecules have their “fingerprints” due to vibrations at infrared wavelengths: for example, the water molecule has a band at 3 μm due to its O-H stretching mode, and at 6 μm due to its H-O-H bending mode. We can distinguish whether a molecule is in the gas or ice based on the shape and pattern of its spectrum.

The formation of stars and planets starts in the tenuous clouds between the stars: they have on average only 10000 particles per cm^3 , a million times less than even an ultra-high vacuum in a laboratory on Earth. They are also cold, about 10 K (-263°C), just above absolute zero. Clouds consist mostly of Hydrogen, with about 10% of Helium. The chemically more interesting elements such as Carbon, Oxygen, and Nitrogen are present at the level of 0.01%. Clouds also contain small dust grains, $\sim 0.1 \mu m$ silicate particles (like sand grains, but > 1000 times smaller) and carbonaceous material, that absorb and scatter the visible light. Given these extremely cold and dilute conditions, one would not expect molecules to form. Yet observations have shown that clouds have a very rich chemistry, with more than 300 different molecules detected! The molecules can be either in the gas phase, or as ice on the cold grain surfaces; at the low pressures in space, molecules are not in liquid form. Dust grains play an important role in astrochemistry: they not only store molecules that freeze-out from the gas in the ice but they also make molecules such as H₂O from reactions of O and H, and more complex species like CH₃OH (methanol) from reactions of CO with H.

Webb observations have answered several important questions. Here just a few examples are given from our programs. Astronomers carry out these observations in teams of researchers that have different expertise: some team members are experts on the data reduction and analysis, others carry out the necessary laboratory experiments, whereas a third group ensures that complementary data with other facilities (e.g., the Atacama Large Millimeter Array, ALMA) are taken, and a fourth group focuses on chemical models. As part of the IceAge collaboration, the ice inventory has been measured in dark clouds prior to star formation, showing that many molecules are already formed at this early stage (see [here](#)). As part of the JOYS program complex molecules including C₂H₅OH (ethanol), CH₃OCHO (methyl formate), and CH₃COOH (acetic acid) have been identified for the first time in ices, answering the important question of whether they are indeed formed in ices rather than in the gas. Ammonium salts have also been found. The “Cheers” NASA/ESA press release highlights these results in more detail ([Cheers! NASA’s Webb Finds Ethanol, Other Icy Ingredients for Worlds](#)). Overall, interstellar clouds have a rich chemical

composition with water and more complex molecules present around nearly all forming stars. The building blocks for prebiotic material are thus widespread.

Clouds are stable for millions of years but eventually they can collapse under their own weight and form a protostar at their centre. Because of angular momentum conservation, a rotating disk of gas and dust is naturally formed around young stars. Their size is roughly comparable with that of our own Solar System (~ 100 astronomical units) and this is the location where new planets are built. Observations with ALMA have shown that virtually all young stars have disks: the ingredients for planet formation are thus also common. Can the rich array of molecules that are made in clouds be transported to these disks? Webb can probe the chemical composition of the inner hot part of the disk where terrestrial planets are thought to be made, out to a few au (comparable with the orbit of Jupiter). ALMA is more sensitive to the outer colder part, so these two instruments complement each other.

What do we know of water in disks? An important concept is that of snowlines, the disk radius where it is warm enough for water ice to sublimate into the gas. Another important fact is that the tiny micron-sized dust grains collide, stick and grow to larger sizes in disks becoming more like pebbles (few cm in size) and eventually planetesimals (comet-like bodies of a few km in size). These icy pebbles can drift inward from the outer disk and thus enhance the inner disk with water and oxygen. However, pebbles can also be stopped from moving inwards in so-called dust traps in the outer disk, having the opposite effect: the inner disk would be highly depleted in water. Such dust traps are widely seen as rings and gaps in ALMA continuum images of disks. MIRI has shown that even disks with large cavities and dust traps still have some water in their inner disks, demonstrating that their terrestrial planet-forming zones are not completely devoid of water. See [here](#).

Early JWST-MIRI results show that there is a wide variety in the chemical composition of disks: some disks are rich in H_2O whereas others have strong CO_2 emission. Surprisingly, the disks around very low mass stars and brown dwarfs ($< 0.3 M_{\text{Sun}}$) appear to be very hydro-carbon rich and water poor, with strong bands of C_2H_2 (acetylene), CH_4 (methane), C_4H_2 (di-acetylene) and even C_6H_6 (benzene) detected. The underlying cause of such a different chemistry in disks around lower-mass stars is still unclear, but can be addressed with Webb observations of much larger samples in the coming years. See [here](#).

In summary, Webb enables astronomers to measure the chemical composition of both ices and gases across the full trail of star- and planet formation, and can thus help answer the question: what sets the composition of new planets? So far, a large variety in the chemical composition of planet-forming regions has been found, which may be linked to the mass of the star and the structure of the disk. At the time of the Shaw-IAU workshop, comet C/2023 A3 (Tsuchinshan-ATLAS) was visible with the naked eye in the night sky. The chemical composition of comets is similar to that found in ices in clouds. By looking at comets, we are thus watching the left-over building blocks and an important piece of the history of our Solar System!

Tracking Down the Cosmic Origins of Earth's Water with JWST

Speaker: Giulia Perotti, Max Planck Institute for Astronomy, Germany and Niels Bohr Institute, Denmark

Collaborators: V. Christiaens (University of Liège and KU Leuven), Th. Henning (MPIA), and the MINDS collaboration

Astronomers and geologists have long pondered how Earth became water-rich, with its oceans, glaciers, and rain pouring from the sky. Water, which is made up of the first and third most common elements in the universe, is an easy molecule to form. However, the details of its delivery on rocky planets remain poorly understood. Thanks to the great power of the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST), it is now possible to study in detail the origins of water in the rocky planet-forming zone of disks, the birthplaces of planets. In this talk, I describe the fundamental properties of disks and present recent JWST results of PDS 70, a young protoplanetary system that hosts at least two giant planets. The much higher sensitivity of JWST compared to previous infrared space observatories revealed a water vapour reservoir in the rocky planet-forming zone of the system, indicating that rocky planets that may form there have access to a water reservoir. How much of that water will be incorporated into the cores of rocky planets? How much will be dispersed? I conclude by discussing future prospects using JWST in tandem with other world-class observatories to continue tackling this fundamental question.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/lAdSVEY-1Ac>

Water is fundamental to life on Earth, making the search for water on other Earth-like exoplanets highly significant. While detecting liquid water on exoplanets remains elusive, new observations from the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) suggest that water could already be prevalent during the early stages of planetary formation, specifically in regions where Earth-like planets typically emerge.

The origin of Earth's water and whether similar processes occur on other Earth-like exoplanets is a topic of ongoing debate. The leading hypothesis posits that water-rich asteroids in the outer regions of planetary systems collides with the surface of young planets. However, this idea hinges on the occurrence of random events. Our recent findings propose an alternative, regular mechanism that may provide planets with water from the onset of their formation.

Planets form within dust and gas disks around young stars, much like how Earth and the Solar System's planets did 4.5 billion years ago. The Atacama Large Millimeter/submillimeter Array (ALMA) has captured thermal images of many such disks at different developmental stages. These images provide crucial insights into the processes that lead to planet formation.

Figure 1. An artist's impression of the dust and gas disk surrounding the star PDS 70. Earth-like planets typically form in the central region, close to the star, though none have been detected here yet. So far, only two gas giants, PDS 70 b and c, have been identified in this system. As they grow, these planets have carved a wide gap in the disk, resulting in an outer ring made up of gas and icy solid materials like dust and pebbles. Credit: J. Neidel/MPIA/HdA.

Water in the inner disk of the star PDS 70 is particularly noteworthy (Figure 1). As part of the MINDS (MIRI Mid-Infrared Disc Survey) program, we analyzed the radiation from the gas and dust disk around PDS 70 using the Mid-InfraRed Instrument (MIRI) on JWST (Figure 2). By examining the disk's spectral components, we identified water vapor at temperatures of around 330°C (600 Kelvin) in the inner regions, where rocky planets typically form (Perotti et al. 2023). This discovery challenges expectations, as previous searches suggested the inner disk of PDS 70 would be dry. The presence of water in this 5.4-million-year-old disk is unexpected, given that planet formation, including the birth of two gas giants, PDS 70 b and c, is actively occurring. While smaller rocky planets remain difficult to detect, our observations suggest water could have been present in early planet formation, enhancing the possibility that other Earth-like planets also possess early water supplies.

Figure 2. Water everywhere: a portion of the light spectrum, captured by the MIRI instrument onboard of JWST, from the rocky planet-forming zone of the disk around the star PDS 70 (orange line), a physical model has detected several spectral lines originating from hot water vapor (blue line). Credit: mattweis based on an illustration by NASA, ESA, CSA, Joseph Olmsted (STScI).

This discovery raises intriguing questions about the potential for life on other planets. If water is a common element during the formation of rocky planets, it could significantly improve the chances of finding habitable worlds. The ongoing MINDS research aims to determine how widespread water is in planet-forming zones. But how does water enter these disks? Disks around young stars are born from interstellar molecular clouds, where water exists as ice grains. As the star forms, these ice-coated grains become part of the disk, and as they migrate inward, the ice vaporizes. Although ultraviolet radiation from the central star can break down water molecules, the dust and gas in the inner disk offer some protection, allowing water to persist or form anew from inflowing gases.

Understanding which of these mechanisms dominates is a key question. JWST's observations, along with data from other telescopes, are helping researchers piece together the origins of water on rocky planets, offering crucial insights into the conditions necessary for life.

Reference: Perotti et al. 2023, Water detection in the terrestrial planet-forming zone of the PDS 70 disk, Nature.

Exploring Distant Worlds with the James Webb Space Telescope

Speaker: Néstor Espinoza, Space Telescope Science Institute (STScI), USA

In this talk, I introduce some of the science the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) is enabling for the field of extrasolar planets. In particular, the field of exoplanet science itself is introduced in the context of our own Solar System, as well as the big questions it might enable to answer and why JWST is a perfect observatory to perform studies of these objects. I exemplify JWST exoplanet science via two sets of science results: the detection of remnant planets around white dwarfs and the detection and characterization of exoplanet atmospheres around small planets. The techniques that enable these discoveries are introduced and discussed.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/AlwQrpfl01g>

JWST Universe

Speaker: Milena Ratajczak, University of Warsaw Astronomical Observatory, Poland & Ola Birke, Science Now Studio, Poland

Collaborators: Jan Pomierny (Science Now Studio) and Pedro Russo (Leiden Observatory and Dep. Science Communication & Society, Leiden University)

The JWST Universe Experience offers an innovative fusion of art and science through its photographic exhibition, immersive experience, and educational programme. Visitors are invited to explore the beauty of the cosmos through stunning images captured by the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST), presented as scientific marvels and artistic masterpieces. Interactive technologies and hands-on activities (including LEGO workshops) complement the visuals, making the Universe more accessible. Designed for all ages, the experience fosters a deep understanding of space exploration while inspiring curiosity about the mysteries of the cosmos.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/70XqWuaYevI>

I. JWST Universe: Bridging Science and Public Fascination

The JWST Universe project, developed by Science Now in collaboration with Leiden University, NOVA, and SRON, presents the groundbreaking achievements of the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST). This initiative aims to create an accessible yet profound experience that bridges the divide between the scientific community and the general public captivated by JWST's advancements and imagery. Through a comprehensive ecosystem of formats – photographic exhibitions, immersive experiences, and educational programmes – JWST Universe brings the marvels of the cosmos closer to people of all backgrounds.

II. Creating an Ecosystem of Formats

The JWST Universe is designed as a flexible ecosystem of formats, including a photographic exhibition, an immersive experience, and an educational program. These elements are conceived to operate both independently and in conjunction, providing a cohesive, multi-dimensional exploration of JWST's findings. This adaptability allows each format to complement the others, offering audiences various ways to engage based on individual interests and preferred learning styles.

1. Photographic exhibition: cosmic imagery as art

What if JWST images were treated as works of art? This inquiry led to a photographic exhibition where JWST's images are presented on large, backlit canvases, elevating them to an art form that inspires awe. Each canvas reveals breathtaking cosmic scenes, allowing visitors to navigate the exhibit at their own pace. Accompanying the visuals are descriptive texts, audio guides, and interviews with scientists, enabling viewers to choose the most accessible medium. Chapters in the exhibition provide focused insights/themes in a concise yet captivating format.

Figure 1. JWST Universe exhibition at Old Observatory in Leiden (NL). Fot. Michał Ostaszewski.

Exhibition chapters:

- **Technological Marvel** – This chapter explores the intricate engineering behind JWST. The focus is on the telescope’s complex instruments, its origami-like deployment, and its impressive journey to 1.5 million kilometers from Earth.
- **Other Worlds** – Here, visitors learn about JWST’s contributions to the discovery and study of planets, showcasing the telescope’s tools like the coronagraph that allows us to glimpse planets hidden by starlight. This chapter reveals the diversity of exoplanets and JWST’s potential to uncover details about distant worlds.
- **Early Universe** – This section delves into JWST’s ability to capture infrared light from the Universe’s infancy, unveiling the first galaxies formed after the Big Bang. Through redshifted light, JWST looks back billions of years, enabling us to witness the Universe’s formative stages.
- **Life cycles of stars** – Focusing on stellar evolution, this chapter illustrates how stars are born, evolve, and ultimately die in spectacular supernovae. With JWST’s infrared capabilities, the exhibition presents stars hidden within nebulae and details the elements stars produce, contributing to the diversity of the Universe.
- **Galaxies Through Time** – Visitors explore the diversity and evolution of galaxies, from spirals to irregular shapes. This chapter emphasizes JWST’s role in uncovering the mysteries of galactic formation and the distribution of dark matter through its gravitational lensing observations.

Each chapter enriches the exhibition’s narrative, inviting visitors to explore JWST’s discoveries across a vast array of cosmic phenomena. Additionally, at its core, JWST Universe goes beyond viewing the JWST as merely a scientific tool, embracing its role as a cultural symbol. This platform highlights the telescope’s broader significance, inviting audiences to see it as part of humanity’s quest to understand our place in the cosmos. For its first edition, we invited Leandros Ntolas to showcase his installation.

2. Immersive experience: engaging technology

The immersive experience extends the exhibition’s reach by incorporating state-of-the-art technology to create a multi-sensory journey – by including other mediums, beyond the visuals, for example music. Designed to inspire a deeper appreciation of space, this format uses visuals and interactive elements to envelop audiences and blend scientific exploration with artistic

Figure 2. “The Reconstruction of Mystery” – Leandros Ntola at Old Observatory in Leiden (NL). Fot. Michał Ostaszewski.

impression. This setup allows participants to feel as though they are traversing the cosmos.

3. Educational Programme: Hands-on learning

To make the knowledge about JWST’s scientific instruments approachable, the educational program includes a series of interactive workshops. Tailored for diverse age groups, the sessions encourage participants to construct models of JWST’s instruments or famous images, such as the “Pillars of Creation”, using specially selected LEGO bricks. This hands-on approach transcends traditional learning, allowing attendees to interact with astronomical concepts and gain insight into the science behind JWST’s discoveries.

Each workshop is designed so that it can be either led by a facilitator or self-paced that provides flexibility in how the activities are conducted. Clear instructions are included to make the building process easier for participants and to help guide facilitators through the activity. The workshops and activities are scalable, allowing facilitators to adapt the level of detail and knowledge shared based on the age and level of interest of the audience, ensuring that all participants, regardless of background, can engage meaningfully with the content. As mentioned earlier, a workshop can be an integral part of an exhibition or immersive experience, or it can be an independent activity.

III. Making Science Accessible: Creativity in Communication

Central to the JWST Universe project is the mission of making scientific knowledge more approachable. By adopting creative communication strategies, the project bridges the gap between complex science and public curiosity. Each format within JWST Universe is designed to foster a welcoming learning environment that brings scientific insights into the public sphere in engaging, innovative ways.

In summary, JWST Universe is dedicated to creating educational opportunities that inspire curiosity and foster understanding. Through a carefully structured ecosystem of formats, the project not only showcases the achievements of the JWST but also reimagines how space science can be communicated to the public, making it an invaluable resource for both scientific and educational communities.

Webb: Bringing the Mission and Its Science to School Students and the General Public

Speaker: Joanna Holt, The Netherlands Research School for Astronomy (NOVA) and Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS), The Netherlands

Collaborators: Joris Hanse and Marieke Baan (NOVA)

The JWST captures the imagination of the world, inspiring all both young and old. From technological challenges and its 'origami mirror' to its powerful cameras looking deeper into the universe than ever before, JWST is fascinating on all levels. With the MIRI-instrument being built in the Netherlands, the mission also has special national interest. With this in mind, NOVA coordinated a number of activities bringing JWST and its science to a broad cross-section of the Dutch population. The activities included press events, live webcasts, educational webinars for school students and teachers, and themed planetarium shows with expert guest speakers, taking place from prior to launch - summer 2024. In this talk we give an overview with particular focus on the content choices made.

What's important?: When putting together a suite of activities for a mission like JWST, we identified three crucial elements to take into account:

- i) The first is to identify where interest from your audience may lie. Some people will be triggered by the science, but often public interest in astronomy and missions like JWST is strongly linked to other factors, such as time and aspects of national interest. Knowing this will help you plan effectively.
- ii) Second, it is important to identify your audience and tailor your activities accordingly, both in terms of the platform, or the type of activity you will arrange, and what type of content is appropriate.
- iii) Third, for real impact, it is crucial to interact with your audience to truly engage them.

Identifying audience interest: As mentioned above, the most obvious interest in a mission like JWST is interest in the science. For a detailed discussion of the science aspects, we refer readers to other summaries presented in this session, particularly the contribution of Prof. Ewine van Dishoeck. Here, we would just like to reiterate that JWST is a revolutionary telescope, giving us a glimpse of the Universe in until now unexplored parts of the electromagnetic spectrum combined with incredible light collecting power and image resolution. Many of the main science questions JWST is designed to address naturally fall within the questions we know to be of great public interest, such as the study of exoplanets.

A second key interest trigger is timeliness, when the mission appears in the news. In Figure 1,

Figure 1: Timeline of the JWST milestones and associated NOVA events.

we show the broad mission timeline used by NOVA to plan events and activities. We highlighted three key times: i) the run up to and around launch, ii) the release of the first images and, iii) the first science results and the release of new public images. These were times when we expected the mission to have significant news coverage and so be visible to, and trigger interest in, a broad audience.

Finally, interest in missions like JWST can also be linked to national interest. This can potentially speak more to some audiences than the timeliness (i.e., in the news) or scientific aspects. With JWST, there was a strong national interest in the Netherlands - the MIRI-spectrometer was designed and built by the NOVA Optical-Infrared group in collaboration with other Dutch partners. Furthermore, the MIRI-co-principle investigator is based at Leiden University. NOVA took every opportunity to highlight this, including the people involved in the many events discussed in this talk and also the press activities. Highlighting the national involvement can be very powerful. It brings something, which at face value seems far away close to home and can make the public feel involved. For younger people, it highlights the study and career opportunities available on their own doorstep.

Activity planning: With the timeline in place, the next step is to identify which audiences to focus on at which times, and how to reach and interact with them. As discussed above, we identified three key milestones. Figure 1 summarises the activities planned to coincide with these milestones.

- i) Pre-launch & launch: We held a Star Party (planetarium show) and an Education Webinar aimed at teachers. In the hours around the launch, we arranged various public lectures and webinars, including a live-stream during the launch. Within the first few weeks of school after the launch we held a second educational webinar, this time also open to secondary school students.
- ii) Release of the first images: We planned a number of events and public lectures and a special Star Party including the new imagery.
- iii) Approximately two years later after the release of the first public images and after the first science results, we felt it was a good time to tap into renewed interest and hold a third Star Party.

Star Party: The Star Party is a fully live and interactive planetarium show aimed at a broad audience in a large dome theatre. NOVA has its own network of mobile planetariums, but for the Star Parties, we work together with Omnisum in The Hague (capacity 300).

The first Star Party was held approximately a month before launch. The focus lay on the launch, the technical journey the telescope would take en route to L2 and a look forward to what we could expect. The second coincided with the release of the first images, and these images were the focus of the Star Party. We knew interest would be high because of the expected press coverage of both of these events. We also planned a third Star Party approximately two years after the first images were released, again as there was expected to be significant time interest with the release of new images and new scientific results. In this Star Party, the focus lay on the new results and what we had learned so far with JWST. Each show was a sell out and the audience was mixed, from keen amateur astronomers with a lot of background knowledge to people with little prior knowledge of the topics.

For the Webb Star Parties, we used a special approach – a combination between a public lecture by our special guest, in this case Professor Ewine van Dishoeck, and a more typical NOVA planetarium show led by a NOVA planetarium expert. The parts of the show led by an expert use slides as is common in public lectures, which were switched off during planetarium sections. Using two speakers and covering topics with two different presentation styles, and also levels, made the star parties accessible for a broader audience. In addition to being live, the show was also interactive – we had three question rounds, spending at least 30 minutes of the total 90 minutes answering audience questions. The need for the mixed-level approach was also confirmed during these question rounds. Some of the audience was keen to ask questions directly to our expert, others felt more comfortable asking what they themselves perceived to be more basic questions to the planetarium presenter. The format has proven to be very successful and we have been arranging similar themed shows around three times per year on different topics.

Education Webinar: The Education Webinars were fully online events, partly because of Covid restrictions, aimed at science teachers. For the second webinar, secondary school students were also able to participate. The format included a science talk by a guest scientist, breakout workshops with lesson tips, a planetarium show, and informal interaction (e.g., quiz), lasting around two hours in total. The format was fully interactive – participants could ask questions both live and via the chat function. As with the Star Parties, the timing of the webinars was well thought out. The first was pre-launch, to give teachers input to be able to talk about Webb in their lessons around launch. It is likely that students will ask question about what they have seen in the news and teachers are often looking for ways to make lesson materials more relevant for their students. We repeated the webinar with some small changes shortly after launch to give more ideas and further link the mission and its science to what would be done in the classroom. The events were well attended, with approximately 150 participants for each webinar.

Other activities: More common activities, such as events and public lectures, both live and online (partly because of Covid) were held to coincide with the launch and the release of the first images -- these were times when we expected significant interest in more scientific details of the mission. For example, the day before the launch, a number of public lectures were held discussing various aspects of the mission and during launch there was a livestream in which experts discussed what was happening and the public could ask questions via the chat. When the first images were released, a similar set of events were arranged, physically this time as the Covid restrictions were lifted, including public lectures and an event where the Dutch scientists involved reacted to the first images.

The Golden Eye: JWST in Schools

Speaker: Priya Hasan, Maulana Azad National Urdu University, India

Collaborator: S N Hasan (Maulana Azad National Urdu University)

The JWST has received a lot of attention in social media and news and hence is a very appropriate tool to be used in schools and colleges for Astronomy Outreach and Education. I describe the many times I have used its images as well as press releases and published papers to explain important concepts in astronomy. Also, with the constant flow of ground breaking discoveries, it is very important to explain their importance in our understanding of astronomy. I describe these examples in my talk.

Talk link: <https://youtu.be/Vri-bnS3cYg>

It is very important to let people know about recent advances in Astronomy, especially the ones that are seen in new items and social media. Hence, we have been having various sessions with school children on the James Webb Space Telescope. They need to understand what the excitement is all about.

We often go to schools to address this. Depending on the duration, we plan our session. If there is time for a hands-on session, we have a session on telescope making and students make groups of 3-4 to make telescopes. This is very effective in clearing concepts about telescopes and some basic optics. In case there is only time for a session (talk/discussion) we give an overview talk on telescopes. We talk of JWST as an infrared space telescope and explain to the students' important aspects of telescopes, space telescopes and the importance of infrared observations. We finally conclude the session with images of JWST and explain their importance.

Figure 1. Telescope making sessions (left and middle). A school astronomy outreach session (right).

POSTER CONTRIBUTIONS

In Praise of Raw Data: Sustainable Printing Techniques to Engage Students with Astronomical Images

Presenter: Melanie King, Canterbury Christ Church University and Royal College of Art, UK

Collaborator: Claudia Mignone (INAF)

Telescopes return almost daily images of celestial bodies that communicate science through colours, shapes and structures, contributing to our collective imagination of the Universe. The goal of this project is to bring back the “material” aspect of astronomical observations by exploring images from James Webb Space Telescope, discovering the richness of raw data, from artifacts like cosmic rays and bad pixels to the actual scientific information about planets, stars, galaxies. Images will be printed using sustainable analogue photographic techniques, acknowledging the importance of using materials wisely on a planet with limited resources. Two formats are being developed: an advanced printing workshop for art students and a basic version for secondary schools.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14483112>

How do we, as humans, picture the vast nature of the Universe? Telescopes on Earth and in orbit, along with spacecraft exploring the Solar System, return almost daily a wealth of images portraying planets, stars, and galaxies, which populate all realms of print and digital media, contributing to our collective imagination of celestial bodies, the cosmos, and outer space. The most recent addition to this fleet is the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST), the most powerful astronomical observatory ever launched into space, whose first images in July 2022 captured audiences worldwide with their sheer beauty and cosmic grandeur (Pontoppidan et al. 2022). JWST observes the cosmos in infrared light, wavelengths that are not perceived by human eyes, prompting the question of how those images are produced. This question is actually relevant for all observations of the cosmos, whether in visible light or any other wavelength of the electromagnetic spectrum: astronomical image processing is a data visualisation exercise that involves several parameters to provide a factual, possibly also aesthetically pleasant visual representation of the measurements collected by telescopes.

Is there a best combination of these parameters for the general public to appreciate these views of the cosmos? Astronomers and science communicators have been investigating this question (Smith et al. 2010, Rector et al. 2017). In Science and Technology Studies, scholars have been exploring materiality in science communication, pointing out the role of objects,

structures, spaces and places in the public perception of science, as the effects that are tied to these elements have the potential to elicit positive emotions towards the scientific process (e.g., Davies, 2014). Addressing questions such as “How are scientific visuals produced?” or “Where do these images come from?”, which abound in online news and forums, makes it possible to connect with learners in an affective, disembodied fashion, recentering the engagement around emotions of pleasure and delight. The authors decided to investigate whether it becomes easier to grasp these concepts when learners can enjoy a direct involvement in the processing of images from outer space, and chose to do so by exploring different printing techniques to convey the behind-the-scenes processes that are involved in the creation of astronomy images for public consumption.

As a first step, in July 2024, Dr. Claudia Mignone and Dr. Melanie King met with Alyssa Pagan and Joe De Pasquale, Science Visuals Developers at the Space Telescope Science Institute. The aim of the meeting was to discuss how astronomical images from JWST are processed, also in relation to Hubble photographs. King was particularly keen to understand raw data artefacts within the images. King and Mignone also met with Prof. Mark McCaughrean, who is a JWST interdisciplinary scientist and former Senior Advisor for Science & Exploration at the European Space Agency. With decades of experience analysing and processing astronomical images, especially in the infrared domain, McCaughrean has his own way of processing astronomical images which differ to those produced at NASA.

Following these meetings, King wanted to make a feature of the raw data artefacts in the astronomical images as they can tell us about the process of producing the image. For example, some astronomical images from the Hubble Telescope feature trails from cosmic ray interactions. With JWST images, there are artefacts which include six pointed stars or diffraction spikes, which arise from the six mirrors of the telescope. In the raw files, there are also overexposed dots which resemble black holes, and trails on the edges of images from software processing. King was keen to print the images using sustainable printmaking processes. Firstly, Melanie King worked with Park Press to produce risograph prints of the Carina Nebula and Pillars of Creation images by JWST. Risographs are produced using otherwise obsolete machines, and the technology is both similar to screen printing and photocopying. A digital image is loaded onto a computer and split into colour channels, in a manner which mirrors astronomical image compositing processes. A master or ‘screen’ is produced, which allows one colour of ink to be selectively applied to paper. In this session, King was only able to print 2 colours due to availability of ink, but it is theoretically possible to build up to a full colour image. Many elements of the risograph process are sustainable, as the masters are based from starch and are biodegradable. The inks are made from a soya base, and the paper is made from recycled fibres.

In addition to this, King worked with photographer Clare Hewitt, botanical ink maker Carolyn Morton and paper maker Danielle Phelps to produce a screen print of the Tarantula Nebula. Hewitt, Morton, and Phelps have been working to produce a fully sustainable photography book and have spent months researching their individual processes to find a combination that works. For the Tarantula Nebula image, paper was made with recycled cotton fibres by Danielle Phelps. In addition to this, the team used paper made from recycled coffee cups and an ink was made from foraged oak gall by Carolyn Morton.

In future, King would like to work with the cyanotype process, building up colours through selective toning processes. This is work in progress: eventually, King and Mignone would like to

produce an easily replicable technique that can be reproduced in an educational environment. This will familiarise students with astronomical imaging techniques, whilst simultaneously educating students on sustainable printmaking techniques. The aim of this project is to empower people by providing a stepwise, facilitated approach to scientific data via the use of photographic techniques, researching the best resources and communication tools to achieve this. We wish to encourage a change in perspective of people with no previous experience in photography and/or astronomy, presenting these topics as approachable rather than distant, ethereal, almost intangible.

References:

- Davies, S. R. (2014). Knowing and Loving: Public Engagement beyond Discourse, *Science & Technology Studies*, 27(3), pp. 90–110
- Pontoppidan, K. M., Barrientes, J., Blome, C., Braun, H., Brown, M., Carruthers, M., Coe, D., DePasquale, J., Espinoza, N., Garcia Marin, M., Gordon, K. D., Henry, A., Hustak, L., James, A., Jenkins, A., Koekemoer, A. M., LaMassa, A., Law, D., Lockwood, A., ... Nota, A. (2022). The JWST Early Release Observations. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 936, 1
- Rector, T. A., Levay, Z. G., Frattare, L. M., Arcand, K. K., & Watzke, M. (2017). The Aesthetics of Astrophysics: How to Make Appealing Color-composite Images that Convey the Science. *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, 129, 975
- Smith, L. F., Smith, J. K., Arcand, K. K., Smith, R. K., Bookbinder, J., & Keach, K. (2011). Aesthetics and Astronomy: Studying the Public's Perception and Understanding of Imagery From Space. *Science Communication*, 33(2), 201-238

James Webb Telescope: Towards an Expanded View of the Universe

Presenter: Somaya Saad, NRIAG, Egypt

James Webb, the largest space telescope ever built, has travelled a million miles into space and is four times farther away than the moon to begin its work observing the formation of stars, planetary systems, and exoplanets. Webb is designed to answer some of the biggest questions about the Universe. Here I review some of the first results of James Webb within two years of its launch. With its ability to capture the spectrum in the infrared range, James Webb can reveal a lot about the origin of the Universe, the seeds of the first galaxies, the Solar System and exoplanets, and answer many related questions.

Poster link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14482974>

Why James Webb?: Webb is an infrared telescope key to characterizing the atmospheres of exoplanets. The benefit of making infrared observations is that, at infrared wavelengths that molecules in the atmospheres of exoplanets have the largest number of spectral features. The ultimate goal, of course, is to find a planet with a similar atmosphere to that of Earth. Webb is telling us more about the atmospheres of extrasolar planets, and perhaps will even find the building blocks of life elsewhere in the Universe. In addition to other planetary systems, Webb is also studying our own Solar System.

James Webb First Images:

- Webb has observed the deepest and sharpest infrared image of the distant universe so far, the field stars SMACS 0723. This new deep field image uses a lensing galaxy cluster to find some of the most distant galaxies ever detected. Webb with its capabilities will help in studying deep fields and tracing galaxies back to the beginning of cosmic time.
- Webb has observed the Southern Ring Nebula, a planetary nebula or an expanding cloud of gas that surrounds a dying star, approximately 2,000 light years away. For the first time, Webb with its powerful infrared capabilities has detected the second dying star.
- With a rare look Webb's view the compact group of galaxies Stephan's Quintet, which located in the constellation Pegasus, reveal the velocity and composition of the gas near its supermassive black hole at the center.
- Carina Nebula: Webb's look at the 'Cosmic Cliffs' in the Carina Nebula unveils the earliest, rapid phases of star formation that were previously hidden. Looking at this star-forming region in the southern constellation Carina, as well as others like it, Webb can see newly forming stars and study the gas and dust that made them.

Figure 1: **James Webb First Images:** Carina Nebula (upper right), Southern Ring Nebula (upper left), the field stars SMACS 0723 (lower right), and Stephan's Quintet (lower left).

Webb and Other Worlds: Where and How do Planetary Systems Form and Evolve?: Until recently, the only planetary system we could study was our own Solar System. Now astronomers have found evidence for thousands of planets around stars other than our own Sun. These are known as exoplanets. Because of this we are getting closer to answering key questions such as:

Figure 2: This image shows the exoplanet HIP 65426 b in different bands of infrared light, as seen from the James Webb Space Telescope. Credit: NASA, ESA, CSA, A. Pagan (STScI); Science credit: A. Carter (UC Santa Cruz), ERS 1386 Team.

Is earth the only planet hosting life? Do other planetary systems exist similar to ours? Are we alone in the universe?

Webb's Impact on Exoplanet Research: Building on the legacy of NASA's Hubble Space Telescope, Spitzer Space Telescope, and other ground- and space-based observatories, James Webb Space Telescope will be expanding our understanding of exoplanet atmospheres.

References:

- NASA, ESA, CSA, G. Villanueva (NASA-GSFC), S.K. Trumbo (Cornell University); Image Processing: G. Villanueva (NASA-GSFC), A. Pagan (STScI).
- NASA, ESA, CSA, A. Pagan (STScI); Science credit: A. Carter (UC Santa Cruz), ERS 1386 Team.

DISCUSSION SUMMARY

This year's special science session focused on the first two years of the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST). The session was divided into three sub-sessions: the assembly of galaxies; from star and planet formation to exoplanet characterisation; and JWST in outreach and education. The session aimed to provide an overview of the remarkable scientific discoveries that the JWST and the people working with it have given us. Additionally, it highlighted examples of how JWST releases have been used in education and outreach.

The assembly of galaxies session started with an overview talk on JWST by Macarena García Marín, who highlighted the scientific motivation for the building of the telescope, and touched on the most astonishing discoveries in different fields of astronomy. Following which, Eric Koch talked about the research being done on nearby galaxies, which has revealed the existence of hundreds of 'bubbles' resulting from the evolution of massive stars. Additionally, he advertised the upcoming citizen science project: BubbleZoo. In the third contribution of this session, by Jan Scholtz, we learned how JWST is exploring some of the first galaxies and black holes, highlighting the discoveries of the first of them.

Next, Klaus Pontoppidan gave us a glimpse into the creation of the first JWST images, from how the first targets were decided, to how the images are made with public outreach in mind. Ewine van Dischoeck talked about the research being made to understand the materials from which planets are formed, showing some exciting early results. Giulia Perotti followed with a concrete example of the discovery of water molecules in the rocky planet-forming zone of the protoplanetary system PDS 70.

The last sub-session started with an overview on exoplanetary science with JWST by Néstor Espinoza, who very creatively went through the most impressive discoveries in the field. The second part of this sub-session featured talks on how JWST data has been utilized in educational contexts with Milena Ratajczak and Ola Birke telling us about an innovative exhibition that fuses art and science; Joanna Holt who gave us insights on how to plan for educational and outreach activities around the releases of JWST data; and Priya Hasan who gave practical examples of JWST images used in schools.

This session not only underscored JWST's scientific accomplishments but also demonstrated its impact as a powerful tool for education and inspiration. Its discoveries continue to reshape our understanding of the Universe, while fostering curiosity and learning worldwide.

Compiled by: Samantha Brown-Sevilla

WORKSHOP AND COMMUNITY DISCUSSIONS

astroEDU Workshop

Session organiser: Livia Giacomini (INAF), Giulio Mazzolo (astroEDU associate editor), Gwen Sanderson (OAE), Federica Duras (INAF), Edward Gomez (LCO)

WORKSHOP SUMMARY

AstroEDU, the open-access platform by OAE, offers educators a monthly opportunity to discover new, peer-reviewed, high-quality educational activities in the fields of Astronomy, Earth sciences, and Space Science. AstroEDU is today in three different languages and is testing new technologies like the A.A.A., the A.I. Assistant (under test at the moment) that will be introduced to improve user experience.

In this workshop, we provided an overview of the activities that have been published to date and offer insights on how to use the A.A.A. to search for the right activity to effectively integrate into the classroom. During the second part of the workshop, participants were also guided through an interactive process that involved analyzing and discussing case studies in the context of the publication journey.

This workshop was designed to introduce AstroEDU to both teachers and researchers involved in education, providing a comprehensive understanding of how to use and create high-quality educational resources that can benefit educators worldwide.

Arabic-Speaking Community Discussion

Session organisers: Abd Alfady Morcos and Somaya Saad (NAECs Egypt)

DISCUSSION SUMMARY

A pivotal session was conducted in Arabic to enhance collaboration between Arab countries and advance astronomy education across the Arab world. This session was organised by the **Egyptian NAEC Team** with support from the Astronomy Education Center in Egypt, and the Office of Astronomy for Education, at the 6th Shaw-IAU Workshop. It included participants from Egypt, Iraq, Sudan, and Jordan, overcoming challenges such as unstable internet access in Morocco, Mauritania, and Qatar.

Session Moderation: The session was moderated by **Dr. Abd Alfady Morcos** with assistance from **Dr. Somaya Saad**.

Key Presentations:

1. **"Astronomy Activities for Supporting Education Among Displaced Sudanese Families"**
Mr. **Hassan Baba** (NAEC – Sudan) presented initiatives that organise astronomy activities for Sudanese children and families in Egypt. These programs were supported by Egyptian institutions such as the National Research Institute for Astronomy and Geophysics.
2. **"Astronomy for All: An Innovative Vision for Teaching Astronomy Using Infographics"**
Dr. **Ali Al-Edhari** introduced a creative approach to simplifying astronomy education through visually engaging infographics.
3. **"Astronomy Education Program at South Valley University"**
Dr. **Iman Fouad** (South Valley University – Egypt) highlighted efforts to integrate astronomy into university curricula and organise advanced training programs in collaboration with astronomy specialists.
4. **"Activities of the Astronomy Education Office in Jordan"**
Mrs. **Dalal Al-Lala** (NAEC – Jordan) described activities that included public lectures, workshops, and events aimed at promoting astronomy awareness across Jordan and beyond.
5. **"Elements of Astronomy Education in Egypt: Heritage and Modernity"**
Dr. **Somaya Saad** discussed Egypt's astronomical heritage and the integration of traditional and modern tools to enrich astronomy education.

Key Recommendations:

- Establish a **regional network for astronomy educators** to share knowledge, coordinate initiatives, and overcome resource limitations.
- Enhance access to **modern astronomical tools and facilities**, such as observatories and digital resources.
- Integrate astronomy into **formal educational curricula** at all levels to foster scientific literacy among students.
- Utilise the **astronomical heritage of the Arab world** to create culturally relevant and engaging educational materials.
- Develop programs aimed at involving **underprivileged communities**, ensuring equitable access to astronomy education.
- Organise regular **regional workshops and conferences** to strengthen collaboration and exchange innovative teaching practices.

This session underscored the collective commitment of the Arab-speaking community to developing astronomy education as a bridge for regional integration and scientific advancement.

Hebrew-Speaking Community Discussion

Session organisers: Ayelet Weizman (NAEC Israel)

DISCUSSION SUMMARY

In this special session there were eight presentations of space education projects taking place in Israel in the field of space education, in formal and informal education. The audience were teachers and educators interested in various aspects of space education, and each presentation was followed by some Q&A. The presenters spoke in Hebrew but prepared their slides in English. The summarising outline with links to the presentations can be found [here](#).

Portuguese-Speaking Community Discussion

Session organisers: Eduardo Penteado (OAE Heidelberg), Joana Latas (NUCLIO and Center for Research in Education and Psychology of the University of Évora (CIEP-UE), Portugal)

DISCUSSION SUMMARY

The Portuguese-language session of the 6th Shaw-IAU Workshop on Astronomy for Education was a collaborative effort between the International Astronomical Union's Office of Astronomy for Education (OAE) and the Portuguese Language Office of Astronomy for Development (PLOAD). Organised by Eduardo Penteado (OAE) and Joana Latas (PLOAD), and moderated by Rosa Doran (NUCLIO), the session was held in alignment with the World Science Day for Peace and Development on November 10th. The theme, "Astronomy Education: Pathways to Development and Peace," highlighted how astronomy education serves as a powerful tool for fostering sustainable development and promoting peace.

The session began with a panel of diverse speakers from Portuguese speaking countries sharing their initiatives and insights into using astronomy education to address societal challenges. Here, astronomy, education, and development are closely integrated. From Brazil, **Larissa Okiyama** presented "Closer to the Sky: Co-creating Astronomical Knowledge in the Favela Complex of Cantagalo Pavão and Pavãozinho." Her project focuses on co-creating knowledge with underserved communities by integrating astronomy with local culture through night sky observations, art classes, and decolonial educational resources. By engaging with children and young adults, the initiative provides tools for lifelong learning and addresses systemic inequalities in education and employment opportunities.

Continuing with the panel, **Miguel Gomes** from Luanda Science Center, the first one in Angola, discussed the strategic option of using Astronomy to bridge science and society in a country where there is a strong desire to make scientific culture accessible to a wider audience. He introduced "Astronomy on Wheels", a mobile science project designed to bring astronomy education to remote schools. Using portable modules and a mobile planetarium, the initiative overcomes geographic barriers and inspires curiosity about science among students who otherwise have limited access to educational resources. Gomes discussed the logistical challenges of implementing such a project and its potential to foster development in Angola.

From Cape Verde, **Ivanilda Cabral** shared "Cape Verde Towards the Future with Astronomy." Her talk explored the limited integration of astronomy into the country's educational system.

While astronomy is currently taught only minimally, Cabral emphasised the importance of introducing it as a formal subject at the university level. By bridging traditional knowledge about the skies with modern scientific approaches, she envisions astronomy becoming a driver for local educational and economic development.

Yara Simango from Mozambique concluded the panel with “Astronomy Education as a Tool to Address Gender Inequalities in Mozambique.” Her initiative focuses on empowering young girls in underserved communities through astronomy education. By challenging stereotypes and providing role models, Simango aims to increase female participation in STEM fields, addressing broader issues of gender inequality, poverty, and social exclusion. Her work illustrates how astronomy and, in a broader context, scientific education can be used to promote societal transformation.

Following the panel, **Alan Alves Brito** from Brazil delivered the keynote address, “Astronomy Education: Pathways to Development.” Brito framed astronomy education as a means of liberation and progress in the 21st century. His talk emphasised that astronomy can inspire critical thinking and foster inclusivity. By addressing social inequalities and promoting equity, it can contribute to building a more just and sustainable society. Brito’s reflections offered a powerful framework for understanding how the experiences shared in the panel contribute to broader goals of development and peace.

The session highlighted the versatility of astronomy education in addressing a wide range of challenges, from gender inequality to geographic inaccessibility. Across all the presentations, a recurring theme was the ability of astronomy to inspire and empower individuals, particularly those in underserved communities. For example, Okiyama’s work in the favelas of Rio de Janeiro demonstrated how integrating local culture with scientific knowledge can create transformative educational opportunities. Similarly, Gomes’s mobile science project showcased the importance of bringing resources directly to communities that face barriers to access and to complement formal and non formal educational contexts.

Cabral’s efforts in Cape Verde pointed to the untapped potential of formalising astronomy education within the existing higher level system, while Simango’s initiatives underscored the role of education in breaking cycles of poverty and inequality. Together, these projects illustrate that astronomy education is not confined to the teaching of scientific concepts but extends to fostering critical thinking, creativity, and social change. Brito’s keynote provided a unifying lens through which to view these efforts. He reminded the audience that astronomy is a science of exploration and connection, capable of bridging divides and inspiring action toward a better future. The session reinforced that science for development is not about advancing knowledge but about people and how to build more equitable and sustainable societies.

In conclusion, the session underscored the transformative power of astronomy education in different contexts as a pathway to development and peace. It demonstrated how diverse approaches—from mobile planetariums to empowering young girls—can be tailored to address specific challenges while contributing to global goals. The OAE-PLOAD collaboration and the alignment to the World Science Day for Peace and Development, highlighted the importance of collective action in leveraging astronomy for a brighter and more inclusive future.

Romanian-Speaking Community Discussion

Session organisers: Elisabeta Ana Naghi (NAEC Romania) and Felicia Elena Călmuc (Palatul Copiilor, Romania)

DISCUSSION SUMMARY

During the 6th Shaw IAU Workshop, with the invaluable support of the organisers, a session dedicated to the Romanian astronomy community was held in Romanian. The event was highly appreciated by participants, who expressed their gratitude for having the opportunity to share their experience as astronomy educators and promoters in Romania. These experiences were closely related to the workshop's topic: astronomical observations from both scientific and educational perspectives.

The session was coordinated and moderated by Ms. Elisabeta Ana Naghi, the Romanian NAEC and inspector for Mathematics and Astronomy at the Romanian Ministry of Education, with the support of Felicia Elena Călmuc, English teacher for non-formal education at Palatul Copiilor, city of Craiova.

The Romanian session was divided into three sections, each illustrating a distinct approach based on the professional status and the perspectives of the speakers regarding the impact of astronomical observations.

The first section included presentations by science experts from research departments of various institutions, including Harvard College, the Astronomical Institute of the Romanian Academy, the Ministry of National Defense, and the Naval Academy "Mircea cel Batrân" Constanța. These experts focused on how astronomical observations have been used in numerous scientific fields, influencing human life from ancient times to the present day.

Section I

- *"Time, Spirituality and Astronomical Observations: Sacred Time"*, Daria Teodora Hărăbor, 3rd year at Harvard College, Physics and Mathematics.
- *"The Use of Robotic Observatories in the Monitoring of Artificial Space Objects"*, Trelia Mădălina, Astronomical Institute of the Romanian Academy, Bucharest, Romania
- *"The Alliance Between the Army and Astronomy"*, Tudor Georgian, Ministry of National Defense, Romania

- *"Applied Astronomy: Astronomical Navigation"*, Pocora Andrei, Naval Academy "Mircea cel Batrân" Constanța, Constanța County

Afterwards, the second section included presentations by professionals from various educational institutions, including inspectorates, theoretical highschoools, and doctoral schools. These professionals focused on how modern scientific tools can be effectively integrated into engaging teaching methods and strategies to make astronomy data available and accessible for students interested in studying cosmic space.

Section II

- *"The Sky and Our Stars"*, Crăciun Petru, ISJ SV, Suceava County
- *"The Sky and Everyday Life"*, Cosovanu Ilie, ISJ SV, Suceava County
- *"Parallexes & Astronomical Observations"*, Ghergu Cezar, Benjamin Franklin Theoretical High School, Bucharest
- *"Gravitational Waves"*, Mirițescu Cătălina, IFAE Barcelona, Doctoral School, Spain

Finally, the third section was dedicated to astronomy educators, including primary and secondary teachers, and NGO educational workers, who presented astronomy projects they had successfully implemented with students. These projects were showcased as examples of good practices in the field of astronomy education.

Section III

- *"Climate Detectives"*, Buduleanu Alina Marilena, High School No. 29, Galati County
- *"School Projects & Astronomical Observations"*, Cosman Carmen Diana and Serafim Maria, "Dacia" High School, Oradea, Bihor County
- *"Starting the Adventure of Knowing the Universe Through Observations"*, Borșan Maria, "Ion Bob" High School, Cluj-Napoca, Cluj County
- *"A Trip to the Universe with BIT&EVO"*, Mariana Mihaela LAZAR, Secondary School No. 12 Brasov, Brasov County
- *"EarthKAM - NASA Missions for Students"*, Kallos Camelia, Technological High School of Constructions and Environmental Protection, Arad, Arad County
- *"Exoplanets for Education" (Exo4Edu)*, Bîrlan Mirel, Astronomical Institute of the Romanian Academy, Bușu Carmen, High School No. 168, Bucharest, Naghi Elisabeta Ana, Ministry of Education, Bucharest
- *"Endless Universe"*, Cosmin MICLOS, Ucenicul Astronom-NGO

In addition to the speakers, approximately 40 to 50 Romanian participants attended the presentations and discussions during the session, finding them extremely interesting.

In conclusion, all participants agreed that the Romanian Session provided an excellent opportunity to learn about the latest scientific research in the field of astronomical observations. It also highlighted how modern teaching methods can integrate these advancements to engage students of various ages and knowledge levels in astronomy education. Furthermore, many participants expressed gratitude for the opportunity to speak in Romanian, as it eliminated the language barrier that can sometimes pose challenges for speakers. Overall, we hope this tradition will continue in the future and extend our gratitude to the organisers for their hard work and support in hosting the Romanian session of Shaw-IAU Workshop.

Spanish-Speaking Community Discussion

Session organisers: Samantha Brown-Sevilla (OAE Heidelberg), Breezy Ocaña Flaquer (NAEC Dominican Republic) and Juan Ángel Vaquerizo (NAEC Spain)

DISCUSSION SUMMARY

This year the Spanish session centred on fostering collaborations and sharing knowledge among the National Astronomy Education Coordinators (NAECs) from several Spanish-speaking countries. The primary goal was to showcase successful educational projects and initiatives implemented by the NAECs in their respective countries. The hope was to identify models that can be adapted and replicated in regions with fewer resources or different constraints.

The following NAECs presented innovative projects that have made significant contributions to astronomy education in their regions.

Title: *Little Astronomers: Travelling in the Cosmos for Grades K-2*

Author: Jessica A. Xitumul

Country: Guatemala

Title: *Experiences in the creation and implementation of an astronomy programme as its own subject at secondary school level*

Author: Melissa Solares

Country: Guatemala

Title: *CosmoLab: from the Classroom to the Universe, working with teachers in Tenerife to reach all students on the island*

Author: Irene Puerto

Country: Spain

Title: *Professional Learning Community based on the development of experiences using real astrophysical data in the classroom*

Authors: Irma Fuentes Morales, Carla Hernández, Rubén Montecinos, Maribel Cornejo, Fernanda Alarcón, Ignacia Benito, and Jocelyn Alarcón

Country: Chile

Title: *Astro Mobile and The Astronomy Course with Clue*

Author: Adams Martínez

Country: Panama

Title: *Workshop on Astronomical Data Analysis in the Dominican Republic*

Author: Thara Caba

Country: Dominican Republic

Title: *Speak With Them: Women in Astronomy*

Author: Nayra Rodríguez

Country: Spain

The session underscored the importance of adaptability and creativity in addressing the challenges of astronomy education in diverse contexts. Participants noted that the successful elements of these projects often stem from their ability to engage local communities, the use of affordable and accessible materials, and the incorporating cultural heritage into their programs.

At the end, different strategies for replicating these projects in other Spanish-speaking countries were discussed. A feedback survey was distributed to the participants to build on the energy and ideas generated during the discussion. The survey aims to identify which projects participants are most interested in adopting or adapting, highlight perceived limitations and barriers to implementation in their respective countries, and facilitate connections between participants and the organisers of specific projects for further guidance and support.

The results of this survey will be key in shaping follow-up actions, such as creating a mentorship network or resource-sharing platform to assist NAECs in their efforts. These initiatives aim to kick-start collaboration, facilitate knowledge exchange, and empower NAECs to address challenges more effectively. We hope these goals ultimately contribute to the growth and success of the NAEC community.

<http://astro4edu.org>

@astro4edu

THE
SHAW
PRIZE
邵逸夫獎

IAU